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INDIAN ASSOCIATION FOR RADIATION PROTECTION

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Mangalagangothri, Mangaluru

**Radiation Protection for Sustainable Nuclear
Energy: Adapting to Climate and
Technological Changes.**

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35th IARP National Conference

On

**Radiation Protection for Sustainable Nuclear Energy: Adapting to Climate
and Technological Changes**

IARPNC-2025

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Organised by

Indian Association for Radiation Protection (IARP)

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Preface

On behalf of the Indian Association for Radiation Protection (IARP), we are delighted to present the **Book of Abstracts** for the 35th National Conference on "**Radiation Protection for Sustainable Nuclear Energy: Adapting to Climate and Technological Changes**". This conference, jointly organized by IARP, the Centre for Advanced Research in Environmental Radioactivity (CARER), and the Centre for Application of Radioisotopes and Radiation Technology (CARRT), is being held from **29th to 31st January 2025** at **Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri, Karnataka**.

This conference aims to address the challenges and opportunities in the field of radiation protection amidst evolving climate and technological landscapes. It provides a platform for experts, researchers, and practitioners to share advancements, exchange ideas, and foster collaboration. The scientific programme includes one plenary session, eight invited talks, one panel discussion, and numerous oral and poster presentations.

The Book of Abstracts is a compilation of the scientific contributions received for this conference. A total of 265 abstracts were accepted, showcasing the diversity and depth of research in the domain. These include 226 poster presentations and 39 oral presentations.

The conference covers a broad range of thematic areas, including:

- Radiation Protection in Emerging Nuclear Technologies
- Radiation Safety and Protection in Nuclear Fuel Cycle Facilities
- Radiation Safety and Protection in Accelerators, Medical, Industrial, and Other Sectors
- Radiation Dosimetry
- Nuclear Instrumentation and System Development
- Environmental Monitoring and Assessment, including radioisotope applications for climate change and atmospheric studies
- Radiation Protection Philosophy, Risk Estimates, Regulatory Framework, Systems of Protection, Standards, and Regulation
- Existing Exposures

We extend our sincere gratitude to all authors, reviewers, and members of the organizing committee for their efforts in curating this volume. This Book of Abstracts represents the collective knowledge and innovation of participants and will undoubtedly inspire fruitful discussions and future collaborations.

We wish all participants an intellectually stimulating and engaging conference experience.

**Convener,
Scientific Programme Committee,
IARPNC2025**

29th January 2025

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Abstracts of Contributory Papers

INDUSTRIAL SAFETY MANAGEMENT PRACTICES TO ENHANCE SAFETY CULTURE IN BARC

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Introduction

BARC comprises multidisciplinary R&D facilities and laboratories related to nuclear technology. Health and safety aspects are mainly two types categories viz. Radiological and Conventional. BARC has a rich tradition of nurturing safety culture and committed to integrate safety into all R&D activities through comprehensive Accident Prevention Programme (APP).

Accident Prevention Programme (APP)

It involves hazard identification, safe work procedures development, safety motivational efforts and database management of accidents.

Top management plays a key role when improving occupational safety, because better safety culture requires resources – both work time and financial input.

Zero accident vision

To achieve zero accident vision, a safety framework and dissipation of safety information to all workers in time bound manner is the first step. Leading indicators are proactive, preventive, and predictive measures that provide information about the effective performance of safety activities and lagging indicators are active measures reflect the past occurrence and frequency of incidents/ accidents. In BARC IHSS adopted following additional leading and lagging indicators for achieving zero accident vision:

Safety Database Management: Safety trekking analysis software developed for in-situ injury database. Its analysis capabilities supports overall safety system which works on networking and cloud computing.

Inspection: Safety inspection/ walk through survey carried out in order to monitor any unsafe conditions and unsafe acts. Deficiencies are reported immediately for corrective actions and followed up for preventing recurrences.

Training: Safety training and orientation to workers is

introduced whenever (1) workers' tasks change, and (2) new machines introduced, or (3) long absenteeism. Height pass testing facility plays a major role for construction workers as it provides the workers information about all the possible hazards at the workplace. This is a positive channel to demonstrate proper use of PPEs during the work. **Audio-visual awareness:** Adequate numbers of signboards/ safety posters depicts safety messages as reminders for observance of safety practices during work.

Conclusion

BARC is committed to ensure the highest standard of OHS and IHSS took initiative towards achieving the goal. Under APP, following elements have included: (a) An organization structure to ensure safety commitment at workplace. (b) Hazards identification, evaluation and control through safety procedures and effective control measures. (c) Safety inspection to identify unsafe conditions. (d) Accidents /incidents investigation for root cause analysis. (e) Planning for effective management of emergencies.

No standard solution exists for achieving the goal of Zero Accidents. Improving safety is a never-ending task: even when performed well, it is never finished.

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References

“Occupational safety and health issues for construction projects”, Praveen Dubey et.al, ICMSCGC, IIIE, Nagpur, Oct 25-27, 2013
“Vision Zero Incident: Concepts And its Implication for Construction Projects in BARC”, Praveen Dubey et.al., DAESOPM at Kudankulam, 2017.

RADON EXHALATION AND THE DISTRIBUTION OF URANIUM, THORIUM, AND POTASSIUM IN SOIL OF KODAGU DISTRICT, KARNATAKA

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Introduction

Natural radioactivity is a ubiquitous phenomenon on Earth and the levels of background radiation varies depending on location, altitude, and human activities. The rate of ²²²Rn exhalation is influenced by radium concentration, porosity, density, diffusion coefficient, and meteorological parameters. Geological features like rock formation, stone cracking, and bedrock composition also play a key role in ²²²Rn exhalation (Mustonen, 1984). Studies measuring ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K in soil help in correlating radon exhalation rates with these elements.

Materials and Methods

The soil samples were collected from various parts of Kodagu District, Karnataka and the geo-coordinates of the sampling sites were noted during sampling. A scintillation-based Smart Radon Monitor (SRM) was used to measure the exhalation rate of ²²²Rn in soil. The activity of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K in soil samples was measured using NaI(Tl) gamma ray spectrometer.

Results

The ²²²Rn mass exhalation rate was varied from 5.29 to 54.75 mBq kg⁻¹ h⁻¹. The ²²²Rn surface exhalation rate was observed to vary from 0.30 to 3.06 mBq m⁻² h⁻¹. The higher radon exhalation rate was observed in which the geological composition comprised kyanite – mica schist of the Sargur group.

The activity concentration of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K was found to vary from 12.06±0.14 to 48.9±0.27 Bq kg⁻¹; 29.06±0.07 to 227.77±0.27 Bq kg⁻¹ and 109.94±1.34 to 530.22±4.38 Bq kg⁻¹ respectively. The associated hazard coefficients due to these radionuclides were also estimated in the

present study. The ²³²Th average activity concentration 79.42 Bq kg⁻¹ of the present study was found to be higher than the Indian average value of 64 Bq kg⁻¹ and world average value of 30 Bq kg⁻¹, also higher when compared to the population weighted world average value of 45 Bq kg⁻¹ (UNSCEAR, 2000). Whereas, the average activity concentration of ⁴⁰K was lower than the Indian and world average value which indicates minimal use of fertilizers in the study region.

Conclusion

A systematic study of radon exhalation rate from soil samples and ²³⁸U, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K activity in soil samples of the Kodagu District, Karnataka was carried out. The highest ²²²Rn exhalation rates were observed in areas comprising kyanite–mica schist of the Sargur group. The ²³²Th average concentration in the study area was higher than both the Indian and the world values, indicating elevated thorium levels in this region.

References

- Mustonen, R. (1984). Science of the Total Environment, 33(1-4), 153-158.
- UNSCEAR, (2000). Sources and Effects of Ionizing Radiation, United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation (UNSCEAR) 2000 Report.

EFFICIENCY OF STANDING WHOLE-BODY MONITOR AS A FUNCTION OF SIZE

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Introduction

The Standing Whole-Body Monitor (SWBM) Standfast-II at IGCAR is used to assess internal radiation exposure due to fission products under routine and emergency situations. During emergency all age groups including children have to be monitored. Efficiency value is a prerequisite for activity estimation and it is a function of body size. This study estimates the system's efficiency for different age using Monte Carlo simulations with numerical Indian BOMAB phantoms.

Materials and Methods

SWBM consists of two detectors each of dimensions 10.15 cm x10.15 cm x40.64 cm .It has a shielding thickness of 5cm lead equivalent material. It was modeled along with Indian BOMAB phantoms of different ages (Mehta, 2003) in FLUKA using FLAIR. The phantoms were standing on the floor of the SWBM inside the subject chamber facing the detector. Subroutines were written to simulate homogenous distribution inside the individual parts of the phantoms. The system efficiencies were estimated by summing the individual detector efficiencies obtained using the detect card for energy range of 120 keV to 1500 keV. For improved efficiency, 5-year-old Indian phantom was positioned 30 cm above the floor. Efficiencies were also estimated for ^{131}I present in the thyroid.

Results

For a particular age the efficiency increases and then decreases with energy, with a maximum at 392 keV. As age increases, the efficiency decreases, with the 4-year-old phantom placed at a height of 30 cm. Compared to the BARC standing wholebody monitor (Sankhla, 2015) the efficiencies of Indian BOMAB phantoms of different age were less by 2 to 30%. Efficiencies were fit as a function of body physique ($\sqrt{W/H}$) and energy (Kramer, 2014) were fitted using eqn (1).

$$z = z_0 + a * E + b * \sqrt{W/H} + c * E^2 + d * \sqrt{W/H}^2 + f * E * \sqrt{W/H} \quad (1)$$

Where Z is the counting efficiency, E is the photon energy, W is the weight, H is the height and a, b, c, d and f are the curve fit parameters. This fit estimates the efficiency with $\pm 85\%$ agreement for all phantoms and energies. These predicted values are well within the performance criteria of 50% to -25%. In actual scenario the distribution is going to be uniform so the dose estimated using BOMAB phantom efficiencies will be more accurate compared to cylindrical or point source efficiencies.

The minimum detectable doses of ^{137}Cs and ^{131}I were estimated to be in the order of few μSv for all age groups for different post intake time using the MDAs calculated with the simulated efficiencies & age dependent dose coefficients, for a counting time of 1minute. As the post intake period increases the effect of age increases. The study revealed that the use of Indian adult phantom efficiency and retention factor and dose coefficients for adult will result in an error upto 450%. The minimum detectable dose on the 15th day post intake is 4 times greater than at 3 hrs. So in case of ^{131}I immediate counting is essential.

Conclusion

This work will result in an accurate estimation of internal dose to all age groups.

References

- Mehta DJ, Singh I S, Sharma R C. (2003) RadiatProt Environ (2003); 26;327-32.
- Gary H Kramer and Kevin Capello. (2014) HMLTD-02-16.
- Rajesh sankhla, I.S.Singh, D.D Rao and K.S. Pradeepkumar (2015), BARC newsletter.

UNINTERRUPTED IN-VIVO MONITORING AND ACCURATE DOSE ESTIMATION THROUGH QUALITY ASSURANCE

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Keywords: Quality control, Control charts, In vivo monitors, Intercomparison, spectral parameters

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Introduction

IGCAR houses a variety of in-vivo monitors based on gamma spectrometers. These monitors are subject to a variety of deviations like gain drift, changes in linearity, error in readout and analog to digital conversion. These deviations would result in the variation of spectral parameters. In the absence of a procedure for the regular observance of the performance of the monitors and prompt correction the estimated doses will be inaccurate and also result in an inordinately large maintenance to restore to the standard response. A variety of techniques are used to achieve a stable instrument. At IGCAR this stabilization is achieved through a robust quality assurance program involving choice of electronic components, measurements, plotting and analyzing quality control charts. This paper discusses the QA carried out for seven systems such as Shielded chair, two standing wholebody monitors, two shadow shield counters, thyroid monitor, HPGe based lung monitor at IGCAR

Materials and Methods

A procedure manual documenting the quality assurance plan for all the monitors is prepared. Daily background and standard source measurements are made with the optimized timing specific to each monitor. ^{137}Cs point source is used for the quality control. Spectral parameters like peak channel, resolution, source counts and background counts were read from the pulse height spectra. Control charts were plotted to infer the deviations from the mean value and corrections initiated. In case there is a deviation, the cause is identified and corrective actions such as electronic adjustment, temperature control and change of electronic components are taken up. Apart from this, annual calibration of the monitors are carried out with appropriate phantoms loaded with radioactive sources and compared with the previous values. IGCAR also

participates in intercomparison exercises for activity measurements, dose computation methods and numerical simulations (Vrba, 2013).

Results

The annual variation in spectral parameters was within 5% and background variation was less than one standard deviation for a period of 6 years for all the in-vivo monitors. These variations are acceptable as per the ISO criteria (ISO, 2010). Interpersonal variation was also quantified as <5%. The electronic adjustment which is mostly the gain is once in a month. Results of the annual calibration agreed by 95% every time, unless and otherwise some modifications have been carried out. The results are compiled annually as a report. In all the intercomparison exercises our results were agreeing by 95% with the true value (IAEA, 2007).

Conclusion

Implementation of a robust QA program at IGCAR would result in the accurate estimation of internal exposure if any.

References

1. ISO (2010), Radiation protection — Performance criteria for Radiobioassay
2. Vrba, T., et al., (2013) EURADOS intercomparison exercise on MC modeling for the in-vivo monitoring of Am-241 in skull phantoms (Part I), Radiation Physics and Chemistry.
3. IAEA (2007) Intercomparison exercise on internal dose assessment.

COMPARISON OF SHIELDED CHAIR COUNTER AND STANDING WHOLEBODY MONITOR FOR ESTIMATION OF INTERNAL EXPOSURE

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Introduction

Two types of NaI(Tl) based whole body counters namely Shielded chair (SC) and Standing Whole-Body Monitor (SWBM) having detectors of different size and shapes, as well as different counting geometries are being used for the assessment of internal exposure of fission products at IGCAR. This paper compares the performance of the two systems.

Materials and Methods

Shielded Chair has NaI detector of 20.0 cm diameter and 10.15 cm thick while Standing Wholebody monitor consists of two detectors each of dimensions 10.15 cm x 10.15 cm x 40.64 cm. SWBM has 2.63 times higher sensitive area than that of SC. The chair of the SC is made of 10 cm lead equivalent and the detector with 8 cm lead bricks while SWBM has 5 cm lead equivalent material. Both the systems are calibrated using Indian adult BOMAB phantom with uniform distribution.

Results

The efficiency of SWBM is 1.92 to 2.03 times higher than that of SC in the energy range of 300-1500 keV. This is due to the combined effect of proximity of the subject to the detector as well as the detector area. SWBM has almost equal efficiencies for localized activity in thorax and pelvis but in case of SC efficiency for thorax activity is 3 times higher than that of pelvis. The efficiency for ^{131}I present in thyroid is 14% higher in SWBM compared to that of SC. The ^{40}K background count in SWBM is half that of SC enabling the quantification of naturally occurring ^{40}K in subjects. The closer counting geometry of SWBM results in 4 times higher Compton scattering factor for ^{133}Ba due to ^{137}Cs in SWBM compared to SC. Minimum

Detectable Activity (MDA) of ^{137}Cs in SC for 600s is 250 Bq. The same MDA of 250 Bq for ^{137}Cs can be achieved with a counting time of 100 s in SWBM. MDA for ^{131}I present in thyroid is 450 Bq in SC compared to 372 Bq in SWBM. The reduction is due to the higher efficiency. These values are lesser than the recommended action levels for interventions (Carlos, 2009). Sometimes when persons report for counting, there may have a trace level of external contamination. In SWBM, ratio of the counts of supine and prone geometries is used to discriminate internal and external contamination.

Conclusion

Quantification of naturally occurring ^{40}K in subject is possible in SWBM. The SWBM can be used for rapid monitoring because of ease of positioning. The system enables us to discriminate between external and internal contamination. SWBM has equal sensitivity for radionuclides present in thorax and pelvis. In case of thyroid monitoring the adult efficiency can be used for all age groups as the neck of different age groups can be placed at fixed position by raising the height of the standing platform.

References

1. TMT handbook, Triage, monitoring and treatment of people exposed to ionizing radiation following a malevolent act, Carlos Roja-Palma et al., 2009.

SMD CHIP RESISTORS AS EFFECTIVE THERMOLUMINESCENT RETROSPECTIVE DOSIMETERS

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Keywords: SMD chip resistor, TL, Retrospective dosimetry.

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Introduction

The growing risk of radiation accidents and terrorism involving radioactive materials has enhanced the need for accessible materials that enable rapid and accurate radiation dose assessment, especially for the public without dosimeters (*Pradhan et al 2014*). Retrospective dosimetry using thermoluminescence (TL) and optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) is effective for dose assessment in such scenarios (*Pradhan et al 2012*). Various electronic components, due to their radiation sensitivity, and ubiquity, have shown potential for dosimetry (*Beerten et al 2009*). This study investigates TL properties of surface-mounted device (SMD) chip resistors, optimizing detection through filter combinations and analyzing key dosimetric characteristics.

Materials and Methods

SMD chip resistors (100 Ω , 1 k Ω , and 10 k Ω), commonly found in portable electronic devices, were used in this work. The elemental composition of the sample was analyzed using FTIR and XRF spectroscopy, revealing the main component to be an alumina ceramic substrate. TL measurements were carried out using a Risø TL/OSL Reader (model TL/OSL-DA-20) equipped with a bialkali PMT and Hoya-U340 filters in front of the PMT. An in-built beta source ⁹⁰Sr/⁹⁰Y (43 mGy/s) was used for beta irradiation. Gamma irradiations (for fading study) were performed using a gamma chamber with a ⁶⁰Co source (0.49 kGy/hr).

Results

TL sensitivity was checked for both unirradiated and irradiated resistors (100 Ω , 1 k Ω , 10 k Ω). Due to the lower inherent signal of the 100 Ω resistors, further analysis was done on this sample. The TL glow curve exhibited three main peaks at 92 °C, 200-215 °C, and 365 °C, with the 200-215 °C peak

selected for dosimetry, and a temperature range of 150-270 °C was chosen for quantitative studies. The effect of the Hoya-U340 filter in various combinations revealed that a 5 mm U340 filter enhanced detection sensitivity by 16 times. The TL homogeneity was estimated to be within $\pm 10\%$ and can be applied as needed.

T_m - T_{stop} analysis identified three traps that are in line with the glow curve peaks. Based on these results, the preheat temperature was set to 100 °C, with a 30 s preheat time. The TL signal repeatability was within $\pm 1\%$, showing no sensitization over 10 cycles. The dose response was linear from 86 mGy to 10 Gy, with a strong linearity index. The minimum detectable dose (MDD) was 1.86 mGy. Fading studies showed that preheating reduced signal fading by $\sim 25\%$ over ten days. Single aliquot regenerative-dose protocol confirmed accurate dose recovery with a good recycling ratio.

Conclusion

The strong TL sensitivity, high repeatability, excellent linear dose response, low MDD, and accurate dose recovery demonstrate that SMD chip resistors are effective TL dosimeters for retrospective dose assessment, especially when conventional dosimeters are unavailable.

References

- Beerten, K., Clemens, W., and Filip, V. (2009) *Radiation Measurements* **44**, 620-625.
- Pradhan, A.S., Kim, J.L., and Lee, J.I. (2012) *Journal of Medical Physics* **37**, 121-123.
- Pradhan, A.S., Lee, J.I., and Kim, J.L. (2014) *Defect and Diffusion Forum* **347**, 229-245.

AMMONIUM OXALATE MONOHYDRATE AS EPR BASED CHEMICAL DOSIMETER

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Introduction

Electron Paramagnetic Resonance (EPR)-based chemical dosimeters are specialized tools for measuring radiation doses and are extensively applied in dosimetry for radiotherapy, medical imaging, blood irradiation, food preservation, and radiation sterilization [Regulla et al 1982]. EPR dosimetry works by detecting unpaired electron spins in irradiated materials, producing a distinct signal directly proportional to the amount of radiation absorbed. This method offers high sensitivity, precise, and non-destructive measurements. Alanine/EPR dosimetry is a standard method used for dose measurement across a wide range of radiation doses (from mGy to kGy). The current study aims to evaluate the potential of an alternative chemical dosimeter for industrial applications. Some formates and oxalates have recently been used as EPR-based dosimeters [Hassan et al 2000; Waldeland et al 2011]. In this study, ammonium oxalate monohydrate is selected due to the formation of stable oxalate radicals, $-\text{O}_2\text{CC}\cdot\text{OH}^-$, upon irradiation.

Materials and Methods

Polycrystalline ammonium oxalate monohydrate (Sigma-Aldrich) was used as a chemical dosimeter. An X-band EPR spectrometer (Bruker India Scientific Pvt. Ltd.) was used to record the EPR spectrum. To obtain a strong EPR signal with maximum sensitivity, the EPR spectrometer parameters were optimized for irradiated ammonium oxalate prior to the dosimetry studies. The samples were irradiated using a gamma chamber (GC 5000) with a dose rate of 0.5 kGy/hr for the dosimetry studies

Results

Ammonium oxalate exhibits an optimal EPR signal at 0.2 mW microwave power, 10^5 receiver gain, 4G modulation amplitude, microwave frequency 9.75 Hz, modulation frequency 100 kHz and a 20.48 ms time constant. The EPR spectra of irradiated ammonium oxalate show a single EPR line at $g = 2.0090 \pm 0.0038$ due to oxalate radicals ($\text{O}_2\text{CC}\cdot\text{OH}^-$) formed during irradiation, which is used for dosimetry studies. The peak-to-peak height of the dosimetry signal is used to construct the dose-response curve. An EPR dose calibration curve was established for irradiated ammonium oxalate, and the response was found to be linear from 10 Gy to 1 kGy. Fading studies revealed an approximate 8% loss of signal intensity after one month of storage following irradiation.

Conclusion

This work investigates the potential applicability of ammonium oxalate monohydrate as an EPR-based chemical dosimeter. The dosimetry properties of the ammonium oxalate/EPR dosimetry system were studied by optimizing EPR parameters. It demonstrated a satisfactory linear dose range, and quite stable EPR signal. The EPR dosimetry properties of ammonium oxalate monohydrate suggest that it could be used in applications such as food preservation, disinfestations, and the sterile insect technique.

References

- Hassan, G. M., Ulusoy, U., & Ikeya, M. (2000). JJAP, 39(11R), 6236.
Regulla, D. F., & Deffner, U. (1982). Int. J. Appl. Radiat. Isot., 33(11), 1101-1114.
Waldeland, E., Helt-Hansen, J., & Malinen, E. (2011). Rad. Meas., 46(2), 213-218.

EXHALATION RATES OF RADON AND THORON GASES FROM KALPAKKAM, PARANGIPETTAI AND KANYAKUMARI BEACH SAND SAMPLES: A COMPARATIVE STUDY.

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Introduction

The gases radon and thoron are released/exhaled from rock, water and soil matrices. Measurement of the exhalation rate of radon from soil and building materials is the best way to quantify environmental radon concentration. Radon and thoron exhalation rate is influenced by environmental factors such as climatic conditions, water content, and geology (Masahiro et al., 2004). The concentration of radon in the outdoor environment is less due to dilution; in confined spaces such as coal mines, its concentration becomes very high and can severely impact health. Lung cancer is a probable result of high indoor radon concentration. In this study, an attempt was made to estimate the exhalation of ²²²Rn and ²²⁰Rn from the beach sands of select regions of Tamil Nadu.

Materials and Methods

The study area included three coastal zones, Kanyakumari (KNK), Parangipettai (PRP) and Kalpakkam (KPK). These zones vary in their natural background radiation levels. The beach sand samples collected from the three zones were dried, weighed, and subjected to RAD 7 analysis. From the obtained activity concentration, the exhalation rates of the gases were estimated.

Results

The radon mass exhalation rate of the three zones ranged from BDL to 35.8 mBq kg⁻¹ h⁻¹. The maximum exhalation was noted in a KNK sand sample and the minimum in a PRP sand sample. Thoron surface exhalation

rate ranged from 106 to 68,980 Bq m⁻² h⁻¹. The highest exhalation rate of thoron was observed in a KPK sand sample, and the lowest in a KNK sample. The world average values of radon mass and thoron surface exhalation rates are 57 mBq kg⁻¹ h⁻¹ and 3600 Bq m⁻² h⁻¹, respectively (UNSCEAR 2000). The minimum detectable activity (MDA) is 2 mBq/kg/h for radon mass and 59 Bq/m²/h for thoron surface exhalation rates.

Conclusion

From this investigation it can be inferred that radon and thoron exhalation rates of KNK samples were much higher than those of PRP and KPK samples. This may be due to the high concentration of monazite in the KNK beach sand. The exhalation rates of both radon and thoron in all the three zones were significantly different [ANOVA (F = 3.19; df = 2,43; p > 0.05) and (F = 1.09; df = 2,43; p > 0.05), respectively]. In all the three zones, the radon and thoron (exhalation) values were nonnormally distributed.

References

Hosoda, Masahiro, S. Michikuni, S. Masato, Y. Yuji, and F. Masahiro (2004). "Radon and thoron exhalation rates and their some correlating factors." Rn 21: 21.

UNSCEAR (2000) United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation. Sources and effects of Ionizing radiation, report to the general assembly with scientific annexures, Vol.1, Annex B: Exposures from natural radiation sources. United Nations, New York.

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF A FINITE ANGLE METHOD BASED 3D MULTI-GROUP NEUTRON TRANSPORT MODEL FOR CRITICALITY AND SHIELDING ANALYSIS OF NUCLEAR FACILITIES

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Keywords: Fast breeder reactor, criticality safety, radiation shielding, Neutron transport, Finite angle method.
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Introduction

The Boltzmann neutron transport equation (NTE) is solved numerically for criticality and shielding analysis of nuclear facilities (Vaz, 2009). The discrete ordinate method (SN) with level symmetric quadrature sets (LQN) is the most widely used technique for solving the NTE. However, it suffers from the so-called ray-effects which results from the inability of the quadrature formula to accurately integrate the angular flux distribution in heterogeneous medium (Lewis and Miller, 1984). The most obvious remedy for ray-effects is to increase the number of directions. However, the LQN method yields negative weights beyond order S20 and are not physically correct. So, different techniques were investigated earlier to address this issue (Longoni G. et al., 2001). In this work, we employed an advanced angular discretization technique called Finite Angle Method (FAM) which does not require explicit evaluation of quadrature weights. This method does not impose any restriction on number of angles and on local angular refinement (Modest and Mazumder, 2023). In this work, a multi-group neutron transport model has been developed using the FAM based angular discretization scheme for 3D Cartesian geometry.

Method

The NTE is directly integrated over all the three spatial and two angular variables to obtain the semi-discretized form of NTE. The face averaged fluxes are approximated in terms of cell center fluxes using linear-step (central difference and upwind) scheme to obtain the final discretized form of NTE. The shielding problem is solved by employing source iteration technique and the criticality problem is solved using traditional outer-inner iteration strategy.

Results

A code named NETRENA (Neutron TRansport Equation Numerical Algorithm) has been developed based on the numerical model and validated by solving different criticality (LWR and FBR) and shielding (EIR-2 and Iron-Water) benchmarks (Takeda and Ikeda, 1991; Kokonkov and Nikolaeva, 2015). The neutron flux and k_{eff} values have been evaluated with different number of spatial cells and control angles. The code predicted values approach the reference values with the refinement of space-angle grid. The deviation is less than 100 pcm for k_{eff} values. The zonewise averaged neutron fluxes are in good agreement with the reference values with relative error less than 5%.

Conclusion

A finite angle method based 3D multigroup neutron transport code (NETRENA) has been developed. The code has been validated using different criticality and shielding benchmark problems. From this study, the efficacy of code has been demonstrated for criticality and shielding analysis.

References

- Vaz, P., (2009) Radiat. Phys. Chem., 78.
- Lewis, E.E. and Miller, W.F. (1984), John Wiley & Sons.
- Longoni G. et al. (2001) Trans. Am. Nucl. Soc., 84.
- Modest, M.F. and Mazumder S. (2023) Academic press.
- Takeda, T. and Ikeda, H. (1991) Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology, 28.
- Kokonkov, N.I. and Nikolaeva, O.V. (2015). Keydish Institute Preprint.

ENGINEERING SILICONE RUBBER BASED POLYMER COMPOSITES WITH MULTIFILLERS FOR ENHANCED GAMMA SHIELDING, THERMAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

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Introduction

The use of gamma radiation for various purposes requires effective radiation shielding. Traditional materials are often heavy and lack in sufficient mechanical properties. Advanced polymer composites offer exceptional properties and versatility for this application.

Materials and Methods

This investigation focuses on composites made from silicone rubber matrix incorporating tungsten oxide (WO₃) and chromium (Cr) as multifillers. The composites were fabricated by open mold casting technique, using 30 parts per hundred rubber (phr) of WO₃ and varying Cr concentrations (10, 30, 50 and 70 phr). The distribution and elemental composition of the fillers were analyzed using Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FE-SEM) with Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectrum (EDX). Mechanical and thermal properties were assessed using a Universal Testing Machine (UTM) and Thermogravimetric analyzer, respectively. The gamma shielding capabilities were studied using Cs-137 radiation source at energy of 662 keV, by evaluating key shielding parameters such as Linear Attenuation Coefficient (LAC), Mass Attenuation Coefficient (MAC), Half-Value Layer (HVL) and Relaxation Length (RL).

Results

The FESEM images confirm the incorporation of fillers resulting in a uniform distribution within the polymer matrix and the increased amount of the filler is evidenced by EDX mapping. The thermogravimetric analysis indicates that the pristine sample experiences a weight reduction of 75% between 400° and 600°C, whereas the composites containing fillers exhibit a weight loss ranging from 45% to 55% as the filler

content increases from 10 to 70 phr. The tensile strength is found to improve from 0.4 MPa for the pristine to 0.85 MPa for the 50 phr filled composite, although a slight decrease to 0.83 MPa is observed for the highest filled composite. The LAC increases with filler concentration but decreases as gamma photon energy rises. There is an increase in MAC value up to 50 Phr of chromium concentration, then a decline at 70 Phr, possibly due to agglomeration effects. The composite with 30Phr of WO₃ and 50Phr of Cr shows better results exhibiting MAC value of 0.0819 cm²/g at an energy level of 662 keV. Correspondingly, the Half-Value Layer (HVL) values decrease from 6.7 cm to 5.02 cm. A comparative study reveals a better performance of the silicone rubber reinforced with 30 phr WO₃ + 50 phr Cr comparable to that of lead & is also found to be lightweight.

Conclusion

The novel polymer composite material exhibits effective radiation shielding properties comparable to those of lead & barite, while also demonstrating good thermal and mechanical stability.

References

- Ambika, Nagaiah, N., Harish, V., Lokanath, N., Sridhar, M., Renukappa, N., & Suman, S. (2016). *Radiation Physics and Chemistry*, 130, 351–358.
- Jayakumar, S., Mani, V., Saravanan, T., Rajamanickam, K., Prabhu, A. D., & Philip, J. (2021). *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 138(42).

COMPREHENSIVE IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF RADIOLOGICAL DISPERSAL DEVICE (RDD) SCENARIOS: ADDRESSING CONVENTIONAL AND RADIOLOGICAL EFFECTS

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Keywords: RDD, impact assessment, exposure, blast, aerosol cloud.

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Introduction

Response to incidents involving Radiological Dispersal Devices (RDDs) is a multifaceted problem requiring technical expertise and strategic preparedness. While the likelihood of non-state entities employing RDDs is low, state-sponsored terrorism significantly elevates this threat. To counter such dangers, several countries have developed assessment tools like RODOS and ARGOS, focused on analyzing the dispersal effects of radioactive aerosols clouds. However, RDDs also generate conventional explosive impacts, such as blast waves and shrapnel spread. This shrapnel often becomes radioactively contaminated, intensifying injuries and creating localized radiation hotspots. Contaminated shrapnel complicates medical treatment by introducing radioactive material into wounds, raising exposure risks for victims and medical staff. Radiation hotspots further challenge first responders, necessitating strict exposure management during emergencies. Establishing exposure time limits is essential for reducing risks and ensuring effective operations. Nonetheless, current computational models do not fully integrate the conventional and radiological impacts of RDDs. A new set of computational tools has been developed to provide a comprehensive analysis of the combined effects in RDD scenarios.

Materials and Methods

The computational modules for RDD scenario evaluation are built within a modular framework, integrating analytical components to assess blast effects, shrapnel trajectories, and radioactive dispersion. Blast effects are estimated with semi-empirical models (Cooper 2018), calculating blast-over-pressure and damage. Mott's theory predicts fragment size and distribution, while Bishop's method computes contaminated shrapnel trajectories, accounting for aerodynamic and environmental factors. The Gaussian Puff

model, with Pasquill-Gifford adjustments, simulates radioactive aerosol dispersion, providing accurate contamination maps. Calculating exposure-time constraints assists in managing responder dose.

Results

The numerical computation modules have been developed using python language, and integrated to a web -based application for impact assessment. The application has been developed using client-server architecture, where the frontend of the application is implemented using Angular framework, and the backend using Python based FastAPI framework and PostgreSQL database. The system allows users to investigate a variety of RDD scenarios, which include studying the effects of blast, the spread of shrapnel, and the dispersion of aerosols. The outcomes of these analyses are presented in a structured manner and can be easily exported in PDF format.

Conclusion

A robust suite of numerical computational modules has been developed to assess RDD impacts. These modules bridge conventional and radiological effects, providing essential tools for emergency responders and planners. The user-friendly platform enhances training and strategic planning, improve readiness and response to RDD scenarios.

References

Cooper, P. W. Explosives Engineering. John Wiley Sons, 2018, July 19

CALCULATIONS OF EFFECTIVE RADIATION QUALITY FACTORS FOR HIGH-ENERGY COSMIC RAYS

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Introduction

The primary sources of radiation in space missions are the Van Allen Belts, Solar Particle Events, and Galactic Cosmic Rays (GCRs). Among these, GCRs expose astronauts to high-Z and high-energy particles, including protons, alpha particles, and heavier ions. The equivalent dose concept, which incorporates a radiation weighting factor (w_R), may overestimate doses at such high energies. Consequently, calculating the Quality factor (Q) is essential for accurately estimating dose equivalents. The Quality factor, which gauges the biological effectiveness of radiation dose, is defined differently by the ICRP and NASA. While ICRP bases Q on Linear Energy Transfer (LET), NASA considers the atomic number and energy of the radiation. Current astronaut dose assessments rely on ICRP-123 coefficients, utilize voxel phantoms, as outlined in ICRP-110 (ICRP, 2009). Recently, ICRP-145 introduced advanced mesh-type computational phantoms (MRCs) (Kim et al., 2018). Our study aims to estimate dose conversion factors using MRCs and Q values. As a preliminary investigation, this presentation describes our methodology for calculating Q and applying it through Geant4, a Monte Carlo simulation toolkit, within a water phantom model (Allison et al., 2016).

Materials and Methods

The ICRP-defined Quality factor function, segmented into three regions (below 10, 10 to 100, & >100 keV/ μ), was employed. For each Monte Carlo step in radiation transport simulations, LET was calculated using the G4Step function in the G4UserSteppingAction class of Geant4. Q was averaged over the absorbed dose rather than over the entire mass, as shown in Eqs.(1) & (2):

$$Q = \frac{1}{D} \int_{L=0}^{\infty} Q(L) D_L dL \quad \dots (1)$$

$$Q_T = \frac{1}{m_T D_T} \iint Q(L) D_L dL dm \quad \dots (2)$$

where D is absorbed dose, L is LET and m is mass. The energy deposited in each step was summed across events, and the square of this sum was used to estimate error via the Central Limit Theorem.

Results

Quality factors were calculated for protons, alpha particles, carbon, magnesium, and iron, with energies ranging from 1 MeV to 100 GeV. Data analysis, performed using the ROOT framework (Brun & Rademakers, 1997), showed that Q for protons decreased monotonically with energy, reaching a peak of 1.98 above 10 MeV. Q values for alpha particles, C, Mg, & Fe displayed skewed bell-shaped distributions, with peak Q values occurring at 20–25 for energies per nucleon of approximately 5, 25, 200, and 2500 MeV/ μ , respectively.

Conclusion

The calculated Quality factors align with published data (ICRP, 2013). This approach can be extended to MRCs for enhanced Quality factor calculations in space radiation protection.

References

- ICRP. 2013. *ICRP Publication 123. Ann. ICRP* 42(4).
- ICRP, 2009. *ICRP Publication 110. Ann. ICRP* 39 (2).
- Kim CH, et. al. *Ann ICRP*. 2018 Oct 47(3-4):45-62. doi: 10.1177/0146645318756231.
- Allison J., et. al. *Nucl Inst and Meth in Phy Research Section A:Volume 835*, 2016, 186-225.
- Brun R and Rademakers F., *Nucl. Inst. & Meth. in Phys. Res. A* 389 (1997) 81-86.

RADIOLOGICAL PROTECTION MEASURES DURING H-3 TRACER PREPARATION & INJECTION FOR HYDROLOGICAL INVESTIGATIONS

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Keywords: Tracer injection, core sampling, H-3, DAC, Protection factor

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Introduction:

Groundwater (GW) serves as a major source of drinking water in India and provides for 60% of India's irrigation needs and 85 percent of its rural domestic water supplies. In view of the ground water level fluctuations in urban areas of Bengaluru, a set of radiotracer experiments were carried out at certain sites in Bengaluru jointly by CGWB and IRAD, BARC for groundwater recharge studies. This abstract deals with the safety and radiological protection measures during various stages of the study undertaken.

Materials and Methods:

The Tritium radiotracer (low energy beta emitter with $\beta_{\max}=18\text{keV}$) as HTO is transported in a AERB type approved package by air and delivered to the destination city. The HTO with an initial concentration of about 0.5Ci/L has to undergo successive and multiple dilutions to bring down the concentration to a usable level of 20 $\mu\text{Ci/ml}$. This is done in a fume hood to take care of any inadvertent spills during handling. Tritium-in-air generated during handling is monitored using dry ice by the cold finger method to estimate potential internal exposures to the personnel handling the Tritium activity at the lab. Multiple sample vials have to be prepared for various injection sites. The entire process is carefully monitored by the accompanying health physicist/RSO. Handling precautions suggested during handling of high concentration and initial dilution procedure are double gloves, bottle respirator (Protection Factor=5) and TYVECTM suit worn above regular clothing. A ratio of 1 ml of the atmospheric condensation collected to 5ml of DIN based cocktail is used to count the sample-cocktail mixture in a Liquid Scintillation counter (LSC). Resultant activity in Bq/ml is converted into Bq/m³ of H-3 in air (with knowledge of the ambient air's absolute humidity). The activity can then be reported in

fractions of DAC in air[1]. The work carried out in the injection phase involves injection of about 2ml HTO (20 $\mu\text{Ci/ml}$) using a micropipette/medical syringe through a 5mm (dia)stiff brass pipe into a freshly dug hole of 500mm depth and 30mm diameter at each site. After injection, fresh soil from the dugout material is used to back-fill the injected holes. Brightly painted metallic markers are placed in four directions around the back filled cores for future identification and the precise GPS location is logged. In this stage, HP precautions comprise of gloves, lab-coats, rubber shoes and a wet cloth napkin in lieu of a bottle respirator. The HTO injection was done at five suitable sites selected by CGWB. Cold finger samples were also collected close to the points of injection. After conclusion of the monsoon season, H-3 movement in the soil due to monsoon recharge needs to be assessed, for which, various depths of the soil cores were extracted at depths of 0.5m, 1m & 1.5m. These soil cores are double sealed with location tags in PVC ZiplocTM bags for transfer to IRAD labs in BARC for moisture extraction and further analysis while following the earlier listed Health Physics precautions.

Results & conclusion:

Evaluation of cold finger samples for H-3 in air during dilution, injection and core extraction phases showed less than 0.01DAC of airborne Tritium (HTO) indicating radiologically safe procedures of the experiment.

References:

[1] Tritium Sampling and Measurement, M.J.Wood, R.G.C.McElroy, R.A.Surette and R.M.Brown, Health Physics Journal (Dec-1993)

ESTIMATION OF NATURAL RADIOACTIVITY IN SOIL SAMPLES FROM NAVALGUND, DHARWAD DISTRICT, KARNATAKA, INDIA

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Keywords: Activity concentration, absorbed dose, gamma-ray spectrometry, surface soil, hazards indices

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Introduction:

Soil, one of Earth's primary natural resources, contains minerals and organic components known as NORMs (Naturally Occurring Radioactive Materials), the concentrations of which depend on the nature of the parent rock and soil. The radiation emitted by these NORMs is referred to as terrestrial background radiation. The present study focuses on estimating natural radioactivity levels and radiation hazard indices in soil samples collected from Navalgund, located in the Dharwad District of Karnataka, India.

Materials and Methods:

Soil samples were collected from selected locations to represent varying geological and environmental conditions. Gamma spectrometry, utilizing a high-efficiency 4" × 4" NaI(Tl) detector, was employed to estimate activity concentrations of gamma-emitting radionuclides. Spectra obtained from the detector were analysed using a PC-based 1k multichannel analyzer system (WinTMCA 32). Each sample's spectra were acquired for a counting period of 60,000 seconds (16.67 hours). Assuming that the daughter products of ²³⁸U and ²³²Th are in equilibrium, the activity concentrations of these radionuclides were calculated using the prominent gamma photo peaks of their respective daughter products. Based on these activity concentrations, radiological parameters were calculated for all the samples.

Results and discussion

The activity concentrations of the radionuclides in the soil samples were found to be as follows: ²³⁸U: 31.25 ± 0.198 Bq/kg, ²³²Th: 54.74 ± 0.12 Bq/kg, ⁴⁰K: 252.44 ± 1.91 Bq/kg The mean gamma absorbed dose rate at a height of 1 meter above the ground was 34.47 nGy/h. Various radiological

parameters were also calculated, including the annual effective dose equivalent (AEDE), radium equivalent activity (Raeq), and external hazard index (Hex).

Conclusion:

The calculated values for the radiological parameters were within the safety limits recommended by international standards. The results suggest that the soil in the Navalgund region poses negligible radiological health risks, as all hazard indices remained within the safe thresholds. This study provides essential baseline data for radiological hazard assessments and environmental monitoring in the Dharwad District and will serve as a reference for future studies on natural radioactivity.

References

1. Ramola R.C., Gusain G.S., Manjari Badoni, Yogesh Prasad, Ganesh Prasad and Ramachandran T.V., ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, ⁴⁰K contents in soil samples from Garhwal Himalaya, India, and its radiological implications, *J. Radiol. Prot.*, 28, 379-385, 2008.
2. S. Rajesh, Avinash P R, B. R. Kerur and S. S. Anilkumar. Assessment of Natural radioactivity levels in soil samples of Bidar district by Gamma Spectrometry.

NOVEL TRILAYERED POLYMER COMPOSITE - A RADIATIVE PROTECTIVE MEDICAL WEAR

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Keywords: Polymer Composite, Gamma Shielding, Layered.

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Introduction

Gamma radiation is a powerful tool with wide-ranging applications, especially in medicine. However, it can be harmful if not handled properly. To mitigate these risks, effective radiation shielding is crucial. Traditional lead shielding, while effective, has limitations like toxicity and heaviness. This study explores polymer composites as a potential alternative to lead. The goal is to identify a polymer composite shield that offers superior performance in terms of radiation attenuation, lightweight and durability.

Materials and Methods

In the present study, tri-layered polymer composites with Liquid Silicone Rubber (LSR), due to its light weight and flexibility, as the matrix and chromium, bismuth and tungsten as fillers were fabricated by simple open mould technique. These fillers are distributed across the three layers at varying concentrations (30, 50 and 70 phr) to optimise radiation shielding properties. Multiple shielding parameters like Linear Attenuation Coefficient (LAC), Mass Attenuation Coefficient (MAC), Tenth and Half Value Layer (TVL, HVL), Mean Free Path (MFP), Atomic and Electronic Cross section (σ_a , σ_e) and Effective Atomic Number and Electron Density (Z_{eff} , n_e) were subsequently derived to evaluate the shielding efficiency of the materials (Kuttukaran et al 2023).

Results

The results indicate that increasing the filler concentration in the composites led to improved shielding properties at specific energies. As the photon energy increased, the shielding parameters generally decreased due to variations in photon interaction mechanisms at different energy ranges (Oto et al 2015). A comparative study revealed that the layered polymer composites exhibited superior mass attenuation coefficients across higher energy ranges starting from 662 keV when compared to lead & barite due to multiple absorption and scattering at boundary layers. Thus, the combination of 100

phr LSR with 70 phr of chromium, bismuth and tungsten demonstrated the best performance, particularly at 662 keV having values 0.369 cm²/g (MAC) and 1.089 cm⁻¹ (LAC) and density value of 1.7207g/cc.

Conclusion

The study successfully demonstrated the potentiality of novel tri-layered polymer composites as lightweight and flexible alternatives to traditional lead-based radiation shields. These composites are effective particularly at higher energies and excel in performance for applications in the medical field, especially in the development of protective wears like gloves, aprons etc.

References

- Kuttukaran, S. S. M R, Ambika. C, Malathi. & N, Nagaiah. (2023). *Materials Today Proceedings*, 89, 75-83.
- Oto, B., Yıldız, N., Akdemir, F., & Kavaz, E. (2015). *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, 85, 391-40.

GAMMA IRRADIATION APPLICATIONS IN THE FIELD OF MEDICAL, INDUSTRIAL AND AGRICULTURE AT IGCAR

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Introduction

In Radiation processing, a product or material is intentionally irradiated to improve, preserve or modify its characteristics. This process is carried out by placing the product in the vicinity of a radiation source for a fixed time interval whereby the product is exposed to radiation. The amount of energy required for realizing the desired effect in the product is determined through research.

Materials and Methods

Gamma-ray emitters like cobalt-60 and caesium-137, by virtue of their energy and fairly long half-life (cobalt-60- $T_{1/2}$ -5.27 years & 2.505 MeV; caesium-137- $T_{1/2}$ -30.1 years & 0.662 MeV), are preferable radiation sources. The radionuclide cobalt-60 is the most commonly used source for radiation processing because of its ease of production and in-solubility in water. Gamma Chamber is a compact, self-shielded research irradiator having preset volume for irradiation. Radiological Applications and Technology Division (RATD), IGCAR houses THREE Gamma Irradiation Chambers (GICs). In these two were new units installed in June 2024. These units were supplied by Board of Radiation and Isotope Technology (BRIT), Mumbai. The dose rates inside the irradiation volume of GICs are verified periodically by Fricke dosimeter consisting of air saturated acidic ferrous sulphate solution. The dose rates are calculated from the absorbance measurements of ferric ions formed as a result of irradiation.

Results

Researchers from facilities of IGCAR & BARCF are using these irradiators for assessing radiation stability characteristics of samples such as, polymer nano-composites, LED lights, CCD cameras, organic extractants and electronic components that find applications in high radiation fields. In addition, the irradiation requirements of educational and research institutions viz.,

Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Indian Council of Agricultural Research, Cancer Institute (WIA), Chennai, King Institute of Preventive Medicine and Research, Central Leather Research Institute, etc., are catered by these units. Human amniotic membranes, separated from the placenta of screened maternal donors are processed for use in burn patients, as graft over non-healing skin ulcers. The processed and pre-packed tissues are subjected to a radiation dose of 25 kGy for achieving high Sterility Assurance Level (SAL). Freeze dried bone samples harvested from cadavers are irradiated to 25 kGy for achieving high Sterility Assurance Level (SAL). The irradiated samples shall be used as a scaffold material for needy patients. Biomaterials imitating corneal extracellular matrix useful in treating corneal stromal injury under development in CLRI, Chennai are irradiated to 15 kGy for sterilization. Fresh sugarcane buds are irradiated to 15 Gy towards development of high sugared and red rot resistant sugarcane varieties. Seeds of millets and sesame and saplings of floral varieties are irradiated towards development of new varieties. Face masks being used as a protection measure during COVID-19 pandemic are irradiated (15 - 25 kGy) and their potency for reusability was analyzed using laboratory generated aerosols.

Conclusion

The use of gamma radiation has a wide range of applications in various industries. These include industries such as sterilization of medical products, food preservation and agriculture.

References

- Gamma Irradiators for Radiation Processing. IAEA. TecDOC.
- ISO 11137 – 1 Sterilization of health care products – Radiation.
- Radiation Processing of Food & Medical products –Technical Document, 2014, BRIT.

INTEGRATED PHOTON DOSE MEASUREMENT IN ZONE -2 AREAS IN INDUS ACCELERATOR COMPLEX

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Introduction

Indus Accelerator Complex houses two synchrotron radiation namely Indus-1 & Indus-2. Indus-1 is a 450 MeV electron storage ring whereas Indus-2 is a 2.5 GeV storage ring. There are 7 licensed beamline in Indus-1 whereas 19 beamlines are licensed for regular operation in Indus-2 by Atomic energy regularity board. These beamlines are regularly operated for carrying out scientific research by users from universities and national institutes.

The radiation environment in the complex consists of bremsstrahlung X-rays of high energy up to the energy of electrons in the storage ring due to interaction of electrons with accelerator structure and residual gas molecules in the vacuum chamber. The bremsstrahlung photon energy spectrum ranges up to the incident electron energy. Photo-neutrons which are generated due to the interaction of bremsstrahlung x-rays are also present in the complex. However the neutron dose rates are much lower compare to the bremsstrahlung doses.

The Indus complex is divided into 3 zones based on the radiation levels. They are zone-1(accessible area), zone-2(restricted area) and zone-3(prohibited area).

In present work, integrated photon dose in the zone -2 areas of Indus complex were measured using CaSO₄:Dy thermoluminescent dosimeters during the period, 2020 to 2024 in various sets of measurement. The paper gives the details of measurement and results obtained.

Materials and Methods

For the measurement TLDs were initially annealed and calibrated using Co-60 source.

For dose measurement 7 radiation monitoring stations were established in the Indus complex. Radiation monitoring stations consists of a cylindrical high density

polyethylene (HDPE) phantom of dimensions 30 cm x 30 cm. The TLDs were placed in the front surface of phantom facing the radiation for recording dose from all the conditions of Indus operation during measurement period like beam injection, storage and beam killing events.

As the spectrum measurements and simulation studies indicate that bremsstrahlung photons in zone-2 area are of the order of few MeV, no dose build up factors are applicable and hence not considered.

Results

TLD installed near to beamline-1 & 5 in Indus-1 have shown maximum dose up to 11 μ Sv/shift (8h) or 1.4 μ Sv/h in the beamline-1 area of Indus-1 experimental hall.

As per Indus radiation zoning criteria, maximum allowed radiation level in zone-2 area is 10 μ Sv/h, which works out to be 80 μ Sv/ shift (8 h). Based on the present measurement data if a person works in zone - 2 for 8 hours he may receive a maximum dose of \sim 11 μ Sv/shift (8 h), which is \sim 7 times lower than the allowed dose limit in zone-2 of Indus complex.

All the other locations in Indus complex showed doses close to background levels.

Conclusion

The integrated photon dose measurements carried out during the years 2020-2024 confirms that the radiation level in the zone -2 areas of Indus Accelerator complex are well within the acceptable limits of zone-2 criteria of Indus Accelerator Complex.

References

1. <http://www.rrcat.gov.in>

EFFECT OF UV-C RADIATION AND EDIBLE COATING ON CONTROLLING SPROUTING IN POTATO

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Introduction

Potatoes are an essential crop in developing countries because they may be used as a cash crop to sustain the incomes of small farmers and provide substantial yields on small pieces of land. Due to improper storage conditions cause sprouting, weight loss, rotting, greening, and sweetening potato losses during storage account for about 50% of crop production. Sprouting is a serious issue that reduces the nutritional value of potatoes and results in significant weight losses from the surface of the tuber. If consumed, solanine can harm both people and farm animals. Ionizing radiation, low temperature storage, and chemical treatments are thought to be substitute techniques for preventing sprouting.

Materials and Methods

A ventilated UV-C treatment structure was used for this investigation. The chamber was constructed using MS sheets and welded wire mesh. The size specifications are 95 cm in length, 40 cm in breadth and 95 cm in height with a storage capacity of 25 kg. It was equipped with two UV-C lamps of 15 W emitted at 253.7nm for each one. A total of 18kg of potatoes were treated in the UV-C at 15watts. The exposure durations of 30, 60 and 90 minutes respectively. To ensure a full exposure on the entire surface of the tubers, the position of the tubers was reversed upside down and were exposed to the same duration of UV light again. Three replicates for each treatment of UV-C are applied

Results

Weight loss for control samples were higher than the UV-C treated with essential oil edible coated potato samples. Weight loss generally increased with longer UV-C treatment durations and higher pulse electric field voltages. Weight loss ranged from 0.71% to 5.20% across different voltages. The firmness tends to decrease with longer UV-C

exposure durations, as seen in the decreasing trend in firmness values from week 1 to week 4. The total respiration rate of control samples was higher at the end of the storage. The potatoes treated with optimum voltage 30KV (60) with edible coating shows the least increase in respiration rate and less wrinkles on the surface of potato. All treatments were significantly delayed sprouting especially in 30KV (60minute) treatment, which stopped complete sprouting at the time of measurement

Conclusion

The duration of UV-C treatment (30, 60, 90 minutes) and the voltage of pulsed electric field (20kV, 30kV and 40kV) significantly influence the quality attributes of potatoes. Generally, exposure of UV-C radiation has antimicrobial properties, reducing the microbial load on the surface of potatoes. The combination of UV-C treatment and PEF treated edible coating solution at 30KV (60) shows effective results compared to others. This integrated method (UV-C with PEF) demonstrates potential in extending the shelf life of potatoes by effectively inhibiting sprouting and maintaining desirable quality

References

1. Emragi, E., Kalita, D., & Jayanty, S. S. (2022). Effect of edible coating on physical and chemical properties of potato tubers under different storage conditions. *LWT*, *153*, 112580.
2. Hassan, H., Abd El-Rahman, A., & Liela, A. (2016). Sprouting suppression and quality attributes of potato tubers as affected by post-harvest UV-C treatment under cold storage. *Int. J. Adv. Res*, *4*, 241-253.

RADIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT OF SOIL SAMPLES AROUND K130 AND K500 CYCLOTRON VAULTS

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Introduction

Naturally Occurring Radioactive Materials (NORMs) are present in the soil in trace quantities. In addition to these natural radionuclides, there are anthropogenic radionuclides, which are artificially generated for various industrial applications. At Variable Energy Cyclotron Centre (VECC), K130 cyclotron (operational since 1977) and the recently operational K500 cyclotron produce energetic heavy ion beams that generate secondary neutron and gamma radiation. These neutrons can activate stable isotopes in surrounding materials, making them radioactive, particularly surrounding high-radiation areas like the cyclotron vault and cave. Prolonged neutron exposure raises concerns about potential radioactivity in the surrounding soil, necessitating an understanding of the isotopes produced via neutron activation. This knowledge is critical for assessing occupational and environmental safety. To address this, a study was conducted surrounding VECC's high radiation zone (Vault and Cave), focusing on identifying radioactive isotopes in soil samples resulting from continuous cyclotron operation.

Materials and Methods

Soil samples were collected from six locations from the outside of both the K130 and K500 cyclotron building, with each sample taken from a depth of up to 20 cm from the surface and approximately 3 kg collected per site. After drying for 24 hours, the samples were sieved through a 2-mm mesh to remove large impurities and homogenized. The prepared soil was placed in airtight 250 ml PVC containers, sealed, and stored for a month to establish secular equilibrium between the progeny of any naturally occurring radioactive materials (NORM). The analysis was conducted in the Low Background Laboratory of the Health

Physics Unit (HPU) at VECC. A closed-end, horizontally mounted HPGe detector (Make: BSI; Model GCD-30 185) with 4096 channels, coupled with a computer-based MCA acquisition board (Make: GBS Elektronik; Model: MCA 527), was used for the measurement. Data acquisition and analysis were performed using Spectra-lineGP software, with a counting time of 5000 seconds for calibration, background, and sample measurements.

Results

It is found that the radioactivity in the soil samples primarily originates from natural radionuclides. ⁴⁰K is the major radionuclide detected in the range of ~220-350 Bq/kg across the samples. Other naturally occurring radionuclides, such as ²³⁸U and ²³²Th and their progeny were found in range of 25-60 and 20 -75 Bq/kg respectively. The average Radium equivalent activity was also calculated and found ~125 Bq/kg. While the soil samples do show radioactivity from natural sources, there was no evidence of neutron activation products in the gamma spectrum indicating no soil activation due to cyclotron operation.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the cyclotron operation at VECC campus indicated no radio-activation of soil due to operation of the facilities. This study is also important to ensure the continued safety of the VECC environment and its workers.

References

Mohammad Kamal Hossain et al., (2010) *Journal of Environmental Protection*, **1**, 10-14.

PRELIMINARY DOSE ASSESSMENT INSIDE VAULT DURING OPERATION AND MAINTENANCE OF K-500 CYCLOTRON AT VECC

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Keywords: neutron dose rate, main probe, bore probe, Faraday cup

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Introduction

The K-500 superconducting cyclotron at VECC accelerates heavy ions to higher energies for advanced research in nuclear physics and other areas. However, the operation of this accelerator poses significant challenges in radiation protection, primarily due to complex radiation field resulting from different nuclear reactions of the ion beam with structural materials and experimental targets. One of the critical safety considerations for the K-500 accelerator is the production of neutrons and gamma rays as secondary radiation, due to accelerated ion beam hitting different accelerator components. To ensure radiation safety, a comprehensive study of the radiation environment within the cyclotron vault was conducted, focusing on identifying hotspots and mapping dose distributions during operation and maintenance.

Materials and Methods

Radiation dose measurements were conducted at various locations within the cyclotron vault where beam interactions are likely to occur. Four locations probable for elevated radiation levels were identified for the study. The beam tuning process often results in beam interactions with the Faraday Cups (FC01, FC04) which are used to measure beam currents. Hence, near FC01 and FC04 radiation doses were expected to be high. Dose rate (neutron and gamma) for the N⁵⁺ beam with an energy of 30 MeV/A was measured at a distance of 1 m from these locations using Neutron REM meter, Make: Ludlum, Model: 42-49B & 30 and Gamma Survey Meter, Make: Automess, Model: 6150 AD. Additionally, dose rates at two spots near the main probe and bore probe inside the cyclotron machine, prone to beam interactions during acceleration, were measured during maintenance.

Results

During operation for the N⁵⁺ beam with an energy of 30 MeV/A, the average normalized dose rates at FC01 were measured as 1.75 mSv/h/nA for neutrons and 28.1 μSv/h/nA for gamma radiation. At FC04, the corresponding normalized dose rates were 1.77 mSv/h/nA for neutrons and 30 μSv/h/nA for gamma. During maintenance, the average dose rates observed at the main probe and bore probe were 1.5 mSv/h and 3.0 mSv/h, respectively.

Conclusion

The identification of radiation hotspots and dose mapping will help in minimizing radiological hazards and assessing probable dose received in case of any emergency. The findings emphasize the need for more extensive radiation mapping for different ion beams with varied parameters and also detailed study of radioactivity generated from the nuclear interactions.

References

1. Safety manual, K-500
2. S K Mishra et al, AOCRP6, India, 2023

RADIATION SOURCE TERM FOR PETAWATT TI:SAPPHIRE LASER PLASMA FACILITY AT RRCAT

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Keywords: Laser plasma, FLUKA Monte Carlo, Source term.

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Introduction

The concept of table top electron accelerator is being realised through wake field acceleration during laser plasma interaction in gas jet target. At laser peak intensities $\geq 10^{18}$ W/cm², the laser plasma produced on thin metallic foil can generate high energy electrons (100s of MeV). These electrons can penetrate through the thin foil and generates sheath field at the target rear surface. The electric field generated is very high ($> \text{TeV/cm}$), thus ionizes the hydro-carbon contaminants at the target surface and accelerates protons (10s of MeV). A Petawatt Ti:sapphire laser plasma facility is under commissioning at RRCAT for studies on generation of high energy electron, proton and ions. The high energy electrons and protons thus produced will interact with the target and the experimental chamber to produce secondary radiation like bremsstrahlung and neutrons. Hence the radiation safety assessment is very much essential. The paper describes the evaluation radiation source term for bremsstrahlung, neutrons and residual activity in the facility and its safety implications.

Materials and Methods

In the Petawatt facility, 100 MeV electrons, 5 GeV electrons and 50 MeV protons are expected to be generated from solid or gaseous targets. Radiation dose rate from bremsstrahlung, neutrons and induced activity generated in the facility are evaluated using FLUKA code. Since radiation type and yield strongly depend upon the material and geometry of the target, a conservative approach of conversion efficiency of 50% laser energy to particle flux is used for calculating the flux of the radiation produced (Liang *et al* 2017). Also a continuous irradiation for 500 shots at an interval of 10

sec, followed by 1 sec and 6 min cooling times was assumed for calculation of induced radioactivity. Prior to the simulation, benchmarking of the simulation methodology was performed for energies up to 1 GeV (electron) and 250 MeV (proton) with reported data.

Results

The radiation source term obtained for bremsstrahlung and photo-neutron from electrons were 0.963 & 0.015 mSv/pulse (100 MeV) and 0.192 & 0.029 mSv/pulse (5 GeV). The neutron dose from 50 MeV protons was 0.245 mSv/pulse. Uncertainties in the results are within 3%. The dose rate from residual activity after 1 sec of cooling time at 1 m from the plasma chamber was found to be 1.21, 3.05 and 96.90 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ for 100 MeV electrons, 5 GeV electrons and 50 MeV protons respectively. The dose rate reduced to 7.39 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ (proton case) and less than 1 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ (electron case) after 6 min cooling time. Exposure control during maintenance will be done based on actual measurements and entry will be permitted with TLD badges.

Conclusion

The radiation source term due to 100 MeV electron, 5 GeV electron and 50 MeV proton was evaluated for Petawatt facility. The residual dose rate after a cooling period of 1 sec is higher due to activity build up from short lived isotopes. The dose rate reduced significantly after 6 min. cooling period and found acceptable.

References

- Liang T., Bauer J. M., Liu J. C. and Rokni S. H. (2017) *Radiation Protection Dosimetry*, **175** (3), 304–312.

RADIOLOGICAL STATUS OF HTS FACILITY AT RRCAT, INDORE

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Keywords: SCRF cavity, cryo module, source term

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Introduction

Superconducting RF cavities (SCRF) are required for accelerating protons to high energies. These bare cavities are first tested at Vertical Test Stand (VTS) facility for measuring their quality factor. After qualifying at VTS the dressed RF cavities are tested in a Horizontal Test Stand (HTS) facility for evaluating their actual performance expected when used for accelerating protons. HTS facility was established at RRCAT, Indore to qualify two fully dressed SCRF cavities. During the testing of the SCRF, RF power is fed to the cavity (single cell or 5 cell) to generate high field gradient. The radiation environment in this facility consists of bremsstrahlung x-rays and photo-neutrons generated by the field emitted (FE) electrons within the cavity. The paper describes the radiation safety aspects of the operation of HTS facility at RRCAT, Indore.

Materials and Methods

Radiation source term was estimated assuming maximum energy of FE electrons (25 MeV) equal to the maximum field gradient generated across the cavity. FE current assumed to be 2 μ A from the 50 W beam power and 1% of field emitted electrons attaining maximum energy of 25 MeV along the axis (Bruce Hanna *et al* 2012). Source term for bremsstrahlung x-ray and neutron from medium Z materials are estimated (Swanson W P *et al* 1979) for the shielding assessment. GM based area radiation monitors (Canberra, USA make) inside vault and radiation monitors (25 litre ion chambers-ECIL, India make) in accessible areas were installed for continuously monitoring the radiation level. Radiation survey was

performed using Victoreen survey meter (Photon) and Wendi rem-meter (Neutron).

Results

Radiation source terms were estimated to be 2.6 Sv/h (photon) and 0.139 Sv/h (neutron). Radiation shielding of 1.8 m ordinary concrete (OC) and 12 cm thick mild steel in forward direction (0^0 for 1st cavity), 1.6 m OC in lateral direction (90^0) and 2.3 m OC in the forward direction (0^0 for 2nd cavity) were provided (Electric field in both the cavities are in opposite direction). During testing of 5 cell SCRF cavity, maximum photon field of 24.7 mSv/h was observed inside vault at 4.60 MV/m field gradient and less than 1 μ Sv/h in the accessible areas outside the vault. The photon and neutron dose rate were found to be less than 1 μ Sv/h in control room and other nearby areas.

Conclusion

Radiological surveillance was provided during operation of HTS facility. The radiation field in the accessible area remains less than 1 μ Sv/h during the 5 cell SCRF cavity testing at HTS facility. As the radiation levels inside the vault is high, radiation interlock systems, such as search and scram switches and door interlocks are to be maintained in a healthy state to prevent any inadvertent entry and radiation exposure.

References.

- Hanna B. (2012) *Technical Report on Estimate of X-Ray Shielding for Operation of HTS-2 Horizontal Test Cave*
- Swanson W. P. (1979), *Technical Reports Series No. 188*, International Atomic Energy Agency, Vienna

IMPACT OF WALL SCATTERING AND MAZE GEOMETRY ON NEUTRON DOSE DISTRIBUTION IN A PROTON IRRADIATION CAVE

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Keywords: neutron dose, in-scattering factor, maze design, Monte Carlo

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Introduction

In a proton irradiation cave, scattered neutrons from the surrounding walls significantly influence the overall neutron fluence profile, creating deviations from the $1/r^2$ law traditionally used for neutron dose estimation away from source (beam dump). This deviation is especially critical in caves with multiple mazes, where if scattered neutron contributions are not considered properly, it can lead to underestimations in dose calculations. In the present study, Monte Carlo simulations have been carried out to assess the effect of scattering of neutrons through the walls and maze opening area inside the proposed cave.

Materials and Methods

In the present study, a proton cave with room dimensions of 15 m x 5 m is considered where 18 MeV, 10 μ A proton beam is directed straight towards the beam dump (material: Cu, thickness 0.1 cm). A concrete maze structure is present to reduce the streaming of neutrons generated due to proton interaction with the target. A space of 1.6 m is maintained inside the maze to avail a passage for transportation of instruments inside the cave room. To understand the effect of surrounding wall and other geometrical parameters, simulations have been carried out considering typical cave room ceiling heights, for e.g., 3.5 m and 2 m, which also reflect different maze cross sectional areas. Simulations are performed with the FLUKA (G. Battistoni et al, 2015) Monte Carlo code (version 4-3.4), employing $4E+9$ histories and maintaining relative statistical errors below 5%. At first, simulations are carried out to obtain neutron fluence without local shielding around the beam dump, assuming 1 m-thick surrounding walls. Then, two cases have been compared: (a) $H^*(10)$ scattered: neutron dose equivalent with this present geometry, (b)

$H^*(10)$ direct: no surrounding wall. Different points have been chosen from the beam dump in the forward direction as well as inside the maze and the ratio of $H^*(10)$ scattered and $H^*(10)$ direct, referred as in-scattering factor, have been estimated.

Results

The simulation results indicate that with increasing distance, the scattering contribution first increases, and then decreases. The position of the peak and the amount of decrease depends on the room dimension and distance of walls from the source position. At the entrance point of maze inside the cave i.e. the mouth position, the in-scattering factor varies from 2.4 to 2.1 depending on maze opening area. Inside the first leg of the maze, this factor is maximum at locations where it is more closely surrounded by wall; thus, hotspots of higher neutron dose can be observed at those locations. Similar observation was also given by Tesch (1982) who used a factor of 2.0 for a passageway of approximately 2 m² cross section.

Conclusion

This study highlights the significant role of wall scattering and maze geometry in determining neutron dose distributions within proton irradiation caves. This factor is influenced by the maze opening size, ceiling height, and proximity of walls, with localized hotspots of higher dose observed in areas closely surrounded by walls.

References

- G. Battistoni et al (2015) *Annals of Nuclear Energy* **82**, 10-18. K. Tesch. (1982) *Particle Accelerators*, **12**, 169- 175

EFFECT OF MORPHOLOGY OF BISMUTH OXYIODIDE BASED FLEXIBLE COMPOSITES ON HIGH-ENERGY RADIATION ATTENUATION

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Introduction

Usually high-density and high-atomic number fillers are necessary to obtain desirable X-ray attenuation characteristics from radiation shields [1]. Bi-nanoparticles and its different oxyhalides are attractive choice for this purpose. However, the effect of heterogenous morphology generated due to alternation of addition of precursor on attenuation has not been studied previously. Herein two different kind of heterogeneous morphology has been produced and their X-ray attenuation characteristics have been evaluated.

Materials and Methods

Two types of BiOI were prepared by alternating the sequence of addition of precursor resulting different kind of nanoparticles. Subsequently, Polycaprolactone composites (PCL/BiOI) with carbon nanotubes was prepared by solution mixing procedure. These nanocomposites were stacked together for X-ray attenuation studies.

Results

The X-ray transmittances of the composites were measured using a diagnostic X-ray machine at two different energy 30 kVp and 120 kVp. The pristine polymers did not show any noticeable reduction in X-ray transmission. As expected with addition of BiOI filler the X-ray attenuation increased significantly. The X-ray attenuated was quantified by comparing the thickness required for 80% drop of initial intensity. It was found that the composites with BiOI (I-first) exhibited the thickness of 0.3 mm whereas that for BiOI (Bi-first) was 0.42 mm. The difference in attenuation efficiency for two types of composites may be due to the extent of distribution of BiOI (I-first) and BiOI (Bi-first) in PCL composites. The observation was supported by morphology inspection of composites as well. It was observed that the BiOI (I-first) distributed well compare to BiOI (Bi-first) in PCL matrix leveraged attenuation characteristics of composites at much lower thickness. Mechanical properties like tensile modulus and tensile

strength are important properties to study for probing the flexibility of composites. Pristine PCL shows tensile modulus of 353 MPa which has a good agreement with literature reported value. With addition of BiOI (Bi-first) the tensile modulus become 397 MPa and that for BiOI(I-first) composites was 420 MPa. The greater modulus of BiOI (I-first) was due to the better load transfer between PCL macromolecules and BiOI (I-first) nanoparticles.

Conclusion

This study investigated the effect of two different types of nanoparticles into the X-ray shielding capabilities of PCL based composites. The findings indicated a significant relationship between the mechanical characteristics of these composites and the sequence of addition of precursor which was able to tune the morphology of nanoparticles. It was found that BiOI (I-first) was able to exhibited better dispersion and distribution inside PCL matrix, which imparts positive effect on mechanical properties and X-ray attenuation characteristics. These results implied that through meticulous optimization of filler morphology by tuning the synthesis route, it was possible to develop flexible shields with superior X-ray attenuation.

References

[1] Suman S. K. et. al. (2023) Polymer Composites **44**, 5819-5829.

CHARACTERIZATION OF RADIOACTIVE WASTE GENERATED DURING ⁹⁹MO BATCH PRODUCTION

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Keywords: ⁹⁹Mo production, Liquid/solid waste, radioisotope characterization, γ spectrometry

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Introduction

In nuclear medicine, ^{99m}Tc, a decay product of ⁹⁹Mo is among the most versatile and essential radionuclides for diagnostic imaging. High-purity molybdenum trioxide (45-90 g of MoO₃, >99.5% per batch) target is irradiated in the high flux research reactor (thermal neutron flux of 1.8×10^{14} n/cm²/s) yielding ⁹⁹Mo via ⁹⁸Mo(n, γ)⁹⁹Mo reaction. ⁹⁹Mo is processed at Isotope production facility at BARC by dissolving the irradiated target in 4N NaOH at 60°C. The sodium molybdate (Na₂MoO₄) solution is filtered and dispensed for clinical use. Characterization of radioactive waste produced during ⁹⁹Mo batch production is presented.

Materials and Methods

During the regular batch production, approximately 200ml of liquid waste and around 80 g of solid waste are generated. Annually, 40-45 weekly production batches are processed. Generally, the stored waste products are transferred to waste management facility after a decay of 2-3 months. Samples extracted from waste stream of six different batches (four liquid samples and two solid samples) were analyzed via gamma spectrometry. The percentage activity of each radionuclide is calculated with respect to the production date.

Results

Gamma spectrometry analysis revealed a consistent presence of ⁹⁹Mo, ⁵⁹Fe, ⁶⁰Co, and ^{92m}Nb across liquid waste samples, with Mo-99 showing a predominant average of 98.5% of total radioactivity. Minor isotopes including ⁵⁹Fe, ⁶⁰Co, and ^{92m}Nb averaged at 0.003%, 0.004%, and 1.53% respectively. Solid samples exhibited diverse isotopic profile, including fission products (FP) such as ¹³⁷Cs (0.03%), ¹⁰⁶Ru (0.13%), and ⁹⁵Zr (0.07%) alongside primary isotopes ⁹⁹Mo

(97.24%) and ⁶⁰Co (1.13%). Additionally, ⁵¹Cr (0.9%) was present alongside trace levels (~0.1%) of ¹³⁴Cs, ⁶⁵Zn, ¹⁰³Ru, ¹⁵⁴Eu, and ⁹⁵Nb. The presence of FPs like ¹³⁷Cs, ¹⁰⁶Ru, ⁹⁵Zr, ¹³⁴Cs, ¹⁰³Ru and activation products viz. ⁶⁰Co, ⁵¹Cr and ⁵⁹Fe in solid waste suggests minor surface contamination of the target container or its activation during irradiation at reactor prior to reaching Isotope production facility.

Conclusion

From the present study, it is concluded that the radioactivity content of annual radioactive waste generated at this ⁹⁹Mo production facility is of the order of 30 μ Ci in liquid stream, which contained predominantly short-lived radionuclides, whereas the activity content in solid waste is about 9 mCi (radioactivity concentration in Bq/g * decay factor for 2.5 months storage period * no. of annual production batches i.e 45 * 80g) due to the presence of long-lived isotopes. Notably, this cumulative radioactivity is several orders of magnitude lower than the annual ⁹⁹Mo production activity (~900 Ci). ⁹⁹Mo (T_{1/2}- 2.75 d) decays almost completely to ⁹⁹Tc during the storage at the facility. The residual activity of ⁹⁹Tc (T_{1/2}- 2.14 x 10⁵ y) in the waste stream is negligibly small compared to its exemption value, confirming the waste's compliance with regulatory standards and negligible radiological impact.

References

- Shreenivas, V., Narayani, K., et al. (2012) Proc. IARP National Conference, IARPNC2012, Mangalore.
- IAEA (2023) IAEA Safety Standards Series No. GSG-17, IAEA, Vienna

NEUTRON YIELD AND SPECTRUM FROM PHOTO-FISSION TARGET BY 50 MEV ELECTRON BREMSSTRAHLUNG

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Introduction

The fissions induced by high energy xrays produced by electron accelerators find immense use in quantification of fissile materials, producing radioactive ion beams (RIB), rare isotopes etc. (Essabaa et al. (2003), Priyamvada M. Dighe et al. (2019), S Selek et al (2015). The neutron spectra and the yield from this reactions vary with the X-ray spectra and the target combination and these data forms the basis for radiation shielding requirements. This paper presents the photo-fission yield and the corresponding neutron yield from the various uranium carbide targets (UCx) intended to be used for the production of RIB.

Materials and Methods

The studies were done using Fluka (Version 4.3.2.) Monte Carlo simulations (G. Battistoni, et al. (2015), <https://fluka.cern>). A pencil beam of energy 50 MeV electrons falling on a thick tungsten target of 4.5 mm thick is simulated. The geometry of the simulation is as follows. The tungsten target is followed by a graphite block of thickness 30 mm to stop the transmitted electrons and UCx photo fission target. The length of the photofission target assumed in 21.45 cm. Photon stopper of material tungsten is placed after the fission target. The bremsstrahlung produced from the tungsten target induces the fission reactions. The neutron yield and spectra are scored using USRBDX option of the Fluka code. The total neutrons produced from the photo neutrons from the tungsten target, UCx target, and stopper and the fission neutrons from the UCx target as well are scored. Simulations were made by changing the number of carbon atoms of UCx target from 2 to 8.

Results and discussion

Neutron yields: The neutron produced are photo-neutrons from tungsten and uranium and fission neutrons from Uranium carbide target. The total neutron yield from

the system is estimated to be $7.69\text{E}+13$ n s⁻¹ mA⁻¹ and $7.06\text{E}+13$ n s⁻¹ mA⁻¹ for the UC2 target and UC8 targets respectively. The corresponding fission rates are $7.04\text{E}+12$ s⁻¹ mA⁻¹ and $5.97\text{E}+12$ s⁻¹ mA⁻¹. Photo neutron yield from the tungsten target and the photon stopper are estimated separately and found to be $4.15\text{E}+13$ n s⁻¹ mA⁻¹. Neutron spectrum: The neutron spectrum obtained has 60% of neutrons upto 1 MeV energy, 39.9% are in between 1 MeV to 10 MeV and 0.1 % falls above 10 MeV. These fractions are important for estimating the shielding requirements and quantifying the induced activity in air and structural materials.

Conclusion

The neutron yield and the energy spectra of a typical uranium photo fission target produced by 50 MeV electron bremsstrahlung beams studied in detail by changing the composition of uranium-carbide target. By changing the target composition, UC2 to UC8, the fission yield and the neutron yield decreases by 15% and 8% respectively.

References

- S. Essabaa et al. (2003) Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research B204, 780–784.
- Priyamvada M. Dighe et al. (2019) Nuclear Inst. and Methods in Physics Research, A 946 ,162624. S
- Selek et al (2015) J. Phys.: Conf. Ser. 590 012059.
- Website: <https://fluka.cern>
- G. Battistoni, et al. (2015) Annals of Nuclear Energy 82, 10-18.

COMPARATIVE SHIELDING EFFICACY OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS AS LEAD ALTERNATIVES FOR GAMMA SHIELDING

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Introduction

Gamma radiation is widely used in nuclear industries, healthcare, research, and various other sectors, increasing the demand for effective shielding materials to ensure personnel safety. Traditional gamma shields like lead offer high attenuation due to their density and atomic number, but lead's toxicity, weight, and chemical instability make it less desirable. Consequently, there is a growing demand for alternative materials that are safer, lighter, and maintain effective gamma shielding properties. High-density, high-Z metal oxides such as bismuth oxide (Bi_2O_3), tungsten oxide (WO_3), and barium sulfate (BaSO_4), when embedded in polymer matrices, show promise as lead-free shielding solutions. This study uses Monte Carlo simulations to compare the gamma shielding efficacy of these composites with lead across different photon energies, evaluating their potential as viable lead replacements for radiation protection.

Materials and Methods

In practice, Bi_2O_3 , WO_3 , and BaSO_4 are embedded into polycarbonate, chosen as the matrix for its amorphous structure and ability to evenly distribute nanoparticles, enhancing radioprotective properties. In this study, Monte Carlo code (Ferrari et al., 2005) was employed to model dose rates for various shielding configurations using these materials. A spherical gamma source, either a high-energy photon emitter (Co-60, Cs-137) or a low-energy gamma emitter (Tc-99m), was placed within a cylindrical shield backed by a thin stainless-steel support. Dose rates were measured at a 5 cm distance outside the shield and compared with those from a lead shield for reference. In the MCNP material card, the shielding materials were represented by their pure elemental compositions, excluding the polymer matrix, with densities

based on values provided in Table 1 of Mehrara et al. (2021).

Results

The dose rate at a distance of 5 cm from the shielding surface is compared for each type of shielding material and for each radionuclide source. The ratio of dose rates at the detector location with the composite shield to that with lead is calculated for each radionuclide with various gamma energy emitters ($R = D_x/D_{\text{lead}}$), where $x = \text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3$, WO_3 , and BaSO_4 . It is observed that the value of R exceeds 1.5 for high-energy gamma emitters, such as Co-60 and Cs-137. However, for low-energy gamma emitters, the R -value is approximately 1 for Bi_2O_3 and WO_3 , while for BaSO_4 , the value is higher due to its lower density. For lower energy photons due to dominance of photo electric effect with high electron dense elements like W, Bi the shielding effectiveness remains as good as lead. At higher photon energies, as discussed by Mehrara et al. (2021), the mass attenuation coefficient of Bi_2O_3 decreases, leading to a greater contribution from Compton scattering. As a result, the shielding effectiveness becomes relatively less efficient.

Conclusion

The results showed that the composite materials have promising gamma radiation shielding properties, particularly for low-energy gamma rays. Hence, these materials can be used as lead-free alternative for radiation.

References

- Mehrara, R., Malekie, S., Kotahi, S.M.S. et al. (2021) Sci Rep 11, 10614.
Ferrari A, Sala P R, Fasso A and Ranft J (2005) Yellow Report 200510.INFN/TC_05/11, SLAC-R-773.

DOSE RATE ASSESSMENT AND SHIELDING THICKNESS ESTIMATION FOR 6MEV LINAC FACILITY

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Introduction

LINAC device is a source of high energy penetrating radiation, widely used in medical, industrial and research application. The proposed LINAC facility will be used for radiation processing application like modification of polymeric materials, medical devices sterilization, waste treatment and food preservation. The proposed LINAC device will be operated in pulse mode with duty cycle 5ms. The maximum bunch current of LINAC device will be 100mA with an electron exit energy 6.0 MeV. The average electron flux is $6.23E+17$ electrons/cm²/s [1, 2]. The electron beam will be passed through copper target caused generation of bremsstrahlung radiation-a continuous photon energy spectrum. The designed workload value is $6.5E+03$ mSv week⁻¹. In the current study, simulation code MCNP is used to estimate angular and energy distribution of bremsstrahlung radiation per incident electron. The dose rate within and just outside facility estimated from absorbed energy in ionization chamber by simulation technique and deterministic code CGQAD [3]. The shielding thickness was estimated based on the requirement of effective dose rate of 0.04 mSv week⁻¹ in normal occupancy area.

Materials and Methods

The LINAC facility produced electron beam from photocathode material using laser beam wavelength of 450nm. The electrons are accelerated with 120MV/m electric field gradient to achieve the exit energy of 6.0 MeV. These electrons pass through copper target to bremsstrahlung radiations. An electron transport simulation estimated the Bremsstrahlung photon intensity per incident electron $5.07E-03$ photons/cm²/sec with maximum photon energy 6MeV. Nearly 61% photons are in the forward direction ($\theta < 60^\circ$), 26% photons emitted sideways and 13% photons emitted into backward direction ($150^\circ < \theta < 180^\circ$). Energies are grouped into suitable bins to estimate dose rates. The dose rate mapping estimated at important location where direct or indirect human occupancy is possible. Photon energies

are continuous, so dose rate are evolved for one duty cycle using absorbed energy in 1cm x 3cm air cylinder equivalent to ion chamber and verified with CGQAD. The estimated dose rate for average electron flux at Iso-centre is 6.45 Sv week⁻¹. The shielding thickness is evaluated with consideration of dose limit in uncontrolled area near wall. This dose limit leads to contact dose rate on wall of 0.04 mSv week⁻¹ with use factor (U=1) and occupancy factor (T=1).

Results

Total 20 dose points were identified within and around the proposed facility to estimate dose rates. The dose rates at primary and secondary barrier $4.8E+02$ mSv week⁻¹ and 1.64 mSv week⁻¹ respectively. These barriers are at 3m distance from LINAC device head including 1m thick concrete wall. 3.1 TVL at primary barrier and 1.0 TVL at secondary barrier reduced the dose rate below 0.04 mSv week⁻¹.

Conclusion

In 6MeV LINAC facility bremsstrahlung photons are generated through copper target around 61% photons emitted in forward direction. Higher shielding thickness needed at primary barrier. It reduced the dose rate below acceptable dose limit. The dose rate at 1.0m from the wall of facility is less than 0.041 mSv week⁻¹ due to suggested shielding thickness.

References

1. "Structural shielding Design and Evaluation for Megavoltage X-ray and Gamma Ray Radiotherapy Facility" NCRP Report 151 (December 31 2005)
2. "Radiation Protection for Particle Accelerator Facility." NCRP Report No 144 (March 4 2005)
3. Subhshaiha, Sarangapanii GUI2QAD-3D A graphical user interface for QAD –CGPIC program –June 2001

ASSESSMENT OF LEAD EQUIVALENCE IN LEAD GLASS USED FOR RADIATION SHIELDING APPLICATIONS

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Introduction

Lead glass, a type of glass infused with lead oxide, is widely used in shielding applications for its ability to attenuate radiation while maintaining optical transparency, making it ideal for protective windows in medical, industrial, and nuclear settings. Radiology utilizes ionizing radiation for diagnosing and treating various medical conditions. Radiology professionals are regularly exposed to ionizing radiation, which poses health risks if appropriate protective measures are not in place. One effective means of protecting the eyes from radiation exposure is through the use of lead glasses. Materials used for manufacturing protective devices against diagnostic X-rays complies with specifications outlined in IEC 61331-1, which require the attenuation equivalent thickness to be expressed in terms of lead equivalence (mm Pb) for specific radiation qualities [1]. Lead equivalence (LE), indicated in mm Pb, represents the thickness of lead that provides equivalent attenuation provided by the material for a given radiation energy.

Materials and Methods

Measurements are conducted using a 320 kV X-ray machine (Model: MG325, YXLON International). The air kerma rate is measured under three conditions: (a) without the test object in the radiation beam, (b) with the test object in the beam, and (c) with reference lead sheets of varying thicknesses (0.1 mm, 1 mm, 2 mm) in the beam. The measurements are taken using a secondary standard ionization chamber (A4 Exradin, 30 cc nominal volume) and a PTW Unidos E electrometer. To ensure accurate determination of the attenuation properties, a narrow-beam geometry is maintained throughout the measurements. Narrow beam geometry setup minimizes the contribution of scattered radiation, ensuring that attenuation is attributed solely to primary photons. Attenuation ratio, A_n is determined using the relation:

$$A_n = \frac{\dot{K}_o - \dot{K}_B}{\dot{K}_I - \dot{K}_B} \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

where, \dot{K}_o is the air kerma rate without the lead glass in the radiation beam, \dot{K}_I is the air kerma rate with the lead glass in the radiation beam, and \dot{K}_B is the air kerma rate due to background radiation. Based on user requirement, X-ray beams (40 kV to 160 kV) are established and characterised as per the recommendations of IEC-61331 -1. HVL of these beams fulfils the requirement of the IEC. The lead glass sample is placed near the collimator and A4 ionization chamber at a distance of 200 cm, from the focal spot of X ray tube. Lead equivalence (mm Pb) is determined by comparing the attenuation of the lead glass to that of measured attenuation ratios of lead sheets (interpolation between nearest matching points) using the linear or exponential interpolation.

Results

The lead equivalence and attenuation ratio of lead glass samples are determined for various users, which depends on the thickness and the specific composition of the samples. For a lead glass of ~2 mm lead equivalence, typical measurement uncertainty is better than $\pm 8.0\%$.

Conclusion The composition of protective materials, such as lead glass, is typically undisclosed by manufacturers instead, is specified in terms of lead equivalence (mm Pb), which depends on the energy of the X-rays and thickness of the lead glass. Lead equivalence, determined using the above method gives more accurate LE values than using the attenuation ratios given in IEC 61331-1, as the actual values may differ due to differences in photon fluence spectra in different testing laboratories.

References

1. IEC 61331-1:2014, Protective devices against diagnostic medical X radiation - Part 1
2. L. Buermann (2016) Jinst Technical Report, doi:10.1088/1748-0221/11/09/T09002.

APPLICATION OF FAILURE MODE AND EFFECT ANALYSIS TO MEDICAL EMERGENCY MANAGEMENT IN HIGH DOSE IODINE THERAPY

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Introduction

Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA) is a systematic approach to analyse process risks, evaluate failure effects, and develop corrective actions. The absence of protocols for management of medical emergencies in shielded isolation rooms during high dose iodine therapy challenges radiation safety and patient care. The aim of the study is to analyse the risks in patient care and radiation hazard to healthcare personnel during medical emergency management in high dose iodine therapy and take initiatives in mitigating them thereby enhancing patient care and radiation safety of staff.

Materials and Methods

The process of FMEA includes several key steps. These steps encompass the review of processes, brainstorming potential failures, establishing a Risk Priority Number (RPN) scale, listing the effects of each failure mode, assigning ratings for severity, occurrence, and detection, calculating the RPN for each effect, prioritizing failure modes for action, recommending appropriate actions, and continuously monitoring the resulting RPNs as failure modes are addressed and eliminated.

Results

In the process mapping, a total of 11 processes and 43 sub-processes were identified. The FMEA focused on managing and improving efficiency in patient care and reducing unwanted radiation exposure to staff. To decrease the risk priority number (RPN), several measures were implemented. These included developing policies and protocols for medical emergency management, conducting training to increase awareness, and implementing a checklist to reduce human errors. As a result, the overall RPN score decreased from 5104 to 2682. For patient care, mitigation plans targeted processes with RPN scores over 100,

resulting in a decrease from 3620 to 1998. Similarly, plans for reducing unwanted radiation exposure to staff focused on processes with RPN scores over 60, leading to a decrease from 1484 to 684 in the RPN score.

Conclusion

FMEA is a highly effective tool in evaluating system failures, improving patient care, and reducing radiation exposure for healthcare workers. It enables targeted interventions, optimizing care delivery, mitigating risks, and prioritizing safety. FMEA ensures improved outcomes for high dose iodine therapy patients and healthcare professionals.

References

- Bailey, D. L., Humm, J. L., Todd-Pokropek, A., & Van Aswegen, A. (n.d.). *Nuclear Medicine Physics A Handbook for Teachers and Students*.
- Huq, M. S., Fraass, B. A., Dunscombe, P. B., Gibbons, J. P., Ibbott, G. S., Mundt, A. J., Mutic, S., Palta, J. R., Rath, F., Thomadsen, B. R., Williamson, J. F., & Yorke, E. D. (2016). The report of Task Group 100 of the AAPM: Application of risk analysis methods to radiation therapy quality management. In *Medical Physics* (Vol. 43, Issue 7, pp. 4209–4262). AAPM - American Association of Physicists in Medicine. <https://doi.org/10.1118/1.494754>.

STUDY ON THE SIGNIFICANCE OF GEO-LOCATION OF MICRO METEOROLOGICAL STATIONS ON SHORT-TERM GAUSSIAN PUFF MODELLING IN COMPLEX TERRAINS USING AR-41 AS A GAMMA TRACER

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Introduction

The wind field and associated micrometeorological parameters have shown a complex flow pattern over complex terrain, which becomes even more intricate during averaging periods shorter than one hour (Jana and Chaudhury 2024). In addition, the geopositioning of micro-meteorological observatories as data sources for the surface layer is anticipated to play a crucial role in nearfield, short-term air dispersion modelling systems over such terrain, especially in the context of radiological and nuclear emergencies. Herein, the impact assessment study uses data from micro-meteorological observatories of different geo-locations at the same site using the Gaussian Puff Model with Ar-41 as the tracer.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted on a fair-weather day in January 2024, focussing on the mapping of short-lived radioactive Ar-41 distribution at 10 min. intervals. This was due to standard daily source terms from the 100 m stack of Dhruva Research Reactor. The Gaussian Puff model was utilized along with 10 min. averaged data from two experimental micro-meteorological stations (MMS-1 near Bhabha Point and MMS-2 at Mandala Hill Top), which are nearly 4 km apart on the complex terrain of the BARC Trombay site. The stack's geo-location is within one km distance of MMS-1. The γ -dose rate was assessed at each receptor's point, considering all Gaussian Puffs in influence, assuming spherical puff ($\sigma_y = \sigma_z$, representing air dispersion coefficients) at a distance (R), with the radius of influence restricted to 1 km. The basis of the γ -dose model was a semiinfinite cloud model at ground level. Neglecting uncertainty factors, the study examined the correlation between the estimated and measured dose rates using a linear

relationship. This was based on a model receptor, measuring instrument and wind direction at the line of sight from the 100m stack location of PHWRR. There were three cases for estimating γ -dose rate due to the presence of MMSs, expounded as follows: (1) Case-1: existence of only MMS-1 (2) Case-2: existence of only MMS-2 and, (3) Case-3: existence of both MMS-1 and MMS-2.

Results

It is important to note that the measured γ dose rate at the receptor point was above the background level (70 nGy/h) during the first 15 hours of the day. The Pearson correlation coefficient (Cc) between the measured and assessed γ -dose rates at a receptor point located 300 meters downwind was as follows: Case-1: Cc=0.07, T-TEST~0.09 Case-2: Cc=0.73, T-TEST~0.01 Case-3: Cc=0.79, T-TEST~0.00 In this particular scenario, the influence of MMS-2 was predominant in Case-2 than in Case-1. The Cc is highest in Case-3 when both MMS-1 and MMS-2 were considered.

Conclusion

It can be concluded by analyzing the result that there was significant heterogeneity between data of MMS-1 and MMS-2 on the study date and it was verified. It is possible as it is a non-monsoonal winter day over a complex terrain along the coast of the Arabian Sea. On this particular day, neither the local land breeze nor sea breeze could influence to reduce the heterogeneity observed in the high-resolution micro-meteorological observations in the wind field. As a result, the presence of MMSs at two geo-locations could decrease the uncertainty in the mapping of atmospheric γ -doses.

References

Jana and P Chaudhury (2024): Proc. ICRESH 2024, Springer Nature, ISBN 978-981-97-3086-5, 687-700.

RADIOLOGICAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF RADIOACTIVE WASTE DISCHARGED FROM NUCLEAR MEDICINE FACILITIES

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Introduction

Radionuclide therapy is a therapeutic application of nuclear medicine (NM) which relies on the principle of targeted radionuclide therapy, whereby radioactive materials are selectively delivered to specific tissues or tumours within the body. Majority (around 80%) of the radionuclide administered to the patient for the treatment would be eliminated through urine which need to be handled as radioactive waste and discharged as per the regulatory requirements which is generally achieved by delay and decay. In this work, radiological impact analysis of the liquid effluents released from NM facilities located in places without a public sewerage system has been carried out.

Materials and Methods

To achieve the stipulated limits for discharge of radioactivity to the sanitary sewerage systems, the effluents from the dedicated toilets of the NM isolation wards are managed by collecting and storing in delay-decay tank system. The activity is allowed to decay there to authorised limits before discharging into the sewerage system. In places where public sewerage systems are not available, the effluent is discharged to a septic tank for further decay and finally discharged to a soak pit. The activity (effluent) in the soak pit starts to leach out (infiltrate) to the surrounding soil and eventually reaches the groundwater and starts migrating from there, ultimately reaching public wells / utility points.

The main processes driving the movement of the radionuclide in groundwater are advection and diffusion while adsorption and decay affects the distribution of the activity. The infiltration rate of the surrounding soil e.g. sand, clay, loam etc. determines the source term (activity release rate from the soak pit). The migration of the activity from the soak pit has been modeled

using Visual MODFLOW Flex software (Waterloo Hydrogeologic, 2024). It solves the governing equation for groundwater flow & solute transport using finite-difference method (FDM). The radionuclide concentrations at various downstream distances are used for evaluation of the radiological dose to the public from the drinking water pathway. The migration of the radionuclide in the vadose zone has been neglected to make the dose estimation conservative. In this study, I¹³¹ is used as the radionuclide for modeling purpose.

Results

The radionuclide movement in groundwater has been carried out for three typical groundwater velocities viz., 1/3 m/day (slow), 2/3 m/day (medium) & 1.0 m/day (fast). The radionuclide concentrations at 5 m, 10 m, 20m, 30 m, 50 m & 80 m downstream distances from the soak pit are evaluated and used for radiological dose estimation. A daily water intake of 3 litres has been assumed for dose evaluation. It is found that at 5 m downstream from the soak pit, the dose exceeds the permissible limit of 1 mSv per annum assuming a groundwater velocity of 1/3 m/day. Hence, public wells should be located more than 5 m away from the soak pit.

Conclusion

Radiological dose to public from effluent discharge from NM facilities is estimated using conservative assumption. It is found that public wells should be located more than 5 m away from the soak pit.

References

Waterloo Hydrogeologic (2024), *Visual MODFLOW Flex 10.0*, Waterloo Hydrogeologic Inc., Canada.

EFFECT OF GAMMA IRRADIATION ON THE STRUCTURAL, OPTICAL AND ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES OF CADMIUM SULPHIDE NANOPARTICLES

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Introduction

Nanomaterials have gained immense attention due to their properties to that of the bulk characteristics [1]. Understanding their mechanism and determining a new course for synthetic methods are important issues in nanoscience and nanotechnology since the novel properties of nanomaterials depend on their size, structure, and shape. By studying semiconductor nanoparticles, we were able to comprehend their low-dimensional physical characteristics and investigate their enormous potential for a range of uses. In this regard, CdS nanostructures are being widely investigated for applications in semiconductor lasers, non-linear devices, display devices, biological applications, and as a window material for heterojunction solar cells due to their high absorption coefficient [2]. There are wide varieties of research is undertaken to explore CdS nanoparticles, however there are sparse research is reported on effect of Gamma irradiation on the physical and electrical properties of CdS nanoparticles.

Materials and Methods

Ethylene glycol, sodium sulfide flakes purified, and cadmium nitrate tetrahydrate are used to synthesize CdS nanoparticles. All of the chemicals used here are analytical grade and have not undergone any additional purification. In order to synthesize CdS nanoparticles, 0.1 M cadmium nitrate tetrahydrate solution in 40 ml of double-distilled water (DDW) is continuously stirred at room temperature. Ethylene glycol is then added dropwise to regulate the nanoparticle's size. To create a homogenous mixture, 0.1 M Na₂S solution in DDW is added to the solution dropwise while being vigorously stirred after 5 minutes. The atomic ratios of Cd and S were kept at 1:1 by selecting the molar ratio concentrations of both solutions. After two hours of reaction time, the obtained reddish-yellow precipitate was washed and dried. Further, two hours of annealing at

600°C, this reddish yellow precipitate will transform into a yellow hexagonal CdS nanoparticle. The synthesized nanoparticles are further irradiated with 20 kGy gamma dose.

Results

XRD measurements confirmed the Hexagonal CdS nanoparticles with lattice parameters as $a = b = 4.1500 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 6.7320 \text{ \AA}$ and matched with the JCPDS card number 01-080-0006. Further, 20kGy irradiated samples resulted in reduction in crystallinity in the material. The optical properties are investigated using UV-Vis spectroscopy analysis. The absorbance of the material resulted in decrease in optical bandgap for irradiated sample. The direct band gap CdS is obtained to be 2.23 eV, after irradiation bandgap reduced to 2.18 eV. The electrical conductivity measurements confirmed that the conductivity increased for irradiated sample. The AC electrical conductivity measurements are also revealed the increased conductivity of the irradiated sample. Nyquist plot confirmed double semicircle for irradiated samples and also observed decreased semicircle diameter. The results revealed that the irradiated sample poses better properties than the bare state.

Conclusion

The gamma irradiation resulted in reduction in crystallinity, reduction in bandgap and increased conductivity of CdS nanoparticle is witnessed. Further, irradiated CdS nanoparticles also resulted in increased dielectric constant with reduction in grain resistance

References

1. S. Suresh, Appl Nanosci 4, 325 (2014).
2. Materials Science and Engineering: B 294, 116487 (2023).

RADIATION SAFETY IN TREATMENT OF HEMATOLOGICAL MALIGNANCIES AND OSL INVIVO DOSIMETRY

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Introduction

Radiation safety measures in the treatment of hematological malignancies help us to provide guidance for the radiation professionals who are practicing these special procedures. The faced difficulties and the knowledge of error management lead to a path towards increased patient safety¹. In addition to radiation safety, a cross verification of the administered doses is another milestone in improving safety. Multiple detectors are suitable for in vivo dosimetry in radiation therapy treatments. Initially, we have performed in-vivo dosimetry of TBI patients with gafchromic films, ionization chamber and semiconductor diodes. Gel Dosimeters are another option for dosimetry^{2&3}. This present study investigates the surface dose measurements of Volumetric Modulated Arc Therapy (VMAT) planning in Total Body Irradiation (TBI) patients using Optically Stimulated Luminescent Dosimeters (OSLDs)⁴. The study also aims to evaluate the dosimetric uniformity along the body axis along with the safety issues.

Materials and Methods

A total of 25 VMAT-TBI patients were selected from database and there QA plans were fired on three different Alderson Rando phantoms: pediatric small, female and male phantom to measure surface doses using OSLD (using myOSLchip reader by Radpro International GmbH). Calibration was done for 2 Gy at the VERSA HD Linac by delivering dose at Dmax. Bolus is also used to find the impact in surface doses. Inline and crossline dose profiles for uniform dose distribution along superior-inferior and right-left of each arc isocenter i.e. at chin, chest, abdomen and pelvic isocenters.

Results and Discussion

A total of 250 measurements were taken for surface dose measurement. Each patient has 10 measurement points. The minimum to maximum percentage dose difference for all selected patients is from 0.05% to 8.36%

(within $\pm 10\%$) in which all 25 patient's variations is within 5%, except some points where increase is upto 8.36%. Also, the maximum dose increase of 9.9% was observed with bolus compared to no bolus measurements. Dose profiles at each arc center were found uniform, ranging between 1.6 Gy and 2.1 Gy. The already used dosimeters also showed the variation within $\pm 10\%$ ⁵. The practical experience of cross verifying the administered doses helped to seek information in dosimetric variation and hence, quite useful in designing the clinical treatment framework for such special treatment procedures. Hence, the planning methodology, chances of errors with solutions, clinical impact should be addressed to improve the safety standards.

Conclusion

The found dose variation is within $\pm 5\%$ except some point where dose is up to 8.36%. A 15.9% of maximum increase in doses was observed with bolus. The use of bolus is also recommended in VMAT TBI in vivo dosimetry. Despite of the overall uniform dosimetric profiles, the outliers indicate the need of careful monitoring during treatment of VMAT TBI or multi-isocentric techniques. The consistency in the treatment means accuracy and quality in dose delivery, and efficient and effective learning showing the involvement of responsible radiation professionals. The care must be taken while deciding junction regions of the adjacent arcs and junctions should be avoided in the critical OAR regions.

References

1. Sarkar PK (2012) *Radiation Protection and Environment* V 35 I(3 & 4).
2. Reena K, Budhi SY and Pankaj K.(2023) *J of Medi and Chem Sci*, 6, 2964-73.
3. Reena Kumari, Pankaj Kumar, & Arun Oinam Singh (2019). *AIP Conference Proceedings* pp 2142.
4. Mangili, P., et al. (1999). *Radiotherapy and Oncology*, 52(3), pp 275-284.
5. Sengupta, A., et al. (2020). *J of Applied Clinical Medical Physics*, 21(2), pp 102-108.

ESTIMATION OF RETENTION EFFICIENCY TESTING OF FILTER BANKS FOR CONTROLLING EFFLUENT RELEASE IN FAST BREEDER TEST REACTOR

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Introduction

In nuclear facilities safety of occupational workers and public are of paramount importance. In this context it is essential to control the internal and external exposure by safety practices and by maintaining clean environment. The radioactive contaminants of effluents such as radioiodine (I 131) and fission products (Cs 137, Sr 90) from various radiation facilities needs to be filtered before releasing it to atmosphere, for this filters are installed in exhaust systems of nuclear facilities. As a part of regulatory requirement, it is mandatory to maintain the efficiency of filter banks within limits as per technical specification. The retention efficiency of the filter banks shall not be less than 99.5% for particle of size greater than 0.3 micron and 99% for I-131. This paper focuses on methodology adopted for estimation of retention efficiency of FBTR filter banks for particulate and radio iodine to control the effluent release from the plant to environment.

Materials and Methods

Poly dispersed liquid aerosol of Di-Octyl Phthalate (DOP) / Poly Alpha Olefin (PAO), Particulate Counter, Aerosol Generator, HpGe Detector, elemental iodine, activated charcoals are major items equipped to evaluate the filter efficiency. In DOP method high concentration of the particulate is released into the upstream of the filter. Measurements are then taken with a calibrated particle counter to establish whether or not the particulate has made its way through either the filter or its casing downstream. For testing Iodine retention efficiency, of HEPA Filters combined with activated charcoal beds with high surface area of adsorptions (1000 m²/g) impregnated with 2wt% KOH and 2wt% KI. In-situ testing of HEPA filter was carried prior to Charcoal filter by adopting DOP test method and efficiency is calculated by measuring upstream and downstream concentration. By injecting radioactive active iodine (I-131) into the air stream ahead of the charcoal bed and finding out the iodine removal efficiency of the

filters. The active iodine (I-131) with Na₂S₂O₃ of activity range 2.5 to 10 mCi mixed with 20% KI, 10% NaNO₂, and 35% KOH in a 3-neck round bottomed flask inside the dedicated glove box and iodine vapor are generated by adding H₂SO₄ drop wise. The samples are collected from both upstream and downstream using charcoal cartridge and are counted using HpGe based MCA system. The expression used to estimate the retention efficiency & Charcoal filter is given below.

$$\text{Efficiency(\%)} = \frac{C_u - C_d}{C_u} \times 100$$

Where C_u and C_d are Upstream and Downstream counts respectively.

Results & Discussion

Since commissioning of fast breeder test reactor retention efficiency testing of filter banks were carried out successfully and the observed values from 2011 on an average of 99.97% for particle of size >0.3 micron and 99.5% for I-131 were maintained for both filter banks A & B which were within the specified regulatory limits i.e.'s 99% for particulate & 99.5 for Iodine. All the personnel involved in the work were provided with personnel protective equipment (PPE). Neither personnel contamination nor air activity release was observed during insitu testing.

Conclusion

Retention efficiency testing of the filter Bank reveals that filtering efficiency for I-131 & radioactive particulates are within the limit as per regulatory guidelines. The collective dose per testing was 40 Person-μSv per testing which proves the robust methodology and safety practices adopted for the testing. Maintaining the efficiency of the filter banks controls the effluent release to atmosphere and ensures the safety of the occupational workers and common public.

References

IGC/SG/RSD/RSS/92628/TS/3006/REV – D, "In-Situ Iodine Filter Testing Procedure". IAEA Tech series 122 & 243.

DIURNAL VARIATION OF 3-H ACTIVITY IN AIR MOISTURE SAMPLES AT KALPAKKAM

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Introduction

Kalpakkam nuclear complex mainly caters to middle and back end of nuclear fuel cycle operations such as PHWR, FBTR reactors, KARP reprocessing plants and WIP & CWMF waste management facilities and host of allied facilities. Low-level radioactive gaseous waste generated from these nuclear facilities are treated, diluted and discharged to atmosphere through stack after compliance of limits laid by regulatory authorities. 3-H as HTO is a major radionuclide in gaseous effluent, which is a soft beta emitter. In Kalpakkam regular 3-H monitoring program is in place. An automatic air moisture collection sampler indigenously designed and developed by ESL, Kakrapar (Nankar, 2020) was used to study the diurnal variation of 3-H in air moisture samples at a location near the fence post of Madras Atomic Power Station (MAPS).

Materials and Methods

The automatic air moisture collection sampler using thermoelectric cooling technology based on Peltier effect is programmed to collect the condensed air moisture on hourly basis. Similarly, another sampler based on the same technology collects the air moisture cumulated over a period of 24 hrs. The two samplers were placed at fence post (1.6 km WSW w.r.t MAPS). Continuous sampling was carried out using the samplers for a period of three consecutive days during November, 2023. 8 ml of collected samples were mixed with 12ml of Ultima Gold scintillation cocktail and analysed using Low Level Liquid Scintillation Analyser (HIDEX 300 SL). The MDA of this method is 0.06 Bq/ m³.

Results

Hourly 3-H activity during 72 hrs study period ranged from 0.07 to 52.95 Bq/m³. In the 24 hrs cumulated samples for three days

the activity varied from 3.05 to 12.99 Bq/m³. The average of hourly 3-H activity for 24 hrs was computed (2.31 – 11.02 Bq/m³) which was in good agreement with cumulative sample activity. The observed 3-H activity levels are comparable with activity levels at other NPP sites in India (Nankar, 2023). The results of hourly variation of 3-H activity during 24 hrs for three days showed two maxima and one minimum. The maximum concentration was observed during midnight 00:00 to 02:00 hrs and 10:00 to 12:00 hrs. The minimum activity prevailed during 03:00 to 06:00 hrs.

Conclusion

3-H activity in air moisture samples was measured using hourly and cumulative automatic air samplers. The study indicated that the activity levels were low and comparable with other NPP sites in India. Diurnal variation of 3-H activity was studied which showed two periods of higher 3-H activity and one minimum. The observed activity levels of 3-H were low which indicates negligible impact on environment.

References

- Nankar, D.P., Patra, A.K., Joshi, C.P., Saradhi, I.V., Vinodkumar, A. (2020). IARPNC-2020.
Nankar, D.P., Patra, A.K., Joshi, C.P., AmolChandrakar, Saradhi, I.V., Vinod Kumar, A. (2023) Journal of Env. Radioactivity 261(2023)107 123

OPTIMIZATION OF INVERSE DISTANCE WEIGHTED (IDW) INTERPOLATION METHOD IN GIS FOR TERRESTRIAL RADIATION MEASUREMENTS

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Introduction

Tobler's first law, one of the fundamental tenets, of geography states that everything is related to everything else, but near things are more related than distant things. Spatial dependence and auto-correlation are extensively used in data-science and GIS (Geographic Information System). Four models of univariate interpolation are readily used in the field of GIS viz., kernel density estimation (heatmap), line density, inverse distance weighted (IDW) and triangulated irregular network (TIN). These models are vastly to interpolate environmental data like temperature, precipitation, pollutant concentration, AQI, dose-rates, etc. In this manuscript we have used values of ambient equivalent dose-rate [$H^*(10)$] measured at specific locations in Mumbai region to interpolate an overall dose-rate map extending to the regions where no data was available.

Materials and Methods

Mumbai lies in the western coast of India with elevation from MSL -1 m to ~350 m. A Handheld radiation survey meter with 1.4" × 2" NaI (TI) and GM detectors was used to carry out natural background radiation (NBR) measurements at 310 locations in the Mumbai region. The measurement type used is ambient dose equivalent rate [$H^*(10)$ ADER] nano-Sievert per hour (10⁻⁹ Sv.h⁻¹ or nSv/h). In IDW three important parameters to be tweaked are distance coefficient (power), barrier curves and spatial resolution (Paul A. Longley et al., 2015). IDW uses a simple linear or polynomial equation to provide weights to different points depending upon their respective distances. The farther the point from measurement location, the less weightage (inverse) is provided to the value. We have used QGIS (Ver. 3.38.2), geoscientific data abstraction library (GDAL) processing toolbox for vector interpolation. To compensate for the cosmic radiation, the elevation boundaries were used as structural breaks in interpolation (QGIS Development Team, 2022).

Results

Based on the distances and the land-use type, the values estimated by IDW may not be accurate as expected. This problem can be overcome by using 90% of the data for performing interpolation, and using remaining 10% of the data to check the validity of the model using a Bayesian approach. The performance of the interpolated values can be assessed by RMSE (root mean square error) to address the heterogeneity in the data collected from different geographical regions and can be used to find the optimal 'Distance Coefficient, p', the inverse distance correlation power, which can be put in the final interpolation equation. We tried power (p) from 1 to 4, however, we found that the distance coefficient factor p of 2 is optimally suitable, and can be used for other similar studies.

Conclusion

Selection of interpolation model and then optimisation of parameters in the selected model plays an important role in prediction accuracy. In IDW, using distance coefficient factor p of 2 is an optimized power for allocating the weightages to values for interpolation. Powers > 2 must be taken into account only when an empirical formula is available, otherwise higher coefficients will use exponentially higher computing resources for similar datasets. A Bayesian Hierarchical model with advance Kriging can be explored for updating such data.

References

Paul A. Longley et al. (2015) Geographic Information Systems and Science. 3rd edn. West Sussex: John Wiley & Sons (ESRI Press).
QGIS Development Team (2022) QGIS Geographic Information System. QGIS Association. Available at: <https://www.qgis.org>.

SITE SPECIFIC CARBON CONTENT AND C-14 ACTIVITY IN MANGO LEAVES AROUND RAWATBHATA SITE

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Keywords: Carbon content, specific activity, Mango leaves, Pyrolyser

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Introduction

Carbon-14 is a radionuclide with global occurrence with natural and anthropogenic origin. It is a pure beta emitter with half-life of 5730 years. In addition to natural production, ¹⁴C is also produced during the operation of nuclear reactors, and enters the atmosphere to become part of carbon cycle. Considering its biological importance, ¹⁴C activity in the vicinity of nuclear facilities is monitored regularly. Knowledge of site-specific values of carbon content in the sample is important to accurately calculate ¹⁴C specific activity (Bq.kg⁻¹C). The present study quantifies the ¹⁴C specific activity and carbon content in mango leaves around Rawatbhata Rajasthan site.

Materials and Methods

Mango leaf samples (95 nos.) were collected from ten different locations around the RR Site up to radial distance of 5 km. Few samples are collected from farther distance at 300 km. Thermal oxidation of the leaf samples were performed using Pyrolyser Trio system (RADDEC). In Pyrolyser, oxidation of the samples is carried out at high temperature in the presence of oxygen (flow rate: 0.1 lpm) and produced CO₂ gets trapped in a bubbling setup containing 10 mL of Carbon-Trap (3-methoxypropyl-amine). The quantity of CO₂ absorbed in the absorber can be determined gravimetrically. 10 mL of liquid Scintillator (Carbon count) was added to the Carbon-Trap. The ¹⁴C activity was determined by subjecting it to liquid scintillation counting (Quantulus 1220 (PerkinElmer make) as per standard procedure. For determination of carbon content in the samples, the ash left out after oxidation in sample boat, was measured gravimetrically.

From the difference in weight (before and after combustion of the sample), the carbon content in the sample was determined as per reported method by Negi et.al.

Results

In the analyzed mango leaves, the carbon content varied in the range of 32-42% with overall mean value of 38 %. The mean value of ¹⁴C specific activity in the mango leaf samples collected at RR site up to 5 km is 242 ± 11 Bq.kg⁻¹C. ¹⁴C specific activity in mango leaf samples at farther distances is 226 ± 1 Bq.kg⁻¹C and this value is in good agreement with specific activity of naturally produced ¹⁴C in atmosphere reported by Krajcar Bronic as 226 Bq.kg⁻¹C. Ratio of ¹⁴C activity in vicinity of RR Site to ¹⁴C activity naturally produced (300km distance) is 1.07. The proposed methodology has been successfully used for determination of ¹⁴C in different types of biota samples.

Conclusion

In the collected mango leaf samples carbon content varied in the range of 32–42% with overall mean value 38 %. The mean specific activity of ¹⁴C in mango leaves around RR site is 242±11Bq kg⁻¹ C indicating the capability of low-level determination of ¹⁴C in the environment.

References

- Negi JDS, Manhas RK, Chauhan PS (2003). *Curr Sci* 85:1528–1531
- IAEA (2010) Report IAEA 472, Vienna
- Krajcar Bronic, J., Obelic, B., 2009. *Appl. Radiat. Isot.* 67 (5), 800–804.

NATURAL RADIOACTIVITY LEVELS IN MATERIALS USED AT THERMAL POWER PLANT AND STEEL PLANT

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Introduction

Naturally occurring radioactive material (NORM) contains radioactive elements of natural origin in the environment. NORM predominantly contains Uranium, Thorium, their daughter products and Potassium in different matrices of environment and vary by location. NORM in any industrial raw and waste materials can disperse to the surrounding environment during physical or chemical processing (Xin Wang, 2015). This study presents the specific activity of NORMs in the raw and waste material from coal - fired power plant and steel industry.

Materials and Methods

For analysis of NORM, samples of coal, fly ash and iron ore pellets collected for 12 months from thermal power and steel plant industry in Tamil Nadu. The dried samples were packed in polyethylene bottle (250 ml) and sealed hermetically. The samples were kept for 30 days for secular equilibrium between ²²⁶Ra and ²²²Rn. The activity of the samples was measured using p-type High Purity Germanium detector (HPGe- 100%) for a period of 85000 sec.

Results

The activity concentration of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K in power plant coal ranged 1.60 – 43.12 Bq/kg, 1.90 – 54.21 Bq/kg and 3.82 – 82.89 Bq/kg with an average of 14.24 Bq/kg, 16.61 Bq/kg and 39.41 Bq/kg, respectively. Concentration of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K in coal fired power plant fly ash ranged 54.35 – 90.91 Bq/kg, 50.40 – 117.50 Bq/kg and 104.54 – 247.5 Bq/kg with an average of 71.46 Bq/kg, 79.49 Bq/kg and 171.55 Bq/kg, respectively. Activity concentration of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K in steel plant coal ranged 2 – 29.51 Bq/kg, 1– 29.04 Bq/kg and 4.75 – 27.94 Bq/kg with average of 12.20 Bq/kg, 13.88 Bq/kg and 8.43 Bq/kg, respectively. Concentration of ²³⁸U,

²³²Th and ⁴⁰K in steel plant fly ash ranged 52.40 – 140.31 Bq/kg, 42 – 139.17 Bq/kg and 61.48 – 162.8 Bq/kg with an average of 89.27 Bq/kg, 79.22 Bq/kg and 118.49 Bq/kg, respectively. Concentration of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K in steel plant iron ore pellets ranged 6.6 – 43.56 Bq/kg, 3.5 – 39.06 Bq/kg and 2.66 – 23.92 Bq/kg with average of 13.53 Bq/kg, 10.99 Bq/kg and 8.50 Bq/kg, respectively. In thermal power plant and Steel plant the waste fly ash activity concentration of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K are higher than input coal.

Conclusion

The measured activity levels of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K coal, fly ash and iron ore pellets from thermal power plant and steel plant samples from this study, are comparable with the reported values elsewhere. NORM data from different industries will be useful for evaluation of radiation safety for population and workers when raw and waste material used for building and landfill area. The obtained data will be useful to compare, monitor and assess any changes of natural radioactivity levels in the surrounding environment.

References

- Xin Wang, Qiyan Feng, Ruoyu Sun and Guijian Liu. (2015), Minerals 2015, 5, 637–646;
- Truong Thi Hong Loan *et al*, (2022) Nuclear Engineering and Technology, vol.54, no.4, pp.1431 – 1438
- H. Mohamed (2023) Volume 21, No 4 International Journal of Radiation Research
- Jakob, M., Steckel, J.C., Jotzo, F. et al. (2020) Nature. Climate. Change 10, 704–707

DECADAL TREND AND SEASONAL VARIABILITY OF GROSS BETA ACTIVITY IN AIRBORNE PARTICULATE MATTER AT KAIGA, KARNATAKA

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Keywords: Seasonal variation, Gross β activity, Decompose, Trend

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Introduction

Atmospheric radioactivity stems from both natural and anthropogenic sources, leading to potential radiation exposure through both internal and external means. This study aims to assess gross beta (β) activity in airborne particulate matter over a decade (2011–2020) in the Kaiga region of Karnataka, India. This study primarily focuses on analyzing long-term trends and characterizing seasonal variations in the gross β activity levels at Kaiga.

Materials and Methods

Particulate samples were collected weekly using glass fiber filters at the Environmental Survey Laboratory, Kaiga, using a vacuum pump at a flow rate of 50 LPM. The long-lived gross β activity was measured using a plastic scintillator-based low background β counter. The weekly data for ten consecutive years (2011–2020) was aggregated into monthly averages, and the resulting time series was subjected to seasonal decomposition using the 'decompose' function from the 'Stats' package in R software. Trend analysis was conducted using the Mann-Kendall (MK) test (at $\alpha=0.05$) and Theil-Sen slope.

Results

The gross β activity concentration (mBq.m⁻³) ranged from 0.2 to 3.1, with a GM of 0.5 and GSD of 1.9. Seasonal decomposition of the time series data revealed distinct seasonal patterns. The seasonal component (St) showed that gross β activity is generally lower from June to September, with the lowest seasonal factor (average of all detrended values of a month, i.e. $St = \text{Avg}(Y_t - T_t)$, Y_t : original time-series, T_t : trend component of time-series) observed in July (-0.25). The average annual rainfall in the region is around 3700 mm, which occurs during the southwest monsoon from June to September. The intense rainfall during the monsoon period likely reduced airborne particulates through wet deposition and dust suppression (Huang, 2009, Alegría, 2021).

Conversely, the seasonal factor was found to be positive from November to April, peaking in January with a value of +0.35 likely due to the drier conditions, which promote particulate resuspension. For long-term trend analysis, the data was de-seasonalized by removing the seasonal component from the original time series and applying the MK test to estimate the underlying trend. The results ($|z| > 1.96$, $p < 0.05$; 'z-value' is standardized MK test statistic used to assess the significance of trend) indicated a marginal decreasing trend in the gross β activity from 2011–2020, with Sen's slope of -0.003. The slight negative (-0.003) slope suggests that the rate of change over time is minimal. The observed decreasing trend might be influenced by environmental factors, such as regional climatic changes over the study period, although further analysis is required to confirm specific causes.

Conclusion

This decade-long study demonstrates significant seasonal variation in gross β activity in airborne particulate matter at the Kaiga site, with the lowest levels observed during the monsoon season and the highest during winter. These findings underscore the importance of considering seasonal effects in the assessment of airborne radioactivity.

References

- Huang, Y., Tao, Y., Lin, J., and Shang-Guan, Z. (2009) *Chemosphere*, 75(7), 929-933.
Alegría, N., Hernández-Ceballos, M.Á., Herranz, M., Idoeta, R., and Legarda, F. (2021) *Atmosphere*, 12, 1323.

STUDY OF DIURNAL VARIATION OF WIND PATTERN AT KUDANKULAM COASTAL SITE

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Key word: Boundary layer, diurnal, atmospheric dispersion

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Introduction

The part of the atmosphere that is directly influenced by the presence of the earth's surface is known as the planetary boundary layer. Many atmospheric parameters like wind, pressure, radiation fluxes and precipitation are subject to a distinct diurnal variation process, which is driven mainly by solar radiation. Understanding the diurnal cycle of wind is essential with regard to the aforementioned practices. In this paper the diurnal variation of wind pattern at Kudankulam site is presented.

Materials and Methods

A 30 m high micro meteorological tower established at 0.7 km WNW from the KKNPP site is used for collection of data. The meteorological data for the period 2003-2023 is analyzed for distribution of hourly mean wind speed and direction.

Results

The monthly predominant wind classes and directions and percentage frequency of their occurrences exhibit certain wind patterns. In the winter months December, January and February, the predominant wind direction sectors were NE, ENE and NNE. During April to October, the predominant wind direction sectors shifted towards W, WSW and WNW and the wind speed class 20-28 km/hr was the highest with frequency of 45%. During north east monsoon, wind speed was low and the wind speed class 6-11 Km/hr was observed with a frequency of 43%. The maximum wind speed occurred in the months of June and July during south west monsoon period and fall appreciably by the middle of August and minimum occurred in the month of November. This is due to the stable temperature stratification of the atmosphere in winter. The hourly diurnal variation of wind speed at two heights (10 m and 30 m) indicates maximum wind speed during the

afternoon hours around 14:00 to 17:00 hrs and had a clear acceleration after sun rise and heating of ground surface and a well-defined deceleration after reaching the afternoon peak till sunrise. The diurnal pattern of wind speed generally displayed a maximum during the early afternoon and a minimum during night-time (Crawford and Hudson, 1973). Such a daily pattern is a surface driven phenomenon attributed mainly to the oscillation of the transfer of momentum. The diurnal pattern of wind speed is closely tied to terrain conditions (Shu et al. (2015a)).

Conclusion

The Kudankulam Site experiences a tropical climate resembling other coastal sites like Kalpakkam. Predominant wind directions are NE, ENE and NNE during north east monsoon and W, WSW and WNW during south west monsoon with wind speed in the range of 20-28 km/h. The maximum wind speed is normally observed in the July month when westerlies are well established. The meteorology at Kudankulam site favours good atmospheric dispersion resulting in negligible dose to public during normal plant operation.

References

- Crawford, K.C. and Hudson, H.R. (1973) Journal of Applied Meteorology, 12(1), 127–132.
- Shu, Z.R., Li, Q.S. and Chan, P.W. (2015a) Energy Conversion and Management, 101, 644–657.

HEAVY METALS IN RIVER SEDIMENTS NEAR A URANIUM MINING AREA IN EAST SINGHBHUM, INDIA

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Introduction

Anthropogenic activities introduce heavy metals, which are transported and deposited in sediments, potentially impacting ecosystems and human health through biomagnifications. The geo-accumulation index (**Igeo**) quantifies the level of heavy metal pollution in sediments by comparing observed concentrations with natural background levels, providing a standardized classification from unpolluted to extremely polluted. The potential ecological risk index (PERI) introduces toxicity response factors of elements of interest, which provides simple and quantitative values for an ecological risk assessment system (Zheng et al 2019). This study assesses heavy metal concentrations in river sediments using the Igeo and PERI to evaluate pollution levels and ecological risks associated with these metals.

Material and methods

The study examines the Subarnarekha (S/rekha) River in East Singhbhum, India, an industrialized region known for U and Cu mining, steel production, and power generation. Low-grade U ore at Jaduguda (0.05% U₃O₈) results in significant tailings, with treated effluents discharged into the Juria Nala, which merges with the Gara and S/rekha Rivers. Sediment samples were collected upstream (U/S) and downstream (D/S) during pre-monsoon (May) and post-monsoon (November) seasons. Samples were air-dried, sieved, homogenized, and digested using a microwave-assisted system. Heavy metals (Zn, Pb, Ni, Cd, Co, Mn, Cr, Cu, U, Fe) were analyzed using ICP-OES (HORIBA-JY, Ultima 2) under optimized conditions. Triplicate analyses ensured accuracy, with quality control using reference material (LKSD-1) achieving over 85% ± 5% recovery at a 95% confidence level.

Results and Discussion

The study found significant variations in heavy metal concentrations across locations. Zn ranged from 49.5 to 204 mg/kg, with the highest levels U/S, while Pb ranged from 35.5 to 88 mg/kg, peaking at Juria Nala D/S. Ni concentrations varied between 45.5 and 233 mg/kg, with the highest levels also at Juria Nala D/S. Mn showed extreme accumulation, ranging from 853.3 to 42,318 mg/kg, with the highest levels at Gara D/S. U ranged from 2.65 to 30.95 mg/kg, peaking at Juria Nala D/S. Co levels ranged from 24.4 to 71.6 mg/kg, with the maximum at Gara D/S. The Igeo analysis across sampling locations reveals varying degrees of metal accumulation. Ni and Cd show moderate accumulation downstream, particularly at Juria Nala D/S (1.19 and 1.12, respectively). Mn records the highest Igeo at Gara D/S (5.05), suggesting substantial accumulation. U is most prominent at Juria Nala D/S (2.93), reflecting localized accumulation. Zn, Pb, Co, Cr, Cu, and Fe remain low to moderately accumulated across locations.

Conclusion

All sampling locations show PERI values below the **moderate risk** level. Sediments at Juria Nala D/S exceed the **low-risk** category due to localized heavy metal contributions, but the risk decreases downstream, remaining well below the moderate threshold. This indicates localized phenomena without significant downstream propagation of ecological risk.

Reference

Zheng L., Zhou Z., Rao M., Sun Z. (2019) Environ Geochem Health 42, 1401-1413.

CHARACTERISATION OF MAJOR AND TRACE ELEMENTS IN SOIL SAMPLES FROM THE STATE OF GUJRAT

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Keywords: EDXRF, Pollution indices; Trace and Toxic Elements.

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Introduction

Monitoring trace and toxic elements in soil is essential for protecting the environment and human health, improving agricultural productivity, and adhering to regulatory standards. This study focuses on formulating the EDXRF technique to analyze 16 elements in soil samples collected from 105 locations across the entire state of Gujarat, India. Toxic metals in soil can originate from various sources, including the use of chemical fertilizers, weathered parent materials, mining activities, traffic emissions, and agricultural and industrial operations (Jin *et al.*, 2019). This study categorizes the elements into trace elements (Zn, Pb, As, Br, U), minor elements (Ba, Zr, Rb, Mn, Sr, Cr, V), and major elements (Al, Fe, K), all of which were characterized using the EDXRF technique. The findings provide a detailed elemental profile of soil samples which can contribute to more effective environmental management strategies and planning efforts.

Materials and Methods

Soil samples were collected in sealed polythene bags and refrigerated until analysis. Each dried, finely sieved (<63 µm) sample (0.8 g) was mixed with 0.2 g of cellulose powder (Sigma Aldrich) and compressed under 25 tons of hydraulic pressure for 3 minutes to form pellets (Tiwari *et al.*, 2013). EDXRF was chosen as the analytical technique since it requires minimal preparation time, is cost-effective, and eliminates the need for hazardous chemicals like those used in acid digestion for sample preparation.

Results

The elements were categorized based on their concentrations into major (percentage levels), minor (above 100 mg/kg), and trace (below 100 mg/kg). Among major elements, Al had the highest concentration at 7.2%, ranging from 2.5% to 10.9%. For minor elements, Mn recorded the highest concentration at 657 mg/kg, with a range of 136 to 2074 mg/kg. Among trace elements, Zn had the highest

concentration of 58.7 mg/kg, ranging from 19.1 to 212 mg/kg, while U showed the lowest concentration with a mean of only 1.4 mg/kg.

The order of abundance, based on mean concentrations of the analyzed elements, was: Al > Fe > K > Mn > Ba > Zr > Sr > V > Cr > Zn > Rb > Cu > Pb > As > Br > U.

Various pollution indices were calculated from the results. Contamination Factor (CF) values for many elements were <1, indicating no contamination compared to the earth's crust. However, V, Cr, Cu, As, Pb, and Zr showed moderate contamination with CF values between 1 and 3. Bromine had a high CF value (5.8), indicating significant contamination. The Pollution load index (PLI) values ranged from 0 to 4.5, with a mean of 1.06, suggesting the soil is slightly or not significantly polluted compared to the upper continental crust. Index of geoaccumulation (I_{geo}) values for V, As, and Cr were between 0 and 1, indicating slight contamination, while Br had an I_{geo} value between 1-2, showing moderate contamination in the study area.

Conclusion

EDXRF was found suitable for analysis of elements in soil samples. It also avoids tedious and time taking sample preparation steps. Various pollution indices calculated from the results showed that the soil of the state of Gujrat is mostly unpolluted, however for a few of the studied elements the contamination levels were low to moderate.

References

- Jin, Y., et al., (2019), *Environ. Int.* **124**, 320-328.
Tiwari, M., et al., (2014), *Appl. Radiat. Isot.*, **90**, 53–57.

VARIATION OF URANIUM CONTENT IN GROUNDWATER IN PRINCIPAL AQUIFER SYSTEMS OF INDIA

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Introduction

Uranium is a naturally occurring radioactive element that occurs in primary and secondary minerals due to geological processes. Occurrence of uranium in groundwater is correlated to natural and geological processes. As such, uranium content in the groundwater becomes multiparametric dynamic function of the regional geology, aquifer properties, physicochemical conditions, water uses pattern and extraneous factors like precipitation, recharge rate, residence time, discharges and mixing etc. Uranium data collected under the national survey are segregated into different aquifer zones and analyzed for their correlations (Sahoo S.K. et al, 2021).

Methodology

As per the Central Ground Water Board Report (CGWB, 2012), based on hydrogeological characteristics, the entire country has been classified into 14 principal aquifer systems. About 31%, 20%, 17%, 8%, 7% and 2% of the country is occupied with alluvium aquifers, banded gneissic complex and gneiss aquifers, basalt aquifers, sandstone aquifers, shale aquifers and limestone aquifers, respectively. Remaining 15% of the area is covered with schist, granite, quartzite, charnockite, khondalite, laterites and intrusive aquifers. In the present paper, intrarelationship between the mass concentration of uranium and aquifer characteristics has been investigated.

Observations

Heterogeneous uranium content in groundwater of different aquifers observed. Greater than regulatory limit value has been observed in granitic aquifer, banded gneissic complex and gneiss aquifer, alluvium aquifers, sandstone, and limestone aquifers with few exceptions also in other aquifer. This is attributed to greater rockwater interaction, intensive agricultural activities,

salinity & sea water intrusion, high evaporation intensity in arid climate, enhanced leaching with bicarbonate rich alkali groundwater and conducive oxidizing geochemical setting for higher solubility of uranium from host rock. Relatively lesser uranium content observed in basaltic aquifer, shale aquifer, and laterite aquifers. Lower uranium content in basalts, organic matter and clay minerals in shales and high iron content in laterite soils are the reasons ascribed to lower uranium content in these aquifers. Aquifers in arid and semi-arid regions have a higher uranium content due to low recharge, high evaporation and leaching from uraniumrich minerals due to greater residence time. Lower uranium content observed in alluvial aquifers of coastal areas compared to IndoGangetic alluvial aquifers and alluvial aquifers of Inland basins. In addition, lower uranium content observed in schist, quartzite and khondalite aquifers. Therefore, mitigation measures for the water sources laced with elevated levels warrant regular monitoring, comparison with the established national database and adoption of appropriate remediation technique to avoid any health implication to the public.

Reference

CGWB (2012), Aquifer Systems of India, Central Ground Water Board.

S.K. Sahoo, S.K. Jha, V.N. Jha, A.C. Patra, M.S. Kulkarni (2021), Survey of uranium in drinking water sources in India: interim observations, *Current Science*, 120 (9), pp.1482-1490.

APPLICATION OF IN-HOUSE SYNTHESIZED HYDROXYAPATITE FOR URANIUM RECOVERY FROM ACIDIC RAFFINATE SAMPLES

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Introduction

Uranium is a valuable material used in nuclear reactor as fuel for energy production. It is leached out from ore and is further purified using solvent extraction technique (Dehghan et al., 2024). Due to the inherent limitations in solvent extraction method, trace amount of unrecoverable uranium is released as acidic raffinate solutions. In the current practices, trace amount of uranium left in this acidic raffinate is precipitated along with other constituents and stored in solid form.

Present study is focused on developing an ecofriendly approach using a modified natural adsorbent (egg-shell) to selectively and effectively remove uranium from the acidic raffinate effluent. This method will help in recovering the trace levels of uranium present in raffinate for use and also to reduce its content in the precipitate being stored.

Materials and Methods

Hydroxyapatite (HA) was synthesized using hydrothermal precipitation method. In this study, egg-shell was taken in powder form and phosphoric acid (H₃PO₄) was added as modifying agent. Optimised reaction conditions (Ca/P ratio of 1.67, pH >10, drop wise addition of phosphoric acid) were maintained while synthesizing pure nano-crystalline HA. Synthesized material was characterized using XRD and FT-IR to confirm the formation of desired crystal structure.

In the present study, pH is an important parameter and accuracy of pH measurement was ensured through regular calibration of pH meter. Standard gamma ray sources viz. ¹³³Ba (80.9979 keV, 356.0129 keV), ¹³⁷Cs (662 keV) and ⁶⁰Co (1173 keV and 1332 keV) were used for energy calibration of the High Purity Germanium (HPGe).

Acidic raffinate solution (500 mL) collected from the process stream was

conditioned to attain the optimised pH of 4, for efficient removal of uranium. The concentration of uranium in this solution was estimated using HPGe based gamma spectrometry system. To evaluate the removal efficiency of this synthesized material, one gram of HA was packed in plastic column and this raffinate solution was passed through the column at 5 mL per minute flow rate. Solution after passing through the column was again analyzed for uranium concentration using HPGe detector.

Results and Discussion

From the concentration of uranium measured in feed and eluent solution after passing through HA, the uranium removal efficiency was found to be >92 %, which indicates high affinity of the material for uranium. The detection limit of uranium for the gamma spectrometry system is 46 mBq/mL.

Additionally, a method was also developed to back extract uranium from the HA using 0.1M Na₂CO₃. This carbonate solution which contains uranium can further be acidified for subsequent use in solvent extraction to get high purity uranium.

Conclusion

With the developed ecofriendly material and methodology, uranium can be efficiently removed and recovered from the acidic raffinate solutions for better utilization of valuable uranium resources and waste minimization.

References

Dehghan, I., Khamseh, A.A.G. & Ghadiri, A. J Radioanal Nucl Chem 333, 1243–1252 (2024).

RADIATION DOSE RATE & MONAZITE CONTENT MAPPING ALONG COASTAL KOLLAM, KERALA

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Introduction

South west coast of India has the world's richest shoreline heavy mineral (HM) placer deposits of Ilmenite, Rutile, Sillimanite, Zircon, Garnet and the REE bearing Monazite mineral. The coastal belt of Kollam district, Kerala - a renowned Natural High Background Area (NHBRA), is home to a major DAE unit, IREL Chavara and a state PSU KMML, involved in HM beneficiation. Indian resources constitute about 35% of world resources of Ilmenite, 10% of Rutile, 14% of Zircon and 71.4% of Monazite and about 10% of the world requirement of Garnet [1]. The radioactivity in HM is mainly due to Monazite, a prescribed substance as per the Notification under the Atomic Energy Act, 1962 as it is a Naturally Occurring Radioactive Material (NORM) and the principal resource of Rare Earths and Thorium. This study is for a systematic mapping of radiation dose rate and Monazite content along intertidal area of 50 km long coastal Kollam NHBRA region.

Materials and Methods

Beach sand samples (25 nos) collected at every 2 km distances from Kappil Pozhi (Lat 8.7771° N & Long 76.6760° E) to Azheekal Beach (Lat 9.1344° N & Long 76.4625° E) were subjected for quantification of Monazite mineral using standard protocols for microscopic analysis of HM at NABL accredited R&D Lab of IREL Chavara. The radiation field monitoring in μSvh^{-1} was carried out at ground level & 1m height from same locations using NaI(Tl) based ultralow level Radiation Survey meter of HP Unit, Chavara (under HPD, BARC).

Results

The systematic field mapping at 1 km intervals of external dose rate at 50 km long study area showed that the values in μSvh^{-1} at 1m height varied from 0.11 to 4.27 with mean \pm SD & median values of 1.61 \pm 1.37 &

1.37 respectively. The measured dose rate at ground level in these locations in μSvh^{-1} varied from 0.13 to 5.08 and the average ratio of radiation dose rate at ground level to 1m height was 1.10. The lowest dose rate of 0.11 μSvh^{-1} was observed at Kappil Pozhi (8.7771° N & 76.6760° E) and Thanni beach (8.8349° N & 76.6329° E) and the highest was 4.27 μSvh^{-1} at Karithura beach (8.9683° N & 76.5284° E). The microscopic analysis for Monazite content in the beach sand samples from the same locations were found to be in the range of 0.01% to 2.15% with mean & median levels of 0.78 \pm 0.69% and 0.74% respectively.

The dose rate levels at 1m height and Monazite content were plotted to obtain a linear relationship. The Monazite content in percentage is found to be about 0.49 times (nearly half of) the dose rate at 1m height from the same place in μSvh^{-1} with R² value of 0.94 in the studied area.

Conclusion

Radiation dose rate mapping of 50 km long intertidal zone of Kollam district, Kerala was carried out systematically and Monazite content in beach sand samples from this area was measured. A linear relationship between Monazite content and measured dose rate was derived.

References

1. Mir Azam Ali et al (2001), *Exploration & Research for Atomic Minerals*, Vol.13, 21 p.

SEASONAL VARIATION OF GROSS BETA AND ALPHA ACTIVITY IN AIR PARTICULATE MATTER AT NAPS NARORA

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Keywords: APM, Gross α , Gross β , Radioactivity, Meteorological parameter.

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Introduction

Natural radioactivity present in the environment [1] is due to cosmogenic radionuclide, cosmic radiation, and progenies. The major contributors of gross α and gross β activity are ⁴⁰K and daughter products of uranium and thorium series radionuclides. Rainfall events carries down airborne radioactive materials to the earth's surface, in which some part gets airborne again due to resuspension from various natural processes. Remaining portion of deposited activity transported to other matrices following several pathways. The concentration of radioactivity attached to air particulate matter (APM) varies with meteorological variables [2] i.e. the rainfall, temperature etc. In this paper correlation study of atmospheric concentrations of APM and dust load data observed for last 15 years (2009 to 2023) at NAPS Narora site has been carried out.

Materials and Methods

High volume air samplers are used for collection of APM in on GFA filter papers on weekly basis at ESL NAPS and hourly rain fall events were measured using rain gauge (tipping bucket) and recorded using 24 channel data logger. Filter paper was counted for gross β and gross α using end window GM tube based detector and ZnS(Ag) based scintillation detector respectively. About 702 nos. of samples collected to evaluate gross β and gross α activity during the study period. The activity concentration of gross β and gross α in the particulate matter was determined using following formula

$$A(\alpha/\beta)(Bq/m^3) = (CPM_{gross} - CPMBkg) / (150 * \eta * V)$$

here η : is Counting efficiency (fractional), V: is volume of air samples (m³).

Results

Observed mean concentration of gross β and gross α in air particulate samples for four seasons namely winter (Dec-Feb) (0.63 & 0.15 mBq.m⁻³), summer (Mar-May) (1.15 & 0.27

mBq.m⁻³), monsoon (June-Sept) (0.53 & 0.14 mBq.m⁻³), and autumn (Oct-Nov) (0.67 & 0.18 mBq.m⁻³). The maximum APM load (159.4 μ g.m⁻³) was observed during summer and minimum during monsoon (97.5 μ g.m⁻³). Out of 702 samples, 342 nos. of samples activity for gross β and gross α were ≤ 0.3 mBq.m⁻³ and ≤ 0.03 mBq.m⁻³ respectively. GM of gross β ranged as 0.53 to 1.15 mBq.m⁻³ (GSD: 1.1 to 1.3) and GM of gross α ranged as 0.14 to 0.27 mBq.m⁻³ (GSD: 1.1 to 1.2). Mean monthly rainfall data were monitored during the study period ranged as 0.54 cm to 23.34 cm. APM load shows strong positive correlation ($r_2 = 0.89$) with gross β and gross α ($r_2 = 0.82$) concentration in air.

Conclusion

During monsoon season, lower value Gross β and gross α activity was observed in APM due to wash down effects. Higher concentration of gross β and α activity in air observed during summer season due to higher wind speed and temperature results convective air flow directed from surface to atmosphere. Strong positive correlation between APM load versus gross β and gross α concentration in air observed during the study.

Reference

1. United Nations Scientific Committee on the effect of Atomic Radiation. Radiation Sources and Effect of Ionizing Radiation. United Nations; 2000
2. Miguel Ángel Hernández-Ceballos et. al (2020), Analysis of Alpha Activity Levels and Dependence on Meteorological Factors over a Complex Terrain in Northern Iberian Peninsula (2014–2018), nt. J. Environ. Res. Public Health 2020. 17, 7967.

SEASONAL DYNAMICS OF GROSS ALPHA, GROSS BETA AND BERYLLIUM-7 ACTIVITY IN AIRBORNE PARTICULATES AT THE NAPS NARORA SITE

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Keywords: Beryllium-7, Gross alpha, gross beta, meteorological elements, Co-relation coefficient.

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Introduction

Atmospheric radioactivity arises from natural radioactive decay, cosmogenic production, and human activities, all contributing to particulate radioactivity in the atmosphere. Beryllium-7 (7Be) is a notable radionuclide with a half-life of 53.3 days, generated through nuclear reactions in the atmosphere which quickly adheres to sub-micron aerosol particles. Monitoring gross alpha and beta radioactivity in the air near nuclear power plant (NPP) sites is crucial for detecting possible peaks in radioactivity from nuclear releases. Present study reports the last ten (2014–2023) years of weekly cumulative measurements of gross alpha, gross beta, and 7Be activities in airborne particulate matter, with an aim to study temporal variations and identifying meteorological factors influencing these variations. The research was conducted at the Narora Atomic Power Station (NAPS) site in north India. This region experiences most of its rainfall during the monsoon season (June–September), averaging 700–800 mm annually, with prevailing north-westerly and south-easterly winds.

Material & Methods

Airborne particulate samples were collected using high-volume air sampler operating at a flow rate of 100–120 LPM to collect total suspended particulate matter (TSPM). Weekly cumulative aerosol samples were weighed to determine TSPM concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and counted to measure gross alpha and long-lived gross beta activities. For 7Be determination, monthly cumulative samples by combining four to five weekly collected samples and counted on HPGe detector. 7Be concentration was quantified by detecting gamma at 477.6 keV, with a counting time of 86,400 seconds, yielding a detection limit of approximately 0.5 mBq per sample.

Results and Discussion

Observed seasonal variations in gross alpha, beta, and 7Be concentrations includes (a) geometric mean (GM) values for gross alpha ($0.36 \text{ mBq}/\text{m}^3$) and gross beta ($1.53 \text{ Bq}/\text{m}^3$) activities occurring from April to May, with the highest 7Be concentration ($3.94 \text{ mBq}/\text{m}^3$)

observed between April and June; (b) the lowest GM values for gross alpha ($0.07 \text{ mBq}/\text{m}^3$) and gross beta ($0.37 \text{ Bq}/\text{m}^3$) appearing in August, with the lowest 7Be concentration ($1.13 \text{ mBq}/\text{m}^3$) in July; and (c) 7Be concentrations showing seasonal trends, peaking in summer (April–June) and reaching minimum values during monsoon (July–September) and winter, (November– February). This seasonal trend is likely due to variations in stratosphere-to-troposphere transport rates, as observed by Chao et al. (2013) [1], who identified a “spring peak” in March–April for 7Be. Meteorological factors significantly affect the dispersion and transport of airborne radioactive particulates. Pearson correlation analysis revealed strong negative correlations between radioactive aerosol concentrations and both relative humidity (-0.74 to -0.86) and rainfall (-0.45 to -0.60), indicating effective wet deposition during monsoon seasons. Conversely, a weak positive correlation was found with air temperature (0.40 to 0.54) and strong correlation with TSPM (0.80 to 0.94), suggesting enhanced vertical mixing during warmer months.

Conclusion

This study of seasonal variation patterns of gross alpha, gross beta, and 7Be activities, shows that meteorological elements Air temperature, Relative humidity, and Rainfall play a major role in these variations. Monitoring these variables offers valuable data for predictive modelling of airborne radioactivity, which is essential for environmental protection efforts.

Reference

J.H. Chao , Y.J. Chiu b , H.P. Lee a , M.C. Lee, 2013, Variation of atmospheric Be-7 in relation to PM concentrations, Applied Radiation and Isotopes 78 ,82–87.

STUDY OF DISPERSION AND DEPOSITION OF RADIONUCLIDES FROM CHERNOBYL NUCLEAR ACCIDENT

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Keywords: Chernobyl Accident, Atmospheric dispersion, Ground-shine dose, WRF, FLEXPART.

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Introduction

On 25 April 1986, at 21:23UTC, the Chernobyl nuclear power station (power rating of 1000MWe) suffered a major nuclear accident. It is reported that the release of radioactive material is time-varying and lasted for 10d from the onset of the accident. In the present study, near accurate dispersion and deposition of radionuclides is analyzed for radiological impact assessment in the accidental scenario.

Materials and Methods

The dispersion behaviour depends on meteorological parameters (windspeed/direction, rainfall etc.) and release information (the time-varying source term and release height). Based on the literature (NEA, 2002), 14 of the most significant radionuclides are considered in this study, with a release height of 1.5km above ground (column release). High-resolution flow field simulations are conducted using the 3-way nested Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) meso-scale model with a resolution of 3km. The model is initialized using ERA5 reanalysis data with a 0.25° resolution. For a realistic dispersion and deposition pattern, the FLEXPART-WRF model (Brioude et al., 2013) is used. The modelling domain in FLEXPART is configured with 120×120 grids, each with a 0.5km resolution, covering a 60km×60km area around the site. The doses through different pathways, such as inhalation, immersion, and ground contamination, are calculated using the dose conversion coefficients (DCF) outlined in ECPDA (2020).

Results

It is reported that approximately 1760PBq of I-131 is released into the atmosphere. The simulation indicates that within 1km of the NPP, the thyroid dose

exceeds 700mSv. The observed average thyroid dose near Belarus and Ukraine is ~210mGy, while the simulation estimates a thyroid dose of ~200mSv. Within the 5km zone boundary, the simulated immersion dose is ~300-400mSv due to the release of 6500PBq of Xe-133. Measurements show that within the 30km zone, ground depositions exceeded 1500KBq/m². The simulated deposition pattern indicates deposition levels of ~1000- 3000KBq/m² within the 30km boundary. Due to the long half-lives of radionuclides such as Cs-137 and Sr-90, the deposited activity persists for many years. The cumulative ground contamination dose within the site boundary (1.6km) after 10d is >60mSv and it is estimated to take 60y for this dose to fall below the emergency level of 20mSv. The predicted deposition also indicates that within the 5km zone, the initial activity is ~37mSv. From the analysis it is observed that, this area is expected to become habitable by 2030 as the dose decreases below 20mSv due to radioactive decay and weathering processes ($\lambda_w = 0.00014d^{-1}$). Beyond 15km, the doses are significantly lower, around 10mSv.

Conclusion

This simulation study provides an accurate description of the dispersion and deposition patterns in the case of the Chernobyl accident. The findings can be utilized for radiological impact assessments and planning, such as the relocation of the population within the affected area.

References

- Brioude et al. (2013) *Geoscientific Model Development*.
- NEA (2002) *CHERNOBYL Assessment of Radiological and Health Impacts*.

EVALUATION OF SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION USING KRIGING TECHNIQUE FOR NATURAL RADIOACTIVITY IN SOIL SAMPLES OF CHENGALPATTU DISTRICT, TAMIL NADU, INDIA

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Keywords: Natural radionuclide, Kriging technique, Soil, Chengalpattu district, Tamil Nadu.

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Introduction

The main sources of natural radioactivity are the presence of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th series, and ⁴⁰K in the geological matter of the earth's crust (Scott, D. (1989). The variation in concentrations of these radionuclides will change the distribution pattern in the background radiation level UNSCEAR report (1988). Therefore, one of the most widely known kriging techniques was used to evaluate the spatial distribution of the concentrations of natural radionuclides in soil samples of Chengalpattu districts, Tamil Nadu.

Materials and Methods

To map the distribution of the natural radioactivity. A grid-based sampling (2.5 x 2.5 Km) was carried out and 51 Nos of soil samples were collected covering the entire district. GPS locations are recorded. The study area of the Chengalpattu district, Tamil Nadu is 2945 Km² and lies between latitude: 11° 41' – 12° 60' N, longitude: 78° 59' – 79° 58' N. The collected samples are processed as per the IAEA TRS 295 (1989) for measurement of natural radionuclides (Michel (2001). The gamma-ray spectrometer system contains a scintillation detector NaI(Tl) with dimensions of 3"×3", provided by Alpha Spectra, Inc.-12112/3, connected with an MCA ORTEC-DigiBase multi-channel analyzer of 4096 channels coupled with Analog to Digital Converter (ADC) unit through an interface. The MAESTRO-32 software is used in this work for all spectroscopic measurements and analysis of the data. The Surfer software ver 8.0, kriging interpolation method was applied to the radionuclide data for spatial distribution.

Results

The activity concentrations of the soil samples collected from the Chengalpattu district, Tamil Nadu: ²³⁸U varying from BDL

– 45.96 Bq kg⁻¹ with an average value of 8.19 Bq kg⁻¹, ²³²Th varying from 6.12 – 544.09 Bq kg⁻¹ with an average value of 74.48 Bq kg⁻¹ and ⁴⁰K varying from 14.34 to 1084.24 with an average value of 304.86 Bq kg⁻¹. The average activity concentrations of ²³⁸U and ⁴⁰K are below the Indian average value of 30 and 420 Bq kg⁻¹ whereas ²³²Th average activity concentration is slightly above the Indian average value of 65 Bq kg⁻¹ (UNSCEAR 2008).

The contour map shows the spatial distribution of natural radionuclides plotted using the Kriging method and clearly indicates that the northern part of the district shows high activity concentration of ²³⁸U and ²³²Th, whereas areas close to the eastern boundary of the Chengalpattu districts showed high ⁴⁰K activity.

Conclusion

The activity concentration values of ²³⁸U and ⁴⁰K in collected soil samples of Chengalpattu districts are below the Indian average value, whereas ²³²Th activity concentrations are slightly high. The contour map using the Kriging method clearly shows the spatial distribution of the radionuclides in the study area.

References

Scott, D. (1989). UNSCEAR report (1988). Report to the general assembly, with annexes.

Michel, R. (2001). Proceedings Ecorad, 27-62.

IAEA 1989. A guidebook: Technical Reports Series No. STI/DOC/010/295 TRS 295. IAEA, Vienna, Austria.

UNSCEAR 2008 report, volume I: Report to the general assembly, with scientific annexes A and B-sources. United Nations.

BASELINE MAPPING AND ASSESSMENT OF AMBIENT GAMMA DOSE RATE OF KANYAKUMARI, A COASTAL DISTRICT IN TAMIL NADU, INDIA.

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Keywords: Ambient gamma, contour-map, annual effective dose, Kanyakumari, Tamil Nadu.

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Introduction

Contribution to the environmental background radiation is largely attributed to cosmic rays and naturally occurring radionuclides present in the environmental matrices (UNSCEAR 2000, Bramha et al., 2019). The estimation and mapping of ambient gamma radiation dose is important for assessing dose to public health and also serves as the baseline document for the study area.

Materials and Methods

In Tamil Nadu state, Kanyakumari is the southernmost coastal district. In addition, it has the highest per capita income in the state and leads in education, literacy, and the Human Development Index. An extensive, radiometric survey was carried out in 155 locations covering the entire district. Ambient gamma dose was measured at each sampling location using a digital gamma survey meter (RadEyeTM), Thermo-Scientific, USA, comprising a Geiger Muller (G.M) tube-based for precise and sensitive measurement. The readings were recorded at 1m above the ground level (Pandian et al., 2000). The average ambient gamma (μSvh^{-1}) value was noted from five readings at each sampling station (Padua and Rose 2013).

Results

Survey of the Ambient gamma dose rate was conducted at different locations in the Kanyakumari district, varying from 0.07 – 0.42 μSvh^{-1} with an average value of 0.15 μSvh^{-1} . To understand the proper distribution of the ambient gamma dose rate throughout the entire district, contour mapping was carried out using surfer software (Ver. 8.0).

The average value of the ambient gamma dose for the entire study region was slightly higher when compared to the values (mean of 0.059 μSvh^{-1} in the range of 0.018–0.93 μSvh^{-1}) given in UNSECAR (2000) for different countries and with the all India

average value (0.089 μSvh^{-1} in the range of 0.027–3.051 μSvh^{-1}) reported by Nambi et al. (1987).

From the hourly dose rate, the annual effective dose was computed using the outdoor occupancy factor of 0.2 (UNSCEAR 2008). The annual effective dose was calculated from the survey meter data, varying from 0.12 to 0.73 mSv y^{-1} with average values of 0.26 mSv y^{-1} . The gamma radiation dose level in the study area is lower compared with the permissible limit for the general public, which is 2.4 mSv y^{-1} , according to the regulations of UNSCEAR 2000.

Conclusion

The contour map of the ambient gamma dose rate in the Kanyakumari district clearly shows the spatial distribution dose, which serves as the baseline map. The calculated annual effective dose in the study area showed a lower value, which indicates that the dose received from the background radiation was not causing any adverse effect to the general public.

References

- UNSCEAR (2000). Volume I: Report to the General Assembly, with Scientific Annexes-Sources.
- Bramha, S., Sahoo, S. K., Subramanian, V., Venkatraman, B., & Rath, P. (2019). SN Applied Sciences, 1, 1-10.
- Pandian SS, Sivakumar R, Manikandan MN, Meenakshisundaram V, Raghunath VM, Gajendran V (2000) Appl Radiat Isot 52(2):299–306.
- Padua, J. C., & Basil Rose, M. R. (2013). Radiation protection dosimetry, 156(1), 42-48.

ANALYSIS OF NATURAL URANIUM IN GROUNDWATER OF KANCHIPURAM DISTRICT OF TAMILNADU, INDIA

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Keywords: Groundwater, Uranium, Fluorimeter, Age dependent radiation dose, Hazard quotient.

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Introduction

The groundwater serves as the primary drinking water supply in both rural and urban India as well as in many regions worldwide. This study aimed to examine uranium concentration levels in groundwater and assess potential health effects for the local population in the area.

Materials and Methods

A total of 30 nos of groundwater samples are collected in clean plastic bottles from different bore wells in Kanchipuram districts, Tamil Nadu. The sampling locations are chosen in such a way that they cover the entire district, and the latitude, longitude of each location are recorded with the help of handheld Garmin GPS. The concentration of Uranium in groundwater was analysed using an LED fluorimeter and values were compared after analysing with trace metal analyser. Major cations and anions are analysed using Ion chromatography. Other water quality parameters such as pH, conductivity, total dissolved solids, and total alkalinity have also been analysed for the groundwater samples of the study area.

Results

Assessment of uranium activity concentrations, age-dependent annual effective dosage, and radiological and chemical toxicity risk were evaluated as per ICRP 72 (1996). The Uranium concentration ranged from 0.2 µg/l to 16.7 µg/l, with a mean value of 3.1 µg/l. Uranium contents in the groundwater samples that were examined were found to be significantly lower than the AERB and WHO-recommended thresholds of 60 µg/l and 30 µg/l, respectively (WHO 2011, AERB 2004). The age-dependent annual effective dosage ranged from 0.78 to 19.37 µSv/year, with a mean value of 3.62 µSv/year, much below the prescribed

guideline limit of 100 µSv/year. The lifetime average daily dose of uranium ranged from 0.006 to 0.48 µg Kg⁻¹ day⁻¹. The hazard quotient was determined to be below one, indicating that no significant health impacts are anticipated from Uranium exposure. Upon evaluating radiological toxicity risk, the projected cancer mortality risk was well below the permitted threshold of 1.67×10^{-4} established by AERB. The cancer mortality risk estimates ranged from 4.5×10^{-7} to 3.8×10^{-5} .

Conclusion

The concentration of Uranium in the research region was found to be far below the permitted limits of 60 µg/l and 30 µg/l set by AERB and WHO, respectively. The research indicated that the carcinogenic impacts of radiological toxicity and the noncarcinogenic effects of chemical toxicity are negligible in the study region. No significant correlation could be observed between uranium and the evaluated physicochemical characteristics.

References

ICRP Publication 72; Ann ICRP 26/1 (1996). Singh. B and Kataria. N (2014) Tox and Env Chem 96(10), 1571 -1580.

PARAMETRIC EVALUATION OF MATRIX INFLUENCES ON DETECTOR RESPONSE ACROSS BROAD RANGE OF PHOTON ENERGIES

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Keywords: Efficiency, Uranium-238, Germanium Detector, Monte Carlo, Density

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Introduction

Accurate assessment of the specific activities (SA) of natural radionuclide is crucial for effective environmental radiation monitoring. Quantifying SA necessitates the prior construction of full energy peak efficiency (FEPE) curve tailored to the specified sample geometry. This is typically achieved by using known activity standard sources that closely mimic the physical properties of the environmental sample being analyzed. Experimental determination of FEPE curves is time-consuming; hence Monte Carlo (MC) simulations are used. This study has two primary objectives: (1) to establish FEPE curves using MC simulations for germanium detector by varying parameters such as the height, diameter and density of the homogeneous sample (Uranium-238 volume source) and (2) to assess the impact of nonhomogeneous composition samples with different densities on the calibration trends.

Materials and Methods

A coaxial p-type detector and a sample (IAEA standard calibrated source – RGU in cylindrical 250 mL geometry) are modeled in this work. MC simulations are performed with a standard RGU source on contact with the detector at varying heights (by maintaining constant density) for energies 295 keV, 352 keV, 609 keV, 1120 keV and 1764 keV. The simulations have also been performed for different densities and diameters of the source for the said energies. The FEPE (ϵ) is calculated using the formula $\epsilon = N / (A * I * M) \dots\dots (1)$

where N is the counts/sec(CPS) obtained from the simulation, A is the radioactivity of radionuclide in the standard source, I is the gamma-ray intensity per decay and M is the mass of the standard source.

Results

The detection efficiency of the homogeneous composition sample (RGU)

decreases as the sample height increases from 6 cm to 10 cm and this trend holds true across all energies. Similarly, as the sample density shifts from 1.08 gm/cc to 1.43 gm/cc, the efficiency decreases for various energies, reinforcing the impact of density on efficiency. Additionally, varying the diameter of cylindrical samples from 1.95 cm to 3.15 cm, while maintaining a constant height, results in a noticeable decrease in FEPE. Monte Carlo simulations are also carried out on seven non-homogeneous composition samples with density similar to the standard source RGU ($\rho = 1.362 \text{ g/cm}^3$). Stable CPS measurements are observed for the constant density of the samples relative to the standard source. However, CPS decreases as the sample density increases, with densities ranging from 1.15 g/cm^3 to 2.09 g/cm^3 .

Conclusions

The study demonstrates an inverse correlation between FEPE and homogeneous sample height, diameter and density. Increasing the sample height while maintaining a constant density leads to a gradual decrease in FEPE. Similarly, changes in sample density and diameter also result in consistent reductions in FEPE. In the case of non-homogeneous sample, variations in sample density have a significant impact on CPS, highlighting the importance of matching density to gamma standards in order to minimize CPS fluctuations. Understanding these effects is crucial for ensuring accurate radiation assessment and monitoring in diverse sample conditions.

References

1. Sabatino G., et al. (2019) *J. Instrum* **14**, P05015.

URANIUM LEVELS IN GROUNDWATER SAMPLES IN THE ENVIRONMENT OF MANDYA DISTRICT, KARNATAKA, INDIA AND ASSESSMENT OF ASSOCIATED RADIATION RISKS TO THE POPULATION

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Introduction

Living things are exposed to radiation from terrestrial radionuclides both inside and externally. Because of the possible health hazards linked to prolonged exposure, radionuclides including uranium, radon, and polonium found in environmental sources such rocks, soil, and water are a major cause for concern. Uranium in drinking water poses health risks primarily due to its chemical toxicity and radiological effects. Prolonged exposure can lead to kidney damage and an increased risk of cancer from radiation exposure. The risks depend on the uranium concentration, water consumption rate, and duration of exposure. In order to evaluate radiation concerns, this study examines the amount of uranium in groundwater from the Mandya district, Karnataka, India.

Materials and Methods

In this work, a Quantalase Uranium Analyser UA-1 with an LED Fluorimeter was used to analyze the amount of uranium in water. The detection limit of the device was 0.2 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. A standard uranium solution was used to calibrate the LED fluorimeter, and background counts were noted.

Results

In the present study the uranium concentration in 230 groundwater samples of Mandya district vary from 0.63 to 106.87 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ with geometric mean of 14.44 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. The average uranium concentration is higher in Kalenahalli of Srirangapatna taluk, Rangana Koppal of Pandavapura taluk, Naragallu of Nagamagala taluk and Gopalapura of Mandya taluk with the values of 106.87, 99.04, 98.74 and 92.18 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ respectively. Higher uranium concentration was found near granitic rock exposures and shale formation, while lower concentration

was observed in older rock types. World Health Organization (WHO, 2011), have set a prescribed concentration limit of 30 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for uranium in drinking water, while the Atomic Energy Regulatory Board (AERB, 2004), has established a maximum limit of 60 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. Among all the analyzed samples, 14% showed concentrations exceeding 30 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, which is the safe limit set by the WHO, while 8% of the samples exceeded 60 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, the safe limit set by the Atomic Energy Regulatory Board of India. The radiological and chemical risk due to uranium in water to the population of the study area was also estimated from the measured concentration value.

Conclusion

The concentration of uranium in groundwater samples of Mandya district varied from vary from 0.63 to 106.87 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. Mandya's uranium levels are moderate compared to some of the highest values reported globally, but few localized hotspots were identified. Among all the analyzed samples, 8% of the samples exceeded 60 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, the safe limit set by the Atomic Energy Regulatory Board (AERB) of India.

References

- WHO (2011). Guidelines for Drinking-water Quality: 4th Edition. Geneva: WHO.
- AERB (2004) Drinking water specifications in India. Department of Atomic Energy, Govt. of India.

ANNUAL AND SEASONAL VARIATIONS IN THE AMBIENT AIR QUALITY PARAMETERS AT KALPAKKAM NUCLEAR POWER PLANT SITE (2022-23)

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Keywords: Air Quality, Stable atmospheric conditions, Sea breeze, AQI

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Introduction

Human well-being relies on having clean air. In addition to affecting public health, air pollutants adversely impact ecosystems and the global climate. Populations experiencing lower levels of air pollution generally exhibit improved respiratory and cardiovascular health over both short and long terms. Since the harmful chemical substances that degrade air quality are often emitted alongside greenhouse gases, there is a strong connection between air pollution and climate change. The Environment (Protection) Act, 1986 highlights the significance of evaluating current and expected levels of air pollution through the implementation of a continuous air quality monitoring program at industrial facilities. To effectively manage air quality and ensure compliance with environmental regulations, an Ambient Air Quality Monitoring Program (AAQMP) has been established at the Indira Gandhi Centre for Atomic Research in Kalpakkam.

Materials and Methods

The purpose of this initial study is to evaluate Kalpakkam's ambient air quality trends. A continuous Ambient Air Quality Monitoring system placed within the site is used to assess changes in particulate matter (PM10), particulate matter (PM2.5), and gaseous pollutants such as sulfur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), and carbon monoxide (CO) for the years 2022-2023. In order to effectively assess the air quality and measure these pollutant characteristics on a regular basis, seven micro air-quality monitors covering different sectors and wind flow facilities have also been put at the DAE Kalpakkam site.

Results

This study analyses the changes in concentrations of air pollutants - PM10, PM2.5, SO₂, NO₂, and CO for a period of 2 years (2022-2023). The long-term

observations reveal that the particulate matter and gaseous pollutant concentrations have never exceeded the permissible National Ambient Air Quality Standards (Central Pollution Control Board) standards at our site. Nevertheless, pollutants are present in lower levels in summer due to the influence of sea breeze, while the highest levels are seen in the winter months attributed to stable meteorological conditions observed in the site. In 2022, the annual average of PM10 & PM2.5 was (32µg/m³; 21µg/m³), in 2023, the annual averages of PM10 & PM2.5 were (30µg/m³; 18 µg/m³). In the year 2022, the annual average SO₂ was 7µg/m³; 3 µg/m³ in 2023. While the annual average of carbon monoxide (CO) was measured at 0.3 mg/m³ in 2022, and 0.2 mg/m³ in 2023. In 2022, the annual average of NO₂ was 11 µg/m³ in 2022 and 8 µg/m³ in 2023.

Conclusion

According to the CPCB index, the site's Air Quality Index (AQI), which was derived from these observations, falls into the goodsatisfactory category during the entire study period.

References

1. Srinivas C.V., Venkatesan R., K.M Somayaji and A. Bagavath Singh. (2006), A numerical study of sea breeze circulation observed at a tropical site Kalpakkam on the east coast of India, under different synoptic flow situations J. Earth Syst. Sci. 115, No. 5, pp. 557–574.
2. CPCB, MoEF (1998), National Ambient Air Quality Standards, Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1981, S.O. 935(E).

PRELIMINARY OBSERVATIONS OF THE NEWLY INSTALLED ONLINE ISOTOPE MONITORING SYSTEM AT IGCAR, KALPAKKAM

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Introduction

An Online Isotope Monitoring System (OIMS) system has been recently installed at IGCAR, positioned in one of the predominant wind directions. To monitor environmental radiation levels and to provide early detection and warning of inadvertent radioactive releases, EAD, SQRMG has deployed 27 GM-based radiation monitors (Autonomous Gamma Dose Loggers - AGDLs) around the site as part of the Online Nuclear Emergency Response System (ONERS) operational at site. These detectors measure the ambient gamma dose rates (nSv/hr) and do not identify any specific isotopes. In contrast, the OIMS is a special, advanced and state-of-the-art monitoring system installed for the first time in India, featuring sophisticated spectrometers, a dose rate monitor and an automatic weather station for online detection, identification and quantification of radioactive aerosols such as Cs and I isotopes towards realtime source term estimation in the event of nuclear emergencies. This paper presents the initial observations & measurements by the OIMS at EAD, SQRMG.

Materials and Methods

The OIMS is a fully automated system with a combination of detectors for alpha, beta, and gamma radiation measurements, along with the necessary electronics, air pump, and associated hardware and software. It includes an electrically cooled HPGe detector (30% relative efficiency), a PIPS detector (1700 mm²) for measuring normal aerosols on glass fiber filters, and two 2 × 2” NaI(Tl) detectors for measuring iodine on charcoal filters. The air pump, with a flow rate of 8 m³/hr, directs air through the glass fibre filters first, followed by the charcoal filters. The system also has a proportional counter for dose rate monitoring. An automatic manipulator changes the filters after each predefined cycle. With detection

capabilities ranging from 1 to 5 Bq/m³ for isotopes like Cs137, Co60, and I131, the system is very sensitive. Also, a weather station is included to accurately measure wind speed and direction at the site.

Results and Discussion

The system is installed in the North Sector, approximately 2 km from the MAPS stack. During the summer (Mar-May) and the southwest monsoon (Jun-Sep), prevailing wind conditions are favorable for detecting any potential releases at the detector location. The background dose rate, as measured by the proportional counter, is 80 ± 5 nSv/hr, with a peak dose rate observed in August 2024 at 784 nSv/hr. The dose rates recorded by the system’s proportional counter have been compared and validated against the nearby AGDL showing good agreement. Spectra obtained by HPGe detector has confirmed the presence of 41Ar, which is one of the isotopes routinely released during normal operations from the MAPS reactors. During all instances when dose rates exceeded background levels, the 1293 keV gamma peak from Ar41 was observed, along with the gamma peaks from naturally occurring radon and thoron daughter products, including Pb212, Pb214, Bi214, Tl208 as well as K40. In the absence of any detectable artificial radionuclides, spectra from the PIPS detector are used for the estimation of radon and thoron’s Equilibrium Equivalent Concentration (EEC) values in the air.

Conclusion

Initial observations by the Online Isotope Monitoring System have been analysed and instances of Ar41 releases have been studied.

References

Mathew, A & et al. Radionuclide measurements at International Monitoring Station. J. Environ. Radioact. 272, 2023.

STUDY OF NATURAL RADIOACTIVITY IN MANUFACTURED SAND (M-SAND)

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Keywords: M-sand, NORM, concentration, limit
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Introduction

The sand is a non-renewable resource and is widely used in construction industry. In general, the river sand is used for construction but it has become scarce due to over exploitation. The aggregate material processed from crushed rock gravel; known as Manufactured sand (M-sand) is used as an alternative to river sand. The aim of the present study is to determine the concentration of naturally occurring radionuclides (NORMs: ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, ⁴⁰K) in M-sand and compute the radiation hazards using indices such as radium equivalent (Raeq), absorbed gamma dose rate (DR), annual effective dose equivalent (AEDE), external radiation hazard index (Hex), internal hazard index (Hin), activity utilization index (AUI).

Materials and Methods

The M-sand (51 nos.) collected from various crusher plants around Mumbai were size fractioned into 250 μ m, 125 μ m, <125 μ m particle sizes (PS). The NORMs concentrations were estimated using coaxial p-type high purity germanium detector.

Results

The mean concentration in 250 μ m PS was 9Bq.kg⁻¹(²³⁸U), 12Bq.kg⁻¹ (²³²Th), 193.3 Bq.kg⁻¹(⁴⁰K). The mean concentration in 125 μ m PS was 10.1 Bq.kg⁻¹(²³⁸U), 15Bq.kg⁻¹ (²³²Th), 213.3Bq.kg⁻¹ (⁴⁰K). The <125 μ m PS showed the mean concentration as 13Bq.kg⁻¹ (²³⁸U), 17.9Bq.kg⁻¹(²³²Th), 228.3Bq.kg⁻¹(⁴⁰K). The observed concentrations of NORMs in studied PSs were lower than global average (UNSCEAR, 2000). Raeq in 250 μ m, 125 μ m, <125 μ m are 41Bq.kg⁻¹, 48.2Bq.kg⁻¹, 55.6 Bq.kg⁻¹, respectively and are below prescribed limit of 370Bq.kg⁻¹(UNSCEAR, 2010). DR in 250 μ m, 125 μ m, <125 μ m are 19.4 nGy.h⁻¹, 22.7nGy.h⁻¹, 26.1nGy.h⁻¹, respectively and are lower than world absorbed average

gamma dose rate of 84nGy.h⁻¹ (UNSCEAR, 2000). AEDE was 0.1 mSv.y⁻¹ (250 μ m), 0.1mSv.y⁻¹ (125 μ m), 0.1mSv.y⁻¹ (<125 μ m) and are lower than global average of 0.5 mSv.y⁻¹ (Murthuza et al., 2022). The Hex in 250 μ m, 125 μ m, <125 μ m are 0.1, 0.1, 0.2, respectively, and are much lower than the recommended level of unity (UNSCEAR, 2000). The Hin in 250 μ m, 125 μ m, <125 μ m was 0.1, 0.2, 0.2, respectively and are lower than the standard limit of unity (Darwish et al., 2015). AUI in 250 μ m, 125 μ m, <125 μ m was 0.3, 0.3, 0.4, respectively and the observed values satisfy the criteria of AUI < 2 (Silva et al., 2022).

Conclusion

The concentrations of NORMs in various size fractions of M-sand were increasing with decreasing particle size with no significant variation in radioactivity levels with different size and the concentrations were below the global average. The studied radiation hazard indices were lesser than the permissible limit, indicating that the M-sand from the study area does not pose any radiological hazard to public, on use of it for construction purpose.

References

- United Nat. Sci. Comm. on the Effects of Atomic Rad. Sources (2000) *Exposures from natural radiation sources*.
- United Nations Sci. Comm. on the Effects of Atomic Rad. (2010) *Summary of lowdose radiation effects on health*.
- Murthuza KM, Surumbarkuzhali N et al. (2022) *Materials Today: Proc.*, 65, 2606-2614.
- Darwish DAE, Abul-Nasr KTM et al. (2015) *J of Rad. Res. and Appl. Sci.* 8(1), 17-25.
- Silva LB, Silva LF et al. (2022) *Proc. of the ISSSD 2022*.

SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS OF WET DEPOSITION PARAMETERIZATIONS IN SIMULATING CS-137 DEPOSITION DURING THE FUKUSHIMA NUCLEAR ACCIDENT

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Keywords: Cs-137, WRFv4.3, FLEXPART-WRF, Wet Deposition, Sensitivity

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Introduction

During the Fukushima nuclear accident on 11 March 2011 large quantities of Cs-137 (Stohl *et al*, 2012) were released to the environment. A significant amount of wet deposition (WD) took place over land due to moderate to heavy rainfall events and occasional landward shifts in wind flow. Earlier studies (Arnaud *et al*, 2021) reported significant uncertainty in the deposited activity estimates. In this work we investigate the influence of WD parameterization in the FLEXPART-WRF (Brioude *et al*, 2013) particle transport model framework in producing the observed Cs-137 deposition.

Materials and Methods

We use WRFv4.3 weather model (Skamarock *et al*, 2019) with Goddard cloud microphysics (CMP) scheme in a domain of 1- km resolution to simulate the rainfall features from 00UTC 11- 00UTC 24 March, 2011 when most of the Cs-137 release and rainfall occurred. The deposition is simulated using four WD parameterizations used in different transport models (*viz.* FLEXPART, HYSPLIT, NAME, RATM). The Goddard scheme predicts mass-concentrations of rain, vapor, ice, snow, graupel and hails in cloud using unique particle-size mapping. The WD schemes treat particle scavenging separately as below-cloud and in-cloud processes with specific scavenging coefficient of the form AIB where A , B are model specific constants and I is the rainfall intensity, except for HYSPLIT scheme where both coefficients are constant. The incloud scavenging in FLEXPART additionally considers cloud liquid-water content, cloudbase height and 90% humidity condition for cloud formation. In total 3.59×10^{16} Bq of Cs-137 release is considered from 50-200m height. The simulated depositions are compared with observed gridded deposition of Cs-137 given by MEXT (2011), Japan.

Results

Analysis shows the FLEXPART WD scheme properly simulate plume movement, concentration levels over land and deposition pattern with high-deposition (10^6 to 3×10^6 Bq/m²) centreline towards North-West sector which is in close agreement with observation. All other schemes produce widespread deposition which is slightly shifted towards West-NorthWest sector without any prominent centreline. Also the observed deposited activity around 5km, 10km and 30km radius is closely simulated by FLEXPART scheme. Box distribution analysis indicates mean observed deposition (3.3×10^5 Bq/m²) and the inter-quartile range closely matches for FLEXPART (3.46×10^5 Bq/m²) whereas HYSPLIT, NAME and RATM overestimate it by a factor of 2.55, 3.12 and 3.02. Statistically deposited activity by FLEXPART scheme shows 47.8% correlation, 0.551 for agreement index and 40.6% of values within twice of observation.

Conclusion

The model configuration in the study with FLEXPART WD parameterization could produce statistically close and more realistic Cs-137 deposition pattern in the Fukushima nuclear accident.

References

- Stohl, A., et al (2012) *Atmos.Chem.Phys.* **12** (5), 2313-2343. Arnaud, Q., et al (2021) *J.Env. Rad.* **237**, pp.106712
Skamarock, W. C., et al (2019). NCAR/TN-556+STR. Brioude, J., et al. (2013) *Geosci. Model. Dev.* **6**, 1889–1904.

ESTIMATION OF ²¹⁰PO ACTIVITY IN WATER HYACINTH AND FISH SPECIES IN THAMIRABARANI RIVER OF TAMIL NADU

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Introduction

Polonium-210 (²¹⁰Po) is a naturally occurring alpha emitting radionuclide with half-life of 138 days and environmentally important due to its impact view point (Matthews et al, 2007). ²¹⁰Po is strongly accumulated in marine organisms an important food source for the people. The marine biota mainly fish and shellfish have been found to contain high concentrations of ²¹⁰Po which is considered as the major contributor of radiation dose to humans (Mishra et al, 2009). Water hyacinth is a bioindicator for water pollution due to its absorbing and accumulating capacity of heavy metals. The objective of the study is to measure ²¹⁰Po activity in water hyacinth and fishes and to estimate dose to public.

Materials and Methods

Total 46 Samples of Water hyacinth (Eichornia) and fish species like Channa striata, Clarias Garie Pinus, and Tilapia were collected at different sampling points in Thamirabarani River during the month of September 2023 for estimation of ²¹⁰Po activity. Eichornia (whole) and fishes were separated into muscle tissue, bone and then dried below 55 °C. Five to ten grams of dry sample was digested with Conc.HNO₃ until a white ash was obtained. The ash was evaporated repeatedly with concentrated HCl to convert the ash into chloride medium. Then it was dissolved in 0.5N HCl, and the ²¹⁰Po electrochemically deposited on a silver planchette and counted in ZnS(Ag) Alpha counting system.

Results

The activity levels of ²¹⁰Po in Eichornia was in the range of 0.7 to 1.4 Bq/kg with a mean of 0.7 Bq/kg. The activity levels of ²¹⁰Po ranged from 2.5 to 6.5 Bq/kg with mean of 3.4 Bq/kg and 1.2 to 5.2 Bq/kg with

mean of 1.9 Bq/kg in Channa striata fish muscle and bone, respectively. The measured ²¹⁰Po activity in Clarias Garie Pinus fish, muscle ranged 2.21 to 7.2 Bq/kg with mean of 4.5 Bq/kg, and in bone ranged 0.8 to 4.6 Bq/kg with a mean of 2.7 Bq/kg, respectively. In Tilapia fish, muscle ²¹⁰Po activity ranged 2.5 to 8.7 Bq/kg with mean of 5.2 Bq/kg and in bone 1.2 to 7.1 Bq/kg with mean of 2.9 Bq/kg respectively. The estimated average annual effective dose due to ²¹⁰Po through the consumption of Channa striata, Clarias Garie Pinus, and Tilapia ranged from 10.2 to 15.6 μSv/y. It is comparable with estimated values of 19.4 μSv/y (Mishra et al 2009) and 0.07 to 32 μSv/y (Strok and Smodis, 2011) through the river fish consumption.

Conclusion

The activity concentrations of ²¹⁰Po in muscle is higher than bones in Channa striata, Clarias Garie Pinus, and Tilapia River fishes. The observed dose received due to consumption of fish is a negligible fraction in comparison to the total natural radiation dose.

References

- Matthews, K.M., Kim, Kyu C. and Martin, P. (2007) Applied Radiation and Isotopes 65, 267-279.
- Mishra, S., Bhalke, S., Pandit, G.G. and Puranik, V.D. (2009) Chemosphere 76, 402-406.
- Strok, M. and Smodis, B. (2011). Chemosphere 82, 970-976.

A DIAGNOSTIC TWO DIMENSIONAL WIND FIELD MODEL BASED ON POINT-ITERATIVE TECHNIQUE

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Keywords: Diagnostic, continuity equation, incompressible flows, irrotational.

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Introduction

Modelling wind field is crucial for wind energy assessment, weather forecasting, wind turbine siting and atmospheric dispersion analysis. Diagnostic wind models generate wind fields which satisfy some physical constraint and are highly appealing for practical applications due to their simplicity, cost-effectiveness, efficiency and minimal input data requirement (Ratto, 1994). In present study, we have developed a two-dimensional mass consistent based wind field model.

Materials and Methods

Mass-consistent models operate by making adjustments to observed wind field such that the continuity equation is satisfied for incompressible flows. For this purpose, finite difference-based Point-Iterative numerical technique is employed (Kitada, 1983). The method works by solving two linear partial differential equations simultaneously

$$\partial u / \partial x + \partial v / \partial y = \delta \quad (1)$$

$$\partial v / \partial x - \partial u / \partial y = \omega \quad (2)$$

Horizontal wind components (u and v) are adjusted at each grid point in such a way that the divergence (δ) of original field is reduced while the vertical component of vorticity (ω) is preserved until convergence is achieved based on a specified tolerance (Endlich, 1967).

Results

The developed model is applied to the following standard flow problems: 1. Source/Sink flow 2. Free vortex flow Standard flows under consideration are nondivergent and irrotational, except at singularity. To test the algorithm, these flows were altered to introduce divergence while maintaining irrotationality. A convergence criterion of $< 5\%$ of initial divergence was used. The algorithm effectively reduced the divergence across entire domain while preserving original vorticity, as required.

Number of iterations needed to achieve convergence depends on domain size and extent of divergence in original field. Model accurately reproduces the general flow patterns of standard flows with lower initial divergence. However, as divergence values increase, deviations from standard flow pattern become more pronounced. Also, it is found that both wind components are adjusted more near boundaries than the center of the domain.

Conclusion

Point-iterative method effectively removes spurious divergence without using any explicit boundary conditions and hence, the output non-divergent winds can be used to compute the stream functions. However, the performance is highly dependent on the degree of divergence of input wind field.

References

- Endlich, R. M. (1967) "An Iterative Method for Altering the Kinematic Properties of Wind Fields," *Journal of Applied Meteorology*, Vol. 6, pp. 837-844.
- Kitada, T., Kaki, A., Ueda, H. and Peters, L. K. (1983) "Estimation of Vertical Air Motion from Limited Horizontal Wind Data—A Numerical Experiment," *Atmospheric Environment*, Vol. 17, No. 11, pp. 2181-2192
- Ratto, C. F., Festa, R., Romeo, C., Frumento, O. A. and Galluzzi, M. (1994) "Mass-Consistent Models for Wind Fields over Complex Terrain: The State of the Art," *Environmental Software*, Vol. 9, No. 4, pp. 247-268.

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF SEA AND LAND BREEZE CIRCULATION (SLBC) USING WRF MODEL: SENSITIVITY TO PARAMETERIZATION SCHEMES AND VALIDATION WITH SODAR DATA

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Introduction

Sea and Land Breeze Circulation (SLBC) is an important mesoscale phenomenon occurring due to temperature gradient between land and sea surface. It has implications in development of coastal boundary layer, wind reversal, as well as transport and dispersion of air pollutants. Several factors like thermal forcing, topography, surface characteristics (namely soil type, vegetation) etc. are known to influence onset, duration and intensity of SLBC. Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) models like Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) have been widely used in study of SLBC (Papanastasiou *et al* (2010)).

Material and Methods

Numerical simulation of SLBC using model in a triple nested domain configuration with grid resolutions varying from 9 km, 3 km and 1 km are carried out for Trombay site. The National Centre for Environmental Protection (NCEP) Final Analyses (FNL) at $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ grid resolution are used to provide initial and boundary conditions to the model. In a Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) model several physical processes (for example atmospheric turbulence) not resolved by the model's grid resolution have to be represented by parameterization schemes. In the present study, various combinations of Planetary Boundary Layer (PBL), Surface Layer (SL) and land surface parameterization schemes have been used to represent turbulence in the atmosphere. Duration of simulation is from 01.01.2023 0 UTC to 04.01.2023 0 UTC and sensitivity to turbulence parameterization schemes has been studied. Model results of wind speed and wind direction are compared with measurements from SOund Detection and Ranging (SODAR) instrument operational at the site.

Results

Model results of wind speed and direction in different combinations of parameterization schemes are interpolated in the vertical to match the SODAR levels from 40 m to 500 m. Here, two Land Surface Models (LSMs), namely Noah LSM and five layer thermal diffusion LSM are used. The effect of change in LSM is clearly evident in the simulation of wind flow. It is seen that the model is able to better simulate the onset of sea and land breezes as well as transition from land to sea breeze condition in simulations with Noah LSM as compared to the other LSM for identical choice of PBL and SL parameterization schemes. This improvement in simulation is mainly due to better representation of vegetation, soil hydrological processes in Noah LSM as compared to the simple five layer thermal diffusion model. However, the directional wind shear observed in SODAR data with respect to height and time of day is not resolved in the present simulations. It should also be noted that increasing number of vertical levels closer to the Earth's surface did not improve the results.

Conclusion

The study demonstrated the utility of WRF model in simulation of SLBC.

References

Papanastasiou, D.K.; Melas, D.; and Lissaridis, I. (2010). *Atmospheric Research*, **98**, 101-117.

AN APPROACH FOR EVALUATION OF HYDRO-GEOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES IN GROUND WATER FROM CHENGALPATTU DISTRICT, TAMIL NADU, INDIA

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Introduction

The first of the earth's handful of natural a freshwater resource is groundwater. Rapid urbanisation, unplanned land-use patterns, industrialisation, population growth, and intense agricultural activities have all contributed to a greater risk of soil and groundwater contamination, which has raised concern about groundwater quality in the past two decades. This paper presents information on the assessment of the water quality in and around Chengalpattu District. A total of 51 groundwater samples were taken from different bore wells within the research area. The hydrogeochemical parameters and heavy metals of groundwater samples were assessed to determine their quality and suitability for usage.

Materials and Methods

The study area sampling is carried out using the grid method and samples are collected within the grid (Durai Ganesh et al. 2021). Groundwater from 51 sampling sites was collected in polyethylene bottles, each of 1L capacity. After sample collection, water quality parameters such as pH, EC, TDS, turbidity and alkalinity are determined by using a tabletop water quality meter. Ion chromatography was used to determine the Anions, Cations, and heavy metals.

Results and Discussions

The pH value of groundwater was 6.6 - 8.1 indicating alkaline nature of analyzed samples. The EC values varied between 224.6 to 3535.0 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ with a mean value of 1122.5 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. Total dissolved solids (TDS) values ranged between 143.7 mg/l to 2262.4 mg/l with an average of 718.4. The general order of abundance of cations in the groundwater of this study area is $\text{K}^+ < \text{Mg}^{2+} < \text{Na}^+ < \text{Ca}^{2+}$, while that for anions is $\text{NO}_2^- < \text{F}^- < \text{PO}_4^{3-} < \text{Br}^- < \text{NO}_3^- < \text{SO}_4^{2-} < \text{Cl}^-$ respectively. From the

heavy metals analysis, the following order $\text{Zn} > \text{Cu} > \text{Pb} > \text{Cd}$ was observed. These metals are compared with the recommended values of WHO (2011) and indicate no toxicity in the study area. Turbidity varies from 0.06 to 6.9 NTU. Only one sample location exceeds the recommendation limit of 2.5 NTU (WHO 2011). The alkalinity varied from 10 to 336.00 mg.L^{-1} and three samples exceed WHO (2011) recommended 300 mg.L^{-1} limits. The spatial variation maps were generated using Surfer (kriging method) environment deciphers the uneven distribution of elemental concentrations in the study area.

Conclusion

The physical-chemical parameters and heavy metal concentrations in groundwater were determined and compared with recommended values. The results showed that they are within the allowable limit. This indicates that water quality in Chengalpattu district has no significant anthropogenic inputs and is safe for drinking and irrigation.

Reference

Durai Ganesh, P., Eswaran, G., Senthilkumar., Bramha, S. N., Chandrasekar, S and Ravisankar, R. (2021). Iranian Journal of Science and Technology. **45**, 545-555.
WHO, 2011. Guidelines for Drinking Water Quality. 2nd ed. World Health Organization, Geneva.

APPLICATION OF PELTIER COOLING TECHNOLOGY FOR COLLECTING AIR MOISTURE SAMPLES FOR STUDYING ENVIRONMENTAL TRANSPORT OF 3H

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Introduction

Pressurized Heavy Water Reactors release small amount of Tritium into the atmosphere through stack. The 3H present in the air surrounding the nuclear facility is mainly in the form of tritiated water vapour (HTO). Tritium (3H) is a radioactive isotope of hydrogen which decays to 3He via beta emission with an average energy of 5.7 keV (β_{max} : 18 keV), and a half-life of 12.35 years. This paper presents a systematic study carried out on estimation of 3H by collecting bi-hourly air moisture samples using an in-house developed automated air moisture sampler.

Materials and Methods

The study has been carried out at Kakrapar Gujarat site where four PHWR type reactors are under operation. The continuous bi-hourly air moisture samples (300 nos.) were collected at five selected locations in different sectors covering 1.8 to 3.3 km radial distance from the stack. An automated hourly air moisture collection sampler designed and developed using Thermo Electric Cooling (TEC) technology (Nankar, 2020) which is based on the principle of Peltier effect has been used for collection of moisture samples. Meteorological parameters such as wind speed, wind direction, ambient temperature and relative humidity are also monitored and recorded on bi-hourly basis during the sampling events. The condensed moisture samples were mixed with 10 ml of scintillation cocktail and counted in liquid scintillation spectrometer (LSS) for 3H measurement. The detection limit of the LSS is 0.04 Bq.m⁻³.

Results

The 3H activity (Bq.m⁻³) in air moisture samples collected at five selected locations found to be in the range of ≤ 0.04 -0.74 (GM: 0.09) at Moticher-2.1 km; ≤ 0.04 -

0.43 (GM: 0.07) at Nanicher-2.3 km; ≤ 0.04 -0.38 (GM: 0.08) at Ratania-3.3 km; ≤ 0.04 -2.94 (GM: 0.24) at Koliwada-1.8 km and ≤ 0.04 -2.36 (GM: 0.15) at Kanja-3.2 km. The diurnal maximum 3H concentration was observed during evening to night time for all five locations. These observations are similar to the earlier studies carried out at Kakrapar (Nankar, 2023). A significant positive correlation of 3H in air moisture with absolute humidity was observed with R² value of 0.91.

Conclusion

The developed sampler found to be useful for collecting the continuous air moisture samples automatically in different humidity conditions. The study indicated the applicability of the sampler to find the diurnal maximum 3H concentration. A significant positive correlation of 3H concentration in air moisture with absolute humidity was observed.

References

- Nankar, D. P., Patra, A. K., Joshi, C.P, Saradhi, I. V., Vinodkumar, A. (2020) *Proc. IARPNC Conference, IARPNC- 2020*.
Nankar, D. P., Patra, A. K., Joshi, C.P, Saradhi, I. V., Vinodkumar, A. (2023) *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity*, 261, 107123.

INVESTIGATION ON ALUMINUM DOPED HYDROXYAPATITE FOR MITIGATING U MIGRATION FROM SOIL

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Introduction

Uranium (U) is toxic heavy metal and is water soluble under aerobic conditions. U released in any unforeseen scenarios reaches soil and further fate on migration depends on the soil-liquid distribution coefficient (Kd) (Sukanta et al., 2023). It is important to mitigate the migration of U from the soil to protect the aquatic systems there by human health for sustainable growth. In our previous study, we observed that U Kd in Visakhapatnam's soil is on lower side with values ranging from 0.1 ± 0.007 - 53.6 ± 2.4 L/kg (Sandeep et al., 2023), which indicates probable migration of U from soil. Modified natural adsorbents are found to be promising for scavenging different contaminants including U. Hence, present study investigated the potentiality of Aluminum doped hydroxyapatite synthesized from egg-shell for mitigating U migration in complex geological matrices.

Materials and Methods

Egg-shell for the material synthesis was collected from kitchen waste and is powdered in mixer. Later, it is calcinated at 10000C. Appropriate amounts of $Al(NO_3)_3$ and H_3PO_4 were added for the synthesis of Al doped hydroxyapatite. The synthesized material was characterized using XRD and FT-IR to confirm the formation of desired crystal structure. Small amount of Al doping replaces the Ca^{2+} in HA, which creates extra positive charge and is compensated by additional hydroxyl groups during precipitation which enhances the pH working range of the material as well as U adsorption capacity.

Results

U scavenging kinetics of the material in presence of complex soil and groundwater mixture was tested in the sample which has the lowest Kd value, previously measured. In this experiment, 200mg of Al doped HA was added to soil-groundwater (1:30 S/L ratio) mixture that was spiked with U ($11.1 \mu\text{g/mL}$) and supernatant was separated at regular intervals

for estimating U (using LED fluorimetry) left in water. Results show that, within 10 minutes of contact time 94.7% of the initial spiked U was removed from groundwater indicating material's good efficiency for U scavenging even in presence of high concentration of other ions. After 1 hour of contact time, adsorption reached saturation and is taken as equilibrium time. Further work was carried out by adding Al doped HA to all Kd experiment samples and change in Kd after 1 hour was measured. High Kd values (3497 ± 129.4 to 39223.5 ± 1647.4 L/kg) after adding Al doped HA indicates effective scavenging of U from water making it immobile in the solid matrix there by protecting the surrounding aquatic systems.

Conclusion

With Al doping in HA, the material's U removal efficiency is observed to increase in alkaline samples as well. Significant increase in U Kd value (from 0.1 to 4800 L/kg) after addition of Al doped HA in soil with least Kd indicates effective immobilization of U.

References

- Sandeep P., Sukanta Maity, C. B. Dusane, S. Mishra, Anilkumar S. Pillai. Current trends in Analytical chemistry symposium (CTAC-2023).
Sukanta Maity, P. Sandeep, S. Mishra, C. B. Dusane, D. K. Chaudhary, P. Padma Savitri, J. Sudhakar, Anilkumar S. Pillai, A. Vinod Kumar Environmental Monitoring and Assessment (2023) 195:685.

DISPERSION DYNAMICS OF RADIOACTIVE AEROSOLS DURING OFF-NORMAL CONDITIONS IN VENTILATED CONTROL VOLUME

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Introduction

The presence of radioactive aerosols in ambient air pose an internal exposure hazard for occupational workers. Effective ventilation is an engineered safety feature to reduce occupational exposure. Hence, it is crucial to study the dispersion dynamics of radioactive aerosols when they entrain the ambient air during off-normal conditions and their concentration in HBZ (human breathing zone) in a CV (control volume) with a given ventilation profile.

Materials and Methods

A hypothetical CV with a given ventilation characteristic facing radioactive aerosol leak of a typical size distribution is assumed. The case analyses the dispersion and deposition of aerosol particles and the efficacy of ventilation system to remove the aerosol particles from the ambient air as a function of time. Aerosolved code [1], a particle dynamic coupled CFD code based on OpenFOAM transient solver is used to solve the governing fluid dynamics equations and particle dynamics equations. The dimensions of CV are $L \times B \times H = 4 \text{ m} \times 4 \text{ m} \times 3 \text{ m}$. The CV is ventilated via an inlet (injects air), an outlet (ejects air) along with separate intake (ejects air) and exhaust (injects air) ducts. The intake ducts have four sections each of size $0.3 \text{ m} \times 0.3 \text{ m}$, together form a square of $0.6 \text{ m} \times 0.6 \text{ m}$ at the centre of the roof. Four exhaust ducts are placed on the roof at a distance of 10 cm moving away from the inlet ducts with a rectangular dimension of $0.1 \text{ m} \times 0.6 \text{ m}$. The room has a structural component of height 1.75 m with rectangular pin hole that leaks aerosol into the CV. The pin hole is at a distance of 1.45 m from the bottom of the floor of the room. The CV is operated for ACH (Air Changes per Hour) ranging between 5-40. The aerosol population leaking into the control volume is assumed to be log-normally distributed with $\text{CMD} = 0.18 \mu\text{m}$ and $\text{GSD} = 2.33$, ρ_p (particle bulk density) = 3000 Kg/m^3 .

Results

The case was run for 50 seconds from the incidence of leakage. The dispersion was found to be a strong function of air flow characteristic of the chamber. Particles leave the CV via diffusion and drift through any of the 4 intake sections and outlet. Particle removal from regions (specifically HBZ) inside the control volume was found to be depended on ACH. Higher ACH caused lighter particles ($D_p < 5 \mu\text{m}$) to exit the CV more swiftly eventually decreasing their concentration in the HBZ, while concentration of heavier aerosol particles increased ($D_p > 5 \mu\text{m}$) in HBZ due to reduced gravitational deposition. The deposition of aerosol particles on the various boundary patches of the control volume was also computed, this was also found to be a function of particle size, area and ACH. However, in this computation re-suspension was not considered.

Conclusion

Dispersion of radioactive aerosols for a given size distribution in a ventilated CV with varying ACH has been computed. The effect of particle concentration in HBZ with particle diameter has been established. Particles ranging $1-10 \mu\text{m}$ are most effected upon varying ACH, while particles smaller than $1 \mu\text{m}$ least effected. The deposition fraction gives us an excellent overview of contamination zones following off-normal scenarios.

References

- 1) Lucci, F., Frederix, E. M. A., & Kuczaj, A. K. (2022). AeroSolved: Computational fluid dynamics modelling., *Journal of Aerosol Science*, 159, 105854 (2013).

ROLE OF NUCLEAR ENERGY IN CLEAN ENERGY TRANSITION – A SCIENTIFIC PERSPECTIVE

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Electrical energy is one of the most critical parameters that influence strongly the national growth, industrial development, urbanization, and quality of life i.e. Human Development Index of a country. Currently, around 8500 GWe of electricity generated in the world that supplied to 8 billion population while in India, the same is around 454 GWe (5.3%) for 1.4 billion population. In India, more than 70% of electricity is generated from fossil fuel-based power plants. Emission of greenhouse gases from these plants contribute the largest share (>30%) and causes severe environmental degradation and global warming. To mitigate and adopt the global warming and climate change, Paris Agreement, executed in 2015, with overarching goal to hold “the increase in the global average temperature to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels” and pursue efforts “to limit the temperature increase to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels. India is committed to reduce emissions intensity of its GDP by 45 percent by 2030 from 2005 level and to achieve about 50% cumulative electric power installed capacity from nonfossil fuel- based energy resources by 2030 (Government of India, 2022). India’s power generation installed capacity in the year 2024 -25 (as on 31st October 2024) is 454 GWe and coal, oil and gas-based power stations contribute around 54% followed by solar (20.3%), wind (10.5%), hydro (11.5%), biopower (2.5%) and nuclear (1.8%), respectively. However, 73% of electricity generation is attributed to fossil fuel-based plants followed by hydro (11%), solar (7%), wind (5%), nuclear (3%) and biopower (0.5%) (Niti Aayog, 2024). The installed capacity of solar power is ~ 20%, however the contribution towards electricity generation is ~7%. Similar pattern is observed for wind energy also. This is related to Plant Load Factor (PLF) which is commonly considered

as power plant’s capacity utilization. Highest PLF factor of ~80% of nuclear energy is a common feature of atomic power stations in India and across the world which override other energy options. The PLF of coal based, oil & gas based, hydro, solar, wind and biofuel-based stations are observed to be 70%, 18%, 45%, 17%, 24% and 9%, respectively (Niti Aayog, 2024). In addition, greenhouse gas emissions due to coal based, oil based, natural gas, biomass, hydropower, wind, nuclear and solar is 970, 720, 440, 78 – 230, 24, 11, 6 and 8-83 tonnes of carbon dioxide equivalent per gigawatt-hour of electricity over the lifecycle of the power plant, respectively (UNECE,2022). Apart from highest PLF and lowest GHG emission, reliable, low-carbon and low-cost nuclear power has multiple advantages over other energy sources like providing constant base load power, concentrated, small land foot print, climate compatible, non-dependent on weather, less fuel consumption, etc.. Hence, Nuclear Energy has pivotal role to play in mitigation in global warming and climate change.

Reference

Government of India, 2022, India’s updated first nationally determined contribution under Paris agreement, 2021 -2023.

Niti Aayog(2024), www.iced.niti.gov.in/energy/electricity/generation, accessed on Dec 6, 2024.

UNECE (2022), Carbon Neutrality in the UNECE Region: Integrated Life-cycle Assessment of Electricity Sources, United Nations.

ASSESSMENT OF NATURAL RADIOACTIVITY LEVELS IN SOIL SAMPLES AT KAIGA REGION AFTER FLOODING DURING AUGUST 2019

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Keywords: Natural radioactivity, Redistribution, Flood, Kaiga

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Introduction

Aquatic ecosystems play an important role in the migration of both natural and anthropogenic radionuclides, as well as in their redistribution (Warner and Harrison, 1999). Floods are the most widespread of all natural disasters which are mostly caused by high-intensity precipitation. Large amounts of water released from the dam result in flooding of downstream areas leading to redistribution of radioactivity materials present in soil/sediment. Because heavy flooding occurred on the banks of Kali river, downstream of Kadra reservoir due to high intense precipitation, from the 5th to 8th of August 2019, a post-flood radiological survey was carried out in October, 2019 by collecting soil samples around the Kaiga area and the results are presented in this paper.

Materials and Methods

From 5th to 8th August 2019, due to heavy rainfall in the region and the subsequent release of large amounts of water from the dam resulted in flooding of downstream areas. Soil samples were collected from twenty locations along both banks of Kali river from downstream of Kadra reservoir to Karwar sea which was submerged during flood. Around 2 kg of surface soil samples were collected at a depth of 0-10 cm. These samples were ground, homogenized, and sieved through a mesh smaller than 2 mm for radioactivity analysis. The processed samples were stored in 200 ml cylindrical polyethylene bottles for 30 days to allow secular equilibrium between radionuclides ²²⁶Ra and ²²²Rn and its daughter products and ²²⁸Ra and its daughter products. The activity concentrations of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K were measured using gamma-ray spectrometry with an HPGe detector having 50% relative efficiency, following standard procedures. The activity concentrations of ²³⁸U and ²³²Th were determined using the γ -energies of their daughter products: 609.3 keV for ²¹⁴Pb

and 911 keV for ²²⁸Ac, respectively. For ⁴⁰K, its characteristic γ -ray energy of 1460 keV was directly used.

Results

The radiation levels during this study were found in the range of 0.04 - 0.12 μ Sv.h⁻¹, which were similar to the background radiation level before the flood. The results of gamma spectrometric analysis of post-flood soil samples are as follows (activity range and arithmetic mean): ²³⁸U activity varies from 4.4 to 18.3 Bq.kg⁻¹ dry weight (AM = 11.5 Bq.kg⁻¹ d.w), ²³²Th activity ranges from 5.4 to 26.0 Bq.kg⁻¹ dry weight (AM = 15.3 Bq.kg⁻¹ d.w), and ⁴⁰K activity in soil ranges from 130.6 to 551.5 Bq.kg⁻¹ dry weight (AM = 311.7 Bq.kg⁻¹ d.w). The mean values of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K in pre-flood soil samples in downstream areas are 13.6, 13.1, and 299.5 Bq.kg⁻¹ dry weight respectively. ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K in soil samples from downstream areas before and after the flood period were comparable.

Conclusion

The study was carried out on the redistribution of natural radionuclides such as ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K in soil samples of flooded areas downstream of the Kadra reservoir. It was found that the concentration of natural radionuclides in the soil of post-flood samples was comparable to pre-flood values. The result indicates that there is no redistribution of radioactivity levels due to flooding event.

References

Warner.F. and Harrison, R., (1999) Radioecology after Chernobyl, Mir, Moscow.

NATURAL RADIOACTIVITY IN BEACH SAND SAMPLES AT VISAKHAPATNAM, NORTH COAST OF ANDHRA PRADESH, INDIA

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Introduction

There are some parts along the coastline of India which have higher activity concentration of natural radionuclides causing natural high background radiation areas (NHBRAs) (V. Thangam et al., 2022). This paper presents the studies carried out on determination of natural radioactivity and radiation levels in beach sand samples at Visakhapatnam and Anakapalli districts, which are frequented by public for recreation. The data generated would serve as baseline data for upcoming BARC facility at Visakhapatnam.

Materials and Methods

Ambient gamma radiation levels and its variation were measured at 8 famous beaches using Micro Rem Doserate Meter (Thermo scientific make with NaI(Tl) detector). The readings were taken at 1m above ground level. Around 25 beach sand samples were collected from the same locations. Samples were processed by standard procedure (A.Y. Balbudhe et al., 2013). The concentrations of radionuclides (²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K) in the sample were determined using P type coaxial HPGe gamma ray spectrometer of R.E. 42% (Mirion Tech. make). Gamma spectrometer was calibrated using IAEA standards IAEA-RGU-1, IAEA-RGTh and IAEA-156. Each sample was counted for a period of 86400s (24h). The analysis was carried out using 16k channel MCA and Genie-2000 Inspector software made from Canberra and net activity was estimated in Bq/kg of dry sand. Gamma lines used were 295.3 keV, 351.9 keV of ²¹⁴Pb, 609.3keV and 1764.5keV of ²¹⁴Bi for ²²⁶Ra, 583keV of ²⁰⁸Tl and 911.2 keV of ²²⁸Ac for ²³²Th and 1460.8 keV of ⁴⁰K for ⁴⁰K.

Results

In 6 beaches the radiation levels were in the range of 50 to 500nGy/hr. Mean radiation levels at Visakhapatnam are in the range of 130 to 380 nGy/hr (P.Padma Savitri et al., 2023). ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K activities in sand

samples at those beaches are in the range of 3±1 to 334±6, 7±1 to 2141±12, 77±6 to 500±8 Bq/kg with an average of 78±8, 527±19, 377±13 Bq/kg, respectively. In 2 beaches radiation levels were in the range of 700 to 6000 nGy/hr. On investigating samples from those beaches, it was found that the ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, ⁴⁰K levels were in the range of 503±6 to 1283±12, 3369±15 to 13692±36, 91±4 to 1191±20 Bq/kg, respectively. However they are lesser than the studies reported at coast line at Srikakulam and Vizianagaram districts of AP. (A.Y. Balbudhe et al., 2013). Concentration of ²²⁶Ra and ²³²Th in shore sand is higher than soil in Visakhapatnam whereas ⁴⁰K is in the same range (P. Padma Savitri et al., 2023). Higher values may be attributable to the presence of monazites and zircon in sands.

Conclusion

Two beaches out of six are identified as higher radioactivity areas. Measured absorbed dose rates were consistent with estimated natural radioactivity levels in shore beach sand.

References

1. V. Thangam et al., (2022) *Journal of Radio analytical and Nuclear Chemistry*, 331:1207–1223
2. A. Y. Balbudhe et al., (2013) *Proc. Of National Symposium on Environment (NSE-18)*, 74 - 78
3. P. Padma Savitri et al., (2023) *AOCR6, Mumbai 2023*.
4. P. Padma Savitri et al., (2023) *Radiat Prot Environ 2023*; 46:163-71.

IMPACT OF TROPICAL CYCLONES IN BAY OF BENGAL ON BARC, VISAKHAPATNAM DURING 2013-2024

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Keywords: Visakhapatnam, meteorology, cyclone, storm.

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Introduction

Tropical cyclone (TC) is a natural disaster in the coastal region. The destruction is due to the strong wind, heavy rainfall and associated storm surges, when storm crosses the coast. Tropical depressions commonly develop in the Bay of Bengal (BOB) with some intensifying into cyclones that significantly affects the wind pattern and rainfall in its close proximity. The dispersion of radioactive materials is greatly influenced by near-surface winds, which are driven by large scale weather systems (e.g., the monsoons and extra-tropical cyclones) (Takao Yoshikane et al., 2018). The impact of cyclone is measured in terms of frequency of occurrence, duration, maximum sustained wind intensity, land fall of the cyclone and rainfall.

Materials and Methods

BARCV campus is upcoming at Atchutapuram mandal, located adjacent to seashore south of Vishakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, behind a hillock in south of Jogannapalem village (17.5°N, 83°E). A micrometeorological station consisting of 30m met tower is situated behind the hillock and is 3 km from nearest sea shore. Multi-level meteorological sensors are installed like cup anemometers, wind vane, temperature and humidity sensors along with various single level sensors are installed to measure solar radiation, net radiation and atmospheric pressure. Meteorological data was collected and analysed from sensors installed at 10 m height in BARC, Visakhapatnam during cyclones for the last twelve years (2013-2024). There were no chemical / radiological releases during this period.

Results

There were 22 tropical cyclones and 6 depressions in BOB during 2013-24, out of which 8 had landfall in Andhra Pradesh. As per the data recorded at BARCV, cumulative rainfall during cyclones was in the range of

0.5mm (Vardha2016) to 324mm (Hudhud 2014). For 5 cyclones there was no rainfall recorded as landfall was in other states. The maximum wind speed was in the range of 12km/h (Phailin 2013, Daye 2018) to 80km/h (Hudhud 2014). Low pressure recorded was 852mb (Asani2022) to 1011.8mb (Midhili2023). It was also observed that cyclones occur mostly in the month of October and May in BOB. Variation in recorded temperature in May and October months was in the range 20°C to 37°C approximately. Tropical cyclones are like giant engines that use warm, moist air as fuel. Due to high humidity and local variation in temperatures cyclones occur in May and October months. Only one cyclone Hudhud in 2014 had landfall near Visakhapatnam. However, BARC, Visakhapatnam faced relatively lower impact as the site is at southern hemisphere of cyclone shadowed by hills and hillocks of Eastern Ghats (A. Vinod Kumar et al., 2015).

Conclusion

There was no impact on BARCV by all events occurred in BOB during 2013-2024. This study serves as reference to understand the influence of cyclones on BARC Visakhapatnam. This analysis will be useful during routine/accidental emissions of radio nuclides in future.

References

1. Takao Yoshikane & Kei Yoshimura (2018) *scientific reports* 2018.
2. Vinod Kumar et al., (2015) *BARC Newsletter (March-April 2015)*.

SENSITIVITY OF DILUTION FACTOR TO THE METHOD OF COMPUTING ATMOSPHERIC STABILITY

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Introduction

The atmospheric dilution factor is a critical input for estimating the radiological impact during normal operations and accidental releases of radionuclides from nuclear power plants. Among the key parameters influencing the atmospheric dilution factor is atmospheric stability. Various methods are available to estimate atmospheric stability, including the Bulk Richardson number, gradient Richardson number, temperature gradient method, Obukhov length, and wind direction standard deviation. In this study, atmospheric stability is evaluated using the aforementioned methods, based on long-term meteorological data collected at the Kalpakkam site. These stability estimates are then utilized to compute the annual triple joint frequency distribution, which in turn used for determination of dilution factors.

Materials and Methods

The long term meteorological data during the period 2014-2024 is used for stability calculation over Kalpakkam site. The data is quality checked before analysing. Stability is computed based on the above mentioned methods and it is briefed below. Temperature gradient (TG) method ($\Delta T / \Delta Z$): temperature at 2 m and 50 m are used. Gradient Richardson number (GR):

$$Ri = \frac{\frac{g}{T} \left[\left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial Z} \right) + \Gamma \right]}{\left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial Z} \right)^2}$$

Where Γ is the adiabatic lapse rate, g is the acceleration due to gravity, U is the mean wind speed, T is the air temperature Bulk Richardson number (BR):

$$Ri_B = \frac{\frac{g}{T} \left[\left(\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta Z} \right) + \Gamma \right]}{U_z^2}$$

U_z is the wind speed at 50 m. For calculation temperature at 50 m and 16 m are used. Obukhov length (OL):

$$L = - \frac{\rho C_p T U_*^3}{\kappa g H_f}$$

ρ is the air density, C_p is the specific heat under constant pressure, U_* is the friction velocity and H is the sensible heat flux

Ranges of these stability indices are mapped to Pasquill-Gifford stability classes by many in the past. In the present work, the ranges suggested by Essa et al (2007) are followed. For the calculation of dilution factors, sector averaged Gaussian Plume Model is used and dilution factors are computed for a release height of 100 m and at a distance of 1.6 km away from the release location.

Results

The analysis reveals significant variability in the percentage occurrence of various stability classes among the different methods. For example, for stability category A, the percentages of occurrence are 20.26%, 34.85%, 18.15%, 35.81%, and 24.66% for the BR, GR, OL, TG, and WD methods, respectively. Furthermore, in terms of dilution factors, the method based on the OL is the most conservative, followed by the BR, WD, TG and then the GR. For instance, for the southern sectors, the dilution factors at a distance of 1.6 km are 5.82E-08, 3.88E-08, 1.02E-07, 3.06E-08, 5.74E-08 s/m³ with BR, GR, OL, TG and WD methods respectively. As a reference, with respect to the dilution factor based on the OL method, the variations in dilution factors for the BR, GR, TG, and WD methods are -43%, -62%, -70%, and -43%, respectively. The variability in these dilution factors significantly influences dose apportionment and, consequently, the overall radiological impact assessment.

References

1. Essa, K. S., Embaby, M., Mubarak, F., & Kamel, I. (2007). Estimation of seasonal atmospheric stability and mixing height by using different schemes.

BIOSPHERE MODELLING AND ASSESSMENT (BIOMASS) METHODOLOGY FOR RADIOLOGICAL ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT (REIA)

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Introduction

Nuclear power is projected as a reliable, sustainable and low-carbon source of electricity combat climate change. The proponent of the nuclear industry has the additional responsibility of demonstrating compliance not only with radiological risk but also with the overall sustainability component. A holistic approach, which can act as a decision-making tool, integrating Radiological Environmental Impact Assessment (REIA) into the overall safety assessment is essential for demonstrating the sustainability of the nuclear industry.

Biosphere modelling is conventionally used to assess the dose to the members of a representative person. However, in an integrated approach of safety assessment, a science-based understanding of the geosphere, hydrosphere, atmosphere and biosphere, along with the interplay between these compartments, is essential. The need for a REIA can be related to a nuclear power plant, deep repository, decommissioning site, NORM industry site, hospital etc. and may involve various timeframes, climatic conditions, population/ biota habits, etc. Even though details differ to an extent, all have the commonality of having the same basic need to relate REIA to a wider framework. The dose assessment involving centuries, should consider the dynamic nature of environmental compartments, climate change and their evolution process over time period, during which impact is expected.

Materials and Methods

BIOMASS methodology is a holistic methodical development of safety assessment that was originally developed for radioactive waste management (1). The scope of the methodology is further enhanced and is being used for REIA in the ongoing Methods for Radiological and Environmental Impact Assessment (MEREIA) program of IAEA. The various aspects of BIOMASS methodology for REIA are described below.

Preparation of assessment context: This document clearly specifies the purpose, source, site, regulations, issue history, general plans and

expected outcome using inputs from general, scientific knowledge, previous iterations and reviews, characterization of the present site and identification of potential evolutions of scenarios into the future.

Description of biosphere: This document specifies the identification, justification, and narrative description of the biosphere, as well as the definition of exposure endpoints for REIA.

Development of conceptual model: This document specifies environmental compartments (atmosphere, surface waters, soil, sediment, plant systems and animal systems) involved in the migration of radioactive material and the processes leading to the migration. It is represented as an interaction matrix with diagonal compartments starting with the source of release and ending in the member of the representative person. At this stage, one can screen out insignificant processes and pathways.

Development of mathematical models: The above information is then translated into mathematical models describing the migration of radionuclide transfer and dosimetric models for dose evaluation.

Application of model and validation: The models are applied and tested specific context of safety assessment. If the model is fit for the purpose of overall safety assessment, it is integrated with the overall safety assessment. If not, gap areas are identified, and the process is repeated till the required quality is obtained.

Conclusion

The abstract describes BIOMASS methodology for safety assessment. The detailed paper will describe the methodology with an example and demonstrate its applicability.

References

1. Tobias Lindborg, et al, Safety assessment undertaken using BIOMASS methodology: lessons

DEPTH PROFILE OF NORM LEVELS IN TWO INLAND MINING AREAS OF IREL CHAVARA

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Introduction

The industrial process of beneficiation for Heavy Minerals (HM) requires raw sand as the input material. The Chavara Mineral Division of IREL (India) Ltd situated in the south west coast of Kerala, a renowned Natural High Background Area (NHBRA), is a major DAE unit involved in HM beneficiation. Apart from beach sand mining, mining of inland area having raw sand rich with HM is also practiced by this unit. The radioactivity in HM is mainly due to Monazite, a Naturally Occurring Radioactive Material (NORM) and the principal resource of Rare Earths and Thorium.

Materials and Methods

Sand/soil samples from inland mining areas at a depth upto 5/4 meters were collected from two locations 1) Karithura 8.973°N & 76.528°E and 2) Veluthamanal 9.025°N & 76.515°E. The samples were processed and analysed on secular equilibrium as per standard protocol using an advanced 7.62 x 7.62 cm NaI(Tl) detector shielded with 15cm thick Pb material. Estimation of NORM radioactivity ie, ²³²Th, ²²⁶Ra & ⁴⁰K was by gamma spectrometry using standard gamma energies ie, for, ²³²Th by ²⁰⁸Tl (2.615 MeV), ²²⁶Ra by ²¹⁴Pb (1.764 MeV), and ⁴⁰K (1.461 MeV). The system was calibrated using RG-Th and RG-U standards in defined bottle geometry for quantification.

Results

The NORM radioactivity content in sand samples collected from Karithura inland mining site (in Bqg⁻¹) was 1.92±0.07, 0.26±0.02 & 0.12±0.05 at ground level for ²³²Th, ²²⁶Ra and ⁴⁰K, whereas the same at varying depths of 1m, 2m, 3m, 4m & 5m were 3.45±0.11, 0.47±0.04 & 0.09±0.05; 7.13±0.22, 0.91±0.08 & 0.06±0.04; 13.48±0.47, 1.66±0.15 & 0.05±0.04; 12.61±0.46, 1.57±0.14 & 0.05±0.04 and 9.86±0.35, 1.23±0.12 & ≤0.04 respectively. The ²³²Th, ²²⁶Ra and ⁴⁰K radioactivity content estimated in samples from Veluthamanal inland site (in Bqg⁻¹) was

0.55±0.04, 0.078±0.009 & 0.09±0.05 at ground level, whereas the same at varying depths of 1m, 2m, 3m and 4m were 0.64±0.04, 0.085±0.010 & 0.07±0.05; 0.71±0.05, 0.094±0.011 & 0.06±0.05; 0.66±0.04, 0.085±0.010 & 0.06±0.04 and 0.59±0.04, 0.076±0.009 & 0.05±0.04 respectively. The results indicate that ²³²Th and ²²⁶Ra activity content increases from ground level to 3 meters depth and then reduces steadily to 5 meters depth in Karithura and in Veluthamanal, maximum observed NORM activity was at 2 meters depth. The ⁴⁰K content was found to be steadily decreasing from ground level at both the locations. The observed ²³²Th/²²⁶Ra ratio was in the range of 7.3 to 8.1 at Karithura and 7.1 to 7.8 at Veluthamanal, on par with different studies in Chavara NHBRA areas.

Based on ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K levels, gamma absorbed dose rate in air (ADRA) was calculated by using the equation given in (UNSCEAR, 2000) and ADRA in μGyh⁻¹ varied from 1.28 to 8.91 at Karithura and 0.37 to 0.47 at Veluthamanal and these levels are on par with field measurements at these NHBRA.

Conclusion

The depth profile of NORM levels at two different inland mining sites of IREL Chavara was studied and found that the levels remain unchanged even upto around 5 meters which indicates NORM levels and the associated minerals, mainly Monazite is not a surface phenomenon, at least upto the studied depths.

References

UNSCEAR. Sources, effects and risks of ionizing radiation (2000), Newyork:UN.

STUDIES ON ^{210}Po IN TOBACCO PLANTS IN MYSURU REGION, KARNATAKA, INDIA AND ASSESSMENT OF ANNUAL EFFECTIVE DOSE TO SMOKERS

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Introduction

Polonium (^{210}Po) is a natural alpha-emitting radionuclide with a half-life of 138 days. When inhaled through smoking, the alpha radiation (5.3 MeV) from ^{210}Po may be absorbed in lung tissue, contributing to lung cancer risk. The International Agency for Research on Cancer has classified tobacco smoke as a Group 1 carcinogen, with ^{210}Po being one of the radioactive components contributing to this classification. Understanding ^{210}Po concentrations helps quantify the radiation dose and assess associated health risks, particularly for heavy smokers (IARC, 2004). Karnataka produces around 100 million kilograms of tobacco annually, primarily consisting of Flue-Cured Virginia (FCV) tobacco, which is the major export variety. Mysuru district is a leading producer of tobacco, followed by Hassan and other regions such as Chamarajanagar (TBAR, 2023).

Materials and Methods

Tobacco plant samples were collected from Mysuru, Chamarajanagar, Hassan and Mandya districts of Karnataka, India. The activity concentration of ^{210}Po in tobacco leaves (56 samples), stem (10 samples) and roots (10 samples) were studied using electrochemical deposition followed by alpha counting method (Lavanya et al., 2024).

Results

The activity level of ^{210}Po in tobacco leaves of the study area varied from 12.2 to 86.3 Bq kg⁻¹ (dry weight) with an average of 22.8 Bq kg⁻¹. ^{210}Po Activity in plants is influenced by soil characteristics, climate and geography. Soils rich in uranium or phosphate fertilizers can contribute to elevated ^{210}Po levels. Rainfall patterns, pH, and organic matter in the soil can influence radionuclide bioavailability. The activity concentrations of ^{210}Po in 8 different brands of cigarettes were also investigated to estimate the annual

effective doses of ^{210}Po to smokers. The concentration of ^{210}Po in cigarettes varied from 16.7 to 32.5 mBq per cigarette and with an average of 23.6 mBq per cigarette.

Conclusion

The average value of ^{210}Po in tobacco leaves in Mysuru region aligns well with global averages, which typically range between 20 and 50 Bq kg⁻¹ (dry weight). The activity of ^{210}Po in few samples is slightly higher than most reported ranges but remains within expected levels in regions with higher radionuclide deposition.

References

- Lavanya, B. S. K., Namitha, S. N., Hidayath, M., & Chandrashekara, M. S. (2024). Assessment of radiation dose due to ^{210}Po in water and food samples of Chamarajanagar district, Karnataka, India. *Radiation Protection Dosimetry*, 200(11-12), 1052- 1058.
- International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC, 2004), Tobacco smoke and involuntary smoking. IARC monographs programme on the evaluation of the carcinogenic risk of chemicals to humans, IARC, Lyon, France.
- TBAR, 2023. Tobacco Board Annual Report - 2022-2023, Tobacco Board Govt. of India, Ministry of Commerce & Industry Department of Commerce, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, 2023.

DISTRIBUTION OF ⁷Be ACTIVITY IN AIR AND MEAN RESIDENCE TIME AT NARORA SITE

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Introduction

⁷Be, a natural radionuclide of cosmogenic origin with relatively short lived ($T_{1/2}=53d$), is continuously produced in the upper atmosphere by the spallation process of light atmospheric nuclei such as nitrogen and oxygen when they interact with protons and neutrons of cosmic rays (James et al 20024). Once ⁷Be is formed in the troposphere, it rapidly associates primarily with submicron-sized aerosol particles. ⁷Be enters the troposphere due to the vertical exchange of material from the stratosphere, reaches the earth's surface via dry and wet depositional events. Using specific activity ratios of ⁷Be/³²P and ²¹⁰Bi/²¹⁰Pb are one of methods for estimating residence time. One of alternate method was reported was by Mark Shapiro and Judith L Forbes-Resha using only ⁷Be in air data. In present study, monthly mean air concentration of ⁷Be at Narora site are presented during period 2020-23 and used for estimation of mean residence times for ⁷Be in troposphere.

Materials and Methods

Atmospheric air is sampled at 1.0 m above the ground. The air was continuously pumped by a high volume sampler (Rotovac make 150 lpm) The cumulative samples for a period of one month corresponding to an air volume of about 2000-3000 m³ were collected and placed in a respective geometry for the estimation of ⁷Be activity by gamma spectrometry. ⁷Be at 477 keV gamma peak is used for calculation². Decay correction for ⁷Be activity is applied. Mean Residence Time t_r in troposphere is calculated using following equation²

$$a_r = \frac{P_r}{H} (1 - e^{-\lambda t_r}) \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

Where a_r is observed mean ⁷Be activity in air Bq.m⁻³, P_r is production rate of ⁷Be (atmos.cm⁻².s⁻¹) H is height of tropopause (m), λ is decay constant d⁻¹ and t_r is residence time in d.

Results

The monthly mean ground level air concentration for ⁷Be and Gross Beta during 2020-23 in Narora region was studied. Monthly mean of ⁷Be value ranges from 1.1 to 3.9 mBq.m⁻³. Residence time for Narora site for ⁷Be is varying from 5.5 to 21.5 days with mean value as 11.6 days. Aerosol residence time in the atmosphere is the period of time in which particle remains in the atmosphere, between the injection and removal. Residence time is evaluated using air concentration values from Equation (1). Production rate value taken 2.7×10^{-2} (atmos.cm⁻².s⁻¹), H is taken as 17 Km and decay constant is 1.31×10^{-2} d⁻¹. The residence time observed at Narora region is comparable with reported value in India (Joshi et al 2023). It is also evident from the study that higher precipitations, higher rainy days and lower residence time.

Conclusion

During the present study monthly mean activities of ⁷Be in ground level air is reported during period 2020-23. Seasonal variations were observed for ⁷Be during the study. Higher values are during summer and lower values at Monsoon period. Residence times for ⁷Be were evaluated and having lower value during rainy season and higher during summer. The present study shows that the residence time of ⁷Be for Narora environment was found to be varied from 5.5 to 21.5 days with mean of 11.6 days.

References

James J P et.al.2004), atmospheric transport of ⁷Be in Kaiga environment, RPE,27(1-4),48.

Shapiro M H et.al. J L (1976), Mean Residence time of ⁷Be bearing aerosols in the Troposphere, Journal of Geophysical research, 81, No.15.

R M Joshi et al ⁷Be Activity in Air and Mean Residence time at Kaiga Site IASTA-2023

UNCERTAINTY MODELLING USING FUZZY BASED APPROACH FOR GAMMA RAY SPECTROMETRY MEASUREMENTS

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Introduction

Activity concentration measurements of soil are essential for enabling the assessment of radioactivity distribution in various environmental contexts. In the realm of practical applications involving measurement processes, the primary objective often centers on harnessing measured values to draw inferences or reach conclusions, but measurement uncertainty complicates this process, making it challenging to achieve definitive results. To address this, a high-precision prediction model is crucial to reduce the influence of uncertainty in the outcomes. In this work, an innovative fuzzy[1] approach is introduced to model uncertain knowledge, where fuzzy numbers and membership functions are used to represent uncertain model parameters. When measuring parameter is having probability distribution, Monte Carlo(MC) based uncertainty given more precise values of output. However where information on measuring parameter is vague, Fuzzy approach is the most reliable one.

Methods

In fuzzy set theory, an alpha cut converts a fuzzy set into a crisp set by setting a membership threshold. Elements with membership degrees greater than or equal to the alpha value are included, while those below are excluded.

A combined model to obtain uncertainty in activity concentration (A) is expressed in fuzzy form as

$$A = \frac{NC}{f(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n)} \dots\dots(1)$$

where NC is the net count which is treated as fuzzy, $f(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n)$ represents the function involving other variables (efficiency, time and mass) and n is the number of variables.

Results

The algorithm processes measured values such as net gamma-ray counts, counting time, sample mass and detector efficiency to determine activity concentrations of K-40, Th-232 and U-238. Fuzzy alpha cuts (range from

0.1 to 1) based on a chosen confidence level are defined, and membership functions using eq (2) for net counts (NC) are calculated.

$$\mu_{T'}(x; a, m, b) = \begin{cases} \frac{x-a}{m-a} & a \leq x \leq m \\ \frac{x-m}{b-m} & m \leq x \leq b \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \dots\dots(2)$$

Monte Carlo simulations generate random NC samples and their corresponding A is computed. Uncertainty ranges in A are then calculated and displayed for each radionuclide. In our case study, for K-40, the calculated activity concentration ranges from 181.6 to 428.1 Bq/kg, with uncertainties varying from 28.1 to 40.6 Bq/kg. For Th-232, the concentration ranges from 28.8 to 103.8 Bq/Kg, and the uncertainty range spans from 7.8 to 13.1 Bq/Kg. For U-238, the activity concentration ranges from 10.0 to 44.1 Bq/Kg, with uncertainties varying from 4.1 to 8.7 Bq/Kg at an alpha cut value of 0.1 with 95% confidence interval.

Conclusions

This work optimizes uncertainties in activity concentration using a fuzzy modelling technique applied to a primordial radionuclide dataset. It addresses the challenge of quantifying uncertainties in situations with vague or imprecise environmental conditions, offering an alternative to traditional probabilistic methods. The model is validated using measurement data for U-238, Th-232, and K-40. This enriched output can be effectively used for interpretation, decision-making, quality assurance, comparisons and reporting.

References

Zadeh, L. A. (1965). Fuzzy set. Information and Control, 8(3), 338–353.

ASSESSMENT OF NATURAL RADIOACTIVITY IN THE COASTAL REGIONS OF VARKALA BEACH, KERALA

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Introduction

Natural radioactivity levels in the environment are not uniform and vary significantly based on the underlying geological and geographical features of the region. Southern coastal areas of Kerala, Ullal, Kalppakkam and Manavalakurichi are the well-reported HBRA in India. Regular monitoring of environmental radioactivity is essential, particularly in regions with higher natural background radiation. The present study is a scientific investigation focused on evaluating the natural radioactivity levels in the coastal environment of Varkala beach, Trivandrum district, Kerala.

Materials and Methods

The sand samples were collected from 12 different sampling points on the beach. From each sampling stations, about 2.5 kg of samples were collected from a depth of 10-25 cm in a polythene bag and the samples were then dried in an oven for 24 hours at 110°C to eliminate moisture content. The processed samples were then sieved through 250µm mesh and sealed in 250 ml capacity air-tight plastic containers with standard shape for 30 days to achieve secular equilibrium. Using a 3"×3", flat type NaI(Tl) Scintillation detector, prepared samples were subjected to gamma-ray spectrometric analysis for 30000 seconds and following results were made.

Results

The activity of ⁴⁰K is found to vary from 298±10 to 389±15 Bqkg⁻¹ with a mean value of 332.25 Bqkg⁻¹. The activity of ²²⁶Ra is found to be ranged from 148±8 to 512±8 with a mean value of 302.25 Bqkg⁻¹. Similarly, the ²³²Th activity concentration is found to vary from 412±18 Bqkg⁻¹ to 12125±20 Bqkg⁻¹ with mean value of 3231.58 Bqkg⁻¹. The mean radium equivalent activity, absorbed dose, indoor and outdoor activity concentrations in the sand samples of Varkala beach are 4948.99 Bqkg⁻¹, 2160.30 nGyh⁻¹,

10.59 mSvy⁻¹ and 2.64 mSvy⁻¹ respectively. All the radiological indices are higher than the world average values. The results reveal that the activity concentrations of radionuclides are significantly higher than world average values. Divya et al., (2019) reported the activity concentration of ²³²Th in the Varkala region in the range 968- 9437 Bqkg⁻¹ and Gopinathan et al., (2012) have reported the absorbed dose rate in Chavara- Neendakara region, which is in the range of 1324- 28356 nGyh⁻¹. Shetty and Narayana, (2007) have ²³²Th activity in the Kovalam beach with an average value of 7725.2 Bqkg⁻¹. These values are comparable with the result obtained from the present study.

Conclusion

Varkala beach is one of the famous beaches in Kerala with a unique property of having a large lateritic sea cliff and the beach was initially enriched with laterite soil. But in recent years the beach is found to enrich with monazite rich black sand, and the present study confirms the presence of monazite minerals in the beach, where the activity of ²³²Th is significantly high as reported by Divya et al., 2018.

References

- Radhakrishna, A.P., Somashekarappa, H.M., Narayana, Y., Siddappa, K. (1993) Health Physics 65, 390–395.
- Divya, P.V., Kaliprasad, C.S., Narayana, Y., Prakash, V. (2019) J Radioanal Nucl Chem 322 121-127
- Gopinathan, A., Derin, M.T., Vijayagopal, P., Venkatraman, B., Chaubey, R.C. (2012) PLoS ONE 7:50468
- Shetty, P.K & Narayana, Y. (2007) Int J Low Radiat 4, No.3

LONG RANGE(LoRa) BASED RADIATION EARLY WARNING SYSTEM FOR NUCLEAR FACILITIES

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Introduction

This paper proposes a Long Range (LoRa)-based Radiation Early Warning System at Nuclear facilities site with a wireless communication system for data transfer. The system allows connection to various units to the LoRa transceivers (Lee 2018), and enables data collection within the site. As a proof of concept, the data collected by the radiation sensors is sent to the LoRa gateway, which serves as the central monitoring system from which command messages are sent to various units' components through respective local controllers called as distributed generation (DG) units. The study focuses on using LoRa Node-Red instead of cloud servers that are currently used in most monitoring systems. A range test of the proposed system is carried out to observe the rate of data delivery in a complex topography. It demonstrated over 90% data delivery at 2.5km without line-of-sight condition. Finally, a test was conducted to validate key features like range test of the proposed system by achieving one-directional data transfer in a grid monitoring system.

Materials and Methods

The system uses microcontroller-based device with embedded code. The device would use highly sensitive GM tube as detector and for data transfer will use LoRa. These gamma monitors can detect 3.7 MBq of ⁶⁰Co and 11.1 MBq of ¹³⁷Cs from a distance of 2 m (above a background of 0.1 μ Gy h⁻¹). The data transfer technology is generally categorized into wired communication for data transfer within small grids include ModBus, power line communication & Ethernet and the major wireless communication technologies currently in use includes Zig-Bee, Wi-Fi, WiMax and cellular. LoRa communication technology is proposed for a large area monitoring specially the Protective Action Planning Zone (PAZ), where the proposed system surpasses the need

of existing gateways to enable much longer range of communication. This communication medium facilitates analysis and observation of the data and sends alerts when an alarm is detected. Moreover, the data is available with the facility only and needn't depend on any service provider.

Results

The proposed LoRa-based radiation monitoring system was tested for one-directional communication where data was transferred from a DG unit's local controller represented by the LoRa nodes to the central controller housed by the LoRa gateway connected to the PC.

Conclusion

LoRa-based communication system for data transfer is proposed in this paper. The scheme can be employed to transfer measured data such as dose rate voltage, etc. between the local controllers of DG units and the central controller. It features long-range data transfer up to 3 km, low cost and low power consumption. The system can be deployed in areas where no internet or other form of communication exists, ideally for remote areas of UPZ at NPCIL sites.

References

Lee H and Ke K (2018) Monitoring of Large-Area IoT Sensors Using a LoRa Wireless Mesh Network System: Design and Evaluation. *IEEE T Instrum Meas* 67: 2177–2187.

A COMPARISON OF METHODS FOR ALPHA ACTIVITY ESTIMATION IN LOW LEVEL LIQUID EFFLUENTS WITH HIGH SALT CONTENT

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Introduction

Low level liquid effluents generated at radioactive waste management facilities contain a complex mixture of salts, as a result of reprocessing and waste treatment operations. The level of alpha activity concentration that needs to be estimated in these effluent samples is of the order of 0.037 Bq/mL, the regulatory limit for their release to the environment. In such samples, self-absorption due to inactive salts poses limitation on the accurate estimation of alpha activity concentrations when employing conventional radiometric techniques. In order to overcome this, radiochemical separation using precipitation, ion-exchange and solvent extraction techniques are reported in literature (Kumar V et al. 2012). Organic solvent selectively extract the alpha emitters from the bulk of liquid sample leaving all the inactive salt in effluent. Here in this paper, feasibility of solvent extraction technique is studied and results are compared with conventional method of radiometry.

Materials and Methods

In the study, two solvent systems viz. Carbamoyl Methyl Phosphine Oxide (CMPO) and N, N-Tetra Ethylhexyl Diglycolamine (TEHDGA) were used. The analyses described were done in triplicate. 2 ml of the sample having Total Dissolved Solid (TDS) ~ 0.1 g/mL was evaporated and reconstituted in 3M HNO₃ and extracted into 0.5M CMPO with 30% iso dodecyl alcohol (IDA) in dodecane. The second solvent extraction method involved reconstitution of the same volume of sample in 4M HNO₃ post evaporation, and extraction with TEHDGA. For the both solvent extraction procedures equilibration time was 20 min and Aqueous to Organic ratio was 1:1. After settling, the organic layer was separated and a small quantity of it was plancheted and dried. The dried samples were counted for alpha activity in a ZnS(Ag) detector with efficiency

of 25% and minimum detection activity of 0.06 Bq for 10000 sec counting time.

Results

Of the two methods employed, direct planchet counting of 2 ml of the sample yields an activity concentration of 0.08 ± 0.001 Bq/ml. When solvent extraction method is employed for the same sample using TEHDGA and CMPO solvent systems, the activity concentration estimate increases to 1.04 ± 0.184 Bq/ml and 2.02 ± 0.247 Bq/ml respectively. Thus, it can be seen that for a given volume of the sample, the alpha activity concentration estimation markedly improves by employing the solvent extraction method. CMPO has a higher D value for Plutonium as compared to Americium, which explains the higher activity estimate when CMPO is used as an extractant. In this study, the sample consists mainly of Plutonium.

Conclusion

From the results obtained, it can be clearly understood that solvent extraction is a better method for estimating the alpha activity concentration in high TDS samples. Of the two solvents tested, CMPO seems to have superior extraction properties compared to TEHDGA, and hence this can be the preferred solvent. Further investigations will be carried out into the stripping of the activity into an aqueous medium.

References

1. Kumar V, Kumar A, Mondal S, Sharma JN, Hubli RC, Wattal PK, Suri AK (2012), *Separation and Purification Technology* **98**: 118-122.

EVALUATION OF PERFORMANCE OF SONIC ANEMOMETER IN WIND DATA MEASUREMENTS AT RAWATBHATA SITE

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Keywords: Sonic anemometer, wind speed, wind direction, correlation.

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Introduction

Micro meteorological laboratory of EMAD, BARC is carrying out meteorological data measurement and analysis for estimation of external dose to members of public at Rawatbhata Rajasthan Site. Sonic anemometers calculate wind velocity by measuring the time of travel of ultrasonic pulses between pairs of transducers. The wind's motion affects this travel time, causing a delay in the sound pulse's travel along the wind's direction. The instrument uses this time difference to calculate the wind speed and wind direction. No moving parts, linear dynamic response, good directional response and frequency response limited by sound path length are important features of sonic anemometers. Mechanical wind sensors measure wind speed through the movement of their components. This paper discusses the results of comparison of horizontal wind speeds and 3-D turbulent statistics measured by mechanical wind sensors with a co-located 3-D sonic anemometer over an entire one-year period. Measurement differences and the feasibility of using the 3-D sonic anemometer for routine monitoring are also discussed in this paper.

Materials and Methods

3 D ultrasonic sensors of Metek make and mechanical sensors of wind speed and wind direction of Komoline make (Model: KDS-132) are installed at 10m and 60m heights of 120 m high meteorological tower. In this study, hourly averaged measured data by sonic anemometer and mechanical wind sensors for one-year period (2023) were analysed and compared. Routinely monitored variables of wind speed, wind direction and calm (%) were analysed in this study.

Results

It is observed that during the study period, 24.6% and 26.4% of the times, wind direction is SSW, SW and WSW for Sonic and mechanical wind vane system respectively. The

correlation coefficient for wind directions measured by sonic anemometer and mechanical wind vane is 0.976 and 0.980 for 10m and 60m heights, respectively. The average wind speeds measured by sonic anemometer at 10m and 60m heights are 2.1m/s and 3.4m/s whereas by cup anemometer, measured values are 1.7 m/s and 3.2 m/s, respectively. Observed correlation coefficient for wind speed from sonic anemometer and mechanical wind cup sensor is 0.932 and 0.934 for 10m and 60m heights, respectively. Calm (<0.8m/s) percentage of wind speed data measured by sonic anemometer is 11.6%, and 2.6% while that by wind cup sensors are 34.0%, and 7.0% at 10m, and 60m heights, respectively. Difference in wind speeds and calm percentage of sonic anemometer and wind cup sensors is attributed to presence of mechanical sensors in 3 - cup anemometers which has a minimum threshold whereas, no threshold is required in case of sonic anemometers.

Conclusion

Present study indicated that hourly averaged wind variables of wind speed and wind direction measured by mechanical sensors agree well with those measured by sonic anemometers. However, at lower wind speeds, precision of measurement of Sonic anemometer is better than cup anemometers and wind vane sensors.

References

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EVALUATION OF DILUTION FACTOR AT PUBLIC UTILIZATION POINT OF MOTICHER LAKE AT KAKRAPAR GUJARAT SITE

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Introduction

Tritium (³H), radioactive isotope of hydrogen, is ubiquitous in nature and released in small quantities from PHWR type nuclear power plants. Environmental Survey Laboratories at nuclear power plant sites continuously monitor the concentration of tritium in the environment. This paper presents the result of analysis of tritium activity at different locations in Moticher Lake where effluents from Kakrapar Atomic Power Station (KAPS) are discharged after complying regulatory requirements. Also, extent of dilution available at public utilization point is also discussed in this paper.

Materials and Methods

Site description

Kakrapar Gujarat site comprises of four PHWR type nuclear power reactors of capacity 220 MWe each (KAPS-1&2) and 700 MWe each (KAPP-3&4) which are operational. Moticher lake is a balancing reservoir for the Kakrapar left bank canal and Ratania regulator. Water requirement of plant is met from Moticher lake and liquid waste is discharged into the lake after proper dilution.

Sample collection

Water samples from liquid waste discharge point of KAPS and Ratania (2.3 km from discharge point) were collected during April 2023 to April 2024 on ten occasions. The ³H activity was measured using Ultra low level liquid scintillation spectrometer (LSS). The detection limit of the present system for ³H was estimated to be 5 Bq/l in water.

Results

³H activity (Bq/l) in water and estimation of dilution factor

³H activity in water samples was found to be 753-3440 Bq/l and 6-65 Bq/l at liquid waste discharge point and Ratania regulator,

respectively. The Ratania flow was 313-3719 Cusec and incoming water flow from Kakrapar LBC (Left bank Canal) was 262 to 4550 Cusec. The ratio of ³H activity in liquid waste discharge point to Ratania regulator will give an idea about the extent of dilution available at a given time. The dilution factor (DF) available for liquid waste discharge was 24-222 with an average of 81 during the study period. The various factors affecting the dilution are temperature, flow rate, depth of water body etc. Reji et al., 2023 reported dilution factor of 12.2±2.4 using tritium as a tracer for Kadra reservoir. Considering the uncertainty in computation of DF for aquatic pathways, AERB adopts the lowest value of DF of 10 and 100 respectively for inland and coastal sites (AERB, 2010).

Conclusion

Tritium activity at the discharge point was found to be within the technical specification limit (4000 Bq/l). Using ³H, DF available at public utilization point at Ratania was found to be in the range of 24-222 with an average of 81 during April 2023 to April 2024.

References

1. Reji et al. (2022), Radiation Protection Environment, 45, 127-30.
2. AERB (2010), Effluent Discharge Limits and the Public Dose estimation for NPPs, AERB/OPSD/2010; Mumbai, India.

ASSESSMENT OF PROBABLE MAXIMUM PRECIPITATION USING GUMBEL DISTRIBUTION FOR THE COASTAL SITE TARAPUR, INDIA

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Keywords: Method of Moments, Probability Weighted Moments.

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Introduction

Assessment of Probable Maximum Precipitation (PMP) has the utmost importance for planning, design, management, and risk analysis of hydraulic and other structures in a region. This paper presents the estimates of Extreme Rainfall (ER) and standard error (SE) at Tarapur, Maharashtra using four different parameter estimation methods of Gumbel distribution.

Materials and Methods

Site-specific Maximum Daily Rainfall (MDR) data in (mm) collected at Tarapur site during the period 1961-2020 is used for the analysis. Cumulative density function of Gumbel distribution is given by

$$F(R) = e^{-e^{-(R_i - \alpha)/\beta}} \text{----- (1)}$$

Where α and β are location and scale parameters computed by four different methods- Method of Moments (MOM), Method of Least Squares (MLS), Order Statistics Approach (OSA) and Probability Weighted Moments (PWM) as given in Vivekanandan, 2013 are used to estimate ER(R_T) for different return periods using the relation $R_T = \alpha + Y_T \beta$ and $Y_T = -\text{Ln}(-\text{Ln}(1-(1/T)))$.

Results

Performance of the four methods is analysed by Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Diagnostic test is used for the selection of a suitable method for the estimation of ER for Tarapur site. Gumbel distribution for estimation of ER using four methods MOM, MLS, OSA and PWM has been worked out for different return periods. According to AERB guidelines, (AERB, 2008) the ER+SE (which indicates upper confidence limit will present the value that will not be exceeded by 84.13 % of the events having a desired return period) value is generally considered in arriving at a design value for the site which may be useful during construction time for the nuclear facility or any other civil structure of importance at the site. In the present study, the Mean+SE values for 1000-year return period ERs (based on MDR) given by four methods of Gumbel distribution were compared, and the least value is found to be for OSA

method which is 669.8+60.3mm and maximum of 802.6+87.8mm for MLS method. RMSE value of 197.16 mm is the least for OSA and maximum 249.7 mm for MLS also D test value is 2.21 which is minimum observed for the OSA and maximum of 3.46 for MLS. For checking the adequacy of fitting of the method to the recorded rainfall data, lowest RMSE value is used to evaluate the performance of the estimated annual MDR of Gumbel distribution. It has been observed that since RMSE and D test values for Leiblien OSA method are least compared to other methods, OSA is performing better compared to other methods and is the most suitable and appropriate method for use at the Tarapur site.

1000 year MRI for MDR by OSA is 669.8 mm, using this value short term rainfall depth by empirical reduction formula proposed by IMD for 1 hr, 2 hr, 3 hr, 5 hr, 8, hr and 16 hr has been worked out and found to be 232.2 mm, 292.6 mm, 334.9 mm, 397.1 mm, 464.4 mm, and 585.1 mm respectively.

Conclusion

RMSE and Diagnostic test D-index test values for OSA are lesser compared to other three methods hence performance of OSA method is better, and is best suitable for estimation of design values of PMP.

References

- N. Vivekanandan and S.K. Roy Assessment of Probable Maximum Precipitation Using Gumbel Distribution and Hershfield Method Bonfring International Journal of Data Mining Vol.3 No. 1(2013)
- AERB Safety Guide (2008), Extreme Values of Meteorological Parameters (AERB/NF/SG/S3), Atomic Energy Regulatory Board, Mumbai, India.

ASSESSMENT OF DOSE RATES TO NON-HUMAN BIOTA AROUND RAWATBHATA RAJASTHAN THROUGH TERRESTRIAL ROUTE USING ERICA

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Keywords: ERICA tool, Screening dose, risk quotient, reference organisms

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Introduction

Impact assessment of ionising radiation on non-human biota, in addition to human protection is gaining importance. This shift in emphasis arose from recognition that protecting humans may not be sufficient to ensure protection of non-human biotic species of the environment. The present study evaluates the radiological risk to non-human biota utilizing the ERICA tool due to presence of ¹³⁷Cs (a fallout radionuclide), ²³⁸U and ²³²Th (naturally occurring radionuclides) in the terrestrial environment of Rawatbhata Rajasthan. ERICA is specialised dosimetric tool to determine external and internal dose rates to non-human biota developed as outcome of EURATOM project.

Materials and Methods

Soil samples were collected, processed and packed in suitable geometry for a month for equilibration with daughter progenies. The radioactivity was assayed using gamma spectrometry employing P-type high purity germanium (HPGe) detector for a counting time of 60000 sec. Quality assurance of the measurement was ensured using IAEA-certified reference standards of RGU-I and RGTh-I and CRMs. In the present work, radiological dose to various reference organisms, viz. amphibians, annelids, arthropod, birds, flying insects, mammals (large and burrowing), lichen & bryophytes, mollusc and reptiles of the terrestrial ecosystem around Rawatbhata, is estimated using ERICA (v2.0). Screening dose rate criterion of 10 $\mu\text{Gy h}^{-1}$ was adopted. Dose rates below this threshold are considered to have negligible potential risks of adverse effects. The assessment included the calculation of the risk quotient (RQ) for each selected reference organism, at uncertainty factor of 3.0 to test for 5% probability of exceedance screening dose rate.

Results

The annual average specific activities ($\text{Bq.kg}^{-1} \text{ d.w.}$) of radionuclides in the soil samples varied from 0.4 to 2.2 for ¹³⁷Cs, from 14.0 to 37.0 for ²³⁸U, and from 21.0 to 62.0 for ²³²Th, during the period 2016 to 2023. Maximum dose rate per organism to various reference organisms varied from 8.21×10^{-3} for small burrowing mammal to $1.42 \mu\text{Gy h}^{-1}$ for lichens and bryophytes. Order of radionuclides contributing to dose is ²³⁸U > ²³²Th > ¹³⁷Cs. Because of greater accumulation of radionuclides due to slow growth rate, presence of waxy cuticles and specialised structures for water and gas exchange, lichens and bryophytes receive highest dose. Estimated values of RQ were below unity for all studied reference organisms.

Conclusion

The radiation dose rates due to ¹³⁷Cs, ²³⁸U and ²³²Th for non-human biota of the terrestrial ecosystem surrounding the Rawatbhata Rajasthan were found to be lower than the ERICA screening level of 10 $\mu\text{Gy h}^{-1}$ and RQ less than unity. Terrestrial flora and fauna of Rawatbhata Site are minimally exposed with negligible risk from the radionuclides studied.

References

ICRP, The 2007 recommendations, ICRP publication 103, Ann. ICRP 37, Oxford, (2007)
ERICA Assessment Tool 2.0, available from: www.ERICA-tool.com.
US DOE, A graded approach for evaluating radiation doses to aquatic and terrestrial biota, DOE-STD-1153. US DOE, Washington (2019).

STATISTICAL TRENDS OF ENVIRONMENTAL TRITIUM AROUND RAPS RAWATBHATA (2000-2020)

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Introduction

Rawatbhata Rajasthan site comprises of five operating PHWR units generating 1100 MWe with commercial operation of reactors starting in the years 1982, 2000 and 2010. In PHWRs, tritium (³H) is primarily generated as activation product during interaction of heavy water of moderator and coolant with neutrons. Generated tritium (HTO) is discharged to atmospheric and aquatic environment as per specified regulatory release limits. This paper analyses the statistical trends of tritium in atmospheric and aquatic environment of RAPS Rawatbhata based on measured data during the period 2000 to 2020 using Mann-Kendall non-parametric test (MK test) [1]. It is widely used to detect monotonic trends in the environmental data series. MK tests involve two hypotheses; the null hypotheses which suggest no trend and alternate hypothesis indicating presence of increasing or decreasing trend.

Materials and Methods

A well planned and elaborate environmental monitoring programme is executed by Environmental Survey Laboratory of EMAD, BARC covering radial distance of 30 km around RAPS site to assess the impact of reactor origin releases on environment, if any. The monitoring zones around RAPS site is divided into different circular zones, Z-1 (at 1.6 km), Z-2 (1.6 to 5.0 km), Z-3 (5.0 to 10.0 km), Z-4 (10.0 to 15.0 km) and Z-5 (15.0 to 30.0 km). To estimate the ³H in air moisture and Rana Pratap Sagar (RPS) lake water, samples were collected and analysed using liquid scintillation counting systems (Perkin Elmer, 3170TR/SL and Quantulus 1220) as per standard methodology [2]. The MK test was exclusively applied to the data where tritium activity levels are above BDL values and trend analysis was conducted using geometric mean values of measured results of ³H concentration in air and water samples

Results

Geometric mean (GM) of ³H concentration in air varied from 0.4 to 16.2 Bq.m⁻³ in Z-1. During the study period, GM of ³H concentration in air in the radial zones where members of the general public reside (zone Z-3 to Z-5) is found to vary from <0.10-1.2 Bq.m⁻³. GM of ³H activity in RPS lake water samples varied within range of 7.0 Bq. L⁻¹ to 93.0 Bq. L⁻¹ (Z-1) and from <5.0 to 54.0 Bq. L⁻¹ (Z-3 to Z-5). Trend analysis of ³H in air within monitoring zones Z-1 to Z-5 indicated statistically significant decreasing trend (z < -1.96) and p < 0.05. Further trend analysis for ³H activity due to discharged liquid effluent in RPS lake also indicated statistically significant decreasing trend across monitoring zones Z-1 to Z-5 (z < -1.96) and p < 0.05 during 2000-2020 period.

Conclusion

³H concentrations in air and water around Rawatbhata Rajasthan site are much less than regulatory limits (Z-1 to Z-5). Long term MK trend analysis test of measured data of ³H concentration in air and RPS lake water samples indicated a significant decreasing trend in various zones up to 30 km radial distance at 5% significance level. Further, this decreasing trend is observed despite addition of twin unit of 220 MWe (RAPS 3&4) and (RAPS 5&6) during 2000-2020 indicating continual improvements in the plant operations with significant reduction in discharges.

References

- Pohlert T 2023 Trend: Non-parametric trend tests, R package version 1.1.6
- Hegde A G (1998): ERL procedure manual, Health Physics Division, BARC.

ASSESSMENT OF RADIOACTIVITY AND ASSOCIATED RADIATION HAZARD PARAMETERS IN SOIL SAMPLES OF RAWATBHATA ENVIRONMENT

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Introduction

The primary sources of external exposure of human being are the primordial radioactivity present in the earth crust, mainly ²³⁸U, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K, and their radioactive progenies. Natural environmental radioactivity and the associated external exposure due to gamma radiation depend primarily on the geological and geographical conditions, and appear at different levels in the soils of each region in the world. The aim of this study was to calculate radiation hazard indices of radium equivalent activity (R_{eq}), external and internal hazard indices (H_{ex} , H_{in}), representative level index (I_r) along with external and internal annual effective dose ($AED_{outdoor}$, AED_{indoor}) for Rawatbhata Region, of Rajasthan.

Materials and Methods

Soil samples ($n=60$) were collected from an undisturbed area from different locations around Rawatbhata region, Rajasthan up to radial distance 30 km. Soil samples were initially processed, dried, sieved and packed in suitable geometry and kept for a period of one month to attain secular equilibrium of ²²⁶Ra with its daughter products. After one-month period, samples were subjected to gamma-ray spectrometric analysis using P-type HPGe for counting period of 60,000 seconds. Quality assurance of measurements were ensured by counting certified reference material from IAEA (RGU-I and RGTh-I). Radioactivity concentration of ²²⁶Ra was determined from gamma-ray energies of its daughters ²¹⁴Pb (351.92 & 1120.31 keV) and ²³²Th was determined from gamma-ray energies of its daughters ²¹²Bi (727.17 keV), and ²²⁸Ac (911.07 keV). The radioactivity concentration of ⁴⁰K was determined from gamma-ray energy of 1460.70 keV. Radiation hazard indices were estimated using relation $R_{eq} = A_{Ra} + 1.43A_{Th} + 0.077A_K$, $H_{ex} = A_{Ra}/370 + A_{Th}/259 + A_K/4810$, $H_{in} = A_{Ra}/185 + A_{Th}/259 + A_K/4810$,

$I_r = A_{Ra}/150 + A_{Th}/100 + A_K/1500$, $AED_{Indoor} = D(nGy h^{-1}) \times 8760(h.y^{-1}) \times 0.8 \times 0.7(Sv.Gy^{-1}) \times 10^{-6}$, $AED_{Outdoor} = D(nGy h^{-1}) \times 8760(h.y^{-1}) \times 0.2 \times 0.7(Sv.Gy^{-1}) \times 10^{-6}$, where various notations have standard meanings [Kabir 2009].

Results

Geometric mean concentration of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K in analysed soil samples vary from 12.0-35.0, 16.0-52.0 and 140.0-482.0 Bq.kg⁻¹ respectively. In all samples, activity concentration was in the order ⁴⁰K > ²³²Th > ²²⁶Ra. Estimated R_{eq} for Rawatbhata region vary from 46.0 to 162.0 Bq.kg⁻¹ which is much less than the allowable limit (370 Bq.kg⁻¹). Estimated H_{ex} , H_{in} , I_r , AED_{indoor} and $AED_{outdoor}$ for Rawatbhata region varies from 0.1 to 0.4, 0.2 to 0.5, 0.3 to 0.9, 91.0 μ Sv.y⁻¹ to 249.0 μ Sv.y⁻¹ and 23.0 μ Sv.y⁻¹ to 62.0 μ Sv.y⁻¹ respectively.

Conclusion

The activity concentration of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K in soil samples of Rawatbhata region are lower than the world average values. Studied radiological hazard parameters are much lower than recommended values.

References

K A Kabir and M M Rahman, Journal of Bangladesh Academy of Sciences, Vol.33, No.1, 117- 130, 2009.
Dhanya Balakrishnan, Umadevi A G, IJFPS, Vol. 2, No.3, pp. 41- 43, Sep, 2012.

ASSESSMENT OF PERFORMANCE OF ESL RAPS IN IAEA PROFICIENCY TEST

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Introduction

Environmental Survey Laboratory (ESL) at Rawatbhata Rajasthan Site, carries out comprehensive monitoring and measurement of various radionuclides in different matrices. ESL RAPS is regularly participating in the various intercomparison exercises and proficiency tests as a part of quality assurance programme to ascertain competence in low level measurements. Participation in such exercises help laboratory to demonstrate that measured data generated is of good quality in addition to ensuring compliance of validity of reported results with standards like ISO/IEC 17025. This paper discusses the performance of ESL RAPS in IAEA worldwide proficiency test conducted in 2024 on determination of anthropogenic and natural radionuclides in matrices of water, sediment, bauxite and simulated contaminated surface samples.

Materials and Methods

Gamma emitting radionuclides are determined using HPGe (Co-axial detector, ORTEC make, RE: 100%) with energy resolution of 2.0 keV at 1332.5 keV of ⁶⁰Co is used. Energy and efficiency calibrations were carried using standard radioactive sources with traceability to NIST USA. Liquid scintillation spectrometry technique (LSS, Quantulus 1220) was used for evaluation of ³H, Gross alpha and Gross beta activities. RGU and RGTh reference standards were kept in 60 ml bottle geometry. After gamma counting, 50 ml aliquot of water sample was first distilled to get tritiated water only for analysis of ³H in water. Sr-90 in water sample was determined using radiochemical analysis (Hegde et al.). Simulated contaminated surface sample contained ¹³⁴Cs and ⁹⁰Sr on the surface and IAEA provided QC sample of ¹³⁴Cs and ⁹⁰Sr to determine efficiency for simulated contaminated surface samples. Uranium in water samples was estimated using fluorimetry technique. The final score is assigned as 'Accepted (A)', 'Not accepted (N)' and 'Warning (W)' based on Trueness and Precision

of reported values as per standard methodology of IAEA. For trueness evaluation, relative bias is determined as:

$$\text{Bias} = \frac{(\text{Reported Value} - \text{Target value}) * 100\%}{\text{Target value}}$$

For trueness to be accepted, $|\text{Bias \%}| \leq \text{MARB\%}$, here, *MARB* is *Maximum acceptable relative bias*.

For precision, *P* value is determined as:

$$P = \sqrt{\left(\frac{U_{\text{target}}}{A_{\text{target}}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{U_{\text{reported}}}{A_{\text{reported}}}\right)^2} * 100\%$$

Two conditions are to be fulfilled for precision acceptance: $|\text{Bias \%}| \leq 2.58 * P \%$ and $P \% \leq \text{MARB}$. Even if one of the above two condition is not fulfilled, the final evaluation will be 'Warning (W)' if the trueness condition is satisfied, otherwise, the final evaluation will be 'Not accepted', acceptance of gross alpha and beta activity are evaluated using z-score and zeta-score (Certificate of participation IAEA PT, 2024).

Results

Trueness and precision evaluation of different gamma emitting radionuclides is 'Accepted' for all reported radionuclides. Z-score and zeta-score of reported gross alpha and gross beta in water sample are 'accepted'. Similarly, for sediment and bauxite samples, the final evaluation for all evaluated gamma emitters is 'Accepted' based on trueness and precision. In simulated contaminated surface sample ¹³⁴Cs and ⁹⁰Sr was reported within 5% bias.

Conclusion

Based on the trueness and precision evaluation all reported results in IAEA PT are qualified with final evaluation of 'Accepted'. This further validated the used analytical techniques, traceability of measurement, ensuring high quality of data generated by our laboratory.

References

Hegde et al, ERL Procedure Manual, (1998), Mumbai
Certificate of Participation in the IAEA-TERC proficiency test exercise, page 3-4, 2024.

RADON (^{222}Rn) VARIABILITY AT A WORKPLACE IN THE URANIUM MINERALIZED AREA OF SINGHBHUM, JHARKHAND, INDIA

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Introduction

Across the world, seasonal and diurnal variations in the radon level is investigated for the realistic assessment of the public dose. Such variations are mostly relating to the factors such as geogenic characteristics, climatic conditions and anthropogenic activities. Apart from this, type of the dwelling, characteristics of the construction material, water uses pattern, occupancy and ventilation are some of the key variables deciding the extent of attributable hazard. Action levels are provided for effective implementation of the mitigation strategies (ICRP,1993). Apart from this, specific classifications such as mine, tourist caves and indoor workplaces has been provided for the calculation of doses (ICRP, 2017). Large fluctuations in the radon level due to the seasonal and temporal changes warrants long term measurements are required for carrying out a realistic assessment of the potential exposure. In present study, a work place has been selected for collecting the annual cyclic data for radon.

Materials and Methods

Measurements were carried out using a compact device (AirThings Corentium) based on the alpha spectrometry (silicon photodiode). The sampling mode is the passive diffusion mode with the diffusion time constant of 25 minutes. The room ($\sim 60 \text{ m}^3$) has mixed ventilation system with brick walls, concrete roof, granite floor, doors (2 m^2), windows (4), AC (2) and ceiling fans (6). The system (MDL $< 3 \text{ Bq m}^{-3}$) was placed at 1 metre height in close proximity of the sitting area of the workspace. During the measurement period the radon levels were compared with the reference professional radon monitor (Alpha Guard).

Results

One day, seven day and long-term averages of ^{222}Rn concentration was recorded for investigating the source term, temporal &

seasonal variations. For a continuous measurement for 350 days one day average, seven-day average and long-term average has been recorded. The average concentration of radon has been worked out as 73.4 ± 33.4 , 73.2 ± 26.7 and $77.4 \pm 25.6 \text{ Bq m}^{-3}$ for 1 day, 7 day and long-term measurement respectively. The median concentration of radon for the long-term measurement was 85 Bq m^{-3} against the one day and seven-day median of 70 Bq m^{-3} . Also, the range narrows down for taking long term average (maximum 118 and minimum 41 Bq m^{-3}) against the seven day (maximum 138 and minimum 11 Bq m^{-3}) and one day averages (maximum 175 and minimum 15 Bq m^{-3}). The data was quite symmetrical for the long-term average based measurements with skewness of 0.034. The minimum activity concentration of radon was recorded during the month of July to Sept. reflecting the impact of rain (poor ^{222}Rn emanation). The maximum activity concentration of radon was recorded during the winter (Dec to Feb).

Conclusion

For working out the public exposure and mitigation strategies, if required, representative measurement should account the long-term averages. This will enable to minimize the impact of intermittent temporal variations due to changes in the ambient conditions.

References

ICRP, 2017. Occupational intakes of radionuclides: Part 3, ICRP Publication 137, Ann. ICRP 46(3/4).

EVALUATION OF ²¹⁰PO LEVELS IN MARINE BIOTA FROM MUMBAI HARBOUR BAY AND ASSOCIATED EFFECTIVE DOSE FROM SEAFOOD CONSUMPTION

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Introduction

Marine organisms play a crucial role in assessing the health of marine ecosystems. The concentrations of natural and artificial radionuclides, as well as trace metals in their tissues, provide valuable insights into the environmental status. Naturally occurring radionuclides are significant contributors to the effective radiation dose, with Po-210 a particle-active alpha emitter from the U-238 series with a half-life of 138 days accounting for up to 90% of the natural radiation dose from marine species (Alam, 2011). This study aims to estimate the ingestion dose of Po-210 for the population of the Mumbai region due to seafood consumption.

Materials and Methods

Thane Creek in Mumbai Harbour Bay (MHB) receives treated effluents from domestic and industrial sources in Mumbai and nearby areas. This location was chosen to evaluate Po-210 and establish a long-term record of its impact on natural radioactivity in marine organisms.

Standard procedures were followed for sample collection and preparation. One kilogram of each seafood type commonly consumed in Mumbai was collected from fresh catches in local markets in the study area. The samples were categorized into fish, crustaceans (prawns), and cockles (*Anadara granosa*), retaining only the edible tissue for radiological assessment. Po-210 activity was measured using standard radiochemical techniques and analyzed with ORTEC make alpha spectrometer, equipped with a PIPS detector featuring a 300 mm² active area, 100 μm depletion depth, 35-40 keV resolution, and ~15% efficiency.

Annual Committed Effective Dose (CED)

The CED due to consumption of Po-210 from seafood is calculated using following formula;

$$CED(mSv/y) = A \times IR \times DF$$

Where, A is the mean activity concentration of Po-210 in seafood (Bq kg⁻¹ fresh weight); IR is annual seafood consumption rate (kg y⁻¹) (P. Hemalatha, 2015) and DF is the dose conversion factor 1.2×10⁻⁶ Sv y⁻¹ given by IAEA 1995

Results

The mean activity concentration of Po-210 is 5.3 Bq Kg⁻¹(wet) for fish, 43.4 Bq Kg⁻¹(wet) for crustaceans (prawns) and 84.6 Bq Kg⁻¹(wet) for cockles (*Anadara granosa*). The corresponding annual committed effective doses (CED) to general public are 0.1 mSv y⁻¹, 0.8 mSv y⁻¹, and 1.4 mSv y⁻¹ respectively, following the order: cockles > crustaceans > fish. The results are consistent with other studies along the Indian coast (Macklin Rani, 2013) and show no statistically significant increase over the past 10 years (S. Sugandhi, 2023).

Conclusion

The average CED to the public from seafood consumption is estimated at 0.8 mSv/y. Po-210 variation in different species can be attributed to differences in species' metabolic rates, absorption efficiencies, and habitat characteristics.

References

1. Alam et.al., (2011), *Envir. Health.* pp.1-10
2. Hemalatha et.al. (2015), *J Radioanal Nucl. Chem* (2015), pp. 271–276.
3. Macklin Rani et. al., (2014) *J. J. Radiat. Res. & Appl. Sci.* pp.207-213.
4. S. Sugandhi (2023), *Radiation Protection and Environment*, 46(4), pp.158-162.

TEMPORAL VARIATION OF ¹³⁷Cs AND ⁹⁰Sr RADIOISOTOPES DISTRIBUTION IN MUMBAI HARBOUR BAY

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Introduction

The ambient background radioactivity is contributed by the naturally occurring radionuclides and anthropogenic activities like the atmospheric or underwater weapons testing, nuclear accidents, and discharges from operational facilities. Understanding the longterm behaviour of anthropogenic radionuclides in the environment is vital, especially that of long lived radionuclides as they may get integrated in the human food chain and cause potential exposure in addition [1]. This involves studying their behaviour in different environmental matrices, their persistence, and the rate at which they enter the food chain. ¹³⁷Cs and ⁹⁰Sr are two such radionuclides introduced into the environment through human activities. Radionuclides present in seawater gradually get distributed into the sediment and plants growing in these areas/shores. This absorption can result in their bioaccumulation which may enter the food chain if the vegetation is consumed by herbivores. Hence aim of the present study is to understand the temporal behaviour of ¹³⁷Cs and ⁹⁰Sr in different matrices.

Materials and Methods

Sediment, seawater, and vegetation were collected near the coastal area in Mumbai harbour Bay and analysed for ¹³⁷Cs and ⁹⁰Sr during 2015 to 2023 and their ratios were compared. 20-liter seawater sample was collected for analysis, and standard chemical methods were employed to isolate Cs and Sr from the seawater. Sediment samples were collected from the same locations where aquatic vegetation was growing. Cs analysis was performed using 250-gram sample in a geometry suitable for direct gamma energy measurement using 50% p type HPGe detector. Sr analysis was carried out using standard radiochemical separation procedure for Beta estimation in 20 grams of dry sample using

plastic scintillator based beta counter. Geometric mean of the concentration were compared, and the ratios of seawater to sediment and sediment to vegetation were calculated for both strontium and cesium.

Results

The calculated ratios of the concentration of Cs and Sr between seawater and sediment is observed to be in the range of 10⁻⁵ to 10⁻⁴ and 10⁻⁴ to 10⁻³ respectively indicating accumulation of Cs and Sr activity in the sediment, with Cs demonstrating a significantly higher affinity for sediment as compared to Sr. Whereas the ratios of activity in vegetation to sediment is observed to be higher for Sr (0.3-0.8) compared to Cs (0.003-0.03). The results revealed that Cesium ions have a higher affinity to clay minerals and become immobilized more readily, hence are less available for uptake as compared to Sr which is more bioavailable [2].

Conclusion

The temporal variation studies of Cesium and Strontium have indicated that there is no enhancement in activity concentration in any of the environmental matrices over the ambient levels due to global fallout.

References

1. Prohl, G., Ehlken, S., (2006) Journal of Environmental Radioactivity **91** 41-72.
2. Merz, S., Shozugawa K., Steinhauser, G. (2016) J Radioanal Nucl Chem, 307:1807–1810.

ESTIMATION OF TRANSFER FACTOR OF ^{137}Cs AND ^{40}K FROM SOIL TO PLANT IN RAWATBHATA ENVIRONMENT

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Introduction

Natural and anthropogenic radionuclides deposited onto the ground can enter the root and gets accumulated in above ground in different edible parts of the plants. K and Cs tends to retain in the soil through fixation and adsorption to clay minerals and organic matter, persisting in the plant rooting zone. These dissolved ions can be readily absorbed by roots and translocated to the aboveground plant parts. Transfer Factor (TF) is a dimensionless quantity defined as the ratio of the radionuclide concentration in plants (or in specific plant organs) to the radionuclide concentration in a specified soil layer assuming equilibrium conditions (IAEA, 2010). In the present study, soil-to-plant TF for ^{137}Cs and ^{40}K in Rawatbhata environment are presented using controlled pot experiment studies.

Materials and methods

Soil of specific composition were collected from particular location for study. Trace level of ^{137}Cs activity was added in weighed soil which was dried and homogenised before start of experiment. Activity of ^{40}K (0.012% of stable K) naturally present in the soil was used for TF calculation. Grass and seeds of different plant species, were grown in homogenised soil in the pots during different seasons of the year. After completion of growth, different plant organs (fruit, stem, leaves) were collected, processed, packed in suitable geometry for evaluation of ^{137}Cs and ^{40}K activity by gamma-ray spectrometry technique. Efficiency and energy calibration of the HPGe detector were carried out using the certified reference material from IAEA.

Results

The observed TF of ^{137}Cs and ^{40}K ranged from 0.01-0.02 (avg. 0.02) and 0.77-0.86 (avg. 0.79) in potato, 0.11-0.54 (avg. 0.29) and 0.46-0.53 (avg. 0.5) in grass, 0.34-0.38

(avg. 0.36) and 0.52-0.60 (avg. 0.56) in radish leaves, 0.34-0.91 (avg. 0.71) and 0.35-0.69 (avg. 0.56) in sponge gourd 0.03-0.1 (avg. 0.07) and 0.24-0.4 (avg. 0.31) in lady finger and 0.38-0.75 (avg. 0.56), 0.16-0.18 (avg. 0.17) in cucumber and 0.44 and 0.70 in Chaulai samples respectively. Average values of TF of ^{137}Cs and ^{40}K in plant organs of different species are 0.78 and 0.57 in stem and 0.62 and 0.1 in leaves of sponge gourd, 0.06 and 0.38 in stem of lady finger respectively. Observed trend of TF for ^{137}Cs and ^{40}K is more in stem than leaves for sponge gourd studied with different compartments. Measured TF values are comparable with other worldwide studies (Velasco, 2021 and IAEA, 2010).

Conclusions

Behaviour of ^{137}Cs and ^{40}K in different plant species of Rawatbhata environment are studied through generation of TF. Generated TF may be used as input to dose assessment models for estimating ingestion does to public.

References

IAEA (2010). Hand book of parameters values for the prediction of radionuclides transfer factor in terrestrial and fresh water environment.
H. Velasco and R.M. Anjos (2021). Journal of Environmental Radioactivity, 235-236.

STUDIES ON THE MEASUREMENT OF ^{14}C IN BIOTA AT KAKRAPAR GUJARAT SITE

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Introduction

^{14}C is a radioactive isotope of carbon with a half-life of ~5730 years which decays to ^{14}N by emitting low energy β -radiation with an average energy of 49.5 keV and a maximum energy of 156 keV. In addition to natural production ^{14}C is also produced in the nuclear reactor via neutron capture reactions. A fraction of the generated ^{14}C is released to the environment during normal operation of NPPs. The gaseous release of ^{14}C in the form of $^{14}\text{CO}_2$ is assimilated by plants. Considering the biological importance of ^{14}C in the organism and its long half-life, it is important to monitor ^{14}C activity in the region around the NPPs. At equilibrium, more than 99% of the dose contributed by ^{14}C comes from the ingestion pathway (Peterson et al., 1997).

Materials and Methods

Kakrapar Gujarat site comprises of four PHWR type nuclear power reactors of capacity 220 MWe each (KAPS-1&2) and 700 MWe each (KAPP-3&4) which are operational. Environmental biota samples (164 nos.) such as cereals (14 nos.), pulses (13 nos.), fruits (49 nos.), vegetable (22 nos.), leaf (61 nos.) and grass (5 nos.) are collected from three zones (1.6 km, 1.6-5.0 km and 5.0-10.0 km) around Kakrapar Gujarat Site during the period 2022-2024. All the samples were dried using Delvac make freeze drier. Thermal Oxidation method is employed by using Raddec make Pyrolyser in presence of an oxygen rich environment to convert carbon species into CO_2 . The CO_2 produced from the combustion was isolated from the combustion products through cryogenic trapping (using a cryo-cooler) and then transferred to an amine-based absorber (Carbo-sorb E) to saturate it. The difficulties associated with the determination of recovery and the need for carbon content measurements can be overcome by improvements in the method by saturating the absorber with CO_2 released from the sample combustion. The ^{14}C activity is determined

using Quantulus GCT 6220 liquid scintillation spectrometer (LSS).

Results

Specific activity of ^{14}C in biota: The average specific activity of ^{14}C in biota samples (cereals, pulses, fruits, vegetable, leaf and grass) found to be $236 \pm 6 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1} \text{ C}$. The ^{14}C activity in the vicinity of KAPS in samples collected at farther distances is about $230 \pm 6 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1} \text{ C}$. Specific activity of ^{14}C in biota samples collected around Kakrapar Gujarat site is comparable with Kaiga, Karnataka region (Karunakara et al., 2023). The ^{14}C levels observed at Kakrapar Gujarat site are within the variation of measurement / sampling uncertainty compared to levels at farther distances. The reported MDA of $12 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1} \text{ C}$ with 300 min counting time. The quality assurance was carried out by spiking the ^{14}C known activity on background unwashed sand with zero carbon activity. Using the proposed methodology, we are able to successfully measure the ^{14}C levels in different types of biota samples.

Conclusion

^{14}C activity in biota samples collected around Kakrapar Gujarat site is about $236 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1} \text{ C}$. The studies indicate the low-level measurement capabilities of laboratory for determination of ^{14}C in biota samples.

References

- S. R. Peterson, P. A. Davis, R. R. Rao (1997) Atomic Energy of Canada Limited (AECL) report (RC-1951).
- N. Karunakara, R. S. D'Souza, S. R. Nayak, S. Bharath, K. A. Krishnan, B.N. Dileep, P.M. Ravi (2023) *Science of the Total Environment* **858**, 159756.

NATURAL RADIOACTIVITY LEVELS IN LOCAL FOODSTUFF AROUND A URANIUM MINERALISED REGION

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Introduction

Radiological baseline studies are necessary for evaluating environmental impacts at the pre-operational, operational, and decommissioning stages of nuclear facilities. These studies are conducted for uranium mining facilities only after confirming the presence of uranium deposits with economically viable grades. The current study is part of the baseline studies for the upcoming Rohil uranium mineralized zone, located in the Sikar district of Rajasthan, India.

Materials and Methods

Approximately 5 kg of various locally grown food samples were collected either directly from farms or from the nearest wholesale farm produce centers in Rohil, Rajasthan. The selection of specific food items was guided by a survey of local residents' dietary habits. A total of eleven food types, representing major food groups such as cereals, pulses, and vegetables, were collected, processed using standard method to get white ash (1) and were analysed using high resolution gamma ray spectrometry.

The gamma-spectrometry system having a p-type coaxial HPGe detector shielded with 7.5-cm thick lead having 40 % relative efficiency, and a resolution of 1.8 keV at 1.33-MeV gamma energy of ^{60}Co was used. The gamma spectra acquired for 100, 000 s. The details of quality control and assessment are described elsewhere (2).

Results and Discussions

Except for radio-potassium (^{40}K), natural radionuclides concentrations in all food samples were found to be below detection levels for ^{238}U , ^{226}Ra , ^{210}Pb and ^{232}Th . Fallout ^{137}Cs concentration also found to be below detection level for all samples. ^{40}K concentration in the samples varied for a wide range of 54.2 Bq/kg of carrot to 542 Bq/kg for Guar. For cereals, pulses and vegetables, the radio-potassium concentration varied between

127.5 – 254.6 Bq/kg, 276.7 – 542.0 Bq/kg and 54.2 – 146.0 Bq/kg respectively. The concentration levels found are comparable with that of global levels reported (3).

Conclusion

Our analytical results could be used to estimate the annual effective dose from ingestion of natural radionuclides due to consumption of local foodstuff.

References:

1. Hosseini, T. et al., Radiation Prot. Dosimetry, 121, pp 330 – 332. 2006.
2. Lenka. P. et al., Radiation Protection Dosimetry, 153, 3, pp 328 – 333, 2013.
3. UNSCEAR 2000, Sources and Effects of Ionising Radiation, Vol-1, Annex-B, 2000

VARIATION OF ^{222}Rn AND AMBIENT GAMMA RADIATION LEVELS AROUND ROHIL URANIUM MINING SITE, RAJASTHAN AND PUBLIC DOSE ASSESSMENT

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Introduction

Expansion of indigenous uranium mining activities is paramount for sustainability of atomic power stations in the country to meet the nationally determined commitments of climate change treaties. In addition to operating uranium mines and ore processing facilities in Jharkhand and Andhra Pradesh, it is proposed to start a new uranium mine at Rohil, Sikar, Rajasthan. Benchmarking of baseline natural radioactivity levels in and around the uranium mining site and assessment of natural radiation dose is a part of environmental clearance process. In the present study, spot ambient gamma radiation dose rates and atmospheric radon gas levels are monitored in the villages / population centers around the. Radiation dose to members of the public has been estimated using these input parameters and considering the standard occupancy factor for Indian population and representative equilibrium factors for indoor and outdoor conditions.

Materials and Methods

Environmental radiation survey meter (PM1405) and Professional radon monitor (AlphaGuard) were used for measurement of ambient gamma radiation dose rates and atmospheric radon gas levels at twenty locations. Radon measurement was carried out for one hour at each location during day time and continuous measurement (~12 - 14 hrs) at few locations during night time. Most the houses monitored in the study have cemented ceiling with tile flooring. Strict QA/QC protocol followed to ensure the data quality. Dose assessment to the public based on spot and/or continuous measurement are indicative in nature.

Results and Discussion

Ambient gamma radiation dose rate in the villages around site was observed to be in the range of 80 – 210 nSv/h with a mean value of

110 nSv/h. While, outdoor atmospheric radon gas levels were found to be range of 10 – 45 Bq/m³ and the same in indoor was observed to be in the range of 22 – 76 Bq/m³. Wide variation in the measurements reflects heterogenous surface geology and other influencing parameters. Divergence of radon gas levels in the study area is anticipated due to difference in types of house, construction material, ventilation rate etc. However, the measured levels around the site are comparable to the nationally and internationally reported values. For public dose assessment, annual occupancy of 5840 h indoor and 2920 h outdoor (Rajesh Kumar et. al.) with equilibrium factor 0.4 (ICRP-65) for indoor and 0.8 (UNSCEAR-2000) were considered for radon gas. The total radiation dose due to gamma radiation and radon concentration was found to be 0.89 mSv/y and 1.13 mSv/y in outdoor and indoor, respectively. However, long-term continuous measurement of these parameters may vary over spot measurements.

Conclusion

Outdoor and indoor radon levels around Rohil uranium mining site were observed to be in range of 10-45 and 22 – 76 Bq/m³. Indoor radon levels are well within the action levels. Estimated radiation dose to members of the public residing around Rohil uranium mining site is comparable with other parts of the country.

References

- ICRP, 1993. Protection Against Radon-222 at Home and at Work. ICRP Publication 65. Ann. ICRP 23 (2).
- Sources and effects of ionizing radiation. UNSCEAR 2000 report to the General Assembly, with scientific annexes. Volume I: Sources.

DETERMINATION OF SITE SPECIFIC K_d OF ^{63}Ni AT KAKRAPAR GUJARAT SITE IN SIMULATED CONDITIONS

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Keywords: Kakrapar, distribution coefficient, soil chemistry

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Introduction

The distribution coefficient (K_d) is an important parameter in estimating the potential for the adsorption of dissolved contaminants in contact with soil/sediment. K_d is dependent on many parameters such as type and amount of contaminant, amount of adsorbent etc. ^{63}Ni , produced in the reactor as an activation of stable Ni which is used in various structural materials, is a low beta emitter ($E_{\text{max}} 67 \text{ Kev}$) with half-life of 100 years. Estimation of site specific K_d of ^{63}Ni is useful for contaminant transport modeling in ground water migration studies.

Materials & Methods

One soil sample was collected from Solid Waste Management Facility (SWMF) at 1-meter depth and preprocessed as per the standard sampling protocol (USEPA, 1991). 1 gm of soil was mixed with 600 Bq of ^{63}Ni standard in 30 ml of ground water sample and shaken in an orbital shaker for different time intervals from 0.5 hr to 31 days. 1 ml filtrate sample was mixed with 10 ml of Ultima gold LLT cocktail and counted in LSS for estimation of ^{63}Ni activity in the water samples. Based on the activity estimation, K_d was determined using the following equation;

$$K_d = A_i / C_i$$

Where A_i = Activity concentration of adsorbate/contaminant on the soil at equilibrium/at specified time (Bq/kg);

C_i = Total dissolved adsorbate activity concentration remaining in solution at equilibrium/at specified time (Bq/l)

Results

The adsorption of ^{63}Ni from water to soil for Kakrapar Gujarat Site varied from 17 ± 2 - 3570 ± 44 l/kg for different time intervals of 0.5 hour to 31 days. It is observed that the

absorption is almost constant after 23 days. Hence the site specific equilibrium K_d is estimated to be 3570 ± 44 l/kg (23 days). The Brookhaven National Laboratory (BNL) Environmental Research and Technology Division reported the K_d in the range of 62-331 (l/kg) for ^{63}Ni (Sung et al., 2014). Since, K_d depends on various factor including type of soil, contacts time, pH of soil etc., studies on factors affecting other interdependent parameters on K_d estimation are in progress.

Conclusions

The observed site specific equilibrium K_d was found to be 3570 ± 44 l/kg (23 days). Optimization on the determination of K_d will be carried out by changing the amount of soil and activity.

References

US Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) (1991). EPA/625/4-91/026. Office of research and development, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, Cincinnati, Ohio.
Sung P.Y et al. (2014) Sorption (K_d) WM2014 Conference, March 2- March 6, 2014, Phoenix, Arizona, USA.

INGESTION DOSE FROM ^{40}K DUE TO THE CONSUMPTION OF SOME DIETARY MATRICES AROUND KAKRAPAR

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Introduction

Potassium is one of the most important nutrients and is an essential element in life processes. Potassium has naturally occurring radioactive isotope (^{40}K). When ingested or inhaled, naturally occurring radionuclides are distributed among body organs according to the metabolism of the element involved. Through food chain, natural occurring radionuclide (^{40}K) enters the human body and imparts radiation dose. In the present study, ^{40}K content in different dietary samples was investigated and ingestion dose was calculated for adult population around Kakrapar Gujarat site.

Materials and Methods

Sample collection and processing

Locally produced dietary matrices were collected (128 nos.) around the Kakrapar site during the period 2020 to 2023. Sampling, sample processing, counting and evaluation of radionuclides were carried out as per standard protocol [1].

Gamma spectrometric analysis of sample

P-type coaxial High Purity Germanium (HPGe) detector having 100 % relative efficiency (FWHM of 1.9 keV at 1332 keV gamma energy of ^{60}Co) and coupled with 8 K MCA was used for sample analysis. 1460 keV was used for ^{40}K estimation. HPGe detector was calibrated by using primary reference standard solution containing ^{152}Eu , ^{137}Cs , Am^{241} and ^{60}Co . The efficacy of the sample counting was verified by the analysis of certified reference material such as IAEA-375 (soil) and IAEA-156 (clover).

Results

^{40}K activity in dietary matrices

The ^{40}K activity in cereals (Bq.kg^{-1} dry wt.), pulses (Bq.kg^{-1} dry wt.), vegetable (Bq.kg^{-1} fresh wt.), fruits (Bq.kg^{-1} fresh wt.) and milk (Bq.l^{-1}) was found to be 11-109 with an average of 38, 140-481 with an average of 342, 24-360 with an average of 74, 41-1028 with an average of 283 and 9-65 with an average of 31,

respectively. The increasing order of ^{40}K activity content in foodstuffs was observed to be milk < cereal < vegetable < fruits < pulses. The site specific foodstuff consumption rate was considered for dose calculation [2]. The ingestion dose coefficient of $0.0062 \mu\text{Sv.Bq}^{-1}$ for ^{40}K was used [3]. The annual effective dose due to ingestion of ^{40}K through dietary intake was found to be 71-267 $\mu\text{Sv.y}^{-1}$ with an average of 138 $\mu\text{Sv.y}^{-1}$. Pulses have contributed more to the ingestion dose due to ^{40}K , because of comparatively higher concentration. James et al, 2013 reported the annual effective dose to an adult member around Kaiga site due to the ingestion of ^{40}K through dietary components varies from 114- 152 $\mu\text{Sv.y}^{-1}$ with an average of 136 $\mu\text{Sv.y}^{-1}$ [4].

Conclusion

The annual effective dose due to the ingestion of natural occurring radionuclide (^{40}K) in locally produced dietary matrices collected around Kakrapar Gujarat site was observed to be 71-267 $\mu\text{Sv.y}^{-1}$ with an average of 138 $\mu\text{Sv.y}^{-1}$.

References

- Hegde et al. (1998). Environmental Radiological Laboratory Procedure Manual, Health Physics Division, BARC, Mumbai (1998).
- Dietary Health and Biotic Study by South Gujarat University, Surat, 1999.
- IAEA (1996). Safety Series, No. 115, IAEA.
- Joshy et al., (2013), Radiation Protection Dosimetry, 153(1), 56-63.

SITE-SPECIFIC SOIL-VEGETABLE TRANSFER FACTOR (F_v) OF RADIONUCLIDES FOR VEGETABLES AT DAE SITE KALPAKKAM

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Introduction

Radionuclide transfer factor (F_v) is essential for public dose assessment due to the ingestion pathway, which allows any nuclear industry to assess the radiation dose during normal operations or emergencies. F_v may vary from site to site depending on the physico-chemical properties of the soil and hence a systematic study is required to establish this factor for each site towards realistic estimation of ingestion dose. The study aims to establish a database on site-specific transfer factors (F_v), as per IAEA-472 (2010) guidelines for natural and manmade radionuclides in the terrestrial environmental pathways for the Kalpakkam site.

Materials and Methods

The transfer factor of radionuclides is a measure of the movement or transfer of radionuclides from one environmental medium to another, typically from soil to plants. It is estimated as the ratio of the concentration of a radionuclide in a plant (e.g., Bq/kg dw) to its concentration in the background soil (Bq/kg of dw). To determine the site-specific F_v , an experimental field is developed within the premises of IGCAR, Kalpakkam to conduct experiments. The field is located 2.39 km north of FBTR, 4 km north of MAPS, and 4.52 km northwest of BHAVINI. Vegetables were selected based on their growth preferences in soil and the portion of the plant being used as food. Two leafy vegetables (Spinach and Amaranthus), two under-soil vegetable varieties (Sweet potato, radish), two shrub varieties (Aubergine, Ladies Finger), and two climber varieties (Bitter gourd and Pumpkin) were studied. Samples were collected at different stages of growth and processed for analysis by gamma spectrometer to know the site-specific transfer of radionuclides viz. ^{40}K , ^{226}Ra , and ^{232}Th .

Results

F_v values of ^{40}K , ^{226}Ra , and ^{232}Th in the vegetables are observed to be 6.4×10^{-1} - $2.69 \times$

10^0 , 0.97 - 1.90×10^{-2} , and 1.2 - 5.0×10^{-3} respectively as compared to IAEA TRS 472 reported soil-plant F_v values of 1.3×10^0 , 2.6×10^{-2} , and 5.3×10^{-6} . Radish had a higher concentration of ^{40}K (957.62 Bq/Kg) followed by Pumpkin and Brinjal. The lowest was observed in the Groundnut and Sweet potato. Among the leaves of the vegetables, Spinach has 722.31 Bq/kg of ^{40}K as the highest, and the lowest was observed in Brinjal leaves (161.27 Bq/kg). Groundnut seeds had 191.54 Bq/Kg of ^{40}K and pumpkin seeds had 176.40 Bq/kg. ^{232}Th in Radish, Groundnut, Bitter Gourd, Ridge Gourd, and Brinjal could not be detected and the values were BDL (≤ 1.2 Bq/kg). Lady's finger was having highest activity of ^{232}Th (4.72 Bq/kg) followed by Pumpkin (2.58 Bq/Kg) and sweet potato (0.99 Bq/Kg). Spinach had 11.34 Bq/Kg and Amaranthus had 3.89 Bq/ Kg of ^{232}Th . ^{226}Ra could only be detected in Lady's finger (5.67 Bq/Kg) and Raddish (2.98 Bq/Kg). Amaranthus had 5.67 Bq/Kg of ^{226}Ra activity.

Conclusion

The results of this study establish the site-specific transfer factor of different radionuclides in natural conditions. Obtained F_v values of ^{40}K and ^{226}Ra values are comparable to or lesser than the IAEA reported values (IAEA TRS 472). However, further studies on the transfer values of radionuclides will form a more accurate database for the transfer factors in the soil-vegetable compartment.

References

IAEA (2010): Handbook of Parameter Values for Prediction of Radionuclide Transfer in Terrestrial & Freshwater Environments. Technical Reports Series No. 472 IAEA, Vienna.

ESTIMATION OF ECOLOGICAL HALF LIFE OF CS-137 IN FISH KUDANKULAM, TAMILNADU.

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Introduction

¹³⁷Cs is a long-lived, biologically significant radionuclide with a radiological half-life of 30.2 years. Large amounts of ¹³⁷Cs were produced during atmospheric nuclear weapons tests. As a result of atmospheric testing and radioactive fallout, this cesium was dispersed and deposited worldwide. The long-term behaviour of radionuclides in the environment is an important issue for estimating possible radiological consequences and associated risks. The long-term behavior is quantified by means of the ecological half-life, which is an integral parameter that lumps all processes except radioactive decay that causes a decrease of activity in a specific medium (IAEA, 2010) The aim of this paper is to derive ecological half-life of fish samples collected around Kudankulam Nuclear Power Plant.

Materials and Methods

Marine Fish samples employed in this study were collected from Bay of Bengal at six different locations around Kudankulam for the last 20 years. The ¹³⁷Cs activity in fish was estimated using High purity germanium detector. The ecological half-life (T_{eco}) represents an integral value that sums up all processes contributing to the reduction of radioactivity in the environment (object) beyond physical decay. Effective loss rate constant (λ_{eff}) is estimated from the exponential slopes of Ln transformed ¹³⁷Cs activity concentrations regressed on year. From the λ_{eff} effective half-life is estimated as;

$$T_{eff} = \frac{\ln 2}{\lambda_{eff}} \text{-----} 1$$

Ecological half-life (T_{eco}) is calculated from the effective half-life with the following equation;

$$T_{eco} = \frac{T_{Eff} \times T_{Rad}}{T_{Rad} - T_{Eff}} \text{-----} 2$$

where T_{Rad} is the radioactive half-life.

Results:

The concentration of ¹³⁷Cs in fish samples varied from 0.01 to 0.22 BqKg⁻¹. The effective and ecological half life of fish samples

collected around Kudankulam was evaluated using the above said equation. The estimated effective and ecological half life (year) of fish is 5.3 and 6.5 respectively. This calculated T_{eco} is comparable with the worldwide reported values. Nataliaia et al (2023) reported that the T_{eco} for the different species of fish collected at Chernobyl varied from 5.58 to 6.94. The T_{eco} for ¹³⁷Cs in all fish species combined was 5.54 years in USA reported by J.D.Peles et al (2000).

Conclusion

The present study estimated the ecological half life of marine fish samples collected around Kudankulam. Decreasing trend of ¹³⁷Cs activity in fish shows that there is no buildup of activity in the environment due to the operation of KKNPP units. The evaluated effective and ecological half life also proves the downtrend of ¹³⁷Cs. The estimated ecological half life is comparable with the world wide reported values.

References

- IAEA (2010), *Handbook of Parameter Values for the Prediction of Radionuclide Transfer in Terrestrial and Freshwater Environments, Technical report Series 472*, IAEA, Vienna.
- Nataliia Zarubina, Vladislav Semak and Oleg S. Burdo (2023) *Ecological Half-Life of ¹³⁷Cs in Fish*. *Ecologies*, 4, 463–477.
- Panel J.D. Peles, A.L. Bryan Jr. C.T. Garten Jr (2000). *Ecological half-life of ¹³⁷Cs in fish from a stream contaminated by nuclear reactor effluents*, *Science Total Environment*, Volume 263, Issues 1–3, 18 December 2000, Pages 255-262

ESTIMATION OF ^{14}C DOSE TO THE PUBLIC AROUND KUDANKULAM

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Introduction

^{14}C is a pure beta-emitter that is formed in nature as well as in nuclear reactors and in nuclear explosions. The rate of formation of ^{14}C in reactors depends on the reactor type, being the highest in PHWRs and lowest in PWRs. It may be released to the environment in solid, liquid and gaseous effluent streams. The primary modes of uptake of the radionuclide by the public are ingestion and, to a small extent, inhalation. This paper presents the estimation of ^{14}C radiation dose to the members of public around KKNPP during the normal operation of the reactor.

Materials and Methods

^{14}C dose is calculated by taking into account the ^{14}C activity concentrations in the air, water, food, etc., the dietary habits of local people, e.g., the amount of locally grown food eaten and the dose conversion factor (mSv/Bq) of ^{14}C (AERB, 2005). The public dose evaluation methodologies are detailed in Revised IAEA TECDOC TRS-364 and various AERB safety guides.

Results

Considering the rated and permissible discharges of ^{14}C in KKNPP and the dilution factors of both the atmospheric and aquatic routes as per site specific meteorological data and hydrological data, the annual average concentrations of ^{14}C in air (Bq/m^3) and recipient water (Bq/L) are calculated. Then by using the stable carbon concentration (g/kg FW) in all the matrices as per IAEA TECDOC TRS-364, the concentration of ^{14}C is calculated in all the environmental matrices like plants, animal products, fishes, drinking water, beverages etc. Once the concentration of ^{14}C is known in various matrices, the annual internal (Inhalation & Ingestion) dose of Carbon-14 is determined by using the following equations for both the routes of releases (IAEA TRS 364, 2009).

$$D_{\text{inh}} = C_{\text{x(A)}} \cdot \text{BR} \cdot \text{DCF}_{\text{inh}} \dots\dots\dots 1$$

$$D_{\text{ing}} = C_{\text{x(D,W)}} \cdot \text{HR} \cdot \text{DCF}_{\text{ing}} \dots\dots\dots 2$$

D_{inh} & D_{ing} - annual effective dose due to inhalation & Ingestion of ^{14}C (mSv/y)

$C_{\text{x(A)}}$ - Concentration of ^{14}C in air (Bq/m^3)

$C_{\text{x(D,W)}}$ - concentration of ^{14}C in water & dietary items (Bq/kg)

BR & HR - annual breathing rate (m^3/y) & consumption rate of human being (kg/y)

DCF_{inh} & DCF_{ing} are the dose conversion factor due to inhalation & ingestion (mSv/Bq) respectively. The overall dose is calculated by the sum of both inhalation & ingestion dose and the value obtained in this study is 0.03 $\mu\text{Sv}/\text{y}$. This value is compared with the total dose given in the safety review document, which is one order higher, due to consideration of anticipated operational occurrences (AOO) and considering routes like soil / irrigation etc.

Conclusion

The annual effective ^{14}C dose to the public from KKNPP normal operation is calculated using the TECDOC models and it is compared with the existing calculations and shown that the dose is insignificant compared to the natural dose of ^{14}C (12 $\mu\text{Sv}/\text{y}$) resulting from natural carbon cycle. Since ^{14}C is mobile in the environment, it is important to control the release from nuclear facilities and waste management sites by means of appropriate operational procedures and waste management strategies and practices. It is also essential to establish a regular monitoring for estimation of ^{14}C in air and biota and the resulting dose to human beings.

References

- Methodologies for environmental radiation dose assessment; AERB safety guide No. AERB/NF/SG/S-5, March, 2005.
- Revision of the IAEA Technical Reports Series No. 364: Handbook of parameter values for the prediction of radionuclide transfer in temperate environments (2009)

DECAY CHAINS OF 233TH AND 234TH

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Introduction

Actinides like uranium, neptunium, plutonium, americium, and curium pose environmental and health risks due to their high concentrations in ecosystems[1]. Rutherford and Soddy investigated thorium radioactivity, explaining it as the transformation of elements via α or β^- particle emission [2]. Radioactive decay modes are crucial for nuclear stability, medical applications, energy production, and radiation safety. Nuclear stability depends on the (N/Z) ratio, with proton-rich nuclei decaying via β^+ or electron capture, and neutron-rich nuclei via β^- decay. Nuclear transmutation is the process where an unstable nucleus achieves stability by emitting α , β^- particles, or γ -rays[3]. The important radioactive decay modes are proton radioactivity[4], alpha-radioactivity, β^- -decay[5], spontaneous fission, cluster and heavy particle radioactivity [6]. Mahesh Babu et al.,[7] studied deformations and orientations in alpha-ternary fission of thorium isotopes. Motivated by these studies, we investigated the decay chains of 233Th and 234Th nuclei. Alphadecay half-lives were calculated using an effective liquid drop model. Beta-decay and spontaneous fission half-lives were evaluated using semi-empirical formulae.

Theory

The effective liquid drop model was used to calculate alpha-decay half-lives for 233Th and 234Th, while beta-decay and spontaneous fission half-lives were determined using semiempirical formulae. The study incorporated mass excess values of parent and daughter nuclei to calculate Q-values and referenced previous research to assess the energetics and feasibility of the decay processes.

Results

The study found that the decay chains of 233Th and 234Th primarily proceed through

alpha and beta decays, with alpha decay dominating in both isotopes stability pathways. The calculated half-lives for these decay modes varied from milliseconds to years, depending on the decay process and energy release. The decay sequences revealed that 233Th stabilizes as 205Tl through a series of beta and alpha decays, while 234Th stabilizes as 206Pb. The study also confirmed that proton decay and spontaneous fission were energetically unfavorable for both isotopes.

Conclusion

The decay chains of 233Th and 234Th provide valuable insights into the stability pathways of thorium isotopes. The findings highlight the importance of alpha and beta decays in achieving nuclear stability. These results contribute to understanding nuclear behaviour and have applications in nuclear physics, environmental safety, and radiometric dating.

References

1. R. Watters, T. Hakonson, et al.,(1983) *Radiochimica Acta* **32**, 89 .
2. E. Rutherford and F. Soddy,(2014) *The collected papers of Lord Rutherford of Nelson*, 435-456 .
3. S. Vallabhajosula, (2023) *Radiopharm. Clin. Appl.* 49-62.
4. M. Srinivas, H. Manjunatha, et al., (2020) *Nucl. Phys. A* **995**,121689.
5. H. Manjunatha, N. Sowmya, et al.,(2021) *Nucl. Sci. Technol.* **32**, 130.
6. N. Sowmya, H. C. Manjunatha, et al., (2020) *J. ofRadioanal. and Nucl. Chem.* **323**, 1347.
7. A. Mahesh Babu, N. Sowmya, et al.,(2022) *Nucl. Sci. and Technol.* **33**, 67.

EXPERIMENTAL DETERMINATION OF WATER EQUIVALENT FACTOR OF BIOTA SAMPLES OF KAIGA ENVIRONMENT

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Introduction

The radiological dose due to tritium is assessed by considering its transfer into different environmental compartments of biological matrices. Tritium exists in biological organisms as tissue-free water tritium (TFWT) and organically bound tritium (OBT). OBT can be computed through a specific activity model (TRS-472). The OBT concentration in the plant C_{pfw}^{OBT} products at a steady state is given by the specific activity model. $C_{pfw}^{OBT} = (1 - WC_p) * WEQ_p * R_p * C_{pfw}^{HTO} / WC_p$

Where, C_{pfw}^{HTO} is the tritium concentration in plant material (fresh-weight). WC_p is the water content, R_p is the partition factor. The water equivalent factor (WEQ_p) is an essential parameter in the above expression, corresponding to the water produced per weight of combusted dry matter for OBT computation. In this paper, we report the determination of WEQ_p experimentally for the 67 biological samples collected from the Kaiga environment, where 4x220 MWe Pressurised Heavy water type reactors are operational.

Materials and Methods

A tube furnace system (pyrolyser, Raddec, UK) was used to combust the dried biota sample. The water produced from combustion was trapped in a cryocooler system, and the WEQ_p was gravimetrically quantified. The water equivalent factor was also calculated taking into account the hydrogen content of protein, fat and carbohydrate (7%, 12% and 6.2%, respectively) and the fraction of each molecule type in the dry matter of the biota matrices.

Results

The experimental values of WEQ_p, estimated for various types of leaf samples collected from the Kaiga environment, ranged

from 0.53 to 0.58 with a geometric mean (GM) value of 0.56. Whereas for fruits it ranged from 0.56 to 0.58 with a GM of 0.57. The experimental value for the vegetables ranged from 0.53 to 0.58, with a GM of 0.56. For cereals, the GM value obtained was 0.53. The WEQ_p values were calculated for each species of edible biota based on data on fat, carbohydrates and protein contents and their hydrogen content listed in Gopalan et al. (2016). This study evaluated the contents of exchangeable and non-exchangeable hydrogen (Boyer et al., 2009) in the constituents of dry matter of the biota. The number of carbonbound hydrogen atoms in the dry matter was observed to be higher than those bound to atoms other than carbon in the samples.

Conclusion

The experimentally determined WEQ_p is validated with theoretical values calculated from the hydrogen content of the dry matter. The experimentally measured values of WEQ_p were similar to the calculated values. The percentage deviation between the experimental and calculated value for WEQ_p is less than 10%.

References

Boyer C., Vichot L., Fromm M., Losset Y., Froux F., Guétat P., Badot P.M. (2009). Environ. Exp. Bot., 67, 34–51. Gopalan C., Rama Sastri B.V., Balasubramanian S.C., (2016). National Institute of Nutrition (India); Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR).

URANIUM ANALYSIS IN WATER: QUALITY ASSURANCE THROUGH IAEA-TERC PROFICIENCY TEST

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Introduction

Uranium, a naturally occurring radioactive element, is present in various geological formations and can leach into groundwater sources (Balaram *et al.*, 2022). Elevated concentrations of uranium in drinking water pose significant health risks, primarily due to its chemical toxicity and radiological effects (Jha *et al.*, 2024). Therefore, accurate measurement of uranium in groundwater is essential for environmental management and public health protection. Quality assurance involves implementing quality control measures within laboratories and participating in external quality assessment schemes. International Atomic Energy Agency, Terrestrial Environmental Radiochemistry Laboratory (IAEA-TERC) proficiency test provides a platform for laboratories worldwide to evaluate their analytical capabilities. This study presents our experience pertaining to analysis of water sample for uranium intended to be analysed by Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) which was done by LED fluorimetry as it is being used in our lab for regular analysis. Limitations of LED fluorimetry such as interference from other elements are taken care during analysis.

Materials and Methods

A water sample containing a known concentration of uranium between 0.1 - 15 ng/g was provided by the IAEA-TERC, which was a diluted drinking water from Seibersdorf, Austria. The sample was acidified to pH < 2 for stabilization. We have analyzed the sample using a LED fluorimeter (Quantalase make), following the standard operating procedure at Health Physics Unit (HPU) of NFC. The fluorescence intensity of the sample was measured and compared with a calibration curve generated using uranium standards. The uranium concentration in the sample was then calculated.

Results

Our results for uranium concentration in the water sample analyzed by LED fluorimetry are well in agreement with the reference value of IAEA-TERC obtained by using ICP-MS, a high-precision technique. The relative bias and P-Test in our analysis were -8.0% and 16.7% respectively, which are less than the acceptable value of 30% specified by TERC (IAEA, 2024). This finding highlights the potential of LED fluorimetry as a cost-effective and field-deployable alternative to ICP-MS for routine uranium analysis in water.

Conclusion

Our participation in the IAEA-TERC proficiency test exercise with acceptable results for both accuracy and precision has demonstrated the reliability of LED fluorimetry for uranium analysis in water sample. The technique offers a cost-effective and field-deployable alternative to ICP-MS, making it particularly suitable for environmental monitoring in resource-limited settings.

References

- Balaram V, Rani A, Rathore DPS (2022) *Geosyst Geoenviron* 1(2):100043.
- IAEA-TERC-2024-01 Summary Report *Terrestrial Environmental Radiochemistry Laboratory*, IAEA 2024.
- Jha, S.K., Patra, A.C., Verma, G.P. *et al.* (2024) *Environ Sci Pollut Res* **31**, 47461-47474.

IMPACT OF HEAVY METALS IN BEACH SAND ALONG EAST COAST REGION OF INDIA ON DOSE ASSESSMENT: HYBRID MODELLING APPROACH

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Keywords: soil, dose, gamma transport, heavy metal, Thorium

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Introduction

Presence of thorium and uranium in beach sands contribute to resistant heavy minerals such as monazite, zircon and xenotime which can enhance high activity concentration for the locations. In order to find out the impact of presence of heavy metals such as Fe, Si and Ti in beach sand on dose estimation, exposure due to spatial distribution of radioactivity in beach sand is computed by modeling the gamma transport in soil medium to air. The methodology employed and results obtained are discussed.

Materials and methods

The computation model assumed for dose calculation is rectangular shape geometry with a side of 80 m and 1 m depth of soil medium (Clouvas A, 2000). It is modeled using Point kernel-based Gamma Transport code. The measured concentration of elements Cr, Si, Fe, Al, Mg, Ti, Mn and Zr present in the soil at each sampling site in addition to Thorium and Uranium concentration is used for soil composition data. The air above source term has the same rectangular shape with 1 m height. The energy of photons from daughter products of U, Th decay series are considered for gamma transport.

Results

Results indicated that Annual Effective Dose (AED) values are varying with respect to concentrations of heavy metals in soil from high radiation background regions. The decrease in dose rate is attributed only to wt % of Fe in the soil medium. The mean free path of gamma for 2 MeV photons has less value of 3.01 cm for Fe. Hence, there is less attenuation for photons in high Fe content locations and dose rate at 1m from soil is exhibiting lower values. The obtained values are then compared with UNSCEAR formalism for AED

computation (UNSCEAR, 2000). The range of annual effective dose in the study region is 7.1 - 8.5 mSv. Results showed that there is a difference between Annual Effective Dose (AED) values obtained by two methods. $AED(\text{Model}) < AED(\text{UNSCEAR})$. It is mainly due to variation in concentrations of elements assumed for soil composition in earlier method (UNSCEAR) and their mean free path values in soil medium for given energy of photons.

Conclusion

The present study suggests that dose computation to human population due to activity distribution in soil in a given region strongly depend not only on concentration of U, Th and K but also the presence of Fe in the soil medium. The methodology of combining both modeling gamma transport in soil to air and measurements would give a more reliable dose value which can be further utilized for risk estimation.

References

- Clouvas A, Xanthos S, Antonopoulos -Domis M, Silva J. (2000) *Health Physics*;78:295-302.
- Saito and Jacob et al, (1995) *Radiation Protection and Dosimetry*, 58,29-45.
- UNSCEAR. 2000.

RADIOLOGICAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF A POSTULATED ACCIDENT WITH IODINE RELEASE IN AN INLAND NPP SITE

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Introduction

One of the important aspects for estimation of nuclear damages under Civil Liability for Nuclear Damage Act, 2010 is Radiological Impact Assessment (RIA) of the environment. For this purpose, RIA of Rawatbhata site, an inland site housing 6 operational Nuclear Power Plants, was carried out.

Materials and Methods

In this study, dispersion of 1000 TBq of Iodine (i.e. source term specified by AERB for notifying a nuclear incident under Civil Liability for Nuclear Damage Act) over the inland site is carried out by using the Lagrangian particle model, FLEXPART (Stohl et al., 2005). For realistic estimation, meteorological fields generated by the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF; Skamarock et al., 2008) are used.

WRF model is configured with a parent domain (18 km) and two nested domains (6km and 2km). Simulation is carried out from 00 UTC 04 to 00 UTC 07 April 2023. National Centre for Environmental Prediction (NCEP) Global Forecast System (GFS) data of resolution 0.25° is used as the initial and boundary conditions. It is assumed that release is initiated at 12:00 UTC (17:30 IST) 04 April 2023 and continued till 00 UTC (05:30 IST) 07 April 2023.

Results

WRF simulated surface winds shows drastic directional changes during the study period. The rapidly changing wind distributed the I-131 plume in all the directions causing significant radiation dose in all the sectors. Of the different exposure pathways, dose due to inhalation is the most significant and plume shine dose least significant. Highest radiation doses are observed in the ESE, NNE, SSW, SE, WSW and N sectors. The total dose

estimated due to all exposure pathways (inhalation, ground shine and plume shine dose) for the first 7 days of release shows radiation dose of ~ 5 mSv at 1.5 km from the release location in the NNE and SE. At 5 km radius radiation dose of ~ 2 mSv and at 30 km radius radiation dose of ~0.5 mSv is observed. Thyroid dose estimated shows a value of ~150 mSv at 1.5 km, ~50 mSv at 5 km and ~10 mSv at 30 km radius in the NNE and SE sectors.

Conclusion

To determine the RIA of RAPS site, dispersion and dose assessment is carried for 1000 TBq of I-131. The rapidly changing wind distributed the I-131 plume in all the directions. It is found that, thyroid dose is the most significant and doses in excess of 150 mSv and 50 mSv are noted at 1.5 km and 5 km radius respectively warranting iodine thyroid blocking. The results of this study will be used for subsequent estimation of environmental damages.

References

- Skamarock, W. C., et.al. (2008) *Tech. Note, NCAR/TN 475+STR, 125 pp., Natl. Cent. for Atmos. Res., Boulder, Colo., USA.*
- Stohl, A., et. al. (2005) *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics 5.*
- AERB Safety Directive No.1/2013.*

NATURAL RADIOACTIVITY AND DOSE FROM BUILDING MATERIALS AROUND KALPAKKAM

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Keywords: Natural radioactivity, Gamma ray spectrometry, Radium equivalent activity, External and internal hazard Index, Absorbed dose rate, Annual effective dose equivalent

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Introduction

Natural radionuclides of both terrestrial and Cosmogenic origin account for approximately 85% of an individual's annual total radiation dose). Because most people spend 80% of their time indoors, the concentration of radioelements in construction materials and their components is critical in determining population exposures. Samples (25) of various building materials like Cement, Bricks, Chips, Jelly, Manufactured construction sand, Red soil and wood were collected and analysed for determination of radioactivity and dose.

Materials and Methods

The samples were packed in 250ml PVC bottle, kept for a period of 1 month for secular equilibration, between ²²⁶Ra (U-238 series) and ²²⁸Ra (Th-232 series) and their respective short-lived progenies and counted in 100% HPGe for 85,000sec. The ²³⁸U, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K activity concentration were measured by gamma energy of ²¹⁴Pb (609 KeV, 1120 KeV) and ²¹⁴Pb (352 KeV), ²²⁸Ac (583 KeV, 911 KeV) and 1460 KeV respectively. Based on measured activity concentration of ²³⁸U(C_U), ²³²Th(C_{Th}) and ⁴⁰K (C_K) in Bq/ Kg, total absorbed dose rate in nGy/hr, total yearly effective dose in mSv/y and different radiological hazard indices such as Activity utilization index (AUI), Alpha index (I_α), Internal hazard index (H_{int}), External hazard index (H_{ext}) calculated by using standard equations used in UNSCEAR, 2002) with the full occupancy time T in year (8760 h), the conversion coefficient (F=0.7 Sv/Gy), the outdoor occupancy factor (0.2) and the indoor occupancy factor (0.8).

Results

The activity range of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K in building material samples are 7.1–57.2, 22.3–49.2 and 35.1–472.9 Bq/Kg, respectively. The calculated total absorbed dose rate due to ²³⁸U, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K series ranged from

54.65±1.09 to 141.03±1.89 nGy/hr with average of 91.5 ± 1.5 nGy/hr and corresponding total yearly effective dose is 0.49 mSv/y (S. Ramkumar, 2011). The maximum radium equivalent activity is 135.48Bq/kg with average values of 97.8 Bq/kg. Based on ²³⁸U, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K measurements, the estimated values of Activity utilization index (AUI), Alpha index (I_α), Internal hazard index (Hint), and External hazard index (Hext) are 0.66Bq/Kg, 0.092, 0.33, and 0.28, respectively

Conclusion

The world and Indian average values of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K activity concentrations in building materials are 50, 50, and 500 and 30, 40, 400 Bq/Kg respectively which is comparable with estimated average values of 17.2, 39.5, and 313.0 Bq/Kg. The total yearly effective dose due building materials at Kalpakkam is comparable with the global average value of 0.52 mSv/y. The estimated maximum radium equivalent activity in building material at Kalpakkam is below the permissible limit of ≤ 370Bq/Kg. The radiological hazard indices estimated at Kalpakkam building materials are within acceptable limits and below unity indicating materials are safe for construction use.

References

- UNSCEAR (2002)
- S Ramkumar, S Rajaram, S Venkatraman, and A G Hegde (2011) IJEP 31 (11): 898-906

NATURAL RADIOACTIVITY AND RADIATION HAZARDS INDEX LEVELS IN AGRICULTURAL SOIL AROUND KALPAKKAM

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Introduction

Natural environmental radiation originates from primordial, terrestrial and cosmogenic radioactive materials and can be mobilized or altered by human activity. In this regard, the study on naturally occurring radioactivity materials (NORM) in soils is conducted over period of time to assess total radiation received by public. In this study, the natural radioactivity activity concentration and the radiation hazards index from agricultural soils at around Kalpakkam were analyzed.

Materials and Methods

The activity concentrations of naturally occurring radionuclides ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K were determined in 12 agricultural soil samples randomly collected around Kalpakkam villages, from fertile soil at depth of 5cm. Agricultural soils are more dynamic and disturbed due to crop cultivation. The samples were packed in 250ml PVC bottle and kept sealed for a period of 1 month for secular equilibrium. Samples were counted in 100% HPGe for 85,000sec. ²³⁸U, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K activities were measured by using a gamma energy of ²¹⁴Pb (609 KeV, 1120 KeV) ²¹⁴Pb (352 KeV), ²²⁸Ac (583 KeV, 911 KeV) and 1460 KeV. Based on measured activity concentration of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K activities the Radiological Hazard indices estimated with the full occupancy time T in year (8760 h), the conversion coefficient (F=0.7 Sv/Gy), the outdoor occupancy factor(0.2) and the indoor occupancy factor(0.8).

Results

The activity concentration of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K ranged in agricultural soils 0.33 -28.34, 0.39 – 70.8, 2.92 – 583.1 and mean values of 8.5, 38.1, and 205.3 Bq/Kg respectively. The estimated values of radium equivalent activity (Raeq), absorbed dose rates (nGy/ h), annual effective dose equivalent, and external hazard index (Hex) are 78.7Bq/Kg, 35.4nGy/h,

0.04mSv/y and 0.2 respectively in agricultural soils.

Conclusion

The average values of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K in agricultural soils are less than global average values of 33, 45, 420Bq/Kg, respectively and could be due to various interlinked reasons like parent rocks, climate, soil type, movement through surface drainage system etc. The lower values of Uranium at Kalpakkam coastal site could be due to higher mobility of uranium as UO₂⁺² in water as compared to Thorium. The radium equivalent activity measured for agricultural soils were less than the recommended value of ≤370Bq/Kg. The total yearly effective dosage due to ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K series for agricultural soil is less than global average of 0.52mSv/y.

References

Ghazwa Alzubaidi, Fauziah B.*et al* (2016), The Scientific World Journal, Article ID 6178103

Laura Guidotti, Franca Carini, Riccardo Rossi, Marina Gatti, Roberto M. Cenci, Gian Maria Beone, (2015), Journal of Environmental Radioactivity 142

RADIATION STUDIES IN DEPTH PROFILE SOIL SAMPLE OF BIDAR, KARNATAKA, INDIA.

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Keywords: Activity concentration; Depth –profile; NaI (TI) gamma-ray spectrometry; Radionuclide's; Soil.

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Introduction

In most regions of the world, natural radiation from external sources raises the radiated value; however, in other places, the variance is mostly caused by unusually high or low soil radioactive element levels. Humans are exposed to both internal radiations from radionuclides that are ingested by the body and external natural rays from cosmic rays and radionuclides that are present on the Earth. In gamma-ray spectroscopy, a 4" x 4" NaI (TI) Scintillating Detector is an essential instruments that combine's thallium-doped sodium iodide crystal. The detector is shield with three inch lead on all sides so as to minimize the surrounding radiations entering into the detector the size of the crystal affect its sensitivity and detecting capabilities and it is shield from atmospheric radiation by a lead barrier 1K MCA (Scienti SPEC) was used to examine the spectrum for 60,000 seconds.

Materials and Methods

The study uses a laboratory setting to analyze the soil characteristics of five talukas in the Bidar districts. At depths of 20 to 200 feet, ten samples containing two to three kilograms were taken. After being crushed, sieved, the materials were placed in a container covered with Araldite. The distribution of the depth profile of radionuclides that are naturally occurring of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K samples that were gathered from five talukas in the Bidar district of Karnataka, has been investigated using the following gamma energy for ²³⁸U 1764 keV, ²³²Th 2614 keV and 1460 keV for ⁴⁰K^{1,2}. Determining the extent of radioactive variation concerning the depth profile is the main goal of this investigation.

Results

The estimated depth profile values of activity values for ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K from the borewell samples collected from Bidar, are in the range from 12.2±0.15 to 22.0±0.16

Bqkg⁻¹, 28.6±0.10 to 34.2±0.11 Bqkg⁻¹ and 103.9±4.6 to 208.1±4.18 Bqkg⁻¹ respectively. The estimated depth profile activity values for the ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K found to be more or less shows within 5% range. The correlation graph between uranium and thorium found to be good since there is no leaching out of uranium.

Conclusion

In the present study the author has estimated the depth profile activity concentration of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K and its variation in the range of 20 feet to 200 feet and found the good activity correlation between ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, in the Bidar sample. This work is continued to estimate other talukas of Bidar district samples.

References

1. Nagaraju KM, Chandrashekara MS, Pruthvi Rani KS, Rajesh BM, Paramesh L. Radioactivity measurements in the environment of Chamaraja Nagar area, India. Radiat Prot Environ 2013; 36:103.
2. B R Kerur, T Rajeshwari, N M Nagabhushana, S Anil kumar, K Narayani A K Rekha and B Hanumaiah (2011) Natural radioactivity levels in some environmental samples of North Karnataka Radiation protection and Environment, Page no.810-812.

ASSESSMENT OF GRAB RADIOLOGICAL CONDITION AROUND WASTE CONTAINMENT SYSTEM OF URANIUM PROCESSING FACILITY AT JADUGUDA, INDIA

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Keywords: Tailings pond, Radon, Gamma.

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Introduction

Large quantity of processed fine fraction solid waste tailings is discharged into a stable natural impoundment with site specific engineered control measures and surveillance systems. Due to the presence of residual quantity of uranium daughter products etc. The main radionuclide of concern in waste tailings material from radiological significance is ²²⁶Ra. That is the source of gaseous ²²²Rn which continuously diffuse in to the open atmosphere and may become potential source of inhalation exposure to the residents living in the immediate vicinity. Present paper summarizes the study of atmospheric ²²²Rn & environmental gamma level along the periphery of the tailings confinement system.

Materials and Methods

Radiological monitoring has been carried out all along the tailings pond at the Eastern bund, Western bund, NW Bund, Northern Bund, Southern Bund and NE Bund throughout the year using pre-calibrated Radon Monitor Alpha Guard of 0.62 litre pulse ionization chamber detector. Gamma radiation level was measured at one meter above the ground level using pre calibrated 1" × 1"NaI(Tl) gamma spectroscopic based Isotope Identifier. Few measurements were carried out at locations away from the waste containment system.

Results & Discussion

Measurement was conducted in 2024 on a quarterly basis, with four measurements taken per quarter at each location. The results for atmospheric ²²²Rn concentration and gamma radiation levels for the containment area observed were in the range in Eastern bund 52– 92,

Western bund 47–96, NW Bund 40– 80, Northern Bund 42–66, Southern Bund 45– 68, NE Bund 37-54 Bq m⁻³. The mean ²²²Rn concentration and gamma radiation levels were used to estimate the inhalation dose and external dose to members of the public. The table shows that the average ²²²Rn concentration across the Waste Containment System ranged from 37 to 96 Bq/m³, with an overall average of 60 ± 10 Bq/m³. The external gamma radiation level around the periphery ranged from 0.06 to 0.82 µGy/h, with an average of 0.22 ± 0.12 µGy/h. Corresponding values at places few 100 m away ranged from 21 to 35 Bq.m⁻³ and 0.05 to 0.06 µGy.h⁻¹

Conclusion

Due to significant atmospheric dilution, the ²²²Rn concentration exhibits a lower background level in the Singhbhum region, which closely aligns with previously reported results [1]. This may be also due to variation of meteorological parameters and seasonal conditions in the region. The impact of mining and milling Industry is not significant as revealed in this study.

References

1. Annual appraisal report on radiation monitoring program in and around uranium mining and ore processing facilities at Jaduguda, Singhbhum (E), Jharkhand Annual report -2023, BARC/2024/I/011.

CHARGED AEROSOL DYNAMICS BEHAVIOUR FOR IMPROVING THE FAST REACTOR SAFETY ASSESSMENT DURING SEVERE ACCIDENT: MODELLING ASPECTS

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Introduction

During severe accident conditions of nuclear reactor, radioactive aerosols are suspended inside the containment and constitute the environmental source term due to leakage. These aerosols vary in size range, and are porous non-spherical. Further, they are charged by i) self-charging due to radioactive material decay; and ii) diffusion charging with the bipolar ion field created by radiation. Apart from particle size, morphology & charge properties affect the suspended aerosol concentration decay and to be considered for the evaluation of the source term and impact assessment. A polydisperse aerosol dynamics model developed initially for chargeless particles & validated with the measured behavior of polydisperse standard spherical PAO aerosol & non-spherical porous sodium and fission product aerosols envisaged in sodium cooled fast reactor (Pujala *et al* 2023a). Further, experiments were carried out to measure the change in aerosol dynamics of externally charged PAO aerosols with bipolar and unipolar ions with various charge levels (Pujala *et al* 2023b). This work is to develop and validate a charged aerosol dynamics model for Asymmetric Bipolar Charged (ABC) and Unipolar Charged (UC) aerosols. Charged PAO aerosol dynamics data is used for validation, as the tests with radioactive aerosols are complex, and morphology affects the charge properties.

Materials and Methods

The simplified aerosol dynamics equation is $\frac{dN}{dt} = -fK_0N^2 - (\beta_0 + \beta_e)N$. N is aerosol number concentration. K_0 and β_0 are the parameters of chargeless aerosol (baseline condition BC). K_0 is the coagulation rate due to Brownian, gravitational, and turbulent mechanisms. β_0 is the deposition rate due to gravitational settling, diffusion, and thermophoresis ($\beta_0 = \beta_t + \beta_g + \beta_d$). f is the coagulation correction factor for charged aerosol depends on inter-particle potential. β_e is the additional deposition rate due to the charge. In

ABC condition, the exposure to bipolar ion fields with unequal negative and positive ion properties causes a certain net charge (j_{av}). In UC condition, all particles get charged with same polarity and the net charge levels (j) are more than ABC. The sum of electrostatic, image, and Van der Waal potentials are considered to estimate the factor f (Mick *et al* 1991). For ABC aerosol, f is obtained by averaging the electrostatic attraction and repulsion forces between the particles (Harrison, 1992). For UC aerosol, f is considered from the repulsion forces between the particles. Particles drifting to the surface due to space charge field; and increase in surface attachment of particles by image force ($\beta_e = \beta_{ed} + \beta_{ei}$) are considered.

Conclusion

Simulations carried out for five cases with same concentration $1.3 \times 10^{12}/m^3$ but different charge levels: BC aerosol with $j_{av} = 0$; ABC aerosols with j_{av} of 1.25 and 1.87; UC aerosols with j of -3.4 and 4.2. The concentration decays of both ABC and UC aerosols are enhanced compared to BC and the extent of change is increased with the net charge level. Size growth of UC aerosol is reduced compared to BC and matched with the measured behavior within 20%. Simulated size growth of ABC aerosols is increased by 15% compared to BC, but measurements show no observable change in size growth. The model to be extended to address the radioactive aerosol charge properties and behavior.

References

- Pujala, U., et al. (2023a), *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, 163, 104811.
- Pujala, U., et al. (2023b), *Proc. AOCR6 Conference, AOCR2023, Mumbai*.
- Mick, H.J., Hospital, A., and Roth, P., (1991). *Journal of Aerosol Science*, 22 (7), 831–841.
- Harrison, R.G. (1992). *PhD Diss.* University of London.

VARIATION IN CEC WITH DIFFERENT FRACTIONS OF SEDIMENT IN TARAPUR

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Introduction

Sediment is the ultimate repository of radionuclides and other pollutants discharged into the coastal sea. Besides activities related to nuclear facilities, sediment also stores various traces and toxic metals, and radionuclides occurring naturally and due to fallout. These can reach humans through the aquatic food chain pathway. The cations which can be easily migrated by sediment are measured by CEC. It represents the amount of negative charge in sediment existing on the surface of clay and organic matter. This study aims to find the CEC of the sediment samples from Tarapur coast and its variation with different particle size fractions.

Materials and Methods

A total of 10 sediment samples from different locations along Tarapur coast were collected from the intertidal region during the low tide. They were sieved using mesh sizes 300 μ m, 210 μ m, 106 μ m, and 63 μ m using wet sieving method. Each fraction was dried, weighed and CEC was analyzed using AAS spectrophotometer (Make: GBC SavantAA). Sediment texture was determined in each fraction of a specimen sediment sample using the hydrometer method.

Results

The CEC was determined in each fraction of the sediment i.e. 300-210 μ m, 210-106 μ m, 106-63 μ m and <63 μ m of the sediment samples subjected to the study. The CEC of sediment in different particle sizes varied from 92.7 to 181 meq/100g and the overall mean CEC in 10 different samples varied from 116 \pm 7.0 to 164 \pm 13.4 meq/100g. This indicates that there is not much variation in the CEC values with different particle size fractions of the sediment samples. Shafie *et al* (2013) have compared the CEC in different mineral composites of sediment and reported that the CEC is depended on the mineral composition

of the sediment and the highest CEC value of 200 meq/100g was found in Vermiculite [1]. From the sediment texture analysis, it is found that sand content varied from 48 to 62%, clay content varied from 12 to 24% and silt content varied from 14 to 38%. Kubal *et al* (2016) also have reported the sediment texture around Tarapur site, dominated by sand followed by silt and clay [2]. The result of the present study on soil texture is in agreement with the previous studies carried out at Tarapur site. Also, in the study on texture for different particle sizes, the clay content was found highest in the lowest particle size fraction i.e. <63 μ m and silt was found highest in the high particle size fraction. A slightly high CEC in the last two fractions may be due to high clay content. Sulieman *et al* (2018) have also reported that the CEC has been significantly influenced (positively) by the clay content [3].

Conclusion

The analysis of CEC in different fractions of sediment samples does not indicate an appreciable variation among different particle sizes. The study on texture analysis shows that the variation in percentage sand, clay and silt content is in consistent with the earlier studies carried out at Tarapur.

References

1. Shafie, N.A., Aris, A.Z. and Puad. N.H.A. (2013) *Arab. J. Geosci* **6**, 3049–3058.
2. Kubal, P., Ambekar, A., Prakash, C., Sawant, P.B., Pal, A.K. and Lakra, W.S. (2016) *J. Mar. Res.* **4(2)**, 1-11.
3. Sulieman, M.M., Saeed, I., Hassaballa, A. and Rodrigo-Comino, J. (2018) *Catena*, **167**, 327-339.

FEASIBILITY STUDY OF BRICKS MADE BY USING URANIUM MILL TAILINGS FROM TUMMALAPALLE

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Introduction

Uranium ore in India is of low-grade so when processed, almost all processed ore emerges as waste or 'tailings'. The high-volume low activity tailings are stored in the tailings pond. Disposal and management of tailings requires a large surface area for long-term impoundment in an engineered, designed tailings repository and regular environmental monitoring around the tailings disposal site. Hence management of radioactive U bearing tailing including handling, transport and disposal is a major task. In the view of the above efforts are being made in utilization of tailings in making building materials. In this study, Uranium mill tailings from Tummalapalle site was used making bricks.

Materials and Methods

The major ingredients of brick are silica, alumina, iron oxide, magnesia, lime, and organic Matter. However, the components may vary based on the method and raw materials used. For the preparation of bricks tailings were collected from Tummalapalle tailings pond and air dried for one week. The bricks of dimensions 230mm (L) × 100 mm (W) × 75 mm (H) were prepared via pressing method. Six batches of bricks were made with mill tailings contents in the range 10–30%, with other components such as gypsum, cement, stone chips and fly ash.

Results

Compressive strength and water absorption capacity were tested as per the Bureau of Indian Standards. Compressive strength test was carried out to determine the load carrying capacity of bricks under compression with the help of compression testing machine. Three bricks from each lot were tested by placing the bricks between the plates of the testing machine. The axial load was applied at a uniform rate of 14 N/mm² per minute till failure, and the maximum load at failure was noted. The compressive strengths of the bricks varied in the range of 8.6 – 15.0 MPa

for all six batches. The compressive strength of fly ash brick available in local market was tested and found to be 8.8 MPa.

To determine the water absorption capacity, dried brick specimens were immersed in clean water at room temperature after noting the initial weight. After 24 hours, the specimen was removed from the water and water over the brick was wiped from the external surfaces with a clean cloth. The final weight of the brick specimen was recorded immediately after removing it from the water, and the percentage water absorption was calculated. The water absorption capacity for the bricks found out to be in the range of 8-16 %.

Conclusion

All 6 batches of bricks have qualified for the minimum requirement of compressive strength (3.5 N/mm²) (BIS, 1992). The compressive strength of bricks was found to increase with increase in mill tailings composition. In water absorption test on the brick specimens all the batches have qualified for the minimum requirement of water absorption within the BIS limit ($\leq 20\%$) (BIS, 1992).

References

IAEA (International Atomic Energy Agency), The Long Term stabilization of Uranium Mill Tailings – IAEA TECDOC-1403, (2004) Vienna.

Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS), Methods of tests of burnt clay building bricks, 3495 (1992) 1–4.

INFLUENCE OF GAMMA IRRADIATION ON ELECTRICAL AND ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF LITHIUM ALUMINUM BORATE GLASSES DOPED WITH TERBIUM TRIOXIDE

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Key words: Borate glass; Gama irradiation; Impedance spectroscopy; Thermal properties.

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Introduction

Glassy materials have been employed recently in lasers, optical fiber, optoelectronic devices, optical sensor devices, and lighting devices like LEDs. The most often utilized type of glasses in a various fields are borate glasses. Specifically, borate glasses have many advantages, including inexpensive cost, low melting point, great thermal stability, outstanding transparency and sensitivity, and ease of manufacture and form. Amphoteric oxide Al_2O_3 has been added to borate glass in the current assignment because to improve this glass's opacity, melting point and chemical resistance In addition to amphoteric oxide, alkali oxide such as Li_2O added to the glass matrix which magnify the optical properties, thermal properties and radiation shielding. By incorporating rare-earth ions in to glasses to improve their properties and make them appropriate for a variety of uses, including phosphors, radiation dosimetry, magneto-optical devices, and opto-electronic devices.

Materials and methods

The traditional melt-quench technique is used to prepare glasses using analar grade chemicals. This work aims to investigate the electrical and elastic characteristics of pure and doped lithium borate glasses with varying Tb_2O_3 concentrations both before and after gamma irradiation up to 20kGy. Investigations were conducted into how gamma radiation affected the electrical conductivity, and elastic properties of synthesized glass matrix.

Results and discussion

XRD profiles confirms the non-crystallization nature of prepared samples. In order to comprehend the dielectric

characteristics of the glass matrix in the frequency range between 50 Hz and 1 MHz, the electric modulus, relaxation mechanism, and conductivity parameters were examined which shows the findings are promise for application in semiconducting devices. The Makishima and Mackenzie approach was employed to predict the theoretical elastic characteristics. The rise in elastic moduli values with the addition of Tb^{3+} ions , even following Gamma ray irradiation, indicates that an enhancement in the elastic properties of the materials.

Conclusions

This study suggests that increased non-bridging oxygen and an increase in defects are produced inside the glass structure after irradiation. Due to decrease in conductivity after gamma irradiation shows these glass samples may be used as high efficient for radiation shielding materials, electrochemical devises, and optical lenses.

References

1. M.H.A.Mhareb, Ceram. Int. 49 (2023) 36950–36961 (2023).
2. Evangelina C. Cardillo, Marisa A. Frechero, Optical Materials 149 114878 (2024).

AN UPDATE ON CARBON-14 RELEASE RATE FROM KAIGA GENERATING STATION

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Introduction

Carbon-14 (¹⁴C), a pure beta emitter with a half-life of 5730 ± 40 years, is naturally produced in the atmosphere through cosmic ray interactions, primarily via the ¹⁴N(n, p)¹⁴C reaction (Libby et al., 1945). The natural specific activity of ¹⁴C in atmospheric CO₂ is approximately 226 ± 1.1 Bq kg⁻¹C. Anthropogenic sources of ¹⁴C in the environment are (i) nuclear weapon tests in the 1950s and 1960s, which affected the global inventory of this radioisotope, and (ii) releases into the atmosphere through gaseous discharges from nuclear fuel cycle facilities and nuclear power plants (NPPs), which affects the inventory locally. The airborne ¹⁴C release rate from the Kaiga PHWR NPP for the year 2017-2020 was reported in our previous publication (Bharath et al., 2022). This paper augments the previously published database on the ¹⁴C release rate with additional data for the year 2022.

Materials and Methods

The methodology for the sample collection and the processing were presented in our previous publication (Bharath et al., 2022). In brief, the gaseous effluent samples were collected from the common stack of reactor units 3 & 4 of Kaiga NPP through a set of three bubblers connected in series. The first bubbler with 100 mL of 1M HNO₃ was used to trap the tritium from the sampled gaseous effluents, and the next two bubblers, each containing 100 mL of freshly prepared 2M ultra-pure NaOH solution, were for trapping the oxide form of CO₂ species. The sampling duration was 24 h at a flow rate of 1 L min⁻¹.

The ambient air in the vicinity of the NPP was sampled by drawing air through a set of two gas wash bottles containing 100 ml each of freshly prepared 2 M ultra-pure

NaOH solution for 24 h at a flow rate of 2 L min⁻¹.

After sampling, BaCl₂ was added to the sample solution (gaseous effluent and ambient air samples), and BaCO₃ was precipitated. The BaCO₃ was taken in a specially designed CO₂ regeneration apparatus, and the evolved CO₂ was reabsorbed in a 10 ml + 10 ml mixture of CarbosorbE and Perma-flour scintillator (Bharath et al., 2022). The mixture was then subjected to liquid scintillation spectrometric analysis to determine ¹⁴C activity. From the specific activity value, the release rate was computed (Bharath et al., 2022)

Results

The normalized release rate for the year 2022 varied in the range of 0.072 - 0.226 TBq GWe⁻¹a⁻¹. These values are similar to those of the previous years, 2017 - 2019. The normalized release rate from Kaiga NPP for the year 2022 is similar to those reported by other PHWR NPPs of the world.

The atmospheric ¹⁴C specific activity at a distance 2.3 km from the NPP varied in the range of 235 - 259 Bq kg⁻¹C with a mean value of 244.2 ± 9.8 Bq kg⁻¹C. The excess activity was evaluated by comparing the specific activity recorded for the clean air region. The Maximum ¹⁴C excess activity recorded was 30 Bq kg⁻¹C.

References

1. Libby, (1945), Phys. Rev., 69,679-672.
2. Bharath, Krishnan, K.A., D'Souza, R.S., Nayak, S.R., Dileep, B.N., Ravi, P.M., Mangavi, S.S., Salunke, G.S., Veerendra, D. and Karunakara, N., 2022. Journal of Environmental Radioactivity, 255, p.107006.

RADIOACTIVE WASTE MANAGEMENT TECHNIQUES: CHALLENGES AND INNOVATIONS

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Introduction

Radioactive isotopes are crucial in modern medicine, particularly in diagnostics and therapeutics. Iodine-131 (¹³¹I), a widely used radioisotope, finds applications in thyroid imaging, thyroid cancer treatment, hyperthyroidism management, and diagnosing liver, renal, and urinary conditions. However, the environmental and health risks posed by residual radioactivity necessitate effective waste management strategies. This paper reviews conventional and advanced methods of managing radioactive waste, explicitly focusing on ¹³¹I, and proposes an innovative technique to mitigate associated challenges.

Environmental Risks of ¹³¹I

While ¹³¹I therapy effectively treats thyroid-related disorders, its usage leads to contamination risks. Patients undergoing ¹³¹I therapy excrete residual radioactivity through urine and other biological waste, which can contaminate sewage systems. Furthermore, if inadequately managed, medical instruments, vials, syringes, and other materials used during treatment may also retain ¹³¹I, posing threats to water bodies, soil, and the food chain. These risks underscore the urgent need for robust waste management strategies to prevent environmental contamination and human exposure.

Conventional Waste Management Approaches

Two primary methods are used in nuclear medicine facilities to manage ¹³¹I waste: the delay-and-decay and dilute-and-disperse approaches. The first approach, while effective, presents logistical, hygienic, and radiation hazard challenges due to potential leaks in storage tanks and

pipelines. The second approach, in which the waste is diluted to permissible levels before releasing it into the environment, carries the risk of unmonitored exposures, potentially affecting human health and ecosystems. Given the limitations of these methods in handling radioactive waste in medical installations, there is a need for advanced and sustainable alternatives.

Proposed Advanced Filtration Method

The present work has developed an innovative filtration system using polymer composites coated with halide-based sorbent agents^{1,2}. The polymer-based filtration system efficiently captures and isolates ¹³¹I from biological and liquid waste with over 90% effectiveness. It adsorbs and retains the ¹³¹I within the filtration medium, preventing its release into the environment. These filters are compatible with existing effluent transport systems, requiring minimal structural modifications. Since ¹³¹I is removed from the effluents in the filter system with high efficiency, it alleviates the need for storage tanks for the long-term storage of radioactive urine and other biological waste. Installation of such filters reduces operational costs, making them a viable solution for healthcare facilities.

References

1. Riley BJ et al. Materials and processes for the effective capture and immobilization of radioiodine: A review. *Journal of Nuclear Materials*, 2016.
2. Sakuragi T et al. Immobilization of radioactive iodine using AgI vitrification technique for TRU waste disposal. *MRS Online Proceedings Library*, 2008.

THERMOLUMINESCENCE STUDY OF CO-60 GAMMA IRRADIATED KMgCl_3 NANOMATERIAL FOR RADIATION DOSIMETRY

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Introduction

Potassium Magnesium Trichloride (KMgCl_3) is a good luminescent material which is synthesized using solid state diffusion method [1] resulting in a highly crystalline and thermally stable product.

Materials and Methods

The synthesized sample is characterized by powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique to confirm its orthorhombic crystal structure and the average crystallite size is found to be 66 nm calculated using Debye-Scherrer formula.

Results

The energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) studies confirmed the elemental composition with K-23%, Mg-22% and Cl-52%. The field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) image of the synthesized sample shows agglomerated nanoparticles. The sample is irradiated by Co-60 gamma radiation with different doses such as 0.5, 1, 4, 7, 10 kGy. The thermoluminescence (TL) reader is used to characterize the synthesized nanomaterial after gamma irradiation. The dose response is linear upto 10 kGy. The sample irradiated with 1 kGy is characterized up to 570 K at variable heating rates of 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 K/s. The thermoluminescence glow curve obtained by heating the sample at a heating rate of 2 K/s shows two peaks at 393 K and 475 K. This glow curve is deconvoluted using computerized glow curve deconvolution (CGCD) method [2] which shows five different peaks at 389.5 K, 440.2 K, 464.7 K, 504.1 K and 638.9 K with trap depths 1.04 eV, 1.06 eV, 1.25 eV, 1.01 eV and 1.73 eV respectively. The obtained frequency factors are in the range of 10^{10} to 10^{12} s^{-1} and the glow curve follows general order

kinetics. The minimum measurable dose is found to be in the order of 1 Gy.

Conclusion

The obtained kinetic parameters confirm that the synthesized nanomaterial is suitable for high dose dosimetry application.

References:

1. Poddar, Anuradha, S. C. Gedam and S. J. Dhoble. "Synthesis of KMgCl_3 nanomaterial and luminescence of $\text{Ce}^{3+}/\text{Dy}^{3+}/\text{Eu}^{3+}$ by different routes." *Journal of Luminescence* 158 (2015): 188-196.
2. D. Afouxenidis, G.S. Polymeris, N.C. Tsirliganis and G. Kitis, *Radiation Protection Dosimetry*, 149(4), (2012),363-70.

THERMOLUMINESCENCE STUDIES OF SrO-CAO NANOCOMPOSITE FOR DOSIMETRY APPLICATIONS

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Introduction

Thermoluminescence studies of SrO-CaO nanocomposite for Dosimetry applications have been conducted. It is the first time, that thermoluminescence property of SrO-CaO nanocomposite has been studied systematically.

Material and Methods

The SrO-CaO nanocomposite is synthesized by the solution combustion method using citric acid as a fuel. The structural analysis using X-ray diffraction (XRD) confirmed the formation of a crystalline structure with the sharp peaks and the particle size is estimated from the XRD. The bandgap energy of SrO-CaO nanocomposite is determined by UV-Vis spectroscopy and found to be 3.82 eV. The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy-dispersive X-ray analysis (EDAX) provide detailed insights into the nanocomposite's morphology and elemental composition.

Results

Thermoluminescence (TL) studies were done by exposing the samples to Co-60 gamma radiation with the different doses such as 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 Gy. The dose response is linear in this range and the TL glow curves displayed a prominent peak around 384.69 K. The minimum measurable dose of the SrO-CaO nanocomposite is found to be 0.25 Gy. The kinetic parameters were determined with the computerized glow curve deconvolution (CGCD) method which shows seven different peaks at 391.4 K, 353.6 K, 385.2 K, 425.6 K, 487.2 K, 539 K, and 628.7 K with trap depths ranging from 1 eV to 1.007 eV. The obtained frequency factors are in the range of 10^8 to 10^{13} s⁻¹. The glow curve follows general order kinetics.

Conclusion

The synthesized SrO-CaO nanocomposite is a promising candidate for environmental dosimetry applications in the range of 0.25 Gy to 100 Gy radiation dose.

References:

Prakash, D., & Nagabhushana, K. R. (2016). Thermoluminescence properties of gamma irradiated CaO: Sm³⁺ phosphor. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 379, 136-140.

Baitha, Pankaj Kr, Partha P. Pal, and J. Manam. "Dosimetric sensing and optical properties of ZnO–SnO₂ nanocomposites synthesized by co-precipitation method." *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* 745 (2014): 91-98.

STUDY OF CONTINUOUS BEHAVIOR OF ^{222}Rn PROGENY AND AEROSOL SIZE FRACTIONS IN THE INDOOR AIR

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Introduction

^{222}Rn and its progeny are recognized as important contributors to natural radiation exposure in human habitats. The behavior of ^{222}Rn progeny fractions is affected by various environmental parameters including aerosol size and density, which vary spatially and temporally across indoor and outdoor settings (Porstendorfer, 1994). In this study the influence of aerosol size fractions on the distribution of ^{222}Rn progeny in the indoor air was investigated through the continuous monitoring of both ^{222}Rn progeny and the particulate matter concentrations. While large number of studies have been reported on ^{222}Rn gas concentration in the indoor and outdoor air, studies aimed at understanding the dependence of ^{222}Rn progeny with particulate matter concentration are very limited (Karunakara et al., 2005; Stojanovska et al., 2020).

Materials and Methods

Continuous monitoring of ^{222}Rn and progeny concentrations, and the particulate matter size fractions were measured in the indoor air. ^{222}Rn gas concentrations were measured using the ionization chamber based AlphaGuard (PQ2000PRO, Genitron, Germany), whereas the dual channel ^{222}Rn progeny monitor (BWLM-PLUS-2S, TRACERLAB, Germany) was used to monitor the progeny concentration. Monitoring of particulate matter was performed using continuous aerosol monitor (APT-MAXIMA, Applied Particle Technology, USA).

Results

The indoor concentration of ^{222}Rn gas ranged from $21\pm 9 \text{ Bq m}^{-3}$ to $137\pm 21 \text{ Bq m}^{-3}$, averaging $59\pm 14 \text{ Bq m}^{-3}$. While ^{222}Rn

progeny concentrations ranged from $1\pm 0.1 \text{ Bq m}^{-3}$ to $20\pm 0.6 \text{ Bq m}^{-3}$, with a mean of $6\pm 0.3 \text{ Bq m}^{-3}$. Aerosol mass densities varied between $20 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and $112 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, with PM_{10} concentration ranging from $20 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ to $65 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration from $27 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ to $104 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, and PM_{10} concentration from $30 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ to $112 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. Continuous monitoring revealed similar trends between ^{222}Rn progeny and particulate matter concentrations. The progeny concentration increased and decreased proportionally with aerosol concentration spikes and drops, respectively.

Temporal variations were observed with progeny concentrations peaking during late night and early morning hour, correlating with elevated aerosol levels ($\text{PM}_{10\text{max}} = 65 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$; $\text{PM}_{2.5\text{max}} = 104 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$; and $\text{PM}_{10\text{max}} = 112 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), and reaching minimum values during the daytime ($\text{PM}_{10\text{min}} = 20 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$; $\text{PM}_{2.5\text{min}} = 27 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$; and $\text{PM}_{10\text{min}} = 30 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), particularly around noon.

Conclusion

The indoor ^{222}Rn progeny concentration exhibited a strong dependence on particulate matter concentration and with the ambient environmental parameters.

Reference

1. Porstendorfer, J. (1994). Journal of Aerosol Science 25(2), 219-263.
2. Karunakara, N., Somashekarappa, H. M. and Siddappa, K. (2005). International Congress Series 1276, 342-343.
3. Stojanovska, Z., Kolarž, P. and Žunić, Z. S. (2020). Contemporary Materials 11(1), 14-19.

THERMOLUMINESCENCE PROPERTIES OF IRON DOPED TiO₂ NANOPARTICLES SYNTHESIZED USING CO-PRECIPIATION METHOD FOR GAMMA DOSIMETRY

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Keywords: thermoluminescence, dosimetry, glow curve, radiation, annealing.

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Introduction

Radiation dosimetry is the measure of the absorbed dose of radiation. Thermoluminescence (TL) is a regular and standard technique of measuring ionizing and non-ionizing radiations (Azorin, 2007) in dosimetry that also provides details about the mechanism, trapped charges, energy transfer, and recombination processes in a crystalline lattice emerging in light emission.

Materials and Methods

Iron doped TiO₂ nanoparticles were prepared by chemical co-precipitation method by using titanium tetrachloride (TiCl₄), sodium hydroxide (NaOH) as precursors and Ferric Chloride (FeCl₃) as a dopant. The two chemicals TiCl₄ and NaOH were mixed in 1:4 mole ratio and 1.0% of FeCl₃ was added at room temperature. The white precipitate acquired was subjected to centrifugation, filtering, and washing many times with distilled water. The end product was subjected to sintering at 110 °C until it was thoroughly dried. The obtained products were further annealed at two different temperatures namely, 723 K and 1073 K. The nanoparticles obtained were named as TF₁ (TiO₂: Fe annealed at 723 K) and TF₂ (TiO₂: Fe annealed at 1073 K).

Results

Powder XRD spectrum of annealed TiO₂: Fe showed the existence of brookite crystalline phase and rutile crystalline phase. FESEM morphology of TiO₂:Fe powder shows primarily polycrystalline structure constituted by nanoparticles which include rutile and brookite phases of TiO₂, with grain sizes in the order of

nanometers. Thermoluminescence analysis of TF₁ and TF₂ exhibits TL intensity least for 10 Gy and highest for 10 kGy, out of the studied doses. The TL intensity of the glow curves related to TF₁ and TF₂ gradually increased up to 10 kGy and showed a sudden decrease for higher dose (25 kGy). The range is linear from 100 Gy up to 10 kGy it has been observed that the sensitivity is higher in the case of sample TF₂ than TF₁.

Conclusion

The 1.0 % Cu doped TiO₂ nanoparticles were prepared by co-precipitation technique. Formation of nanocrystalline structure was confirmed using powder XRD analysis. The FESEM analysis confirmed the presence of polycrystalline structure with irregular morphology. The 1% Fe doped sample showed the highest TL intensity and deeper traps. Hence, the sample was selected for dose response studies. The highest dose response for 1 % TiO₂: Fe was observed to be at 10 kGy for both 723 K (TF₁) and 1073 K (TF₂) heat treatments. A good linear TL response of the heat-treated samples was observed between 100 Gy to 10 kGy of gamma irradiation dose showing good sensitivity.

References

- Azorín-vega, J. C., Azorín-nieto, J., García-hipólito, M. and Rivera-montalvo, T. (2007) Radiation. Measures. **42**, 613–616.
- Sharmila, K., Kamat, V. A., Swaroop, K., and Somashekarappa, H. M. (2019) *Proc. AIP Conference, AIP (2019), Mangalore.*

RADIOLABELLING OF ANTI-C-REACTIVE PROTEIN ANTIBODIES FOR IMMUNORADIOMETRIC ASSAY DEVELOPMENT

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Keywords: C-reactive protein, Immunoradiometric assay, Radiolabelling, Chloramine-T.

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Introduction

C-reactive protein (CRP) has emerged as a cardiovascular disease marker for early prediction of cardiac diseases (Ridkar, 2003). The present work reports the preparation of a radiotracer to develop an Immunoradiometric assay (IRMA) procedure to quantify human CRP. Immunoassays are used to measure trace concentrations of hormones/proteins. In IRMA, iodine radioisotope (¹²⁵I), which has a half-life of 60 days, is labelled to tyrosine/histidine residues of antibody, and this labelled antibody is used as a radiotracer (Yalow and Berson, 1960).

Materials and Methods

The paired anti-CRP monoclonal antibodies and the highly purified CRP for standards preparation were procured from Sigma. Radiolabelling was initiated by adding 20 µg of anti-CRP monoclonal antibodies with isotope Na-¹²⁵I, 225 µCi in the presence of oxidized chloramine-T (10 mg/ml) (Hunter and Greenwood, 1962) method. This reaction mixture was incubated for 60 seconds; the oxidation reaction was terminated by adding metabisulphite (10mg/ml) and potassium iodide (50 mg/ml). The reaction mixture was immediately added to the Sephadex G-75 column chromatography for the separation of labelled and unlabelled reactants. Two peaks were observed, in the collected eluant the highest peak was labelled anti-CRP Monoclonal antibodies with ¹²⁵I and the other peak was of free iodide. The paper electrophoresis was performed to calculate the specific activity of the radiolabeled tracer.

Results

The Characterization of the labelled antibodies was performed, and the radioiodination yield was 74.70%. The results showed that the % radiolabeled purity of labelled anti-CRP monoclonal antibodies was 87%. These labelled anti-CRP monoclonal antibodies were used for the development of IRMA.

Conclusion

The radioiodination yield and radiochemical purity were high and the labelling procedure was reproducible. Hence, the present radioiodination method can be adopted for labelling anti-CRP monoclonal antibodies to use as a radiotracer or detector antibody for IRMA development.

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References

- Hunter WM, Greenwood FC (1962) *Nature* **194**, 495–496.
Ridker, Paul M. (2003) *Circulation* **107**(3), 363-369.
Yalow, R.S. and Berson, S.A. (1960) *The Journal of Clinical Investigation* **39**(7), 1157-1175.

THERMAL OXIDATION AND LIQUID SCINTILLATION COUNTING METHOD FOR THE CARBON-14 DETERMINATION FOR QUANTIFYING THE NATURAL AND SYNTHETIC COMPONENTS IN BIO-BASED PRODUCTS

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Keywords: Carbon-14, Tube combustion, LSC, adulteration, bio-based products.

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Introduction

There has been a notable rise in consumer demand for bio-based products in recent years. Adulteration of natural products with synthetic materials that are chemically identical to the natural products is an emerging concern. Conventional analytical techniques such as GC-MS, FT-IR, HP-LC, etc., fail to distinguish between biogenic (natural plant derived) and synthetically derived products¹. Carbon-14 (¹⁴C) measurement is the authentic method for detecting and quantifying the presence of synthetic adulterants in bio-based products. The ¹⁴C specific activity of natural plant-derived products is expected to be in equilibrium with the atmospheric specific activity value of 226 ± 1 Bq kg⁻¹C or 100 pMC (percent modern carbon) with 1950 as the reference year². This is because atmospheric ¹⁴CO₂ is incorporated into the plant biota through photosynthesis, and a state of equilibrium is always achieved. American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) recommends two methods for the ¹⁴C determination in consumer products: (i) accelerator mass spectrometry (AMS) and (ii) benzene synthesis followed by liquid scintillation counting (LSC)³. However, the complex sample preparation, associated high costs, and unavailability in the country for commercial users have posed severe challenges for the exporters of the products. Hence, simpler methods based on the combustion of the sample and direct LSC of the CO₂ species for ¹⁴C determination offer advantages when a large number of samples are to be analysed in batches.

Materials and Methods

A total of 40 samples of commercial products, such as turmeric powder, caffeine, beetroot extract, vanilla extract, berberis extract, wheat extract, moringa extract, etc., were examined in the present study. Samples

were combusted in a tube furnace system (pyrolyser), and the CO₂ species produced were trapped in an amine-based absorber, mixed with a scintillator and subjected to LSC⁴.

Results

Out of 40 samples analysed, 32 exhibited ¹⁴C specific activity between 95 – 105 pMC, while for eight samples, the ¹⁴C specific activity was below 95 pMC. A ¹⁴C specific activity value below 95 pMC suggests adulteration with synthetic or petroleum-based substances. Five of these eight adulterated samples exhibited a ¹⁴C specific activity below 10 pMC, indicating that they are synthetic materials.

Conclusion

The capability of the method based on thermal oxidation and LSC of the CO₂ species for the ¹⁴C determination to quantify the natural and synthetic components in commercial products labelled as "natural products" was demonstrated by analysing varieties of samples. The facilities available at the Centre for Advanced Research in Environmental Radioactivity (CARER) are being used by about 40 industries from different parts of India to check the authenticity of natural products.

References

1. Varga, T., Szejke, D., Nemes, Z., Jull, A.T. and Molnár, M. (2023). Radiocarbon, 65(5), pp.1176-1192.
2. Libby WF. (1946). Physical Reviews. 69:671- 672.
3. ASTM International, 2022.
4. D'Souza RS, Nayak SR, Mohan MP, Bharath S, Krishnan KA, Kamath S, Diéguez A, Tenorio R, Karunakara N. (2021). Journal of Environmental Radioactivity, 226:106345

ACTIVITY CONCENTRATIONS OF ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th AND ^{40}K IN THE VEGETABLES AND EDIBLE GRAINS OF GOGI REGION OF NORTHERN KARNATAKA, INDIA

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Keywords: Gogi, spectrometry, mining, radionuclides, uptake

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Introduction

The radionuclides present in the environment can enter the human food chain through terrestrial, atmospheric and aquatic pathways. While some radionuclides are homologous to essential elements, others are taken up irrespective of their biological necessity. Besides the essential elements for the growth and reproduction of vegetation, several natural radioactive elements like uranium and thorium and their daughter products are known to be present in plants. In this study, vegetables and food grain samples were collected from the Gogi region of Northern Karnataka, India. The Gogi region is known for its uranium mineralisation with the possibility of commercial-scale mining.

Materials and methods

Samples of vegetables and edible grain were collected from several locations in 0-30 km zone of Gogi region, with Gogi village as centre of the zone. The samples were processed, ashed to get uniform white ash, sealed and stored to allow radioactive equilibrium between ^{226}Ra and its progenies [1,2]. The activity concentrations of ^{40}K , ^{232}Th and ^{226}Ra in the samples were determined by gamma spectrometry with a 38% relative efficiency p-type low-background HPGe detector (Canberra USA), and the gamma ray spectrum analysis was performed by GENIE-2000 software [3]. The detector efficiency calibration was performed using IAEA quality assurance reference materials.

Results and discussion

The median values of ^{40}K , ^{232}Th , and ^{226}Ra activity concentrations in the vegetables were 179.1 Bq kg^{-1} , 0.05 Bq kg^{-1} , and 0.1 Bq kg^{-1} , respectively. Similarly, the median values of ^{40}K , ^{232}Th , and ^{226}Ra activity concentrations in the edible grains were 312.7 Bq kg^{-1} , 0.1 Bq kg^{-1} , and

0.2 Bq kg^{-1} , respectively. The activity concentrations of ^{40}K , ^{232}Th and ^{226}Ra observed in the present study was similar to those reported for India and other regions of the world.

Conclusion

This study has established the crucial database on radionuclide activity concentrations in food matrices of Gogi region. The database will be useful for dose and impact assessments in future if the uranium mineralisation is commercial explored in the region.

References

- Environmental Measurements Laboratory (EML). (1983) Procedures Manual. 26th Edition.
- Bhabha Atomic Research Center (BARC). (2008) Standard protocol for evaluation of environmental transfer factors around NPP sites.
- Karunakara N, Yashodhara I, Sudeep Kumara K, Tripathi R M, Menon S N, Kadam S Chougaoankar M P. (2014) Assessment of ambient gamma dose rate around a prospective uranium mining area of South India – A comparative study of dose by direct methods and soil radioactivity measurements. 4, 20-27.

NATURAL AND ANTHROPOGENIC RADIOACTIVITY IN THE RIVER SEDIMENTS IN THE VICINITY OF KAIGA NPP

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Introduction

Environmental radiological monitoring around nuclear power plants (NPP) is paramount in assessing the impact, if any. The Centre for Advanced Research in Environmental Radioactivity, Mangalore University, continuously monitors the environment around the Kaiga NPP. Terrestrial, atmospheric, and aquatic environmental samples are collected regularly around the Kaiga region to monitor the radioactivity. In the current study, sediment samples from Kali River, which supplies water for cooling the condenser of the NPP in Kaiga, were analyzed for physio-chemical parameters and natural and anthropogenic radionuclide concentrations. Sediments are often recommended for long-term monitoring of radioactivity in the environment.

Materials and Methods

Sediment was sampled from nine locations of the Kali River, with two from upstream locations with respect to the NPP and seven from downstream locations. The samples were dried at 110° and sieved in a 250-micron mesh. The pH, salinity, and electrical conductivity were measured by standard methods. The activity concentrations of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, ⁴⁰K, and ¹³⁷Cs were determined by gamma spectroscopy using a 50% nominal efficient HPGe detector (Karunakara et al., 2013).

Results

The conductivity of sediment samples varied from 24.8 - 110.2 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$. The pH ranged from 4.04 - 4.97 in the analyzed samples. Salinity levels ranged from 0.12 to 0.63 dS m^{-1} , indicating that the sediments were not saline.

The activity concentration of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K in sediment samples varied in the ranges of 27.6-112.6 Bq kg^{-1} , 21.2-142.3 Bq kg^{-1} , 549-1790 Bq kg^{-1} respectively. The activity

concentration of ¹³⁷Cs varied in the range of 1.9-22.1 Bq kg^{-1} with a mean value of 7.9 Bq kg^{-1} . The ¹³⁷Cs activity in the upstream locations was in the range of 2.0-6.9 Bq kg^{-1} and in downstream locations in 3.9-22.1 Bq kg^{-1} . These values are similar to those recorded during the preoperational survey to establish the baseline database for the Kaiga NPP region. It may be noted that ¹³⁷Cs in soil were detected well before the construction work of the NPP started at Kaiga. Detailed studies have revealed that the observed ¹³⁷Cs activity in Kaiga and the West Coast region of India was due to the high rainfall in the region, which resulted in higher fallout of this radioisotope through the global fallout phenomenon during the 1950s and 1960s.

Conclusion

The values recorded for natural and anthropogenic radionuclides were similar to those recorded during the preoperational survey for establishing the baseline database for the Kaiga NPP region.

References

Karunakara N, et al. 2013. Soil to rice transfer factors for ²²⁶Ra, ²²⁸Ra, ²¹⁰Pb, ⁴⁰K and ¹³⁷Cs: a study on rice grown in India, Journal of Environmental Radioactivity, 118 (2013) 80-92.

SOIL-TO-RICE TRANSFER FACTORS (F_v) VALUES FOR STABLE ELEMENTS FOR THE TROPICAL MONSOONAL CLIMATE REGION OF THE WEST COAST OF INDIA

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Introduction

Transfer factors (F_v) are numerical values for quantifying the transfer of elements from one environmental compartment (e.g., soil, water, air) to another. While extensive studies have been reported on soil-to-plant F_v values for temperate regions, only a few studies have been reported for tropical regions. In previous studies (Karunakara et al., 2013a; Karunakara et al., 2013b), F_v values were reported for the rice, vegetable, grass, etc., grown in the vicinity of a nuclear power plant at Kaiga, West Coast of India, beset with tropical monsoonal climatic conditions. High rainfall, warm temperatures, and distinct soil properties are some characteristics of the West Coast of India. Heavy rainfall and warm temperatures accelerate soil erosion and leaching of essential elements, such as K, Ca, Mg, and Na. This depletion of essential elements and the distinct physicochemical properties of soil may influence the soil-to-plant transfer elements. A review of the F_v values and data collated by the IAEA (IAEA, 2010; IAEA, 2021) has revealed that the F_v values of Cs isotopes are higher in tropical regions when compared to the temperate zone. This paper reports the soil-to-rice F_v values for rice fields in the Mangalore region.

Materials and Methods

Soil and rice samples collected from local farmers in the Mangalore region (12°48' N, 74°55' E) were dried at 110°C to remove the water content completely. The sample was digested in a microwave digestion system (closed vessel type) and analyzed for major elemental concentrations in an ICP-OES system and trace elements in an ICP-MS system.

Results

The F_v value for rice for Ba, Ca, Co, Cr, Cs, Cu, Fe, K, Mg, Mn, Mo, Na, Ni, Pb, Sr, V and Zn

were determined and the mean values were respectively 3.74E-02, 1.69E-01, 3.55E-03, 1.05E-02, 4.55E-02, 5.06E-02, 6.75E-04, 7.83E-01, 1.32E-01, 5.84E-02, 1.02E+00, 1.81E-01, 1.50E-02, 6.24E-02, 3.35E-02, 3.32E-04, and 4.42E-01.

Conclusion

The F_v values recorded in this study were higher when compared to those reported for temperate regions (IAEA, 2010). On the other hand, the values observed in the present study are similar to those reported for other tropical regions (IAEA, 2021).

References

- Karunakara, N., Rao, C., Ujwal, P., Yashodhara, I., Kumara, S., & Ravi, P. (2013a). Soil to rice transfer factors for 226Ra, 228Ra, 210Pb, 40K and 137Cs: A study on rice grown in India. *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity*, 118, 80–92.
- Karunakara, N., Ujwal, P., Yashodhara, I., Rao, C., Kumara, K. S., Dileep, B., & Ravi, P. (2013b). Studies on soil-to-grass transfer factor (F_v) and grass-to-milk transfer coefficient (F_m) for cesium in Kaiga region. *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity*, 124, 101–112.
- International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). (2010). *Handbook of parameter values for the prediction of radionuclide transfer in terrestrial and freshwater environments* (Technical Reports Series No. 472). Vienna: IAEA.
- International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). (2021). *Soil-plant transfer of radionuclides in non-temperate environments* (IAEA-TECDOC-1979). Vienna: IAEA.

SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF ^{137}Cs IN THE WESTERN GHATS ECOSYSTEM OF KARNATAKA, INDIA

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Introduction

This study reports the spatial distribution of ^{137}Cs in the soil of the Western Ghats region of India, an area known for its rich biodiversity. Soil samples were analysed by gamma spectrometry for the ^{137}Cs activity. The locations selected for the study are not affected by any anthropogenic activities, and therefore, the data obtained on ^{137}Cs activity is expected to provide valuable information on the extent of global atmospheric fallout of this radioisotope due to the weapon testing in the 1950s and 1960s and Chernobyl accident.

Materials and methods

Soil samples were collected from 27 sampling stations in the Western Ghats region of Karnataka, known for its unique identity due to heavy precipitation, scenic beauty, ridges and valleys. The samples were processed following standard procedures [1]. The activity concentration of ^{137}Cs in the soil samples was determined by gamma spectrometry with a 50% relative efficiency p-type low-background HPGe detector (Canberra Industries Inc., USA), complemented by GENIE-2000 software. The detector efficiency calibration was performed using the IAEA quality assurance reference materials. Samples were counted for a duration of 60,000 s.

Results

The activity concentration of ^{137}Cs in the soil ranged from 0.1 to 6.3 Bq kg⁻¹, with a GM of 0.8 Bq kg⁻¹ (GSD = 3.6). The study revealed a non-uniform distribution of ^{137}Cs activity in the region. The soils not affected by runoff due to forest cover show higher activity when compared to the soils subjected to erosion. The region experiences high rainfall with averages of 3,000–4,000 mm, with localised extremes touching

9,000 mm. As discussed in the beginning, the ^{137}Cs in the soil are due to the global atmospheric fallout from the weapon testing in the 1950s and 1960s and the Chernobyl accident. Rainfall is one of the critical parameters that affected the extent of the fallout of ^{137}Cs , derived from weapon testing in the 1950s and 1960s and the Chernobyl accident since it is efficiently removed from the atmosphere by rain.

The values recorded in this study are similar to those reported previously for the West Coast region of India [2] and other regions [3].

Conclusion

The data obtained in this study has provided valuable information on the extent of the atmospheric fallout of ^{137}Cs in the Western Ghat region from the global fallout phenomenon.

References

- Environmental Measurements Laboratory (EML). (1983) Procedures Manual. 26th Edition.
N. Karunakara, H. M. Somashekarappa, Y. Narayana, D. N. Avadhani, H. M. Mahesh, and K. Siddappa. (2010). ^{137}Cs concentration in the environment of Kaiga of the Southwest coast of India. Health Physics, August 2001, Volume 81.
Bhabha Atomic Research Center (BARC). (2008) Standard protocol for evaluation of environmental transfer factors around NPP sites.

QUALITY CONTROL IN MEASUREMENT OF NORMS IN GEOLOGICAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL METRICES USING RADIOMETRIC TECHNIQUES

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Introduction

Quality assurance and quality control are the integral part of metrology to ensure the data quality. Objective of quality assurance is to avoid any error in measurement while the objective of the quality control is to assess the error and/or uncertainty in the measurement. In addition to adoption of National/International standards for measurement of Naturally Occurring Radioactive Materials (NORMs) in geological and environmental matrices using radiometric techniques, various quality control measures are undertaken to assess the accuracy, precision, reliability, bias, detection limit, linearity and sensitivity of the analytical technique. In case of measurement of NORMs, proficiency test conducted by IAEA is an important activity to validate the regional methodology followed and reliability of the analytical technique at the global scale. Over the two decades, there are changes in the methodology adopted for performance evaluation like introduction of zeta-score, changes in u-test, etc. In the present paper, an attempt has been made to understand the scientific basis for the changes in performance evaluation methodology over the last two decades.

Observation and Discussion

Before 2010, relative bias, z-score, u-score values and other estimates were used for performance evaluation of results submitted by participating laboratories (IAEA, 2008). In the recent years (IAEA, 2024), accuracy of the results of participating laboratories assessed using the relative bias (should be less than Maximum Acceptable Relative Bias), z-score (should be less than or equal to 2) and zeta-score (should be less than or equal to 2) while the acceptance criterion for precision are relative combined uncertainty of the relative bias (P)

should be less than Maximum Acceptable Relative Bias and the absolute value of relative bias should be less than 2.58 times of relative combined uncertainty of the relative bias (P). Zetascore introduced in 2024 IAEA proficiency test reflect the efforts to improve the assessment of participating laboratory performance by integrating the evaluation of uncertainties into performance metric. Zscore is a measure of deviation of reported value from target value but zeta-score incorporates the combined assessment of the reported value and the reported uncertainty of the measurement along with target value and its associated uncertainty.

Conclusion

Scientific changes in performance metrics of analytical results help the laboratory to improve their quality of the data which will endorse, once measured, accepted everywhere principle.

References

IAEA (2008), Worldwide Open Proficiency Test: Determination of Naturally Occurring Radionuclides in Phosphogypsum and Water, IAEA-CU-2008-03, IAEA Analytical Quality in Nuclear Applications Series No. 18.
IAEA (2024), Worldwide Proficiency Test Exercise on the determination of anthropogenic and natural radionuclides in water, bauxite, sediment and simulated contaminated surface samples, IAEATERC-2024-01.

FALLOUT RADIONUCLIDE (¹³⁷CS) ANALYSIS FOR ASSESSING CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACTS ON SOIL EROSION-INSIGHTS FROM THE INDIAN HIMALAYAS

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Introduction

Soil sustains life, supports ecosystems, and provides essential services. However, soil erosion, a major land degradation concern in the Himalayas, is being exacerbated by climate change. This fragile region lacks long-term soil erosion data needed to understand the climate change impact on soil erosion. Fallout radionuclide ¹³⁷Cs serves as a reliable tracer for measuring long-term soil movement across landscapes. It offers retrospective, site-specific soil erosion rates critical for addressing the soil degradation. Such studies are essential for formulating effective policies to combat soil erosion and ensure sustainable soil and water conservation in the ecologically sensitive hilly and mountainous regions of Himalayas.

Materials and Methods

This study focuses on the Tehri Dam catchment area in the north-western Indian Himalayas to assess the impact of climate change on soil erosion. Representative ¹³⁷Cs soil samples were collected based on a soil landscape unit map, and soil erosion rates were estimated under different soil-landscape and land use/land cover (LULC) types. The Revised Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) model was validated using ¹³⁷Cs-based point measurements to spatially map soil erosion rate across the landscape (Kumar *et al.*, 2024). To evaluate the impact of climate change, future precipitation was downscaled using IPCC-SSP scenarios and machine learning techniques. The validated RUSLE model, with the R factor adjusted for

future scenarios, was used to spatially predict the impact of future precipitation on soil erosion rates.

Results

The study revealed that forests and grasslands exhibited the lowest soil erosion rates, whereas sparse or non-vegetated barren lands had the highest rates. The average soil erosion rate during the base period was 27.1 t ha⁻¹ year⁻¹. Under future climate scenarios, increased precipitation accelerates soil erosion rates, ranging from 27.8 to 37.2 t ha⁻¹ year⁻¹, corresponding to a percentage increase of 2.5% (SSP1 -2.6) to 37.0% (SSP4-8.5). Forests showed resilience to increased soil erosion from higher precipitation, with the least erosion under low-emission scenarios. This highlights the need to adhere sustainable pathways for effective soil management in hilly and mountainous regions.

Conclusion

The study highlights climate change's role in accelerating soil erosion, emphasizing the need for sustainable, site-specific conservation, afforestation, and deforestation prevention. It emphasizes identifying erosion hotspots using radioisotopes to guide adaptation and mitigation efforts. By projecting future scenarios, it provides a scientific foundation for policies, promoting sustainable land management to protect the fragile Himalayan landscape in the context of climate change.

References

Kumar, S., David Raj, A. and Mariappan, S. (2024) *Catena*, 234, 107591 .

ABSORPTION OF NATURAL RADIONUCLIDES BY MEDICINAL PLANT

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Key words: Medicinal plant, radionuclide, transfer factor, activity concentration

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Introduction

Naturally occurring radionuclides of uranium-238 and thorium-232 series and singly occurring radionuclide ⁴⁰K is common in all living and non-living frameworks of our environment (1). Awareness on the existing concentration of radionuclides in medicinal plants is necessary to verify possible interferences in therapeutic activity, depending on their concentration. There is a need to formulate environmentally secure and economically equitable common regulations both endorsed by radiological, economical, and social jurisdictions.

Material and Methods

Coastal Karnataka in India is known for traditional folklore and Ayurvedic system of medicine based on plant ingredients. The activity concentrations of radionuclides ²²⁶Ra, ²¹⁰Pb, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K in bark and leaves of *Piper nigrum* L., a medicinal plant of coastal Karnataka were assessed by using HPGe gamma spectrometer by following standard methods. The soil to bark, and soil to leaves transfer factors (TF) of the radionuclides, average annual committed effective dose (AACED), and threshold annual consumption rate of medicinal plant were estimated (2-4).

Results and Discussion

It was found that the activity concentrations of ⁴⁰K were higher among all the estimated radionuclides, in both bark and leaves of *Piper nigrum* L. The soil to plant transfer factors for fruit and leaves were found as 0.1 and 0.8 respectively. The average annual committed effective dose (AACED) due to the consumption of bark and leaves, at a consumption rate of 1kg y⁻¹, were found to be far below the world average of 0.3 mSv y⁻¹. The safe maximum consumption

rates of fruit and leaves of this medicinal plant were found to be 13.91 and 2.98 kg y⁻¹, respectively.

Conclusion

The activity concentrations of radionuclides in *Piper nigrum* L., a medicinal plant from coastal Karnataka region were estimated. The study found that the concentration of ⁴⁰K is maximum. The study reveals that there is no radiological health risk due to ingestion of radionuclides, by the consumption of this medicinal plant to treat the diseases. The study may help to bring out a database of concentration and soil to plant transfer factors of radionuclides in medicinal plants. It may also ensure the safety of using the plant medicine to treat the diseases.

Reference

- Eisenbud, M. (1987). Environmental radioactivity from natural, industrial, and military sources, 147, *Academic Press, Inc.*
- EML Procedure Manual. (1983). Edited by Herbert L. Volchok & Gail de Planque, *Environmental Measurement Laboratory*, New York.
- Iyengar, M. A. R., Ganapathy, S., Kannan, V., Rajan, M. P. & Rajaram, S. (1990). Procedure manual In: Workshop on environmental radioactivity, Kaiga, India, April 16 – 18. Bhabha Atomic Research Centre (BARC). (2008). Annual Report. Standard protocol for evaluation of environmental transfer factors around NPP sites. Mumbai, India.

EFFECTIVENESS OF ANNEALING USING OVEN WITH PID BASED CONTROLLER AND CONVENTIONAL CONTROLLER – A COMPARISON

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Introduction

Thermoluminescent Dosimeter (TLD) based on $\text{CaSO}_4:\text{Dy}$ is used as Personnel Monitoring Device for the radiation workers at Kudankulam Nuclear Power Project (KKNPP). Personal monitoring services (PMS) in nuclear power plant play an imperative role in Radiation Safety. Annealing, a thermal treatment (Temperature raised from ambient to set point 230°C and maintained for 4 hours) carried out in hot air circulated oven to erase any irradiation memory from the dosimetric material due to any previous irradiation, thereby allowing re-use of the TLD cards. The Thermoluminescence properties exhibited by TLDs are strongly dependent on the annealing process. The existing oven with conventional controller (A), were replaced with Oven built with PID based (Proportional-Integral-Derivative) controller (B), for better regulation. The performance of these ovens were compared and summarised below.

Materials and Methods

Appropriateness of annealing was verified by randomly taking readout of 5% of TLD cards and read in a calibrated reader. Subsequently the average and standard deviation (SD) of the background were estimated. Reproducibility check was done to ensure the annealing performance and the stability of Reader. The Cycle to Cycle variation (CCV) and CoV for both the ovens were calculated. The temperature of both the ovens was recorded throughout the annealing process.

Results

Annealing verification data

The Average background for oven A and B for reader#1 is 33.5 and 33.3 and for reader #2 is 27 and 27.3 respectively. The SD of the background for oven A & B for reader#1 is 8.0 and 9.3 and for reader #2 is 8.3 and 7.1 respectively. (Acceptance Criteria: The standard deviation, irrespective of the mean,

should be less than $30 \mu\text{Sv}$ (1σ) for all disc readings.)

Reproducibility check data

The Cycle to Cycle variation (%) for Oven A & B is in the range of -1.8 to 1.4 and -1.2 to 1.5 for Reader #1 and -1.6 to 1.5 and -1.2 to 1.6 for reader #2 respectively. Similarly the CoV(%) for Oven A & B for Reader#1 is in the range of 1.7 to 5.2 and 1.8 to 7.2 and for reader#2 is 4.0 to 7.4 and 4.2 to 7.2 respectively. (Acceptance Criteria: For each cycle, mean within $\pm 5\%$ of the grand mean & $\text{CoV} < 7.5\%$.)

Temperature data

The temperature variation of $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ was observed around the set point of 230°C in oven A and B respectively. (Acceptance Criteria: $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$.)

Conclusion

The efficacy of the annealing by the hot air ovens with PID based controller and with conventional controller are satisfactory and the results are of the same order. Both the ovens are acceptable and ensure the goodness of annealing in terms of reproducibility and low standard deviation of background. However the Oven with PID controller are having more control on stabilising the temperature due to combined approach of P,I & D component to address the past, current and future error which ensure precision, stability in control and better regulation of temperature.

References

1. Claudio Furetta, (2003), Handbook of Thermoluminescence.
2. Datta. D, et al., (BARC/2018/E/007) by, RPAD, BARC, Hand book on TLD-based Personnel Monitoring (Rev. 1-2018).

COUNTING EFFICIENCIES OF QUICK SCAN WHOLE BODY MONITOR FOR ADULT AND PAEDIATRIC REFERENCE COMPUTATIONAL PHANTOMS

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Keywords: QSWBM, computational phantoms, counting efficiency, FLUKA

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Introduction

Whole body monitoring of radiation workers for internal radioactive contamination is an essential and regulatory requirement. Partially shielded systems, such as the Quick Scan Whole Body Monitor (QSWBM) and Shadow Shield WBM (SSWBM) are used for this purpose. International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP) publication 110 and 143 provides reference computational phantoms for both adult and paediatric (PRC) populations (1-year, 5-year, 10-year and 15-year). These phantoms represent human anatomy more accurately, enhancing the reliability of dose assessments and monitoring procedures [1, 2]. These phantoms have been used in this study to estimate the counting efficiencies (CEs) of the QSWBM for high-energy photon emitters ($E_\gamma > 200$ keV), using FLUKA code. Results will be helpful in realistic dose assessments in workers and members of the public during emergencies.

Materials and Methods

The QSWBM employs two large sized NaI(Tl) detectors, each having dimensions of 16" x 5" x 3", arranged in a linear array within the detector mounting wall. It has a three-sided shielded cavity made up of 50 mm Pb and 6 mm stainless steel plates. Voxel phantoms are derived from CT scan or MRI data of real individuals, representing the entire body as a 3D array of voxels arranged in columns, rows, and slices, with each organ assigned with a unique identification number. The QSWBM geometry was numerically modelled in FLUKA along with the ICRP adult and PRC phantoms. To maximize CEs, the 1-year, 5-year and 10-year phantoms were positioned at standing heights of 45, 30 and 30 cm from floor respectively. The phantom to detector distances are variable and it ranges from 18.6 cm for adults to 29.3 cm for 1-year-olds. The computational model was validated by comparing the simulated and experimental CEs for ¹³⁷Cs using adult BOMAB

phantom, with < 2% deviation. Monte Carlo simulations were carried out to estimate the CEs for several energies including ¹³³Ba (356 keV), ¹³⁷Cs (662 keV) and ⁶⁰Co (1332 keV), by defining a user-written source routine to simulate uniform distribution of activity in total 36 organs of the whole body altogether in reference phantoms. The DETECT card was used to score energy deposition in the detectors, and 5×10^7 histories were used to minimize the relative errors to < 1%.

Results and Discussion

At any energy, CEs decrease with age, with 1-year-olds exhibiting up to 38% higher CEs than adults. The increased CE in 1-year-old phantom can be attributed to lower self-attenuation and smaller source distribution due to its relatively compact structure. Furthermore, across all ages, CEs decrease with energy. In 1-year-olds and adults, CEs at 356 keV are up to 41% and 35% higher than that at 1332 keV. This reduction in CEs is attributed to the incomplete energy deposition due Compton scattering at higher energies. Voxel phantoms exhibit up to 38% higher CE than BOMAB phantoms. Therefore, using CEs of the latter will underestimate the intake and hence internal dose by up to 38%.

Conclusions

Utilizing the CEs of realistic voxel phantoms will improve the accuracy in internal dose assessments by up to 38% in workers and members of public during emergency scenarios.

References

1. Adult reference computational phantoms. Publication 110. *Annal. ICRP* 39(2), 2009.
2. Paediatric reference computational phantoms. Publication 143. *Annal. ICRP*, 49 (1-299), 2020.

RADIOCHEMICAL ESTIMATION OF ^{226}Ra IN URINE SAMPLE

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Introduction

^{226}Ra , a daughter product of ^{238}U , has a radiological half-life of 1600 y and emits alpha particles ($E=4.78\text{MeV}$). It is a naturally occurring radionuclide, with higher concentrations often found in uranium mining and milling operations [1]. When ingested, ^{226}Ra accumulates in bones & teeth, where it can irradiate blood cells and soft tissues such as the kidneys before being excreted in urine. To estimate levels of ^{226}Ra in individuals, bioassay methods, are commonly employed. While alpha spectrometry with ^{229}Th as a tracer can be used to measure ^{226}Ra in urine, the interpretation of result is complex and time-consuming. Alternatively, ^{225}Ra can be used as a tracer but has a short half-life (14.9 d). In this study, ^{133}Ba ($T_{1/2} = 10.4$ y) was selected as a pseudo-tracer for estimating ^{226}Ra in urine samples. The methodology employed combines cation exchange resin with 2-ethylhexyl diglycolamide (DGA) resin, which effectively separates interferences from elements such as Pb, U, Th, Bi and Po.

Materials and Methods

In this study, 18 urine samples (1 L each) were collected from the public to standardize the procedure. One batch of six samples was spiked with a ^{226}Ra standard in the range of 30–70mBq for standardization. Another batch was spiked with both ^{226}Ra & ^{133}Ba (0.3-0.5Bq) to estimate tracer recovery. The third batch was spiked only with ^{133}Ba (0.38 Bq) to determine ^{226}Ra levels in the urine samples. To assess the repeatability of the method, samples 13–18 were utilized. The samples underwent wet oxidation using conc. HNO_3 and H_2O_2 , followed by $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ co-precipitation. Later the precipitate was dissolved in 15 mL of 3M HCl, and Ba-carrier (50 μg) was added. The sample was then loaded onto a cation exchange column preconditioned with 3M HCl & washed with 20 mL of 3M HCl to remove interfering cations. Radium & barium were then eluted from the column using 30 mL of 5M HNO_3 . The column was positioned above a DGA column

preconditioned with 30 mL of 5M HNO_3 [2]. A total eluted volume of 30 mL was collected for ^{133}Ba recovery estimation, using gamma spectrometry ($E_\gamma:356\text{keV}$) with an HPGe detector. After gamma counting, the sample was evaporated to dryness in a beaker. The residue was then dissolved in 10 mL of 1.5M HCl. To this 3g of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ & 5 mL of isopropanol were added, and placed in an ice bath for 30min. $\text{Ba}(\text{Ra})\text{SO}_4$ micro-precipitate was collected on 0.1 μm filter paper & ^{226}Ra was counted using alpha spectrometry for 86400secs.

Results

The radiochemical recovery of ^{226}Ra ranged from 66% to 90%, with an average of $77 \pm 8.7\%$. The Root Mean Squared Error and relative precision for ^{226}Ra estimation were ≤ 0.25 and 0.09, respectively, meeting ANSI acceptance criteria. The minimum detectable activity by alpha spectrometry is 0.5 mBq/d for a counting period of 86,400seconds. In the evaluation of tracer recovery, the difference in recovery between samples spiked with ^{226}Ra and those with added ^{133}Ba (samples nos. 7-12) was within $\pm 5.4\%$, indicating a strong agreement and validation of the method. ^{226}Ra was found below the detection limit in urine samples. The coefficient of variation of 3.65% further supports the reliability and reproducibility of the method.

Conclusion

This study successfully standardizes a radiochemical procedure using ^{133}Ba as a pseudo-tracer for accurate ^{226}Ra determination in urine samples. The stacked elution method removes interferences from elements such as Pb, U, Th, Bi and Po, enhancing accuracy and reducing sample turnaround time. The method is also suitable for the rapid analysis of ^{226}Ra in emergency urine samples.

References

1. Safety Report series 100 IAEA (2020), 217.
2. Sherrod L. Maxwell et al, (2014) *J Radioanal Nucl Chem*, 300, 1159.

A RAPID TECHNIQUE FOR ESTIMATION OF ^{241}Am IN FILTER PAPER USING POLYMER INCLUSION MEMBRANE

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Introduction

Membrane-based processes have recently garnered significant attention for separation of metal ions. Among these, Polymer Inclusion Membranes (PIMs) have emerged as a promising alternative to conventional solvent extraction methods. PIMs offer several advantages, including high selectivity, operational simplicity, reduced solvents and extractants, and the capability to combine extraction and stripping in a single stage, which leads to lower overall costs. The analysis of alpha-emitting radionuclides in filter paper samples is essential for monitoring of airborne contamination in radioactive laboratories. Additionally, filter paper analysis is a highly sensitive technique for detecting nuclear signatures, playing a vital role in safeguard verification. In this study, we explored the application of PIMs for the extraction of ^{241}Am from pre-treated glass filter paper samples.

Materials and methods

PIMs were prepared using the technique described in the reference [1], but with a modified composition tailored for this study including cellulose triacetate (CTA) 48 wt%, the plasticizer NPOE 24 wt%, and the carrier HDEHP 28 wt%. The uptake of ^{241}Am was investigated across various acidity levels, with the kinetics of uptake further examined at the optimized acidity. For each experiment, 10–12 mg of PIM was added to the solution and stirred for a duration of 15 to 120 minutes. After stirring, the PIM was removed and transferred directly into a HDPE vial. Optiphase Hisafe III cocktail was then added to the vial, and counted in liquid scintillation counter. Blank glass fibre filter paper were spiked with ^{241}Am (42.2 Bq) and subsequently digested following standard protocols [2]. An aliquot of 1g from the resulting stock solution (specific activity 1.6Bq/g) was taken for further analysis.

Results and Discussion

The acidic ligand HDEHP is well known for its effectiveness in extracting trivalent actinides such as ^{241}Am from solutions at a pH range of 2-3. However, at higher nitric acid concentrations, the extraction efficiency decreases due to competition between H^+ ions and Am^{3+} ions. An acid variation study demonstrated maximum uptake at pH 2, with the probable extracted complex being $\text{Am}(\text{HDEHP}.\text{DEHP})_3$. Kinetic study for ^{241}Am uptake at pH 2 revealed that saturation occurred within 15 minutes when extracted from the acidic feed solution. The PIM achieved ~ 90% radiochemical recovery of ^{241}Am within 15 minutes at pH 2. However, the efficacy reduced to 60-65% for glass fibre filter paper, which may be attributed to matrix interference.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates a rapid technique for the separation of ^{241}Am from filter paper samples using PIM. The results indicate that this method not only achieves high radiochemical recovery from acidic feed solutions but also provides a viable approach for extracting actinides from glass fibre filter paper, despite some challenges related to matrix interference.

References

1. Mahanty, B., Mahapatra, P K., Raut, D R., Das, D K., Behere, P G., Afzal, M D. (2016) *J. Membr. Sci.* **501**, 134-143.
2. Panda, S., Reddy, P J., Yadav, J R., Sawant, P D., Kulkarni, M S. (2022) *Appl Radiat Isot.* **186**:110297.

ASSESSMENT OF WHOLE-BODY AND EXTREMITY GAMMA DOSE CORRELATION IN MOX FUEL FABRICATION

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Keywords: Radiation protection, extremities dose, whole body dose, MOX fuel fabrication

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Introduction

To ensure the safety of radiation workers, Atomic Energy Regulatory Board (AERB) provided annual individual dose limits for exposure to ionizing radiation. AERB also set the annual equivalent dose limit for extremities (hands and feet) as 500 mSv to control deterministic effects [1]. Monitoring & controlling of extremity doses is a concern at facilities where the radiation worker is exposed in a non-uniform radiation field of X-rays & gamma rays. MOX fuel fabrication (FF) involves a powder metallurgy process, where PuO₂ & DDUO₂ powder is mixed in various percentage followed by its milling, compaction, sintering for pelletisation. These pellets are loaded into stainless steel tubes and wire-wrapped to form finished fuel pins. All operations are carried out within glove boxes to control internal exposure. However, external exposure is a significant concern, because most of the above operations are carried out manually inside glove boxes (GBs). To control the external exposure due to gamma, shielding is provided in most of the GBs. Despite this external dose to the extremities remains is a critical issue due to non-uniform radiation field on the glove box surfaces & the gauntlets worn by the workers. Therefore, a study was carried out to establish the correlation between external gamma dose to whole body & extremities for MOX fuel fabrication.

Material & Method

During handling of MOX, radiation worker encounter with X-rays & gamma radiation emitted by various isotopes of Plutonium, Americium (²⁴¹Am), Uranium (²³⁷U), and traces of fission products. To monitor radiation exposure, personal dosimetry is employed on monthly basis for average 550 radiation workers at FF. For monitoring of whole-body gamma dose, chest TLDs (Thermoluminescent Dosimeters) are issued to all radiation worker, while about 100 wrist TLDs are also issued to monitor extremity gamma doses. To establish a ratio between whole body & extremities gamma dose, ten years dose data

of Fuel Fabrication (FF) for the period 2014 to 2023 was analyzed. During study data of only those radiation workers were considered whose extremities gamma doses was above recording level of TLD (≥ 0.1 mSv). Moreover, the data were analyzed on yearly basis, both for maximum & average extremities gamma doses and compared with whole body doses over the ten-year period.

Results & Discussion

The ratio between the whole-body to extremity gamma dose, for an individual maximum doses was found to be in the ranged from 1.91 to 8.31. While the ratio for annual average gamma dose, was found in the range from 0.77 to 4.10. In totality, the ratio between the doses for extremities and whole body remained consistently less than 10. The results of dose analysis suggests that extremities doses do not exceed regulatory thresholds even in scenarios where the whole-body dose may trigger an annual investigation level(>20 mSv). Since the dose ratio is always less than 10, therefore regular monitoring of extremities gamma doses may be exempted for MOX fuel fabrication.

Conclusion:

The study of ten-year dose data offer valuable insights into the radiation exposure patterns in MOX fuel fabrication Tarapur and provide a basis for refining radiation protection measures, particularly concerning extremities exposure, in compliance with regulatory guidelines.

References

Radiation Protection for Nuclear Facilities, AERB/NF/SM/O-2 (Rev. 4), 2005

QUALITY FACTORS FOR PROTON RADIATION: A MONTE CARLO STUDY USING ICRP ADULT REFERENCE COMPUTATIONAL PHANTOMS

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Introduction

Estimating radiation-absorbed doses in the human body is challenging since direct measurement is not feasible. Instead, physical or computational phantoms are used to simulate exposure scenarios. Computational phantoms offer flexibility and cost-effectiveness, enabling a wide range of exposure conditions and anatomical variations to be studied through large-scale simulations. However, their accuracy depends on the fidelity of input data and the robustness of the underlying physics models.

The International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP) introduced mesh-type reference computational phantoms (MRCPs) to improve dose assessment accuracy across diverse scenarios. These MRCP phantoms provide a standardized framework for calculating dose coefficients, as demonstrated in recent studies (Yeon, 2019). Building on this framework, this study focuses on determining the quality factors (Q) for protons under anteroposterior (AP) irradiation across an energy range of 1 MeV to 1 TeV. Using the Geant4 Monte Carlo simulation toolkit, this work aims to provide insights into the energy dependence of Q values and their implications for effective dose assessments.

Materials and Methods

The quality factor (Q) was determined using the ICRP-defined function (Eq.(1)), incorporating linear energy transfer (LET) calculated via Geant4 classes. The Q values were averaged across LET (L) ranges, tissue masses, organs, and both sexes (Eqs.(2-4)). Geant4's G4Multithreading mode was employed to accelerate simulations.

$Q(LET)$

$$= \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} 1 & \text{if } L \leq 10 \text{ keV } \mu\text{m}^{-1} \\ 0.32L - 2.21 & \text{if } 10 \leq LET \leq 100 \text{ keV } \mu\text{m}^{-1} \\ 300/\sqrt{LET} & \text{if } LET \geq 100 \text{ keV } \mu\text{m}^{-1} \end{array} \right\} \dots (1)$$

$$Q = \frac{1}{D} \int_{L=0}^{\infty} Q(L)D_L dL \dots (2)$$

$$Q_T = \frac{1}{m_T D_T} \iint Q(L) D_L dL dm \dots (3)$$

$$Q_E = \frac{\sum_T w_T Q_T D_T}{\sum_T w_T D_T} \{\text{sex average}\} \dots (4)$$

where, D is absorbed dose, Q_E is effective quality factor and m_T is mass of tissue, and w_T is tissue weighting factor

Results

The effective Q values for protons demonstrated a complex energy dependence. At low energies, Q values were lower than those observed in water phantoms due to the insignificance of skin doses in effective dose calculations. Q values peaked at approximately 10 MeV, followed by a steady decline until 100–200 MeV. A slight increase was noted in the tens of GeV range, stabilizing around 2.2. The maximum and minimum Q values were approximately 5 and 1.2, respectively.

Conclusion

The results suggest that traditional radiation weighting factors may overestimate dose from high-energy proton radiation (> 10 MeV). A more precise assessment is achieved by calculating dose equivalents, which account for the specific energy and type of radiation. These findings highlight the importance of tailoring dose estimation methods to accurately reflect biological effects across energy spectra.

References

- ICRP, 2020. *ICRP Publication 145*. Ann. ICRP 49(3).
- Yeon Soo Yeom, et. al., *Nucl Engr and Tech*, Volume 51, Issue 3, 2019, 843-852,
- Allison J., et. al. *Nucl Inst and Meth in Phy Research Section A*: Volume 835, 2016, 186-225.

SCREENING PROCEDURE FOR GROSS ALPHA EMITTERS IN URINE USING EXTRACTION CHROMATOGRAPHY

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Introduction

During a nuclear or radiological incident, the first responders and public near the site of incident needs to be assessed for internal contamination rapidly for timely medical intervention. Screening for internal contamination due to alpha / beta emitters is mostly carried out through spot urine analysis as it facilitates high sample throughput enabling rapid dose assessment. In the present study, a rapid screening methodology was developed for estimating gross alpha emitters in urine using the extraction chromatography technique. The method uses a tandem column setup consisting prefilter resin made of acrylic ester polymer and an actinide resin containing P, P'-di(2-ethylhexyl) methanediphosphonic acid as extractant. [1].

Materials and Methods

To standardize the method, 10 urine samples (100 mL each) were collected from unexposed individuals. These urine samples were spiked with 10 ± 0.5 Bq, ²³⁹⁺²⁴⁰Pu. The spiked urine samples were then acidified to 2M by adding 20 mL conc. HCl and were loaded onto stacked columns consisting of a prefilter (1.5 g) and actinide (1.0 g) resin. The stacked columns were preconditioned with 2M HCl prior to sample loading and after the washing step (2M HCl), the prefilter column was removed. The alpha emitting radionuclides were eluted from the resin using 8 mL of 2-propanol. The eluate was collected directly in a 20 mL glass vial and mixed with 12 mL of Optiphase Hisafe-3 scintillation cocktail. HIDEX 300 SL Liquid Scintillation Counter (LSC) was used in α/β discrimination mode for alpha activity measurement. The Pulse Length Index (PLI) was set at 2, and a Region of Interest (ROI) comprising 300-800 channels was employed for determining alpha activity. The method was validated by analyzing 10 urine samples spiked with alpha-emitting radionuclides (U(nat.), ²⁴¹Am, ²³⁹⁺²⁴⁰Pu) and

their mixtures, within an activity range of 1.5 ± 0.07 to 35.0 ± 1.2 Bq

Results

The use of tandem column setup, consisting of a prefilter and actinide resin, in combination with LSC, simplifies the screening process for gross alpha. The use of prefilter resin eliminates the need for the time-consuming wet digestion process for the removal of organics. This standardized screening method takes approximately 2 hours, providing high sample throughput, with a high radiochemical recovery of around 96% for gross alpha.

The detection limit (DL) achieved with the standardized technique was 0.3 Bq/L for a counting time of 30 mins. This detection limit can be further improved by extending the counting time, achieving a DL of 0.2 Bq/L with a counting time of 60 mins or by employing an ultra-low background LSC (Quantulus 1220) for sample measurement. The developed methodology is sensitive enough to detect gross alpha emitters in urine, including the most restrictive alpha emitter, ²³⁹⁺²⁴⁰Pu below derived levels in urine, corresponding to a committed effective dose of 100 mSv [2]. Further, the standardized method meets the acceptance criteria for radiobioassay, outlined by ANSI/HPS N13.30 [3].

Conclusion

The screening method developed is simple, rapid and sensitive for the estimation of gross alpha emitters in urine samples, making it suitable for use during emergency scenarios.

References

1. Barrett, K.E. *et. al.* (2021) *Nucl Med. & Bio*, 96-97:19-26.
2. ICRP (2007) Pub. 103, *Annals* 37 (2-4)
3. ANSI/HPS N13.30 (2011). Health Phys Soc.

ESTIMATION OF GUT ABSORPTION FACTOR OF URANIUM IN ADULTS USING THE DATA ON DAILY INTAKE AND URINARY EXCRETION

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Introduction

Uranium is a naturally occurring radioactive element found in varying amounts in soil, air, water, and food, leading to chronic exposure in individuals. When ingested by food and drinking water, uranium is absorbed into the bloodstream, distributed to different organs and primarily excreted from the body through urine. This present paper presents an estimation of gut absorption factor (f_1) of uranium in adult residents of Mumbai, based on their daily dietary intake and urinary excretion data. Daily uranium intake and excretion were determined by the analysis of duplicate diet samples and 24 hr urine collections from the adult subjects. The uranium in the samples was separated using ion-exchange technique. The concentration of uranium was determined using LED fluorimetry (LF) followed by alpha spectrometry (AS) for obtaining the radiochemical recovery.

Materials and Methods

Duplicate diet samples (16 nos) were weighed and placed in a muffle furnace at 450°C until white ash was obtained. This white ash was then used for radiochemical analysis. Bioassay urine samples were collected over a 24hr duration from 55 adult subjects and were wet digested. The uranium present in both the diet and urine samples was co-precipitated with calcium phosphate. The resulting precipitate was dissolved in 5mL of 8N HCl and taken up for ion exchange separation using an anion exchange resin. Uranium was eluted from the ion exchange column using 1N HNO₃, evaporated to dryness and redissolved in 5mL of 0.1N HNO₃. A 1 mL aliquot of this sample was mixed with 5 mL of sodium pyrophosphate in a cuvette, and the uranium fluorescence was measured using a LED fluorimeter^{1,2}. The remaining sample was electrodeposited in ammonium sulphate medium for 2 hrs. The electroplated sample was analyzed using a PIPS based alpha-spectrometer.

Results

The average radiochemical recovery of uranium in the study was found to be 80%. The minimum detection limit for uranium were 6 ng d⁻¹ using LED fluorimeter and 20 ng d⁻¹ using the alpha spectrometer. The observed dietary intake of uranium in adults ranged from 350 ng d⁻¹ to 1090 ng d⁻¹, with a mean value of 650 ng d⁻¹. Urinary excretion levels varied from 8 ng d⁻¹ to 40 ng d⁻¹, with a mean value of 18.3 ng d⁻¹. The mean values of daily dietary intake and urinary excretion were used to determine the gut absorption factor f_1 using the formula:

$$f_1 = \frac{\text{daily urinary excretion}}{\text{daily uranium intake}}$$

The estimated f_1 value for uranium was found to be 2.8×10^{-2} , which is comparable to the ICRP³ value of 2.0×10^{-2} .

Conclusion

The studies on daily dietary intake and urinary excretion of uranium in adults living in Mumbai were carried out by analyzing duplicate diet and 24 hr urine samples using LED fluorimetry and alpha spectrometry. The gut absorption factor f_1 for uranium obtained from the present study was comparable with that reported by ICRP³ for adults.

References

1. Suja A, Prabhu S P, Sawant P D, Tiwari A K, Sharma R, Sarkar P K (2012). J. Radioanal Nucl Chem, 294: 439- 442.
2. Wankhede S, Chaudhary S, Suja A, Sawant P D (2021), Book of Abstracts, 15th Biennial DAE BRNS Symposium on Nuclear and Radiochemistry (NUCAR-2021), pp 194.
3. ICRP Publication no. 78 (1997); Individual monitoring for internal exposure of workers.

SEQUENTIAL SEPARATION OF URANIUM AND PLUTONIUM IN URINE SAMPLE USING DGA RESIN

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Introduction

In nuclear reprocessing plants, uranium (U) and plutonium (Pu) are extracted using PUREX process. If radionuclides are accidentally released into the working environment during this process, workers may become internally contaminated through inhalation. To ensure health and safety of individuals handling U and Pu, radiation protection agencies require urine bioassay monitoring. Timely reporting of monitoring results is vital for informed decision-making by plant authorities. To achieve this objective, a method that provides faster, cleaner separation with acceptable recovery is necessary.

DGA resin shows high retention of tetra- and hexa-valent actinides in nitric acid concentrations ranging from 3 to 8M. This property has been used for the separation of U and Pu. Some studies have explored the use of either a single UTEVA [1] or a combination of UTEVA with TRU [2], or TEVA with TRU [3] resin columns for the separation of U and Pu. In this work, we have developed a method for the sequential separation of U and Pu in urine samples using a single DGA resin followed by activity estimation using alpha spectrometry.

Materials and Methods

Ten 24 h urine samples were collected from the public to standardize the procedure. The samples were spiked with ^{232}U & ^{242}Pu radionuclide sourced from National Physical Laboratory, UK (Reference No: E05090391 / 01 and E05080352) in the range of 2-5 mBq. These samples were wet oxidized with conc. HNO_3 and H_2O_2 , followed by co-precipitation of calcium phosphate. The resulting residue was dissolved in 15 mL of 5M HNO_3 containing 1M $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, and 500 mg of NaNO_2 was added. This solution was loaded onto DGA resin (0.6-0.8 gm, 50-100 μm size), which had been pre-conditioned with 30 mL of 5M HNO_3 . The column was washed with 20 mL of 5M HNO_3 followed by 10 mL 2M HNO_3 . Initially, U was eluted from the column with 20 mL 0.1M HNO_3 followed by Pu elution

with 20 mL of 0.1M oxalic acid in 1M HCl. The eluted fractions of U & Pu fractions were electrodeposited and counted using alpha spectrometry for a duration of 86,400 secs.

Results

The study was conducted using different molarities HNO_3 , ranging from 3 to 8 M. It was observed that at 5M HNO_3 , clean separation of U and Pu in urine samples was achieved along with acceptable chemical recovery. The radiochemical recoveries for ^{232}U & ^{242}Pu were found to be in the range of 80% to 99% and 63% to 91%, respectively, with mean and standard deviations of $93.0\% \pm 7.9\%$ for ^{232}U and $74.6\% \pm 7.9\%$ for ^{242}Pu . The minimum detectable activity of the method is 0.5 mBq/d for a counting time of 86,400 secs. The method was validated by spiking samples with NPL tracers. Repeatability & reproducibility were evaluated by analysing samples with different analysts. Unat. in 3 out of 10 urine samples of public ranged from 1 to 2 mBq/d.

Conclusion

The sequential separation of U and Pu in urine samples using DGA resin and alpha spectrometry is presented. This method, which uses a single DGA column, offers a simpler and faster alternative to traditional anion exchange and other extraction chromatography techniques. It achieves acceptable chemical recovery rates and is suitable for addressing incidental exposures among of radiation workers.

References

1. Dubla et. al. (2024), *Radiat Prot Environ*, 47(1), 23-28.
2. Thakkar A.H., (2001), *J Radioanal Nucl Chem*, 248, 453-456.
3. Maxwell et. al. (2000), *J Radioact Radiochem*, 11, 28-33.

INTERCOMPARISON OF AMBIENT AND DIRECTIONAL DOSE EQUIVALENTS IN A TYPICAL NUCLEAR FACILITY

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Introduction

The monitoring of radiation exposure in nuclear facilities is a critical aspect of radiation protection and occupational safety. Among the key indicators of radiation dose rate are the ambient dose equivalent $H^*(10)$, which represents the dose to organs and tissues at a depth of 1 cm in the body, and the directional dose equivalent $H'(0.07)$, which reflects the dose to the skin at a depth of 0.007 cm. Accurate assessment and intercomparison of these dose equivalents are essential for ensuring compliance with regulatory limits and for optimizing worker safety. This study aims to investigate the relationship between $H^*(10)$ and $H'(0.07)$ under typical working conditions in a nuclear facility. By intercomparing these parameters, the study seeks to identify potential discrepancies, assess the implications for worker protection, and evaluate the performance of dose monitoring devices.

Materials and Methods

The Ambient Dose Equivalent rate $H^*(10)$ and Directional Dose Equivalent rate $H'(0.07)$ were measured using a RadEye B20 radiation monitor and a pancake-type GM detector with a window thickness of 1.8 to 2.0 mg/cm². $H^*(10)$ was measured for gamma radiation with energies ranging from 17 to 1300 keV, while $H'(0.07)$ was assessed for gamma/X-rays (5–12 keV) and beta radiation (100–200 keV). The measurements were conducted at two points at contact with the surface and 1 meter away at predefined locations in key areas of the nuclear facility, such as decontamination and different areas of operating plant.

The simultaneous monitoring of $H'(0.07)$ and $H^*(10)$ allowed for the estimation of the ratio between the two dose equivalents, calculated as:

$$\text{Ratio} = \frac{H'(0.07)}{H^*(10)}$$

Results

The ratio between the directional dose equivalent rate $H'(0.07)$ and the ambient dose equivalent rate $H^*(10)$ was calculated at two

measurement points: at contact with the surface and 1 meter away. At contact, the ratio ranged from 1.13 to 1.45, while at 1 meter, it varied from 1.00 to 1.84. The higher ratio at 1 meter is attributed to the production of secondary radiation in the air, primarily due to scatter and interaction of gamma rays with air molecules.

It was also observed that the ratio depends on the nature and geometry of the radioactive source. Locations with dispersed radioactive material exhibited higher ratios due to increased surface contamination and less self-attenuation, leading to elevated directional dose equivalents. In contrast, areas where the source was encapsulated and dense medium showed lower ratios since the self-attenuation reduced directional dose equivalently relative to ambient dose equivalent. This analysis highlights the influence of source characteristics and distance on dose distribution.

Conclusion

The ratio between ambient dose equivalent rate $H^*(10)$ and directional dose equivalent rate $H'(0.07)$ was observed to range from 1.00 to 1.84, indicating relatively small differences in exposure. Since the dose limit for skin is 25 times higher than that for whole-body (deep dose), the shallow body dose poses significantly lower risk in routine operations. Therefore, it may not be necessary to continuously monitor $H'(0.07)$, as compliance with ambient dose equivalent $H^*(10)$ limits inherently ensures skin dose safety.

References

Brown, P., & Gomez, E. (2022). Comparative Analysis of Extremity Doses in Nuclear Power Plant Workers. *Radiation Safety Journal*, 55(4), 200–210.

RADIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT OF BANDUHURANG OPEN CAST MINE IN JHARKHAND, INDIA

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Introduction

In terms of the health and safety aspects of the workers in uranium mining industry, it is very important for the assessment of various radiological parameters [1]. The two major concerns are the monitoring of the radon level produced inside the mine site and the exposure due to the gamma radiation. Radon-222 is gas ($T_{1/2}$: 3.82 days), produced from the alpha decay of Ra-226. Inhalation of radon causes internal dose whereas gamma radiation causes external dose of the workers. Most of the studies have been carried out for underground uranium mines in India. To establish the contributions of radon and gamma in the open cast mines is essential for the uranium industry in India. Present study has been carried out in the year 2023 and it includes the trend of radon and gamma levels in open cast mine at Banduhurang open cast mine (Lat.: 220 43' N to 220 43' 45" N, Long.: 880 9' 45" E to 860 11'30" E). Banduhurang mine is located at Singhbhum East, Jharkhand, around 6 km south of Tatanagar railway station.

Materials and Methods

AlphaGuard (DF-2000) and portable radiation detector (RADEYE B20-ER, Germany) were used to measure the radon and the gamma radiation levels respectively. Ambient dosimetry methodology is used for the assessment of radiation dose of mine workers. As a measure of quality control, the instruments were calibrated if required. Radon and gamma levels were monitored with a frequency of thrice in every month.

Results and discussions

Open cast mine working areas are directly connected to the natural environment, thus metrological conditions have significant role to affect the radiological condition of open cast mine. Radiological monitoring included all three shifts throughout the year. The radon levels have been observed in the range 20 – 300

Bqm-3 (mean: 40 Bqm-3). Variations in the levels have been observed around 4 to 5 times higher in the night as compare to the day time. The gamma radiation level was found to be in the range of 0.12 – 1.37 Gyh-1 (mean: 0.63 Gyh-1) and the metrological conditions do not affect significantly. Estimated dose for the workers (388 Nos.) have been observed in the range of 0.05 – 3.10 mSv (mean: 1.66 mSv).

Conclusion

Radon concentration is the major contributor for the assessment of dose in u/g U-mine whereas the gamma dose is the major contributor in the open cast mine. Contributions of external dose due to gamma radiation and internal dose due to radon are assessed around 85% & 15% respectively. These findings are just opposite trend of the reported values for underground uranium mine.

References

[1] Srivastava V. S. et.al. (2004) Proc. Of National Conference on Solid State Nuclear Track Detectors and Applications, at DAV College, Amritsar.

UNCERTAINTY EVALUATION FOR THE CALIBRATION OF RADIATION MONITORS

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Introduction

Radiation monitors are crucial instruments to measure the radiation fields and are used for planning and protection purposes. Accurate calibration of these devices is essential to ensure reliable and precise measurements. However, every measurement always has an associated uncertainty with it.

Uncertainty in measurement refers to the range of values within which the conventional true value lies. It's a way to quantify the “doubt” associated with a measurement result. Uncertainty in measurement arises due to various factors like, the uncertainty of reference standard, human error, environmental conditions, the measurement process itself, etc. It is important to note that the uncertainty is different from error. Error is the difference between the measured and true value while uncertainty is the spread in the true values.

Materials and Methods

The radiation monitors are calibrated by comparing its response against a standardised field at known true values. The calibration factor is then calculated which is the ratio of true value (T) to the mean observed value (O) of the instrument. The uncertainty in the calibration factor depends on statistical fluctuation in the readings of the monitor, its least count, uncertainty in the true value, distance of measurement, etc. The uncertainty is categorised as Type-A and Type-B uncertainty. Type A uncertainty is derived from statistical analysis of a series of measurements whereas Type B is evaluated using non-statistical methods, such as expert judgment, manufacturer's specifications, or calibration certificates. Each uncertainty component follows a particular probability distribution like normal or rectangular distribution.

If ‘y’ is the measurement result (in this case, the calibration factor) and x_i 's are the parameters that contribute to the uncertainty in y, then the contribution from each parameter is calculated as ^[1]

$$u_i(y) = c_i u(x_i)$$

Where, $u_i(y)$ is the standard uncertainty in y due to x_i , $u(x_i)$ is the standard uncertainty in x_i

which is calculated as $\delta x_i / \text{divisor}^{[2]}$ (δx_i is the associated uncertainty and the *divisor* is taken on the basis of probability distribution) and c_i is the sensitivity coefficient which tells how ‘y’ varies with changes in x_i and is expressed as partial derivative $|\partial y / \partial x_i|^{[1]}$. For example, the sensitivity coefficient for calibration factor due to statistical fluctuation in reading is- T/O^2 . In practice, the standard uncertainty is expressed in percentage i.e., $\frac{u_i(y)}{y} \times 100$ %. The combined uncertainty is the square root of the quadratic sum of all the Type A and Type B standard uncertainties.

Results

The uncertainty is reported in the form of expanded uncertainty i.e., the combined uncertainty multiplied by a suitable coverage value k value which tells the confidence level. For the calibration of radiation monitors measuring exposure rate, the uncertainty in the calibration factor is generally of the order of $\pm 4.5\%$ at $k=2$ which corresponds to a confidence level of $\sim 95\%$ for a normal distribution.

Conclusion

Uncertainty estimation is a crucial aspect of radiation monitor calibration. By carefully considering and quantifying the various sources of uncertainty, it is possible to assess the overall reliability and accuracy of the measurements.

References

1. JCGM 100:2008 Evaluation of Measurement Data-GUM.
2. NPL Measurement Good Practice Guide No. 49- The assessment of Uncertainty in Radiological Calibration and Testing.

DEVELOPMENT OF STANDALONE WOUND MONITOR FOR HIGH ENERGY PHOTON EMITTERS

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Introduction

In radiation emergency situations, particularly during incidents involving injuries in nuclear facilities, there is a risk of radioactive materials penetrating through wounds. In such situations, an in-vivo monitoring system is required for assessing the presence of radioactive material at the wound site. This assessment is important for determining the wound content, intake and Committed Effective Dose (CED) received by the radiation worker and /or to the public. To address this need, a trolley based standalone Wound Monitor (WM) has been developed to measure the internal dose due to high-energy photon (HEP) emitters ($E > 200 \text{ keV}$) on hand and forearm. It can be deployed at laboratory or personal decontamination center (PDC), and Operation Theater, as required.

Materials and Methods

The WM consists of a shielded cavity structure designed to facilitate the mapping and placement of the finger, palm, and forearm. The dimensions of the open space within the shielded cavity are 200 mm (W) x 300 mm (D) x 120 mm (H). The shielding arrangement is made of 50 mm lead (innermost layer) which is followed by 2 mm tin and finally, an outermost layer of 1 mm copper. The detector housing is made of seven lead rings, each 50 mm thick and 50 mm in height. It is also equipped with interlocked doors on both the front and rear sides of the shielded cavity. Inside the detector housing, the detector and the MCA are coupled together and fixed. A mechanism for allowing detector movement is incorporated to facilitate measurements at varying distances from the wound site. To enhance usability, the WM includes a camera and LED-based indicator for precise source positioning in relation to the centre of the detector. Transportation/portability of the WM is carried out using SS trolley with lifting mechanism. This trolley features a 2-dimensional movement platform on which the WM is mounted.

The WM employs a 51mm dia x 51mm thick NaI(Tl) detector coupled with a standalone 1 k MCA. The energy calibration of the system is set to $\sim 4 \text{ keV/channel}$. Provisions have been made to calibrate the WM for three specified distances from the detector to the wound: 5mm, 10mm and 20mm. For HEPs emitters, three distinct energy regions were made viz. ^{133}Ba (230-430 keV), ^{137}Cs (550-750 keV) and ^{60}Co (1050- 1450 keV).

Results and Discussion

The efficacy of shielding has been evaluated to determine its effectiveness in reducing background radiation by comparing detector acquisition data with and without the shield in place. The Background Reduction Factor (BRF) observed were 35, 21 and 19 for ^{133}Ba , ^{137}Cs and ^{60}Co , respectively.

The counting efficiency (CE) of WM for ^{133}Ba , ^{137}Cs and ^{60}Co was evaluated using BRIT disc sources for three counting geometries. The CE (cps.Bq^{-1}) for 5mm detector to wound distance is 1.38×10^{-1} , 7.1×10^{-2} and 7.63×10^{-2} for ^{133}Ba , ^{137}Cs and ^{60}Co respectively. The CE for 10 mm distance is 8.36×10^{-2} , 4.16×10^{-2} and 4.51×10^{-2} for ^{133}Ba , ^{137}Cs and ^{60}Co , respectively, whereas for 20mm distance CE observed is 5.62×10^{-2} , 2.78×10^{-2} and 3.08×10^{-2} for ^{133}Ba , ^{137}Cs and ^{60}Co respectively. MDA achieved is $\sim 2 \text{ Bq}$ for ^{137}Cs and ^{60}Co for 5mm distance and counting time of 5 minutes.

Conclusions

The system's ability to achieve a low MDA further underscores its utility in assessing radioactive contamination in wounds during radiation emergencies.

Reference:

Development of a Biokinetic Model for Radionuclide- Contaminated Wounds and Procedures for Their Assessment, Dosimetry and Treatment, NCRP Report -156 (2006)

EQUIVALENT DOSES TO DIFFERENT ORGANS DUE TO EXTERNAL EXPOSURE TO ¹³⁷CS POINT SOURCE

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Introduction

With a wide spread of usage of radioactive materials, there is a little potential for accidental external exposure due to hot spots in any pipelines in any radioactive plant or due to any other type of source. During such cases the person may not be wearing a TLD. In some accidental exposures amputation had to be carried out because of the non-availability of data on most exposed tissue. In this study equivalent doses to different organs are estimated for external exposure to 10 GBq ¹³⁷Cs point source kept at 1m distance at a height of 125 cm for 10 min exposure time.

Materials and Methods.

Numerical simulation was done with monte carlo code FLUKA using ICRP male and female voxel phantoms. The voxel phantom was incorporated using the .vxl file. An isotropic point source was defined using the BEAM and BEAMPOS card. USRBN card with energy as part and unit as 21 BIN was used to estimate the energy deposited in the voxels of individual organs. From the deposited energy the equivalent doses were calculated. In case of bone surface and bone marrow, the photon fluence were estimated for energies in the range of 0.01 to 0.661 MeV using USRTRACK and using the flux to dose conversion factor the dose was estimated. In case of bone marrow the flux was scored in all the spongiosa and for bone surface, the flux was scored in medullary cavity in addition to spongiosa. Five cycles were run with 1×10^7 histories so that the relative error is less than 1%. Only 0.661 MeV gamma photons were considered. Equivalent doses were estimated for the 25 organs.

Results

The effective dose is 0.117 mSv. In both male and female breast received the maximum dose because of its proximity to the source. The second was colon followed by thymus. The least dose was received by pancreas. The maximum deviation between male and female was in the equivalent dose to thymus. This is due to the smaller size of thymus in female and also due to the shorter distance. Compared to

⁶⁰Co the dose received is less (Christelle Huet, 2022), it is due to the less number of photons/emission and lesser energy.

Conclusion

Equivalent doses due to ¹³⁷Cs point source to different organs of male and female were estimated. Using this effective dose was calculated. Expertise in such calculation would assist to take countermeasures in any accidental external exposure scenarios involving different radionuclides, of different shapes located at various positions. Intervention action such as excision of tissue with high damage can be taken, which would prevent the other organs from getting damaged or amputated.

References

Christelle Huet et al., Radiation Measurements, Volume 150, January 2022, 106695.

INVESTIGATION ON THE ACTIVITY CONCENTRATION OF ALPHA EMITTERS IN THE GROUNDWATER SAMPLES- A STUDY FROM THE SOUTHWESTERN PART OF BENGALURU, KARNATAKA, INDIA

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Introduction

Water is one of the most important natural resources for most of lives on this planet. Hence, drinking water should be free from chemical, microbiological and radioactive contaminations. Drinking water sources are being contaminated due to the human activities, dissolution of salts, minerals and radioactive elements. Ingestion of radionuclides through drinking water causes chemical and radiological effects to the human population. Hence, the measurement of their concentration in drinking water is found to be very important.

Materials and methods

In the present study, the activity concentration of Uranium, ^{226}Ra , ^{222}Rn and ^{210}Po radionuclides in the groundwater samples (about 35) of the area around Manchanabele reservoir, Bengaluru, Karnataka state, India has been measured using a well calibrated LED fluorimeter, HPGe gamma ray spectrometer, RAD7 and plating technique respectively.

Results and discussion

The results reveal that the mass concentration of uranium is found to range from 0.88 ppb to 581.47 ppb with a GM of 20.82 ppb. The activity concentration of dissolved radon is found to range from 4.7 ± 1.9 Bq/L to 625.8 ± 47.8 Bq/L with GM of 38.3 ± 12.7 Bq/L respectively. About 34% and 91% of the samples show high concentration of uranium and dissolved radon when compared to maximum contaminant level of $30 \mu\text{g/L}$ and 11Bq/L respectively set by WHO. The activity concentration of radium and polonium ranges from 0.05 ± 0.01 to 0.88 ± 0.02 Bq/L with GM of 0.17 ± 0.005 Bq/L and 7.54 ± 0.5 to 41.9 ± 1.06 mBq/L with GM of 13.1 ± 0.6 mBq/L respectively. The observed values are below the guideline values (1Bq/L for Ra and 100mBq/L for Po). From the activity concentration of these radionuclides, the

annual effective dose due to ingestion for different age groups was evaluated using the relation found elsewhere (ICRP 1998). The result reveals that, infants receive higher radiation dose among these groups. The total annual effective dose from ingestion is found to range from 54.41 ± 6.4 to 2317.99 ± 124.8 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ with GM of 185.35 ± 34.7 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$.

Conclusions

The study shows that 57% of the groundwater samples impart the annual effective dose higher than the recommended value of $100 \mu\text{Sv/y}$ set by WHO. The physicochemical parameters like pH, TDS and conductivity measured in these ground water samples show no influence on the activity concentration of these radionuclides.

References

- World Health Organization (2004). *Guidelines for drinking-water quality*.
- World Health Organization. ICRP (1998) *Database of Dose Coefficients: Workers and Members of the Public*. (Oxford: Elsevier) (Version 1.0. ISBN 0 08 042 7510.

CONTAMINATION MONITORS CALIBRATION SYSTEM

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Introduction

Radioactive contamination monitoring plays a crucial role in ensuring safety in environments involving radioactivity. Effective contamination monitoring is essential for verifying that contamination levels remain within permissible limits, classifying work areas into controlled and supervised zones, preventing contamination spread, and facilitating dose assessment. The reliability and accuracy of contamination monitoring instruments are vital for their application in routine safety practices and emergency response. This paper describes a novel calibration system for contamination monitors, incorporating automated source movement, has been developed to enhance efficiency and eliminate personnel handling of radioactive sources.

Materials and Methods

The newly developed system has inbuilt two sources necessary for accurate evaluation. The system includes Am-241 and Sr(+Y)-90, each with an activity of 1 kBq and an uncertainty of $\pm 3\%$. The active dimensions of these sources are approximately 260 mm \times 180 mm. The dose rate at a 10 cm distance from the source surface is less than 1 μ Sv/h. To ensure accurate readings, the sources are arranged with sufficient spacing to prevent interference between them. The system supports detectors with maximum dimensions of 260 mm \times 180 mm and a weight of up to 2.5 kg. For safety, the radioactive sources are covered with stainless steel (SS) plates. The system's overall dimensions are 1000 mm \times 400 mm \times 1000 mm, with a total weight of 70 kg.

Calibration methodology

The calibration procedure begins by activating the system and unlocking it using a power key. Once operational, the stainless steel cover is removed, and the detector is placed in the designated position. A background count is performed for 60 seconds, after which the appropriate radiation source is selected for measurement. After measuring one source, the process is repeated for the next source. Once measurements are complete, the detector is

removed, the area is secured with the cover, and the system is powered down. The collected data is then used to calculate the detector's efficiency and conversion factor (CF). CF of a surface contamination instrument is given by the ratio of the instrument net reading to the certified surface emission rate of the source per unit time divided by the area of the source. $CF = (M - M_b) / SA$, SA is the certificated surface emission rate per unit area for the radionuclide source ($s^{-1}cm^{-2}$), M is the monitor count rate (s^{-1}) and M_b is the monitor background count (s^{-1}).

Conclusion

The developed calibration system represents a significant advancement in contamination monitoring, combining precision, safety, and user-friendly operation. The integration of automated source movement not only eliminates the need for personnel to handle radioactive sources but also enhances measurement consistency and operational efficiency. This system ensures accurate calibration of contamination monitors, enabling reliable assessment of radiological hazards in controlled and supervised environment which supports regulatory compliance and workplace safety.

References

1. Surface Contamination Measurement Presentation by International Atomic Energy Agency
2. Safety Reports Series No.16 for Calibration of radiation protection monitoring Instruments by International Atomic Energy Agency
3. Technical Reports Series no.120 for Monitoring of Radioactive Contamination on Surfaces by International Atomic Energy Agency

ONLINE ACTINIDE IN-VIVO MONITORING PORTAL: AN OVERVIEW

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Keywords : In-vivo monitoring, Phoswich detector, Array of HPGe, AIVMP

Introduction

The Actinide Monitoring Laboratory (AML) of the Radiation Safety and Systems Division (RSSD) is committed for assessment of internal contamination in radiation workers handling actinides specifically Pu, Am, and U, from various facilities of BARC. Utilizing Phoswich and arrays of high-purity germanium (HPGe) detectors within a totally shielded steel room, AML accurately estimates the levels of Pu, Am, and U in workers' lungs, liver, knees, and any wound sites. Currently, monitoring requests are initiated by health physicist (HP) at various plants through physical forms (10H). Following this, AML performs the assessments, processes the results, stores them in a local database, and subsequently provides monitoring reports to the respective plant authorities. To streamline the communication among the involved parties and to improve data processing, AML recognized the need for digital transformation of these activities. Accordingly, the Actinide In-vivo Monitoring Portal (AIVMP), an online platform, was developed and hosted on the Anunet server allowing access to facilities from both inside and outside the Trombay campus. This work presents the key features of AIVMP, highlighting its role in optimizing internal contamination monitoring and reporting of results across various facilities.

Materials and Methods

The AIVMP was developed using the Angular framework for the front-end, while the backend integrates PostgreSQL, Redis, and the nginx web server with Python FastAPI.

Results

AIVMP offers role based access to its registered users. During registration of a user in the portal, the required role is assigned by the administrator. For example, registered HPs of various plants can register their plant workers and fill their online form 10. If form 10H is previously filled for any worker, the required details can be updated without refilling all the entries. Lab user can verify the details and accept the forms by assigning the available

monitoring slot. The system automatically sends an email to the respective HP, informing them about the assigned monitoring slot. When a worker reports for monitoring at AML, the physical parameters (height, weight, age etc) are verified by the Lab user and measurements are performed using one of the detection systems. After acquisition is completed, the spectrum file is imported into the AIVMP, and analysis is performed to estimate internal contamination. The software subtracts the background spectrum based on the individual's weight and uses the net counts in the specified region of interest (ROI) to estimate activity in the organ. (Mishra, 2018) AIVMP allows users to select different monitoring geometries (such as lungs, liver, knee, lymph nodes and wound), and various monitoring types (including routine, baseline, follow-up, special, task-related, wound etc.). Two levels of report approval are provided in AIVMP. Once the analysis is complete, the draft report is online verified and signed by the OIC, AML and subsequently approved by the Section Head. Once report is approved, AIVMP sends an email to the respective plant HP, for viewing and downloading the monitoring report.

Conclusion

In summary, the AIVMP streamlines the internal contamination monitoring process by digitizing data entry, scheduling, and reporting. The portal's comprehensive functionality allows for precise tracking, improved data analysis, and optimized scheduling, ultimately saving time and resources while ensuring thorough safety oversight for radiation workers across BARC facilities.

Reference L Mishra et al (2018) Rad. Prot. Dosi. 181, 168–177.

STUDY ON THE RESPONSE CHARACTERISTICS OF BUBBLE DETECTOR WITH RESPECT TO REM COUNTER IN NEUTRON DETECTION

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Introduction

The bubble dosimeter is one of the best suitable neutron dosimeter for neutron dose rate measurements in the presence of intense gamma fields. A compact and reusable bubble dosimeter with high neutron sensitivity was developed by immobilising the superheated droplets in a suitable polymer matrix.

Materials and Methods

Bubble dosimeters consist of polyacrylamide matrix in polycarbonate vial in which fine droplets of sensitive low boiling point liquid (isobutene) is dispersed in superheated state. When these droplets are struck by neutrons they evaporate to form bubbles and by counting the number of bubbles and with a calibration graph, the neutron dose rate is estimated. Preparation of bubble dosimeter involves incorporation of known quantity of superheated liquid in glycerol based acrylamide monomer matrix, dispersion of superheated liquid as fine droplets in the matrix by a mechanical stirrer and polymerisation using gamma chamber for immobilisation of droplets in matrix. The sensitivity of bubble dosimeters were tested using a 5 Ci Am-Be neutron source, having an emission rate of 107 neutrons/sec.

Results

The response of the calibrated bubble dosimeters were studied in estimating the neutron dose at various distance and heights. Linearity of the dose response and dose rate response of the bubble detector is presented elsewhere. In the present study, dose rate varied from 48-2.8 mR/h in Rem counter and 56-3.2 mR/h in bubble detectors with respect to distance varied from 50-250 cm in the increment of 50cm. The variation in the dose with respect to height varied from 0-40 cm in the increment of 10 cm was found to be 48-15.5mR/h in the Rem counters and 60-25.3 mR/h in the case of bubble detectors. Response of the both the detectors were studied and the results showed comparatively higher dose rates when measured with bubble detectors. Linear

regression plots of the detectors with respect to distance and height displayed r² value higher than 0.9 which describes that the higher dose rate measured by bubble detectors is not varying randomly. Experiments related to the isotropic angular response and varying response to neutron sources with different energy may explain the dose rate difference among the two neutron detectors used in this study.

Conclusion

Response of the low-cost, high performance neutron bubble dosimeters found to be satisfactory. In comparison with Rem counters, bubble detectors are useful tool in on-site monitoring of neutron dose and have a great potential to be further developed and applied in a wider range of neutron fields.

References

1. D. Ponraju, H. Krishnan, S. Viswanathan and R. Indira, *Radiation Protection Dosimetry*, 144, pp 177-181 (2011).
2. Mala Das, B. K. Chatterjee, B. Roy, S.C. Roy, *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in physics Research*, A 452 (2000) 273-279

INVESTIGATION OF MODIFIED FRICKE DOSIMETER FOR LOW-DOSE IRRADIATION APPLICATIONS

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Keywords: Chemical Dosimeter, Fricke and Low-dose irradiations.

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Introduction

The Ferrous and Ferric chemical dosimeter (Fricke dosimeter) is one of the most commonly used chemical dosimeters with acceptable accuracy in the 20–400 Gy dose range. The Fricke dosimeter is unsuitable for low-dose irradiation (1-10 Gy) applications. The modified Ferrous and Ferric chemical dosimeter with Benzoic acid is used for low-dose irradiation applications. This study evaluates the dosimetric parameters (molar extinction coefficient and chemical yield) of the FBX (Ferrous-Benzoic-Xylenol) dosimeter in low-dose irradiation applications.

Materials and Methods

The FBX dosimeter is prepared with the following chemical composition: 0.2 mol m⁻³ Ferrous Ammonium Sulfate, 5.0 mol m⁻³ Benzoic acid, and 0.20 mol m⁻³ Xylenol orange (XO) in 40.0 mol m⁻³ Sulphuric acid. The molar extinction coefficient value of the FBX dosimeter is determined from the measured absorbance values at 548 nm for different Fe⁺³ ion concentrations. The absorbance values are measured using the UV-visible spectrometer. The molar extinction coefficient (ϵ) is found to be 18753±530 M⁻¹cm⁻¹.

Results and Discussions

The absorbed dose is determined from the established calibration plot between the absorbance values at different dose values. The FBX dosimeter is irradiated in the 1-7 Gy dose range. The radiochemical yield (G) is defined as the number of Fe⁺³ ions formed per 100 eV of energy absorbed in the chemical dosimeter after irradiation. The chemical yield (G) is determined from the calibration plot between absorbance and absorbed dose values. The average G value is found to be 4.7±0.1 X 10⁻⁶ mol/J.

Conclusions

Fricke Chemical dosimeters based on Ferrous and Ferric solutions is used for determination of absorbed dose measurements. For the estimation of absorbed dose in the range

of 1- 10 Gy, modified Fricke dosimeter with benzoic acid and xylenol orange is used. In this study FBX based chemical dosimeter was evaluated for low dose irradiation applications. The molar extinction was found to be 18753±530 M⁻¹cm⁻¹. The chemical yield was found to be 4.7±0.1 X 10⁻⁶ mol/J.

References

1. Moussous O, Medjadj T, Benguerba M. FBX aqueous chemical dosimeter for measurement of dosimetric parameters. Appl Radiat Isot. 2011 Feb;69(2):399-402.

IN-VITRO STUDY ON THE POTENTIALITY OF TRADITIONAL BLACK SEEDS AND INDIAN BLACK BERRY EXTRACTS AS NATURAL RADIO PROTECTORS

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Keywords: Radioprotectors, MTT assay, Low dose X-rays, HEK 293, Indian Black beery, Black seeds

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Introduction

Radiation therapy in past decade emerged as a critical modality of cancer treatment. The complexity of radiation therapy capable to overcome the identifying potential novel radiation modifiers which boost the effectiveness of low levels of radiation on cancer as well as protect normal cells from radiation. Traditional Black seeds and Indian blackberry extracts have been shown to possess anticancer effects that can hinder the development of cancerous cells. Current research looks at the in-vitro analysis of the Traditional Black seeds and Indian blackberry extracts serve as radio protectors in low radiation of X-rays exposure.

Methods

The Traditional Black seeds and Indian blackberries are collected as samples from local markets and investigated. In the present work, the orbital shaker extraction is used with the high-polarity solvent methanol in acidified conditions for both samples. Invitro experiment is used to determine the radioprotective effects of Traditional Black seeds and Indian blackberries on separately and in combination with low radiation X-rays in normal cells (Human embryonic Kidney HEK 293).\

Results

The viability and cytotoxicity were determined using the MTT assay. Doseresponse cell survival curves for normal cell lines treated with Low dose X-rays are illustrated based on the MTT assay results.

Conclusion

It has been shown that traditional black seeds and Indian blackberry extracts having radiation-protective properties that boosts normal cell survival rates. A new approach to understanding the evolution of natural radioprotectors and other radiation modifiers which enhance the radiotherapy treatments in future.

STUDY ON MEASUREMENT OF ANISOTROPY FACTOR FOR A SEALED 185GBQ AM-BE SOURCE

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Introduction

Am-Be is widely used as a neutron source for various applications in nuclear industries. It has a long half life ($T_{1/2} = 433$ years) and a good yield of 2.2×10^6 n/s.Ci. Am-Be source produce neutrons of wide spectrum with energies ranging from 0.025eV to 11MeV and an average energy 4.5MeV. It is used as a calibration source for calibrating neutron survey meters. Measurement of neutron emission rate from Am-Be source is an essential factor prior to use as a calibration source. It is measured by using Manganese sulphate ($MnSO_4$) bath technique or a comparison with a calibrated source using a proper neutron detector such as Long Counter. In IGCAR, it is planned to set up a neutron calibration facility with a sealed 185Bq Am-Be source. The exact neutron emission rate is measured with $MnSO_4$ bath set up at RSSD, BARC and it is found to be 1.1×10^7 n/s. As it is a volume source, it is important to have isotropic emission from the source. So, amount anisotropy from neutron source has to determined before its use as a calibration source. In this work, methodology used to determine anisotropy factor for the 185GBq Am-Be source (X14 type encapsulation) in polar and equatorial direction is described and results are presented.

Materials and Methods

Experimental setup has rotating disc for source and neutron monitor kept at rest. The disc is rotated with a stepper motor controller which is remotely operated by a PC. The experiment is carried out in a large room (8x8x5m) and on a platform from 1.5m from ground level to reduce scattering. Neutron emission rate measurements were carried out in three directions with Atomtex make Neutron Monitor. The first measurement was done by placing the source with the symmetry axis along the Z direction and rotating the source Z-axis to obtain an equatorial measurement. Then the source was tilted so to have the symmetry axes along the neutron monitor's direction and rotated on X-axis and then a Y-axis. Two polar scans were acquired in this configuration with

different rotation (90 degree) along the symmetry axis in order to average possible equatorial anisotropies. Equatorial and Polar scans were taken over the angular range 0 to 180 degree in steps of 15 degree. Background neutron measurement was also carried out for subtraction from actual neutron counts from the source.

Conclusion

Results of anisotropic measurements showed that anisotropy factor is observed in the equatorial scan within the statistical errors. In polar scan, it is found to be a maximum of 1.02 at an angle 90 degree i.e., 2% deviation. Overall the anisotropy factor was found in good agreement with those reported in Literature.

References

- N.J.Roberts, N.N.Moiseev, M.Kralik, Metrologia 48(2011) S239 M.
Amendola, S. Loreti et.al, Journal of Radio analytical and Nuclear Chemistry 301(2014) 109.
H. Park, K. Choi, J. Lee, K.B. Lee, M.Hahan, M.Kralik, Journl of Korean society 47(2005) 603-609.

CLINICAL AND ECONOMIC CONSIDERATIONS OF KILOVOLTAGE ARC BEAM THERAPY

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Keywords: Kilovoltage (kV) arc beam therapy, Clinical efficacy and Treatment planning and delivery processes

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Introduction

Kilovoltage (kV) arc beam therapy is an advanced radiotherapy technique that uses low-energy X-rays (50-150 kV) to target superficial tumors. This modality offers a unique therapeutic profile, with the ability to deliver high-precision radiation doses to tumors while sparing deeper healthy tissues. The growing interest in kV arc therapy stems from its clinical efficacy, operational simplicity, and cost-effectiveness, making it a promising alternative to traditional megavoltage (MV) radiation therapy, particularly for resource-limited settings. This study explores its clinical applications, technical advantages, and economic considerations.

Methods

A comprehensive review of existing literature and clinical studies was conducted to evaluate the clinical efficacy, workflow optimization, and cost parameters associated with kV arc beam therapy. Treatment outcomes, toxicity profiles, equipment requirements, and economic data were compared to conventional MV techniques. Key parameters such as treatment planning, dose distribution, and infrastructure costs were analyzed to assess the feasibility and scalability of kV arc therapy across different healthcare settings.

Results

Clinically, kV arc beam therapy showed significant advantages in managing superficial malignancies, such as skin cancers, head-and-neck lesions, and chest wall recurrences. The therapy's steep dose gradient and high conformity allowed for effective tumor control while sparing adjacent tissues, thereby reducing acute and long-term toxicities. Treatment planning and delivery processes were simplified, with reduced equipment and shielding requirements compared to MV systems. Economically, kV arc beam therapy demonstrated reduced capital investment and operational costs. Compact systems and lower maintenance demands made it feasible for

smaller clinical facilities. Shorter treatment times and increased patient throughput further enhanced operational efficiency. The lower financial burden associated with this modality improved patient accessibility, especially in underserved regions.

Conclusion

Kilovoltage arc beam therapy is a clinically effective and economically viable option for treating superficial tumors. Its simplified infrastructure requirements, cost-efficiency, and reduced toxicity profile make it an attractive alternative, particularly in resource-constrained environments. However, its limited penetration depth restricts application to shallow tumors, necessitating careful patient selection. Future developments in imaging and adaptive planning are expected to enhance its precision and broaden its clinical utility. This modality holds significant promise as a complementary tool in modern radiation oncology, providing improved accessibility and outcomes for patients worldwide.

References:

1. Breikreutz DY, Renaud MA, Seuntjens J, Weil MD, Zavgorodni S, Bazalova-Carter M. Inverse optimization of low-cost kilovoltage x-ray arc therapy plans. *Med Phys*. 2018. doi:10.1002/mp.13153
2. M.B. B, M. F. Role of radiotherapy in cancer control in low-income and middle-income countries. *Lancet Oncol*. 2006;7(7):584-595.
3. Otto K. Volumetric modulated arc therapy : IMRT in a single gantry arc. *Med Phys*. 2008;35(1).

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF ELECTRONIC PERSONNEL DOSIMETER FOR NEUTRON DOSE EQUIVALENT $H^*(10)$ MEASUREMENT USING DIFFERENT NEUTRON SOURCES

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Introduction:

In radiation protection, Electronic Personnel Dosimeter (EPD) plays a vital role in controlling personnel exposure in a mixed-field of gamma and neutron radiation. In this study, the performance of an EPD model name NRF-31 with respect to neutron dose rates was evaluated by using two different neutron sources (PuO₂ and Pu-Be).

Materials & Methods

Experimental Measurements

In this experiment, the field performance of EPD: NRF-31 (Fuji Electrical Co Ltd) was evaluated by using two neutron sources such as Plutonium oxide (source strength: 6.32E+5 n/s) and Pu-Be (source strength: 1.66E+06 n/s) [1]. This dosimeter has three Si semiconductor detectors one each for gamma, fast neutron and slow neutron. Each sensor has 10 x 10 mm² p-type low-resistivity silicon wafer on which amorphous silicon was deposited [3]. The sources were kept away at least from a distance of 1m from the surrounding structural material to minimise intrusion of scattering neutrons. Four EPDs were simultaneously exposed at 10 cm, 20 cm, 30 cm and 50 cm distance from the sources for measurement of dose.

Monte Carlo Calculation:

Monte Carlo code, Fluka was used for this calculation. FLUKA[2] is a general purpose tool for calculations of particle transport and interactions with matter, dosimetry, detector design etc. The watt fission spectrum of ²⁴⁰Pu was used for estimation of neutron dose from PuO₂ box considering 70% neutrons are from spontaneous fission and 30% neutrons are from (α -n) reactions and for PuBe source, neutron spectra available in literature was used in simulation.

Results and Discussion

For PuO₂ source, the theoretically estimated neutron dose equivalent rates $H^*(10)$ by FLUKA and the measured of neutron dose equivalents by

EPD: NRF-31 is in good agreement with maximum deviation of 27.19%. Similarly for Pu-Be source, the theoretical calculated value and experimentally measured value by EPD: NRF-31 were concurrent with maximum variation of 8.64%. These maximum deviations in measurements from theoretically calculated values are attributed to anisotropy of the source to detector geometry when source was very close to the detector. However, the measured dose values were almost matched with the theoretical values for larger distances.

Conclusion

From the comparison of theoretically estimated and measured values of ambient neutron dose equivalent $H^*(10)$ for Plutonium Oxide source and Pu-Be source, it is evident that the performance of the NRF-31 dosimeters is satisfactory. The dosimeter has an added advantage of measuring the thermal as well as fast neutron doses.

References

1. Vega C, H. R., et al. "Characterization of a ²³⁹PuBe isotopic neutron source." (2012).
2. Ferrari A, Sala P, Fasso A, Ranft J. FLUKA: A Multi-Particle Transport Code. 2005
3. Tomoya Nunomiya, et al "Development of new Generation-type Multi-functional Electronic Personal Dosemeters" Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology, sup5, 175-178, 2008.

INTER-COMPARISON OF PASSIVE & ACTIVE PERSONAL DOSIMETER FOR MULTIPLE GAMMA ENERGIES AT MOX FUEL FABRICATION

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Introduction

To control radiation exposure, regulatory body has recommended an annual effective dose limit of 30 mSv with a constraint of 20 mSv for occupational workers [1]. The most accurate method for monitoring the external dose is to measure Hp (10) with a calibrated dosimeter [2]. The fabrication of MOX (mixed oxide) fuel pins for PFBR involves handling of DDUO₂ and PuO₂ in bulk quantity through powder metallurgy route. The MOX powder is mixed & milled followed by compaction and sintering for Pelletisation. These pellets are loaded in SS tubes & then wire wrapped to obtain finished fuel pins. All these operations are carried out manually in Glove Boxes (GBs), thus external exposure is a concern. To control external exposure on the spot, use of an active personal dosimeter (DRD) is essential along with a passive personal dosimeter (TLD) at MOX fuel fabrication (FF). Since various make & model of DRDs & EPDs are available for personal monitoring, an inter-comparison of different DRDs & EPDs with respect to legal dosimeter TLDs [CaSO₄(Dy)] for multiple energies was carried out at FF and presented in this paper.

Materials and Method

At FF the external exposures are mainly due to low energy X-ray & gamma ray emitted from isotopes of plutonium & uranium (17 keV to 400 keV) and ²⁴¹Am (60 keV) present in MOX. In this study, five different types of dosimeters (Polimaster make GM tube based EPDs, Arrow-tech make Quartz fibre Ionization Chamber based DRDs, Thermo Fisher Scientific & Mirion make pin diode based EPDs along with TLD) were exposed under different gamma energies. During the experiment, three standard sources, ²⁴¹Am (60 keV), ¹³⁷Cs (662 keV) & ⁶⁰Co (1173 & 1332 keV) were used for the specific gamma energy response study. However, for multiple energy responses, the same set of dosimeters were exposed with MOX and PuO₂ containers. In each experiment set of three unit of each type of DRDs were exposed along with TLDs in a uniform radiation field. Response of DRDs

were recorded and compared with TLDs reading.

Results & Discussion

Based on the measurements, the percentage variation of all types of DRDs with respect to TLDs is estimated. For standard sources, the percentage variation in Polimaster make EPDs found between (-) 54 to 16 % with respect to TLDs, whereas the variation in Arrow-tech make DRDs and EPDs of Thermo Fisher Scientific & Mirion make was found to be (-) 13 to 12 %. However, for lower energies gamma of MOX and PuO₂, the percentage variation in Polimaster make EPDs was found between (-) 64 to (-) 17 %, while Arrow-tech make DRDs and Thermo Fisher & Mirion make EPDs showed variation between(-) 10 to 10 % with respect to TLDs.

Conclusion

The Arrow-tech make quartz fiber Ionization Chamber based DRDs and pin diode based EPDs of Thermo Fisher Scientific & Mirion make are found to be in good agreement with the expected values. However, GM tube based Polimaster make EPDs were found unfit for personal monitoring at MOX fuel fabrication.

References

1. Radiation Protection Manual for BARC Facilities- SM-2020.
2. IAEA-TECDOC-1564, Intercomparison of Personal Dose Equivalent Measurements by Active Personal Dosimeters, Nov.-2007.

COMPARISON OF KILOVOLTAGE ARC BEAM THERAPY AND VOLUMETRIC-MODULATED ARC THERAPY USING MONTE CARLO SIMULATION

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Introduction

This study compares kilovoltage arc beam therapy (KV-ABT) and volumetric-modulated arc therapy (VMAT) using Monte Carlo simulations to assess their dosimetric performance. The analysis focuses on key parameters, including dose distribution, target coverage, and organ-at-risk (OAR) sparing. KV-ABT, characterized by high soft-tissue contrast and rapid dose falloff, is evaluated for its efficacy in treating superficial lesions. In contrast, VMAT, known for its conformal dose delivery to complex target geometries, is analyzed for deep-seated tumors. Monte Carlo simulations ensure precise modeling of photon interactions and patient tissue heterogeneities, providing insights into the clinical suitability and advantages of these advanced techniques.

Materials and Methods

Monte Carlo simulation was used to model radiation transport for both KV-ABT and VMAT across various clinical scenarios. KV-ABT was evaluated for its ability to utilize kilovoltage X-rays, noted for high imaging contrast and precise targeting of superficial lesions. VMAT was assessed for its use of megavoltage X-rays with modulated beam intensity and continuous gantry rotation, enabling conformal dose delivery for complex geometries.

Results

KV-ABT achieved sharp dose gradients and minimized dose exposure to adjacent normal tissues, demonstrating its efficacy for superficial tumors. However, limited penetration depth restricted its applicability to deeper or larger lesions. Conversely, VMAT provided superior target coverage for deep-seated tumors, reduced dose heterogeneity, and better OAR sparing due to its conformal capabilities. The complementary nature of the techniques was evident, with KV-ABT excelling in superficial cases and VMAT proving effective for geometrically intricate or deeper targets.

Conclusions

Monte Carlo simulations confirm that KV-ABT and VMAT serve distinct roles in radiation therapy. KV-ABT is optimal for treating superficial lesions, while VMAT is the standard for complex, deep-seated tumors. Treatment modality selection should be guided by tumor location, size, and clinical objectives, with Monte Carlo simulations enhancing the accuracy of dose predictions to optimize patient outcomes.

References

1. Dylan Y Breitkreutz, Michael D Weil, Magdalena Bazalova-Carter “External beam radiation therapy with kilovoltage X-rays” *Physica Medica*, 79, 2020, 103-112.
2. Robin Hill, David Eaton, Clive Baldock, “Kilovoltage therapy is well and truly alive and needed in a modern radiotherapy centre” *Physical and Engineering Sciences in Medicine* (2021) 44:341–345.

MONTE CARLO CALCULATION OF DOSE DEPOSITION KERNELS FOR ^{32}P AND $^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$ BETA SOURCES USED IN NUCLEAR MEDICINE THERAPY

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Objective

Beta-emitting isotopes are increasingly being used in radionuclide therapy due to its short range. The point kernel-based convolution/superposition method is a preferred patient-specific dose calculation method in nuclear medicine. The radial distributions of dose around point source in an infinite water medium are known as dose point kernels (DPK). It represents the fraction of emitted energy deposited in a voxel. In this study, DPK is calculated for ^{32}P and $^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$ beta sources using the EDKnrc user-code.

serve as inputs for convolution technique to carry out dose calculations.

Materials & Methods

The EDKnrc user-code simulates the emission of photons or electrons (monoenergetic or polyenergetic) from an isotropic point source and corresponding energy spread in a phantom. It calculates dose and energy deposition kernel (EDK) in the regions defined in the simulation. Also the code estimates different energy fractions such as total, primary and radiative, deposited in the geometry. Monte Carlo simulation is preferred in EDK calculation as it considers transport of secondary particles and their interactions. In simulation, an isotropic point beta source is placed in a water phantom of radius 10 cm and phantom was divided in to spherical shells of radius 5 μm . Energy deposition is calculated up to $1.2R_{90}$ where R_{90} is the radius of the sphere within which 90 % of the emitted energy is absorbed. Up to 107 primary histories were simulated. DPK was calculated by:

$$j\left(\frac{r}{R_{90}}, E\right) = 4 \pi \rho r^2 D(r, E) R_{90} / E$$

where r is the radial distance to the middle of the spherical shells, ρ is the density of the medium, $D(r, E)$ is the dose per particle at distance r and E is the average energy of the beta source.

Results and conclusion

Dose deposition kernels are calculated for ^{32}P and $^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$ beta source using Monte Carlo methods. The calculated dose kernels will

THE EFFECTS OF PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES ON GAMMA EMITTING NATURAL RADIONUCLIDE LEVELS IN THE SOIL OF TIRUNELVELI DISTRICT, TAMIL NADU, INDIA

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Introduction

Humans are exposed to natural radioactivity at different levels depending on the natural radioactive elements present in each area; as such, researchers investigated the natural environmental radiation and radioactivity in soils to conduct background status and detect environmental radioactivity (Radhakrishna et al., 1993). The activity concentrations of ²³²Th and ²³⁸U series and ⁴⁰K have to be determined to calculate the gamma radiation dose caused by these radionuclides. However, there are few investigations relating to the influences of the physicochemical properties of soil on the distribution of natural radionuclides in the soil. The aim of this study is to estimate natural radioactivity content in soil and investigate the relationship between soil parameters and natural radionuclide levels using multivariate statistical analysis.

Materials and Methods

The soil samples collected at different locations in the Tirunelveli district using the grid method. The samples were sun dried followed by drying in an air oven. The soil samples were made to pass through a 1 -mm mesh sieve and are packed in a transparent PVC container, and then kept for four weeks to ensure that the radioactive decay products of ²³⁸U (²²⁶Ra) and ²³²Th (²²⁸Ra) reached secular equilibrium. A 3×3 inch NaI(Tl) detector was used to determine the activity concentration of natural radionuclides in soil samples with a counting period of 20,000 seconds. A standard procedure is followed for the physicochemical analysis of soil samples.

Results and Discussions

The activity concentration and mean (in bracket) values for ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K are 1.70 – 63.24 (12.98), 15.75– 62.24 (162.89), and 46.17 - 456.82 (453.04) Bq kg⁻¹

respectively. The findings show that the mean activity of ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K is higher, while ²³⁸U is lower than the global average values (UNSCEAR, 2000). The average activities were seen in the following order ⁴⁰K > ²³²Th > ²³⁸U. The effects of organic matter content, textural properties and pH value of soil samples on the natural radionuclide levels were studied using multivariate statistical analysis. Natural radioactivity increased with decreasing particle size, and it is in good agreement with earlier findings.

Conclusion

The results of natural radioactivity (²³⁸U, ²³²Th & ⁴⁰K) have been detected in the soil samples in and around Tirunelveli district, Tamil Nadu and compared with the worldwide average. The relations between natural radionuclide level and the physical and chemical properties of studied soil samples were mainly clarified with Pearson correlation, factor, and cluster analysis, and it was found that clay and silt content was the most effective parameter on the natural radionuclide levels.

Reference

Radhakrishna, A.P., Somashekarappa, H.M., Narayana, Y., Siddappa, K. (1993), *Health Physics*, **65** (4), 390–395.

UNSCEAR, (2000) Report to the General Assembly with Annex B: Exposures from natural radiation sources.

ESTIMATION OF ¹³⁷Cs BODY BURDEN IN EXTERNALLY CONTAMINATED RADIATION WORKERS

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Introduction

In India, NaI(Tl) based standing geometry Quick Scan Whole Body Monitor (QSWBM) has been employed in various laboratories for in-vivo monitoring of radiation workers. While whole body counters look for internal contamination, it has been observed occasionally that fixed external contamination in subjects lead to prominent peaks in the detector spectra which can be mistaken for internal contamination. It is important to distinguish external contamination from internal contamination for accurate internal dose estimation.

Materials and Methods

As described in various studies, the presence of external contamination can be identified by anterior and posterior counting of the subject. It is also possible to understand the qualitative picture of contamination using the relative scoring in the two detectors of QSWBM. FLUKA simulations [1] were performed to estimate the ratio between count rates in anterior and posterior (R) whole body counting geometry for BOMAB phantom with internally contaminated ¹³⁷Cs. The ratios were also calculated for external contamination at several locations on BOMAB anterior surface to understand the deviations from internally contaminated case. If the subject is identified to have external contamination which is difficult to be decontaminated within first few days of the intake, internal burden can be assessed using direct urine sample spectrometry using HPGe detection system. Quality Control sample provided by IAEA as a part of worldwide proficiency test, IAEA-TERC-2023-01 packed in 250mL bottle geometry was utilised to calibrate the system for these measurements.

Results

FLUKA simulations with BOMAB phantom geometry having uniform internal ¹³⁷Cs distribution yielded R = 0.91. However, these ratios for external contamination on the anterior plane ranged high, from 1.9 in arms to 9.4 in thorax-pelvis regions for ¹³⁷Cs. Following an incident, if the external

contamination persists for a few days such that whole body counting spectra is not representing the internal contamination alone, direct HPGe measurements of urine samples can be used to estimate activity burden. For 250mL measurement geometry (which is 6.4 times lesser volume than reference daily excretion of 1.6L) and 10000s counting time, MDA value is estimated as 11Bq/d after volume normalization. It may be noted that corresponding Derived Recording Level (DRL) values for ¹³⁷Cs inhalation (5µm AMAD, type F), 1day and 10 days post intake are 3548.4Bq/d and 75Bq/d respectively [2], which are significantly above MDA.

Conclusion

Present work provided insights about ¹³⁷Cs body burden estimation for externally contaminated radiation workers. R values showed near unity values (posterior counting shows slightly higher value) for internal contamination while external contamination at various parts give notably higher range of values. Direct urine spectrometry is proven useful in quicker estimation of internal dose if subject is externally contaminated. HPGe system was calibrated for standard geometry to enable such measurements.

References

- [1] C. Ahdida *et al.*, “New Capabilities of the FLUKA Multi-Purpose Code,” *Frontiers in Physics*, vol. 9, Jan. 2022
- [2] ICRP, “ICRP Publication 137: Occupational Intakes of Radionuclides: Part 3,” *Annals of the ICRP*, vol. 46, no. 3–4, 2017.

ASSESSMENT OF COSMIC RADIATION DOSE RATE AT VISAKHAPATNAM USING THERMOLUMINESCENCE DOSIMETERS AND SOIL RADIOACTIVITY

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Keywords: Cosmic ray, TLD, Dosimetry, Gamma.

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Introduction

Environmental radiation dose mainly arises from terrestrial radiation and cosmic rays. Terrestrial radiation is due to the decay of radioactive materials in the earth crust while cosmic rays come to earth from outer space and cosmic dose rate varies with altitude. Terrestrial radiation levels depends upon the concentration of ^{238}U , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K in soil. In this study cosmic dose rate is estimated for Visakhapatnam city using Thermoluminescence dosimeters (TLD) dose and soil radioactivity measurements

Materials and Methods

Environmental gamma radiation monitoring is carried out using Thermoluminescence dosimetry (TLD) technique. TLDs bearing an identification number are deployed at a pre-designated location around Visakhapatnam for a period of three months. After three months these exposed TLDs are replaced by new set of TLDs. The exposed TLDs are retrieved back to BARC for the further analysis. Annual values for all the locations are evaluated based on sum of the average quarterly values. Soil samples from various locations where TLDs are deployed were collected and analysed for soil radioactivity using High Purity Germanium (HPGe) Radiation Detector. Terrestrial dose rate at a distance of 1m from ground was estimated using

$$D \text{ (nGy/hr)} = ((A_U * C_U) + (A_{Th} * C_{Th}) + (A_K * C_K))$$

Where, A_U , A_{Th} and A_K are specific activities of ^{238}U , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K respectively. C_U , C_{Th} and C_K are conversion factors in terms of (nGy/hr)/(Bq/Kg) for ^{238}U (0.462), ^{232}Th (0.604) and ^{40}K (0.0417) respectively (UNSCEAR 2000). These readings were then converted to annualized values. TLDs are routinely subjected to different quality control tests to maintain the reliability of environmental radiation data.

Results

The specific activity levels of Uranium, Thorium and Potassium present in the soil at different locations were used to calculate the terrestrial dose rate (nGy/hr) using UNSCEAR factors. The calculated terrestrial dose rate values are in the range of 0.6 mGy/y to 1.7 mGy/y. While the environmental gamma radiation levels measured using TLDs around Vishakhapatnam were found to be in the range of 0.8 mGy/y to 2 mGy/y. It is clearly seen from the results that there is a large variation in external gamma radiation levels as well as in calculated terrestrial dose rate values between different locations. This variation is due to natural non-uniform distribution in soil radioactivity. Radionuclides particularly ^{232}Th and ^{40}K in soil show large place to place variation. Based upon the computed terrestrial dose due to above mentioned elements the cosmic radiation component for Vishakhapatnam works out to be in the range of 0.20 mGy/y to 0.26 mGy/y.

Conclusion

Visakhapatnam is situated at coastal region of Andhra Pradesh with the 45 metres of average elevation from sea level. The estimated cosmic radiation dose rate for Vishakhapatnam matches well with values of other coastal cities of India like Mumbai, Kolkata and Chennai (Nambi, et al 1986). Reported value is also comparable with the worldwide average radiation dose rate of 0.27 mGy/y at sea level due to cosmic rays (UNSCEAR Annex B 2008)

References

- UNSCEAR (2000), *Annex A., New York.*
- Nambi K.S.V., Bapat V.N., David M., Sundaram V.K., Sunta C.M., Soman S.D. (1986) *HPD, BARC, India.*
- UNSCEAR. (2008) *Report to the General Assembly, vol. 1, Annex. B, New York.*

PREOPERATIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL GAMMA RADIATION MONITORING AROUND UPCOMING GHAVP NUCLEAR POWER PLANT, HARYANA.

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Keywords: Preoperational, GHAVP, Absorbed dose, TLD, Environmental gamma.

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Introduction

Monitoring of gamma radiation levels in and around the environs of nuclear installations in India forms an important function of Health, Safety and Environment Group. This is essential not only for studying the long term trends of the radiation levels around the installations if any, but also for assuring the population at large about the negligible extent of the environmental impact due to the operation of nuclear facilities. Preoperational gamma radiation monitoring forms a crucial activity in assessing the baseline radiological environment before commissioning any nuclear power plant. Such data is essential for quantifying the environmental impact of plant operations and ensuring regulatory compliance. This study focuses on preoperational gamma radiation monitoring around the upcoming Gorakhpur Haryana Anu Vidyut Pariyojana (GHAVP) nuclear power plant in Haryana. Thermoluminescent dosimeters (TLDs) were deployed to measure environmental gamma radiation levels over two years at ten locations around the plant site on quarterly basis.

Materials and Methods

Thermoluminescence dosimeters (TLDs) are widely used for environmental monitoring programme. The advantages of passive dosimeters for environmental monitoring are that they are small, cheap, reusable and do not require in situ electrical power supply. In this dose is acquired and stored for a long period of time until the system is stimulated by heat. $\text{CaSO}_4:\text{Dy}$, a highly sensitive phosphor, were used for monitoring. These TLDs have been thoroughly characterized based on ANSI (ANSI, 1975). These dosimeters were chosen for their precision, stability, and ability to measure low-dose radiation levels in environmental conditions. Dosimeters are deployed at a height of 1m above the ground at selected locations. These dosimeters are replaced by the fresh batch after every three months period. The collection of old ones and their replacement by new is simultaneous in order to ensure the continuity of monitoring.

After exposure, the dosimeters were read using an automatic TLD reader, which recorded the thermoluminescence output. This output is proportional to the absorbed gamma dose. The absorbed dose was calculated using standardized methodology.

Results

Over the two-year monitoring period, the average absorbed gamma radiation levels across the ten locations ranged from 0.62 mGy/a to 1.01 mGy/a, which aligns with the typical background radiation levels reported for similar regions in India. Indian average gamma absorbed dose rate is $0.82 + 0.18$ mGy/a.

Conclusion

The comprehensive two-year gamma radiation monitoring program has successfully established a preoperational gamma dose baseline for the GHAVP site. The findings indicate that the radiation levels in the region are within normal background ranges, providing a benchmark for future operational monitoring and environmental impact assessment. This study underscores the importance of long-term environmental monitoring using standardized methodologies to ensure public safety and regulatory compliance in the vicinity of nuclear power installations. Future work will focus on comparing operational-phase data with this baseline to detect any potential radiological impact attributable to the plant's activities.

References

- Manish K. Mishra *et al* (2023) *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity* **262**.
- ANSI **575** (1975)

ANALYSIS OF OPERATIONAL GAMMA RADIATION MONITORING IN RELATION TO BASELINE DATA IN AND AROUND KUDANKULAM NUCLEAR POWER PLANT, TAMIL NADU

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Introduction

The Kudankulam Nuclear Power Plant (KKNPP) is the largest capacity Nuclear Power Station in India. There are only nine inland sectors while others are in the Gulf of Mannar, leaving about 60% of the exclusion zone inlands. Two 1,000 MWe pressurised water reactor (PWR) units based on Russian technology were constructed and are operational from December 2014 and March 2017 respectively. An additional four units are under construction in the second and third phases of the project. The beach around this site is rich with monazite and as a consequence shows high background levels ranging from 0.8-1.7 mGy/a as measured using survey meters (Ranjan M. P. et.al.). This paper discusses the preoperational (2003-2014) and operational (2015-2024) gamma radiation levels in and around the environs of KKNPP, using Thermo Luminescent dosimeters (TLDs). Twenty locations were selected for the TLD survey, all of them being situated in the centers of different villages, up to a distance of about 20 km from the site center. Six more locations had been included from the year 2017 around the premises of unit 3 and 4. This will serve preoperational data for unit 3 and 4.

Materials and Methods

The environmental TLD consist of two Teflon embedded CaSO₄: Dy phosphor discs mounted on a machine identifiable TLD card. These TLDs have been thoroughly characterized based on ANSI 545 (ANSI-545) criteria for the environmental radiation monitoring using TLDs. The TLDs were deployed on quarterly basis. The exposed TLDs were replaced by the fresh ones and returned to BARC for dose rate evaluation.

Results

The gamma radiation monitoring was started from the year 2003 on quarterly basis. The quarterly values were normalized to give annual dose rate. The annual average gamma dose rate in preoperational phase (2003-2014) and operational phase (2015-2024) for each location

is compared. The annual average gamma radiation level in pre operational phase varied from 0.78 mGy/y-2.39 mGy/y, whereas in operational phase from 0.77mGy/y-2.31 mGy/y. The observed variation at each location is within 20%. An effort was made to determine the dispersion of the annual dose rate between the pre and post operating phases in every sector of KKNPP in increasing distance from plant site.

Conclusion

This study illustrates how gamma radiation measurements using TLDs are a potentially valuable method for assessing radiological effects in KKNPP region. Large location to location variation in the exposure levels is observed due to the existence of monazite patches. The operational annual average gamma radiation levels are found to be not significantly different from the preoperational levels though anomaly at some locations is due to a considerable amount of monazite-bearing sand, been replaced with building materials such as concrete, which have lower radioactive concentration. This kind of survey not only meets the requirements of the regulatory bodies like IAEA and AERB, but it also gives the yardstick with which to compare the performance of safety measures taken by the authorities at the power plant.

References

Rajan M. P., Varughese, K. G., Vijaykumar, B., George Thomas, Sunderarajan, P., Kumar, M. and Hegde, A. G. (2006) Proc. Asian Oceanic Congress on Radiation Protection (AOCR-2) Beijing, Oct. 9-13, 2006. pp 693-696.
ANSI N-545 (1975).

IMPACT OF REVISED BIOKINETIC MODELS ON DOSE CALCULATIONS FOR ^{137}Cs

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Keywords: ^{137}Cs , retained fraction, biokinetic model.

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Introduction

^{137}Cs is a radioactive substance commonly encountered in the nuclear industry as well as in various industrial as well as medical applications. When inhaled, it can enter the human body and result in an internal dose. The International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP) provides guidelines and models for estimating radiation doses from internal contamination. ICRP Pub. 78 (1997), presents biokinetic models and dose coefficients for ^{137}Cs . In 2017, the ICRP updated these values in Pub. 137. This study compares the differences in internal dose estimates using ICRP 78 and ICRP 137 following the inhalation of ^{137}Cs .

Materials and Methods

ICRP 78 incorporates the Human Respiratory Tract Model (HRTM) and a gastrointestinal (GI) tract model, while ICRP 137 utilizes updated versions of the HRTM along with the Human Alimentary Tract Model (HATM). These models describe the movement, retention, and excretion of ^{137}Cs in the body over time. Cesium biokinetic model described in ICRP 78 uses a simplified single-compartment approach for distribution and excretion of Cs. Whereas, ICRP137 adopts more physiologically based multi-compartment model.

An Octave program was used to solve both models and estimate the whole-body retention of ^{137}Cs (Type F) for 1 to 180 days post inhalation. The dose coefficients used for inhalation of ^{137}Cs are $6.7\text{E-}9$ Sv/Bq from ICRP 78 and $9.3\text{E-}9$ Sv/Bq from ICRP 137. The committed effective dose received by an individual due to the inhalation of 1 kBq of ^{137}Cs was estimated using both ICRP-78 and ICRP-137 for whole body measurement.

Results

The comparison revealed noticeable differences in dose estimates between the two models, with variations depending on the time elapsed after exposure to ^{137}Cs :

- On the 1st and 2nd day post inhalation, the doses calculated using ICRP-137 model were

24% and 10% higher, compared to those calculated using ICRP 78 model. These differences are mainly due to changes in deposition and clearance mechanisms in the updated HRTM and HATM models.

- From the 5th to the 40th day, ICRP 137 estimated dose were slightly lower, ~1–2% less than that those from ICRP 78. This reflects how the new model accounts for the redistribution and retention of ^{137}Cs .
- From the 41st to 180th day, ICRP 137 predicted higher doses, with variations ranging from 1% to 12% compared to ICRP 78. This increase results from more detailed retention parameters in the physiologically based model.

These findings highlights the understanding of biokinetics of ^{137}Cs in the body and its impact on long-term dose predictions.

Conclusion

This study highlights the differences in internal dose estimates for ^{137}Cs when using the biokinetic models provided by ICRP 78 and ICRP 137. The results showed that doses estimated using ICRP 137 were higher during the initial and later periods post-exposure, while they were slightly lower during intermediate periods, compared to ICRP 78. These variations underline the importance of using updated models like ICRP 137 for internal dose assessments, ensuring better radiation protection strategies for workers and the public.

References

1. ICRP 78, Annals of the ICRP 27 (3–4), 1997.
2. ICRP 137, Annals of the ICRP 46 (3–4), 2017.

ORGAN S-VALUES FOR ICRP ADULT REFERENCE MESH PHANTOMS DUE TO ^{131}I PRESENT IN THYROID

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Introduction

Accurate dose estimation is essential in radiation protection and treatment planning, particularly for radionuclides used in nuclear medicine, such as ^{131}I . In 2009, International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP) published adult reference computational phantoms as ICRP 110. These phantoms were developed based on CT and MRI data of actual individuals, for improvement in estimation of dosimetric quantities. However, these phantoms do not represent several walled organs, such as the stomach, the walls of small intestine etc. which were still modelled using stylized phantoms. To address the limitations associated with the representation of certain tissues, the ICRP 145 published a mesh phantom, in 2019. This advancement aimed to provide a more comprehensive and accurate representation of human anatomy, allowing for improved dosimetric calculations.

In this work, S-values for various target organs were estimated for ^{131}I in the thyroids of mesh phantoms. The study also includes a comparison of the S-values for ^{131}I derived from both voxel and mesh phantoms. The comparison with voxel phantoms, which are typically based on simpler geometrical models, allows for an assessment of the differences in dosimetric outcomes between the two approaches.

Materials and Methods

ICRP 145 provides adult mesh-type reference computational phantoms in both polygon mesh and tetrahedron mesh (TM) formats. These phantoms were constructed by converting the ICRP reference voxel phantoms into a mesh format incorporating stylised models for radiosensitive tissues that are represented as thin layers. In this study, radiation transport simulations were performed using the GEANT4 toolkit, which is a widely used simulation framework for modelling the interactions of particles with matter. Adult male and female mesh phantoms in TM format were incorporated into GEANT4. The S-values for

various target organs were calculated based on a uniformly distributed ^{131}I source in the thyroid. These S-value represent the mean absorbed dose per unit of emitted radiation, were then compared to those calculated using the ICRP 110 voxel phantoms.

Results

In this study, S-values were estimated for target tissues: thyroid, liver, brain, pancreas, pituitary gland, breast, lungs, thymus, oesophagus, spinal cord, spleen and spleen. It was observed that the self-irradiation S-values for thyroid were the highest. Also, S-value for a target organ is inversely proportional to its distance from thyroid. Generally, S-values for female phantom were higher than male due to smaller mass of organs in females.

In most of the cases, S-values often differ between voxel and mesh phantoms. For example, variation in S-values for gonads due to thyroid source was found to be significant, with differences of approximately 30% for the male phantom and 40% for the female phantom.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that the S-values derived from mesh and voxel phantoms for ^{131}I distributed in the thyroid exhibit considerable variation. Although both the phantom types are realistic, the observed differences underscore the need for careful selection of phantom models in various applications. Further research is required to understand the sources of these differences. These S values based on mesh phantom will be useful in organ dose assessments for ^{131}I , in various exposure scenarios.

References

1. ICRP Pub.145, 48(1-2), 1-218, 2019.
2. ICRP Pub 110, 39(1-2), 1-165, 2009.

FIELD STUDY TO CORRELATE PHOTON RADIATION CATEGORY WITH DATA OF RATIO OF DISC RESPONSE OF THERMOLUMINESCENCE DOSIMETRY BADGE AT NUCLEAR FUEL PROCESSING FACILITY

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Keywords: TLD, personnel monitoring, radiation category, CaSO₄:Dy

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Introduction

The nuclear fuel processing facility handling plutonium, employs around 1100 workers to carry out various activities, resulting in exposure to different radioactive sources. The TLD monitoring service to the radiation workers of plant is provided on monthly basis. During routine personnel monitoring services using CaSO₄:Dy based TL dosimetry badge different radiation categories (energy range) are observed based on the ratio of readouts of the TLD discs under different filter material of the dosimeter. It may be noted that response of CaSO₄:Dy TLD discs is energy dependent and also the ratio of disc response under different filter region determines the choice of algorithms for evaluation of dose of the radiation worker. The photon energies for each category along with the disc ratios are Photon-1(Energy > 200keV)-0.80 < R21 < 1.25, Photon-2(40 keV < Energy < 200 keV)-1.25 ≤ R21 < 5, Photon-3(Energy < 40 keV) -R21 ≥ 5. The estimation of dose received by worker depends on identification of the photon radiation category. To have better statistics and higher signal to noise ratio, the study was undertaken to identify different photon radiation categories based on the deployment of TL dosimetry badge for 24 hrs in the plant and comparing it with the data generated during TLD monitoring service by the TLD lab.

Materials and Methods

Around 15 locations were chosen at fuel processing facility for the identification of radiation category based on the type of activities carried out by radiation workers and dose rate. At each location, a set of 3 TLD badges were deployed on surface of equipment or in air for a period of 24 h. The control TLD badges were kept in the plant (away from radiation area) to determine the contribution due to local background dose. After exposure at the locations, the TLD cards were read on calibrated TLD card readers. The reader

calibration, category of photon radiation and dose evaluation were performed as per the standard procedures prescribed for personnel monitoring service ⁽¹⁾. The experiment was repeated at few locations for reproducibility of the data.

Results

Photon-1 category was detected at 5 different locations with R21 values ranging from 0.89 to 1.13 and R32 from 0.97 to 1.12. Photon-2 category was detected at 2 locations with R21 values ranging from 1.34 to 4.23 and R32, from 1.11 to 1.19. Photon-3 category was detected at 5 locations with R21 value ranging from 5.18 to 9.33 and R32 from 1.11 to 1.15. Beta-Photon category was detected at 3 locations with R21 values ranging from 1.18 to 2.09 and R32, 1.71 to 7.89.

Conclusion

The field study helps in identifying the various radiation category of photon that can be recorded during routine personnel monitoring service and provides confidence while reporting dose values resulting from different radiation patterns. Any abnormal pattern recorded during routine service can be identified and confirmed before reporting of the final dose. This exercise helps in establishing confidence to TLD processing Lab as well user institution regarding the reporting of dose values.

References

1. Datta,D. et al Handbook on TLD based personnel monitoring. BARC REPORT BARC/2018/E/007 India: Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, (Rev 1 – 2018)

VALIDATION STUDY OF THE QUICK SCAN WHOLE BODY MONITOR FOR IN-VIVO MEASUREMENT AT NARORA ATOMIC POWER STATION

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Introduction

To accurately estimate radioactivity intake among occupational radiation workers, reliable internal contamination monitoring systems are essential. At Narora Atomic Power Station (NAPS), two pressurized heavy-water reactor units have been operational since 1992. A shadow shield whole body counter (SSWBC) being used to measure high-energy gamma photon (HEP) radionuclides specific to NAPS. Recently, a quick scan (QSCAN) whole body monitoring system was successfully installed to enable efficient in-vivo measurement of these radionuclides in radiation workers. This paper presents the operational validation study of the QSCAN system, highlighting its improved sensitivity and effectiveness in internal contamination monitoring.

Materials and Methods

The QSCAN whole body system comprises two NaI (TI) scintillation based detectors, each with dimensions of 4" L x 4" B x 16" H and a resolution of 7.6%. Each detector is coupled with a 1K GSPEC multichannel analyser (MCA) and housed in a shielded enclosure with low-background shielding materials, including virgin lead, virgin plastic, Co-60-free steel, and copper which yields background counts for Co-60, Cs-137, and I-131 of 6.8 cps, 9.0 cps, and 9.3, respectively. Efficiency calibration was conducted using a known quantity of gamma-emitting radionuclides placed in a water-filled BOMAB phantom, designed to match the average Indian adult.

Results and Discussion

The calibration/sensitivity factors (CF/SF) for Co-60, Cs-137, and I-131 was found as 5.6 cps/kBq, 7.1 cps/kBq, and 6.6 cps/kBq, respectively, with MDAs for Co-60, Cs-137, and I-131 as 127 Bq, 116 Bq, and 136 Bq, respectively, with 60 seconds counting time. For routine annual monitoring, observed MDA values correspond to committed effective doses

(CEDs) of Co-60: 67.47 μ Sv, Cs-137: 5.43 μ Sv, and I-131: 41.55 μ Sv, with derived recording level(DRL) percentages as 6.74%, 0.54%, and 4.15%, respectively, based on a threshold of 0.60 mSv.SSWBC system, in use for over three decades, requires over 900s per subject for internal monitoring. Each year, approximately 1,800 occupational radiation workers undergo monitoring at NAPS for routine and special categories. The QSCAN system provides an effective solution for identifying intake cases below regulatory requirements, with enhanced sensitivity and significantly reduced monitoring times (60 seconds).

Conclusion

The QSCAN WBC system provides several advantages over the SSWBC, including high throughput of approximately 30 subjects per hour, efficient in-situ detection of intake, evaluation of committed effective dose (CED), and report generation. With reducing monitoring time (60s) and increasing sensitivity factor and higher figure of merit (FOM) than SSWBC, the QSCAN system enhances resource efficiency, allowing more effective monitoring of radiation workers.

References

Internal commission of radiation protection, individual monitoring for internal exposure of workers: ICRP Publication 78, Annals of the ICRP 27, No. 3- 4(1997).

POLYOXOMETALATE (POM) BASED COMPOSITE MATERIAL FOR THE EXTRACTION OF AMERICIUM: PHOTOLUMINESCENCE STUDY

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Introduction

Polyoxometalates (POMs) are metal-oxide anions by cluster structures of different shapes and sizes [1]. The amenability of POMs to modification with different materials makes them suitable precursors for the development of new composites for separation and estimation of trace level of actinides present in biological/environmental samples. In our earlier investigation, POM based composite materials were explored for the extraction of Am (III) from dilute samples [2]. Here, the extraction mechanism was probed using photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy, with europium serving as a PL probe due to its rich PL spectrum and its role as a surrogate for Am.

Materials and methods

The lacunary POM, PW9 was synthesized according to the literature method [2]. This POM can be transformed into another lacunary POM, PW11 in the pH range 4 to 7. The anionic POM is then loaded onto a resin to form a composite material.

Results and Discussion

The composite material was characterized using different techniques, which suggest the formation of PW11 [2]. This composite was subjected to Eu(III) extraction at pH 7.0, resulting in a very high K_d value (>105 mL/g) [2]. We used PL spectroscopy to understand the interaction of Eu ion within Eu-POM complex in solid, solution and composite forms. The excitation spectra were recorded in 200-550 nm range, with emission observed at 612 nm. Emission spectra was recorded in 570-720 nm range using excitation at 275 nm, 394 nm and 464 nm. The excitation spectra indicated the presence of a ligand to metal charge transfer band (200-300 nm) and two Eu-centered peaks at 394 and 464 nm. The emission spectrum recorded by exciting at 275 nm differed from those recorded at the other two wavelengths. The life time spectra corroborate these findings, showing a longer

lifetime at 275 nm excitation wavelength (>2.5 ms) compared to ~0.2 ms at 394 nm. This suggests the presence of around 4 to 5 water molecules associated with the shorter-lived Eu species, while the longer-lived species appears to have no water molecules. It is also found that in the solution phase, there is less contribution of the short-lived excited species compared to the solid phase. In the composite material, both species contribute to the observed luminescence. The long-lived species is due to the formation of Eu-PW11 complex, where all the sites of Eu are satisfied by the oxo anion of the lacunary POM whereas in the short-lived species there is partial satisfaction by the lacunary POM. The very high K_d value obtained for the Eu(III) extraction may be due to the formation of long-lived species within the composite material.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates an interesting investigation of Eu(III) interaction with the POM under different experimental conditions and provides valuable insights into the mechanism of Am(III) extraction within the composite. The high extraction efficiency indicates these composite materials could be useful for the removal of radionuclides from biological and environmental samples.

References

1. A. R. Bagheri et al., *Analytica Chimica Acta* 1209 (2022) 339509.
2. Suja A. Kumar et al., SESTEC-2024 symposium, Mumbai.

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF ALPHA SPECTROMETRY AND LED FLUORIMETRY FOR URANIUM BIOASSAY

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Introduction

There are various geogenic and anthropogenic sources present in nature that contribute to the presence of uranium in soil and drinking water. The uranium excreted via urine is a useful biomarker for assessing the internal dose due to uranium intake. There are many analytical techniques available for determination of uranium in urine samples such as alpha spectrometry, LED fluorimetry, atomic absorption spectroscopy, ICP-MS, gamma spectrometry, fission track analysis and neutron activation analysis etc. However, above all, alpha spectrometry and LED fluorimetry are widely used. Alpha spectrometry using passivated ion implanted planar silicon (PIPS) detectors is a sensitive technique for the quantitative determination of isotopes whereas LED fluorimetry measuring the fluorescence of uranyl ion is an inexpensive, quick, reliable and sensitive method for estimating ultratrace uranium concentrations. Therefore, a comparative study was done for uranium analysis using both the techniques.

Materials and Methods

Urine samples were collected and spiked with 5mBq of ^{232}U radiochemical tracer obtained from IDS, BARC, Mumbai. After calcium phosphate precipitation, U separation was done using ion exchange resin. The eluent was evaporated and dissolved in 0.1N HNO₃. The sample was divided into two portions. 1ml of the sample was taken for analysis by LED Fluorimeter (MAKE Quantalase Enterprises Pvt. Ltd, Model: LF-2) and remaining 4ml was electroplated and counted in alpha spectrometry (MAKE Electronic Enterprises (I) Pvt. Ltd, India). In LED fluorimeter, 5ml of 5% tetra sodium pyrophosphate (FLUREN) with

1ml of 0.1N HNO₃ was used as blank. Recovery estimation was done by adding required volume of U standard solution of 1ppm (AccuStandard, USA).

Results

The observed minimum detectable concentration (MDC) using LED Fluorimeter is 12ng/L whereas in alpha spectrometry MDC is 20ng/L for 24h counting, at 5mm distance from the detector. The results of both the methods are comparable. However, as the analysis of urine sample involves various steps like pre-concentration, separation of uranium, instrumental analysis etc., that can lead to radiochemical recovery loss. Hence, estimation of overall recovery in a particular sample is to be ascertained to calculate the accurate uranium concentration in the sample.

Conclusion

Compared to Alpha spectrometry, LED fluorimeter decreases the measurement time from 24h to 2 min per sample after chemical separation. It has a comparatively lower detection limit. LED fluorimeter can be used to estimate the gross uranium in urine samples. However, for radiation workers, the internal dose estimation relies on the accurate assessment of uranium isotopes excreted from the body. Therefore, alpha spectrometry is a useful tool in the case of dose estimation and isotopic assay, whereas LED fluorimeter quickly estimates gross Uranium in the sample.

References

- A. Suja et al. (2012) J Radioanal Nucl Chem., 294.
- S. Gondane et al. (2019) Proc. DAE BRNS Symposium on Nuclear and Radiochemistry, NUCAR2019, Mumbai.

FEASIBILITY STUDY OF USING KVCBCT IMAGES AS PATIENT SPECIFIC QUALITY ASSURANCE TOOL

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Keywords: KVCBCT-images, CT-images, HU, Electron density, Gamma index analysis, Patient specific Quality Assurance, dose calculation. Presenting author email:

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Introduction

Kilovoltage cone beam (KV-CBCT) images provide a three-dimensional perspective of the patient during pre-treatment verification, making it possible to reconstruct the treatment plan's dose in 3D. This would determine the viability of using KV-CBCT images as a tool for patient-specific quality assurance (PSQA).

Materials and Methods

This research comprised 13 cervical cancer patients who received treatment at the Department of Radiation therapy and Oncology, Kasturba Hospital, Manipal, from 2023 to 2024. Treatment planning system Monaco software-5.11.03 was used for image registration, Segmentation, Treatment planning and Planned fluence on the KVCBCT and CT images. Treatment plans from routine CT images were replicated to the corresponding patients' KVCBCT images acquired during pretreatment verification. Planned fluence were analysed using Gamma 3D analysis. The resulting dose distribution and planned fluence on the KV-CBCT image-based plans were evaluated to determine if they align with the routine CT image-based plans (Computed Tomography).

Results

Minor, statistically insignificant differences were observed in dose distribution between KV-CBCT and routine CT image-based plans. The planned fluence on KV-CBCT images met gamma criteria for most cases, with occasional deviations in specific anatomical planes.

Conclusion

According to our research objectives, first fraction KVCBCT images successfully facilitated registration, contouring, treatment planning and planned fluence with help of standard planning CT images. However, the PSQA procedure should not be limited to the evaluation of planned fluence alone; it must also include an investigation of the delivered

fluence of the treatment plans. Factors such as errors in MLC leaf motion, gantry movement, fractional monitor units, and dose rate can affect dose delivery, potentially leading to discrepancies between the delivered and planned doses. Therefore, further investigation is needed in delivered fluence. Delivered fluence should be compared with planned fluence to boost the confidence of adopting KVCBCT images as one of the major patient specific quality assurance tools.

References

1. Zhang, J.-Y & Zhang, W.-Z & Lu, J.-Y & Wu, L.-L. (2015). Dose calculations on kilovoltage cone beam computed tomography in radiation therapy for cervical cancer patients. 31. 1592-1595. 10.13929/j.1003-3289.2015.10.036.
2. Shinde P, Jadhav A, Shankar V, Gupta KK, Dhoble NS, Dhoble SJ. Evaluation of kV-CBCT based 3D dose calculation accuracy and its validation using delivery fluence derived dose metrics in Head and Neck Cancer. *Physica Medica*. 2022 Apr 1;96:32-45.

DOSIMETRIC ASSESSMENT OF 6 FF, 6FFF BEAM VOLUMETRIC MODULATED ARC TREATMENT PLANS FOR NASOPHARYNGEAL CANCER WITH AND WITHOUT MULTI-CRITERIA OPTIMIZATION

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Keywords: VMAT, FF, FFF, Head and Neck cancer, Nasopharynx, Multi-Criteria Optimization.

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Introduction

Head and neck cancers, including nasopharyngeal carcinoma, are often diagnosed late, requiring precise radiotherapy to protect nearby organs. The proximity of essential organs complicates treatment, necessitating precise techniques to target tumors while sparing healthy tissues. Advances such as IMRT, VMAT, and FFF beams enhance treatment precision and safety. This study compares 6 FF MV and 6FFF MV beams in nasopharyngeal cancer, assessing the impact of multi-criteria optimization (MCO) on target coverage and organ sparing.

Materials and Methods

56 VMAT plans were developed for 14 nasopharynx cancer patients, utilizing both flattening filter (FF) and flattening filter-free (FFF) beams with and without multicriteria optimization (MCO) at two dose levels simultaneously (70 and 59.64 Gy in 35 fractions). A comparative analysis was conducted using a Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Plans were compared using target dose coverage, Organ at Risk (OAR) sparing, conformity index, homogeneity index and monitor unit.

Results

D95% and D90% were comparable across techniques. HI and CI remained comparable. In MCO, especially 6FFF MCO, improved spinal cord and brainstem sparing without compromising PTV coverage, though 6FFF and 6FFF MCO required more monitor units.

Conclusion

All techniques—6FF, 6FFF, 6FF MCO, and 6FFF MCO—achieved similar PTV coverage. MCO techniques, especially 6FFF MCO, showed better organ sparing for the spinal cord and brainstem. However, 6FFF and 6FFF MCO required more monitor units. The choice of technique should weigh efficiency against organ protection.

References

- Kumar, S. A., MM, M., CA, S., KB, R., Jose, L., Muttath, G., & KP, S. (2021). Dosimetric comparison of FF and FFF beams in VMAT treatment plans of head and neck cancers. *Onkologia i Radioterapia*, 15(7).
- Rolland, J., Favrel, V., Fau, P., Mailleux, H., & Tallet, A. (2023). Dosimetric comparison of VMAT standard optimization (SO) and multi-criteria optimization (MCO) treatment plans with standard mode delivery (STD) or sliding window (SW) for head and neck cancer. *Journal of Applied Clinical Medical Physics*, 24(9), e14013.
- Chen, H., Craft, D. L., & Gierga, D. P. (2014). Multicriteria optimization informed VMAT planning. *Medical Dosimetry*, 39(1), 64-73.

EMPIRICAL RELATION FOR MASS ATTENUATION COEFFICIENTS FOR LEAD AND BISMUTH NANOCOMPOSITES

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Introduction

The study of mass attenuation coefficients (μ/ρ) is critical for understanding the interaction of radiation with matter, particularly in materials designed for radiation shielding applications. Nano-composites of Lead and Bismuth, when dispersed in a suitable matrix, offer a lightweight and flexible alternative to conventional bulk materials, which are often heavy and brittle. Measuring and analyzing the mass attenuation coefficients of these nano-composites provides essential insights into their shielding efficiency across different photon energies. Furthermore, establishing an empirical relationship between μ/ρ and parameters such as mean atomic number (\bar{Z}) and photon energy enables the prediction of attenuation behavior for a wide range of compositions. This study focuses the measurement of mass attenuation coefficients of nano-composites using a gamma-ray transmission method, and deriving an empirical formula.

Materials and Methods

The mass attenuation coefficients (μ/ρ) were determined using a narrow-beam gamma-ray transmission technique, which involves measuring the intensity of gamma rays transmitted through the samples at photon energies ranging from 30 keV to 1.33 MeV. A NaI(Tl) scintillation detector coupled with a multichannel analyzer was used to detect the transmitted gamma rays, ensuring high precision. The mean atomic number (\bar{Z}) of the composites was calculated using the known elemental composition of Lead and Bismuth within the matrix. Experimental μ/ρ values were plotted as a function of photon energy, revealing their variation with energy and \bar{Z} . The data were further analyzed to examine the relationship between μ/ρ and \bar{Z} . Nonlinear regression techniques were employed to fit the experimental data and derive an empirical relation linking μ/ρ with \bar{Z} and photon energy.

Results

This empirical model was validated by comparing the predicted mass attenuation coefficients with the experimental results, showing good agreement across the studied energy range. The developed relation provides a reliable method to estimate the radiation attenuation properties of Lead and Bismuth nanocomposites based on their composition and photon energy. This study highlights the potential of such nanocomposites in radiation shielding applications and lays the groundwork for exploring similar materials with tailored attenuation properties.

Conclusion

The study constructed an empirical relationship with mean atomic number and photon energy. The findings confirm their efficiency as lightweight radiation shielding materials and provide a predictive model for similar composites, supporting their application in medical, nuclear, and aerospace industries.

References

Singh V. Pand BadigerN, (2014)Annals of Nuclear Energy 64. H.C Manjunatha and Chandrika B M, (2019) Radiation Effects and Defects in Solids 174, 542

STUDY OF STRUCTURAL, COMPOSITIONAL AND OPTICAL PROPERTIES EVOLUTION IN B-TEO₂ THIN FILM WITH GAMMA IRRADIATION FOR DOSIMETRY APPLICATIONS

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This research delves into the effects of gamma radiation on the physical and chemical attributes of TeO₂ thin films deposited on glass substrates. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis unveiled a notable increase in crystallinity in irradiated samples, especially for those annealed at 350°C and 400°C, compared to their non-irradiated counterparts. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) affirmed the maintenance of the molecular structure of TeO₂ post-irradiation at 200 Gy, with negligible alterations in the atomic percentages of Te and O (as determined by Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy, EDS). However, a reduction in the relative atomic percentage of Oxygen was observed for the 350°C annealed sample. Raman spectroscopy further corroborated the stability of the chemical composition, although the emergence of new peaks indicative of the β- TeO₂ phase was noted, likely attributable to enhanced crystallinity. While the optical band gap exhibited random variations with increasing gamma dose for 450°C samples, it decreased for those annealed at 350°C. Thermoluminescence (TL) glow curves for all irradiated samples (annealed at temperatures ranging from 0°C to 350°C) displayed characteristic peaks associated with radiation-induced excitation and subsequent emission. These findings offer valuable insights into the radiation response of TeO₂ thin films, highlighting their potential for applications in radiation detection and other radiation-related technologies.

NEUTRON FLUENCE RATE MEASUREMENTS IN EXPERIMENT CANAL OF FBTR

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Introduction

A High Temperature Fission Chamber (HTFC) with broad range neutronic channels is utilized for the Prototype Fast Breeder Reactor (PFBR) core monitoring. One detector from the manufacturing lot must be tested at the Fast Breeder Test Reactor (FBTR)'s experimental canal (517 mm radially from the core centre) prior to placement in the core. Therefore, the first prerequisite before testing the detectors is to estimate the neutron fluence rate of the experimental canal for various energy ranges, i.e., thermal, epithermal, and fission.

Materials and Methods

Due to the high gamma background, high temperature, high pressure, and space limitation, the foil activation method was chosen for the fluence measurements at the given location. As the detectors are coated with enriched uranium (^{235}U), therefore, the best-suited foil for the thermal equivalent fluence measurement would have been uranium foils. However, in the present scenario, both standard Gold (^{197}Au) and Copper (^{63}Cu) foils were used in bare and Cd-covered condition for thermal neutron fluence rate measurements based on (n, γ) interaction. On the other hand, for the measurement of the fission average neutron fluence rate nickel foil was used, which is based on the ^{58}Ni (n, p) ^{58}Co interaction. There are three sets of foils. In each set there is one bare gold, copper, nickel foil and one gold and copper foil covered with cadmium. Each set of foils was inserted into an aluminium holder. These three holders were placed at different elevations using aluminium spacers to cover the sensitive length of the detector, i.e., 283 mm. During the irradiation of foils, the reactor was operated at 400 kWt for 5 hours. The average temperature at these locations was about 205 °C, measured using a thermocouple.

Results

After removal of foils from experimental canal the induced activity has been measured using an HPGe detector at FBTR. Neutron fluence rate is evaluated using formulae: $\dot{\phi} =$

$$\frac{CA\lambda t_c}{\varepsilon N_A w a_i \sigma I_\gamma (1 - e^{-\lambda t_{irr}})(1 - e^{-\lambda t_c}) e^{-\lambda t_d}}$$
 Where $\dot{\phi}$ is fluence rate, C is net count rate under photo peak, A is atomic mass number of target atom, w is weight of foil, N_A is Avogadro number, λ is decay constant, w is weight of sample, σ is reaction cross-section, t_{irr} is irradiation time, t_c is counting time, t_d is a decay time, ε is efficiency of detector for respective gamma energy, a_i is isotopic abundance of parent nuclei, I_γ is gamma abundance of respective energy. Attenuation correction due to foil thickness is also applied. The cross sections used for estimation of neutron fluence rate are as follows: 98.6 barn and 4.4 barn for gold and copper thermal equivalent fluence rates respectively; 1150 barn for gold and 4.4 for copper resonance integral respectively; and 113 millibarn for fission spectra. The thermal equivalent fluence rate reported is temperature corrected. The calculated value of thermal equivalent fluence rate averaged over the detector sensitive length, for copper it is 2.0×10^8 n/cm²/s and for gold it is 3.5×10^9 n/cm²/s. Epithermal neutron fluence rate (above cadmium cut off) from gold is 2.2×10^8 n/cm²/s and from copper is 2.6×10^8 n/cm²/s and fission spectra averaged fluence rate using nickel foil is 5.6×10^5 n/cm²/s. The overall measurement standard uncertainty is $\pm 20\%$.

Conclusion

The experimental canal is 517 mm radially away and at an elevation of -6217 mm from core. Moreover, due to presence of various materials in between including reflector material, the fission spectra get moderated. Hence, the spectra in experimental canal is a mix spectrum with dominance in soft region of neutron spectra.

References

1 P.D. Holt, Passive Detectors for Neutron Fluence Measurement, Radiation Protection Dosimetry, Volume 10, Issue 1 -4, 1 January 1985, Pages 251–264

DEVELOPMENT OF A SI PIN DIODE BASED PORTABLE RADON PROGENY MONITOR

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Introduction

Being radioactive and particulate in nature, the progenies of ^{222}Rn (Radon) are the major contributors to inhalation dose and imposes carcinogenic risk [1]. Therefore, accurate measurement of radon progeny is very important. These progenies are mainly short lived and emit high LET alpha's of 6 and 7.69 MeV along with beta and gamma radiations. This study present the development of a portable and low-cost radon progeny monitor based on alpha spectroscopy using a Si PIN diode detector. The measurement method and its performance evaluation in controlled environment is described below.

Materials and Methods

The Radon Progeny Monitor (RPM) developed in the present study consists of 2 parts: a Filter Paper (FP) sampler and a Si PIN diode (10 mm x 10 mm) with its associated electronics. The airborne progeny atoms are sampled onto a FP using a pump with 5 lpm flow rate and then the alpha's emitted by these progeny atoms are counted by the Si PIN diode. The detector is covered with an aluminum cap on which provision has been made to mount the FP.

The energy calibration of the system was carried out using a Th-229 disc source having multiple alpha energies in the range of 5-8 MeV. The alpha detection efficiency of the monitor was determined by using Am-241 disc source of known concentration.

In order to test the performance of this monitor, experiments were carried out in an 8 m³ calibration chamber with different radon concentrations varying from 900±25 to 6000±200 Bq m⁻³. In each set of experiment, FP samplings were carried out at 5 lpm flow rate of for 10 min. After sampling, the alpha counting of the FP was carried out using RPM to obtain the spectrum for 2 standardized counting intervals of 2-12 min and 15-30 min.

An algorithm was developed to determine the radon progeny activity concentration from the

counts verses energy spectrum. Due to the short-lived nature of the progenies, appropriate decay corrections were implemented during various phases such as sampling, delay and counting phases.

Results

The alpha detection efficiency of the monitor was found to be 20.12 % with source to detector distance of 2 mm in ambient air. Radon progeny activity concentration determined using the developed system was compared against the commercially available Working Level Monitor from Tracerlab, Germany [2] in all sets of experiments. The results show very good agreement with an uncertainty of less than 5 %.

Conclusion

A Si PIN diode based radon progeny monitor was designed, calibrated and its performance was tested in controlled conditions which shows that it can be used as a low cost and portable device for measurement of radon progeny activity concentration.

References

- UNSCEAR (2000) Report to General Assembly with Annexes, United Nations. Sources and Effects of Ionizing Radiation. Tracerlab, GmbH, BWLM-Plus-2S User Manual, Germany, 2021.

STUDY OF TRACK PARAMETERS OF A PARTICLES WITH DIFFERENT ENERGIES IN CR 39 SOLID STATE NUCLEAR TRACK DETECTORS (SSNTD)

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Keywords: Alpha energy, residual energy, CR 39 detector and track diameter .

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Introduction

The CR-39 (poly-allyl diglycol carbonate) solid-state nuclear track detector (SSNTD) is widely used for measuring radon (Rn-²²²) and thoron (Rn-²²⁰) gases, their decay products, and for neutron dosimetry. In this study, the effect of incident alpha particles with varying energies on the track diameter registered in the CR-39 detector was analyzed. When exposed to alpha particles, the CR-39 detector undergoes radiolytic scission, breaking its long polymer chains into shorter fragments. This process produces reactive low-molecular weight radiolytic products, which dissolve more readily in the etchant than the undamaged plastic, forming visible alpha tracks during chemical analysis

Materials and Methods

In the experiment, an ²⁴¹Am source emitting alpha particles with an energy of 5.48 MeV was used. The CR-39 detector was positioned at varying distances from the source to adjust the incident energy. The range of alpha particles in air is given by equation $Ra=0.324 E^{3/2}$ (1), and the residual range after travelling a specific distance in air is given by equation $Er=E_0(1-L/Ra)^{2/3}$. From these equation range of 5.48 MeV alpha particle is calculated as 4.16 cm in air. At specific distances L between the CR-39 detector and the source, the residual energy was calculated. The CR-39 detectors, exposed at various distances, were chemically etched in 6.25N NaOH at 70°C for 5 hours to reveal latent tracks as optically visible tracks. Track counting was then performed using an image analysis system.

Results

Under the specified chemical etching conditions, the bulk etch rate of the CR-39 film was determined to be $1.35 \pm 0.08 \mu\text{m/hr}$. At a distance of 1.03 cm, the incident alpha particle

energy on the detector was 4.53 MeV, resulting in an alpha track mode diameter of 7.4 μm . At a distance of 2.24 cm, the incident alpha energy was 3.27 MeV, producing a mode diameter of 8.62 μm for the alpha track. Finally, at a distance of 3.5 cm, the incident alpha energy was reduced to 1.61 MeV, corresponding to an alpha track mode diameter of 11.10 μm . The alpha tracks on CR-39 films exhibit a greyscale range of R(125-37), G(12-0), and B(12-0), with a minimum track diameter of 1 μm and track roundness values ranging from 1 to 1.5 .

Conclusion

Variations in incident alpha particle energy across different distances showed a clear correlation with alpha track diameters, increasing as the particle energy decreased. This pattern reflects the energy loss characteristics of alpha particles over distance in the CR-39 medium, providing useful insights into track morphology as a function of alpha energy and etching parameters. Additionally, the greyscale values and track roundness metrics confirm the identifiable and measurable characteristics of alpha tracks on CR-39, supporting its utility in precise alpha particle detection and analysis.

References

Determination of the energy of the incident alpha particle by the diameter of the track registered in CR-39 detector, A.M. dahham and N.F.kadhim AIP Conference Proceedings 2386, 080041 (2022).

R.L. Fleischer, P.B price , *Physical review*, volume 156 (1967) number 2

DEVELOPMENT OF SEALED D-T NEUTRON GENERATOR FOR DOSIMETRY AND INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS

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Introduction

Radioisotope neutron sources are employed in a myriad of industrial applications including thickness gauging and petroleum exploration, but they are not well suited for applications that require controlled neutron irradiation and may create safety issues and logistical complications as well. In contrast accelerator-based neutron sources using $T(d,n)\alpha$ and $D(d,n)^3\text{He}$ reactions, known as D-T and D-D generators, generate monoenergetic neutrons with approximate energy of 14.1 and 2.45 MeV, respectively and neutrons production can be controlled electronically.

Materials and Methods

We have worked on the indigenous development of sealed D-T neutron source as an alternative to more commonly used Cf-252 or Am-Be neutron sources [1]. The development of the source requires development of various important sub-components such as Titanium hydride target, solid state gas reservoir. The development of suitable thickness thin film using thermal vapour deposition techniques was carried out and film thickness were critically monitored.

Results

We have used cold cathode Penning ion source to generate D⁺ ions, due to its compact size, minimal auxiliary power sources requirement and no maintenance needs, making it ideal for a sealed device. The deuterium ion beam is accelerated in a DC of upto -90 kV and subsequently hitting on tritium target to produce mono energetic neutrons by fusion reaction. The neutron yield of 1.0×10^8 n/s in “D-T mode”. These kind of neutron generators are widely used as

calibration standards for detector calibrations, industrial and dosimetry applications [2].

Conclusion:

The indigenously developed sealed D-T neutron generator offers enhanced safety, portability, and operational efficiency compared to traditional neutron sources. It enables real-time, in-situ measurements of elemental compositions and densities of geological formations and bulk materials. Previously confined to use in a few research institutions, such generators are now accessible in a range of configurations and are becoming suitable for a variety of other applications such as mining, oil exploration, coal GCV analysis etc.

References:

1. Mayank Shukla, Prashant Singh, Yogesh Kashyap et. al., *BARC newsletter* 15, January-February 2023.
2. Tushar Roy, Shefali Shukla, Yogesh Kashyap, Mayank Shukla, Prashant Singh, M. R. More and L. M. Pant; Proceedings of NUCAR-2023 Mumbai,(2023),165.

IMPLEMENTATION OF A POE CAMERA-BASED VISUAL MONITORING SYSTEM IN THE HOT-CELLS OF A REPROCESSING PLANT

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Keywords: polyimide, PoE, hot-cell, reprocessing

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Introduction

The reprocessing plant is designed to reprocess spent fuel discharged from nuclear reactors. The process equipment in the reprocessing plant is housed in hot-cells with thick walls made of lead or high-density concrete. Using video cameras for visual monitoring is essential for the operation and maintenance of process equipment. Analog cameras have traditionally been used for this purpose due to its simplicity. However, analog cameras are obsolete and suffer from poor-quality video and noise interference. Hence, a state-of-the-art digital video camera with Power over Ethernet (PoE) has been newly implemented in the hot-cell for this application. The Ethernet cable required for this camera was innovatively implemented using Polyimide insulated Radiation Resistant (RR) cables and special hot-cell connectors. The material for cable and connector were tested for suitability in acid vapour, organic vapour and radiation ambience. This system was installed and tested in the hot-cell to transmit video signals using Ethernet.

Materials and Methods

A commercial digital video camera with a CCD sensor and PoE was used. The standard 10BASE-T and 100BASE-TX Ethernet use two pairs (4 wires) out in the Ethernet cable with RJ-45 connector for data transmission. For our application, two separate three-core shielded polyimide insulated RR cables were used for Ethernet communication from the hot-cell to the outside. Instead of the standard RJ-45 Ethernet connector, a 6-pin circular connector suitable for the master-slave manipulator was used. Forty metres of RR cable was required to link the connector to the terminal block in the junction box in the glove box outside the hot cell. A 5-metre Ethernet cable brought the signal outside the glove box to the video monitoring system.

Results

Studies were carried out to determine the suitability of the required length of the RR cable with connectors for reliable Ethernet communication of the video signal from the camera. It was observed that the 6-core polyimide RR cables were not suitable for transmitting the Ethernet signals due to the crosstalk interference between the cores. Hence, Ethernet communication was established using two separate three-core shielded polyimide RR cables. A PoE-based digital camera was installed in the hot-cell for video monitoring. The 6-pin circular connectors were used in the hot-cell for remote maintenance using manipulators.

Conclusion

The hot-cell visual monitoring system was commissioned using a PoE-based digital video camera. For the communication of the digital video signals by Ethernet, 2 x 3-core polyimide insulated cables and 6-pin circular connectors were used. The video images had adequate picture quality and no noise interference. The system's design ensured easy maintenance. This experience validated the use of commercial PoE-based digital video cameras for hot-cell applications in reprocessing plants.

Reference

The Power of Ethernet - PoE & PoE+ Solutions, (2019), PoE Education Series, Digisol 1-8.
RR Cables for Scientific & Nuclear applications, (2020), Axorad catalogue 150.

EVALUATION OF COMMERCIAL VIDEO CAMERAS FOR HOT-CELL APPLICATIONS IN REPROCESSING PLANT

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Keywords: irradiation, gamma chamber, dose tolerance, hot-cells,

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Introduction

Analog video cameras are generally used for visual monitoring in the hot-cells of reprocessing plants. The video camera should withstand high gamma doses and dose rates of up to thousands of Rad and Rad/h. It should also be able to withstand the corrosive effect of vapours of nitric acid and organic solvents. The weight of the cameras shall be low for easy handling with manipulators. Analog cameras available in the market are Black & White (B&W) or colour. The sensing technology is a Charge Coupled Device (CCD) or Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor (CMOS). These types of cameras are evaluated by irradiation in the gamma chamber to estimate each camera's radiation dose tolerance capability.

Materials and Methods

Four analog cameras selected for evaluation are CMOS-based Colour, CCD-based B&W and two different CCD-based colour cameras. The cameras were connected to a Digital Video Recorder (DVR) and display system for a long period in the laboratory to identify any inherent faults. After the test, these cameras were installed in the Gamma chamber for the radiation dose tolerance test. The focus of each camera was adjusted for a short distance of 15 cm to view a uniform pattern image pasted inside the Gamma chamber. The cable used for four cameras is a three-core shielded radiation-resistant cable. The material of insulation for each core and jacket is polyimide. All the cameras were connected to a +12 V DC power supply and the video output of each camera was connected to the 8-channel DVR for live monitoring and recording.

Results

The chamber was irradiated at a dose rate of 70 kR/h. The radiation dose tolerance of each camera is given below.

1. The CMOS colour camera has the highest radiation dose tolerance of 360 kRad. 2. CCD-based colour-I camera has a radiation dose tolerance of 325 kRad. 3. CCD-based colour-II camera has a radiation dose tolerance of 60 kRad. 4. CCD-based B&W camera has a radiation dose tolerance of 35 kRad. New such cameras were tested in the hot-cell of the CORAL reprocessing plant, where the dose varied from 10 to 50 kRad, and the radiation dose tolerance of the cameras was found to be 30 days, 25 days, 4 days, and 2 days.

Conclusion

The CMOS colour camera and CCD-based camera-I are the most suitable for hot-cell applications. These cameras provide the best radiation dose tolerance of more than 325 kRads. The nominal life of the CCD-based camera-I is 25 days in the hot-cell of the CORAL plant.

References

V. Goiffon, et al (2015) IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science, 62, 6, 2965-2970. IAEA, TECHDOC-1693, Hot cell postirradiation examination and poolside inspection of nuclear fuel, p 8,106-27.

DEVELOPMENT OF A SERVER-BASED WEB APPLICATION FOR REMOTE I-131 MONITORING SYSTEM

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Keywords: Radiation, Monitoring, Server-based, Database, Application.

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Introduction

Server-based applications have become a key tool in remote monitoring by allowing real-time data collection and analysis over the network. The Remote I-131 Monitoring System is comprised of two main components: the I-131 monitor and a server-based web application. I-131 monitor, a GM tube-based radiation monitoring device, measures I-131 radiation levels and transmits the data to the web application for storage, processing, and visualization. This paper presents the design and development of the web application, with a focus on its architecture, methodology, and key features.

Materials and Methods

The web application receives radiation level data from the monitor, stores it in the database, and provides real-time data visualization. The application comprises three modules; an application server, a front-end application and a database. The application server has been developed using the python-based web framework "FastAPI"[1]. It handles requests from the front-end application and monitor and manages database operations. It provides various functionalities such as user authentication, receiving data from monitor, alarm generation, uploading data to the database, and fetching stored data. PostgreSQL, an open-source Relational Database Management System (RDBMS), is used for data storage. It ensures efficient management of radiation level data, alarm data, user information, and system configurations. The front-end application is a static website hosted using the Nginx [2] web server and accessible via web browsers. It is developed using the TypeScript-based framework Angular [3] and includes HTML, CSS, and JavaScript for an intuitive graphical user interface (GUI). The front-end application communicates with the application server through HTTP and WebSocket protocols.

The role-based access control has been implemented with three types of logical roles; data logger, data viewer and super user. The role of data logger is given to monitor which sends radiation level data to the application server. The data viewer can access functionalities such as viewing real-time radiation

level profiles, accessing historical data, reviewing generated alarms, and generating alarm reports. The superuser has access to user account management and system parameter configuration features. Username and password-based user authentication has been implemented to prevent unauthorized access. Upon logging into the application, users are granted specific functionalities based on their assigned role.

The monitor sends radiation level data to the server every second using HTTP POST requests. The server integrates the data up to configured acquisition time for single acquisition, then it compares the data against a set alarm threshold. If the radiation level exceeds the threshold, the system triggers an alarm. The data is stored in the database for future reference and presented to the user in an intuitive user interface.

Result and Conclusion

The developed application offers key features such as real-time remote data visualization, access to historical data, alarm generation, data downloading, and the ability to generate alarm reports. The application has been tested with the simulated field conditions and found to be working satisfactorily.

References

- <https://fastapi.tiangolo.com/>
- <https://nginx.org/>
- <https://angular.io/>

DEVELOPMENT OF MULTICHANNEL COINCIDENCE ANALYZER MODULE FOR BETA-GAMMA COINCIDENCE COUNTING

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Introduction

Coincidence counting technique enables absolute measurement of activity of radionuclides decaying by the simultaneous emission of two or more radiations in prompt succession. Present work describes the development of indigenous Multi-Channel Coincidence Analyser (MCCA) module which gives the 512-channel energy spectrum of gamma pulses that are in coincidence with beta detector channel. The coincidence spectrum can be analysed by setting multiple regions of interest (ROIs) during offline analysis, without having to use multiple single channel analyser (SCA) modules during acquisition.

Materials and Methods

The MCCA module is designed to interface with a liquid scintillator-based beta detector and a NaI(Tl) scintillator-based gamma detector. The system consists of two primary components:

Analog Processing Board (APB): The APB processes signals from the beta detector's photomultiplier tube (PMT) anode using a multistage linear amplifier. A comparator converts the analog pulses into corresponding 3.3V CMOS logic pulses. It features two onboard high-voltage (HV) modules. The HV to the beta and gamma detector and the discriminator threshold for the beta channel set via onboard digital-to-analog converters (DACs). Real-time monitoring of HV levels is achieved through onboard analog-to-digital converters (ADCs) interfaced over SPI. The APB interfaces to the FPGA-based coincidence analyser board (FCB) via a 20-pin connector.

FPGA-Based Coincidence Analyser Board (FCB):

The FCB receives logic pulses from the beta detector and preamplifier signals from the NaI(Tl) gamma detector. A digital pulse processing (DPP) algorithm implemented on the FPGA generates two gamma spectra: one for pulses coincident with beta events and another for non-coincident gamma pulses. These spectrums are transmitted to PC over USB interface.

A Python-based GUI software for Windows PC has been developed which acquires coincidence and anti-coincidence spectra from FPGA based coincidence analyser. It allows analysis by adding different Regions of Interest (ROIs).

Results and Discussion

The developed MCCA module has been validated using a 4π beta-gamma counting setup comprising a liquid scintillator-based beta detector and a NaI(Tl)-based gamma detector. Coincidence counting experiments were performed on a Co-60 sample, with varying chemical quenching to get different beta detection efficiencies.

The activity of the sample was determined using the Efficiency Extrapolation Technique (Baerg, 1973), yielding a value of $301.7 \text{ kBq/g} \pm 1\%$.

This result is in agreement with the value of $298.7 \pm 1\%$, as reported by the existing primary standard setup.

Conclusion

The developed compact MCCA offers multiple digitally controlled parameters. It simplifies the coincidence counting setup by eliminating the need for multiple bin based SCA, DAC, ADC, HV, amplifier, timer and counter modules.

References

Baerg A.P. (1975) *Nuclear Instruments and Methods*, **112**, 143-150.

NUSUNON: A NOVEL DEVICE FOR RADIATION MEASUREMENT AND ITS APPLICATION

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Introduction

The objective of this study to optimize the NuSuNon ("Nun Suwasa Noyarivippan") in terms of operating voltage, working pressure and different sources. NuSuNon is fabricated and it is under clinical validation for exhaled Breath Analysis. As a preliminary study, NuSuNon with 3D positive ion detector is employed in the study for gas detection and radiation measurement and protection.

Materials and Methods

NuSuNon employs a 3D positive ion detector which works on the principle of ioninduced impact ionization. The setup consists of a high vacuum chamber, a brass anode, an oxygen-free high conductivity copper (OFHC) cathode, high voltage power supplies, a ⁶⁰Co (35 kBq) radioactive source, a Raspberry Pi microprocessor for observing output signals. Measurements were taken in a nitrogen medium at a pressure range of 2- 4 mbar. The applied cathode voltages range from – 400 V to – 440 V, with a constant anode voltage of 60 V. The parameters analyzed were number of pulses, maximum amplitude, frequency, rise time & fall time. Each experiment is conducted for thrice trials to ensure reliable data.

Results

The experiments showed notable differences in pulse characteristics under various conditions. At different voltages, the number of pulses increased significantly, from 66 ± 3 at - 420 V to 548 ± 27 at - 440 V, with corresponding increases in amplitude and frequency. Similarly, varying the pressure from 2 mbar to 4 mbar resulted in changes in pulse counts, amplitudes, and frequencies, with 3 mbar showing the highest pulse count of 604 ± 30 . Comparing nitrogen and atmospheric air media at 3 mbar, nitrogen showed three times higher pulse counts and twice the amplitude. Experiments with

different radiation sources (⁶⁰Co, ¹³³Ba, and ¹³⁷Cs) demonstrated varying pulse characteristics, with higher energy sources exhibiting more pulses and higher amplitudes, indicating a greater interaction probability.

Conclusion

The NuSuNon has demonstrated its potential in showcasing the performance of radiation measurements and gas detection. Key findings include the detector performance to differentiate between different gamma ray sources of different activities and has the ability to distinguish among different gases. Thus NuSuNon setup can be used in various fields of radiation environment.

References

- Venkatraman, P., Sureka, C.S., 2019. Analysis on the performance of a 3D positive ion detector as propane and argon sensor, Nucl. Instrum. Methods Phys. Res. B 450, 369-373.
- Venkatraman, P., Sureka, C.S., 2019. An In-Vitro Study for Early Detection and to Distinguish Breast and Lung Malignancies Using the PCB Technology Based Nanodosimeter, Sci. Rep. 9, 380.
- Venkatraman, P., Sureka, C.S., 2021. Confirm Suitability of the 3D Positive Ion Detector to Use in the Field of Radiation Protection, and Gamma Spectrometry Application, Phys. Part. Nucl. Lett. 18, 232–238.

DEVELOPMENT OF A RADIATION MONITORING DONGLE FOR AN ANDROID SMARTPHONE

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Introduction

Portable radiation monitoring devices play a crucial role in emergency response management. Integrating radiation monitors with widely used platforms, such as Android smartphones, facilitates the development of compact and user-friendly systems, providing significant advantages in field applications. This work presents a compact Geiger-Müller (GM) tube-based radiation monitoring dongle that interfaces with Android smartphones via a universal serial bus (USB) using a dedicated application.

Materials and Methods

The radiation monitoring dongle system comprises two primary components: a hardware unit (dongle) and an Android application. The dongle is designed to be compact, low-power, and equipped with USB connectivity. The Android application provides an intuitive interface for visualizing and logging data, as well as configuring system parameters.

The dongle uses an ambient dose compensated GM tube (ZP1202 by Centronic) to detect the gamma radiation. Powered by a +5V USB supply, it utilizes an ultra-low-power PIC24FJ128GB202 microcontroller, which serves as the central controller for the dongle. This microcontroller implements USB HID (Human Interface Device) communication and system control. Its external interrupt and timer ensure accurate pulse rate counting. The dose rate is calculated from the pulse rate using the calibration factor of the GM tube, which is stored in the dongle's non-volatile memory. The dose rate data is then transmitted over USB to the connected smartphone every two seconds. A compact, low-power HV supply, controlled by the central controller, is integrated into the design to generate the +500V required for the GM tube's operation [1].

The Android application, developed in Kotlin, acts as the user interface for the dongle. It acquires real-time dose rate data over USB and displays it in the app's intuitive GUI and the smartphone's notification bar. The app includes features such as configurable acquisition time, survey mode, and data visualization in list, graph, and map formats. Additionally, it allows users to archive and export data in CSV format for further processing and analysis.

Results

The dongle can measure dose rates up to 1 mSv/h with an accuracy of $\pm 15\%$. The system's minimum detectable level (MDL) is 1.5 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$. The dongle typically consumes less than 1 mA current at background radiation levels and up to 20 mA at 1 mSv/h. The lowpower design ensures that the dongle operates effectively without placing an excessive power load on the smartphone's battery.

Conclusion

The radiation monitoring dongle system is a portable, handheld, and user-friendly solution for gamma radiation detection. Its connectivity with smartphones, combined with its compact design and optimized power consumption, makes it an effective tool for widespread deployment in radiation emergency management.

References

Design and Development of an Ultra low power, Compact HV supply (ULPoC HV) for GM tube based Systems; Agarwal S., Jain A., Sharma M. K. and Chaudhury P. (2020) *Proc.IARPNC Conference, IARPNC2020, Mumbai*

DEVELOPMENT OF REMOTE CONTROLLED MOBILE RADIATION MONITORING SYSTEM

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Introduction

In radiation related facilities such as nuclear reactor, accelerators etc., manual monitoring may lead to the radiation exposure to the personnel. Besides, manual monitoring may not be possible in inaccessible areas. This paper discusses the design and development of a Remote Controlled Mobile Radiation Monitoring System (RCMRMS) designed to carry out radiation surveys remotely minimizing the proximity to the speculated radioactive sources.

Materials and Methods

RCMRMS is a mobile, wireless radiation monitoring system equipped with a telescopic arm for extended reach in cluttered environment. It has two major components namely Mobile unit and Remote terminal unit (RTU).

Mobile unit is a battery operated vehicle which is controlled by RTU. It has two easily separable parts called as Robot base and Turret, which are joined using drag chain guide. The robot base is the lower part of the mobile unit that uses 4 wheels skid steer drive for locomotive motion to allow zero turning radius. It also contains ultrasonic proximity sensors for collision detection. It controls the yaw motion of the turret. Turret is a tower like structure which is mounted on the Robot base. It has two telescopic arms with length varying from 80 cm to 150 cm. One arm (arm1) is mounted on the Robot base and other arm (arm2) is mounted on the first arm. Both the arms have tilt motion to provide enhanced access in cluttered section. Radiation detection assembly is mounted on arm2 and uses GM detector module for dose rate & NaI(Tl) detector for gamma spectrometry. GM detector module is placed at the end of the arm2 as end effector and has 180 degree horizontal & 90 degrees vertical motion to get better access of the hot spot. It has 2 GM detectors to cover the wide range of the dose rate measurement. Three

cameras are mounted on the turret at various locations for navigating the mobile unit.

Turret has ATMEGA2560 microcontroller as the main control unit which is responsible for communication with RTU and controls all the motions of the mobile robot. Wireless transmitter is mounted on the turret over a telescopic mast with height varying from 1.5 m to 3 m. It communicates with RTU over 2.4 GHz 802.11 WiFi protocol and has Line Of Sight (LOS) range of 1 Km. High range of communication has been obtained by using 'PX2' transceiver which has improved receiver sensitivity and higher transmission power. Mobile unit is powered by 19.2 AH, 6 cells Liion battery pack with over discharge and short circuit protection. Remote terminal unit is a hand-held battery operated compact unit with 10 inches touch screen tablet. A windows-based GUI running in tablet provides controls of Mobile unit, and displays dose rate, dose rate time profile, accumulated spectrum, alarms etc. It also archives time synchronised radiation data and provides offline analysis capabilities.

Conclusion

RCMRMS is a compact system of dimension 500x500x1300 mm³ with the endurance of up to 4 hours, and dose rate measurement range up to 100 mSv/h. Multiple safety features such as communication loss fail safe, tip over protection, obstacle detection etc have been provided in the system. System has been functionally tested in LEHIPA facility during maintenance. It was remotely manoeuvred along the beam-line and dose rate profiling & spectrum was successfully obtained in the real time.

DEVELOPMENT OF SOFTWARE APPLICATION FOR RADIOLOGICAL EMERGENCY RESPONSE LABORATORY

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Introduction

Real-time measurement and analysis of radiological data are essential during the radiation emergencies to mitigate their impact effectively. The Radiological Emergency Response Laboratory (RERL) is a mobile platform designed to monitor and assess the radiological environments in real-time following a radiation emergency. RERL is equipped with various Radiation Monitoring Systems (RMS) for the qualitative and quantitative assessment of radiological situation. This paper presents the design and development of a software application for the RERL to acquire data from various RMS, analyse this data, present various radiological quantities and generate the survey report.

System Description

The RERL is equipped with two large volume plastic scintillators, each having 1 meter length and 2 inch diameter, to detect the small variations in radiation levels, four Geiger-Muller (GM) Counter detectors with varying sensitivity to measure wide range of dose rate and a 2 inch by 2 inch NaI(Tl) detector for gamma spectrometry. Windowsbased desktop application has been designed and developed for the acquisition, analysis, and presentation of data from various RMS installed in RERL. When the application is launched, the RMS and GPS connect automatically, and the application begins receiving data. The data from the RMS is saved in the database with a user-specified survey name after being tagged with time, latitude, and longitude of the measurement location. At the beginning of the survey, the alarm threshold value for each detector is generated based on the prevailing background radiation level. The dose rate at low exposure levels ($< 10 \mu\text{Sv/h}$) is estimated from the gamma spectrum, while higher exposure levels are measured using GM detectors. Spatial profile of the dose rate is

presented on a map, while a time profile is displayed on a chart. The application generates the HTML report of the survey, which includes a list of alarms, dose rate and count rate profiles in both map and chart formats, and the gamma spectrum.

Application Software Architecture

The RERL software application is developed based on client-server architecture. Graphical User Interface (GUI) of the application is a Single Page Application (SPA) built with Angular, while the backend is implemented using Python. The SPA communicates with the backend via ServerSent Events (SSE) and HTTP requests. Upon start up, the Python backend initializes an Uvicorn HTTP server and launches an embedded web browser in kiosk mode to serve the SPA files. The HTTP server processes the asynchronously acquired data from the RMS using the aioserial [1] Python package. The acquired data is parsed, validated and transmitted to the SPA using SSE. The SPA stores data in a PostgreSQL database via HTTP POST requests. Radiological data is presented on Leaflet map and charts. The map tiles of the survey area are automatically downloaded and saved locally when internet connectivity is available.

Results

The developed application has been successfully used in many radiation surveys including radiological surveillance during G20 Summit in New Delhi, environmental radiation surveys in BARC site etc.

References

[1] Chang, J. (2017) "Aioserial: Async serial port library for Python," available at <https://github.com/mrjohannchang/aioserial.py>

LEARNING PLASTIC SCINTILLATOR SPECTRA USING VAE BASED DEEP-NEURAL ARCHITECTURE

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Introduction

Identifying gamma emitting radionuclides from the spectrum of a plastic scintillator (PS) detector is exceedingly difficult due to the absence of a distinct photo-peak, a distinct feature of radionuclide, despite the extensive use of these detectors in gamma detection applications. Recently, the neural network-based architectures shown their capabilities not only to extract unseen features from the data but also can give insight in the physics involved from the data [1].

Materials and Methods

In this study, we explore feature learning from PS-based spectra using a variational autoencoder (VAE), a type of deep generative model designed to learn compact and meaningful data representations. VAE encodes input data into a lower-dimensional latent space while enabling reconstruction of the original input. Its training involves optimizing a combined loss function: a reconstruction loss, ensures the output closely resembles the input, and a regularization term (based on Kullback Leibler (KL) divergence) aligns the latent space with a predefined prior distribution. This dual objective framework allows the VAE to achieve a balance between accurate reconstruction and meaningful latent space representations, facilitating insights into the underlying physical processes of spectrum generation. In our work, we examine the effectiveness of various reconstruction loss functions, including mean squared error (MSE), Wasserstein distance (WD), and total counts loss (TC), which represents the absolute difference in total counts within the spectrum. The VAE model utilized in this study consists of an encoder with 2 layers (512, 256) and a decoder with 2 layers (256, 512). The input spectrum data has a dimension of 1024. We varied the latent

dimension across 4, 16, and 32 during our experiments. To train the model, we generated 100,000 simulated spectra for a plastic scintillator (2" × 2") using Fluka. Six radionuclides—Co-60, Cs-137, Ar-41, I-131, K-40, and Tl-208—were selected, covering an energy range from 100 keV to 3 MeV. Each spectrum comprises varying proportions of these radionuclides, summing to one. The dataset was split into 60,000 spectra for training, 20,000 for testing, and 20,000 for validation to assess model performance. The model was trained for 100 epochs, with the learning rate reduced by a factor of 0.1 every 10 epochs.

Results

Training the model for 100 epochs with latent dimensions of 4, 16, and 32, we observed that the total loss (MSE, TC, WD, KL) indicated faster convergence for a latent dimension of 4 compared to 16 and 32. Reconstruction quality was comparatively better for the lower energy part of the spectrum ($E < 1.5\text{MeV}$) than for the high energy range ($1.5\text{MeV} < E < 3.0\text{MeV}$). This may be due to lower gamma interaction probability at higher energies, making features corresponding to higher energies less pronounced.

Conclusion

The study shows that developed VAE with a smaller latent space can capture essential features to reconstruct the spectrum. Enhancing the dataset with spectra containing more prominent high-energy features would improve the model's performance.

References

1. Kingma, D. P., & Welling, M. (2013). AutoEncoding Variational Bayes. arXiv preprint arXiv:1312.6114.

DEVELOPMENT OF METHODOLOGY FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF ^{90}Sr AND ^{137}Cs CONCENTRATION IN FILTER PAPER SAMPLES

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Introduction

^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr are prominent long lived fission products found in radioactive waste. And to mitigate the release of radioactive aerosols into the environment, HEPA filters are employed in exhaust lines of nuclear facilities. They are required to be disposed due to reduction in the particle removal efficiency of the filters. Before disposing the filters, ^{137}Cs is estimated using gamma spectrometry. For ^{90}Sr estimation, time consuming radioanalytical procedures are followed [1]. In the present study, a simple and rapid technique for simultaneous estimation of ^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr in filter paper is proposed using combination of gamma spectrometry and Liquid Scintillation Counting (LSC) without radioanalytical separation.

Materials and methods

Glass fiber filter paper was used for spiking $^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$ ($37 \pm 0.1 \text{ kBqg}^{-1}$) and ^{137}Cs ($30 \pm 0.1 \text{ kBqg}^{-1}$). Packard Tri Carb 4910TR LSC was used for gross β measurement due to $^{137}\text{Cs} + ^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$. Gamma-ray spectrometry for ^{137}Cs was performed using BSI make GCD-50 190X coaxial germanium detector. Quenching was observed using standard quench indicating parameter, transformed Spectral Index of External Standard (tSIE). Calibration curves were generated for $^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$ and ^{137}Cs using LSC. For estimation of ^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr in the filter paper samples, 1cm^2 glass fiber filter paper samples were spiked in duplicates with known concentrations of ^{137}Cs (50.2 ± 0.1 to $195.5 \pm 0.4 \text{ Bq}$) and $^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$ (28.0 ± 0.4 to $100.0 \pm 1.5 \text{ Bq}$). Samples were dried and placed in 20 mL capacity borosilicate glass vials and were subjected to gamma spectrometry for ^{137}Cs measurement. ^{137}Cs activity was then converted into count rate (cpm) termed as A based on LSC counting efficiency (CE) using the calibration curve. 5 mL Optiphase HiSafe III scintillation cocktail

was added to all the samples and were counted in 0-2000 keV energy scale using LSC for 30 minutes counting time. This gave gross count rate (B) due to $^{137}\text{Cs} + ^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$. To know the count rate due to $^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$, ^{137}Cs cpm is subtracted from the gross cpm obtained using LSC, B-A. This $^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$ cpm is converted into activity by using the CE for $^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$ obtained from the calibration curve. $^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$ activity was divided by 2 to get ^{90}Sr activity.

Results and discussion

A relationship between %deviation and the $^{137}\text{Cs}/^{90}\text{Sr}$ activity ratios were observed. For $^{137}\text{Cs}/^{90}\text{Sr}$ ratio ≥ 2 , %deviation in case of ^{90}Sr lied in the range of -10% to 5%. For $^{137}\text{Cs}/^{90}\text{Sr}$ ratio less 2, it was in the range of -7.6% to 3.8%. This was due to the influence of ^{137}Cs activity on ^{90}Sr activity. MDA for ^{90}Sr and ^{137}Cs obtained using LSC and gamma spectrometry was 0.04 Bq and 0.08 Bq respectively for 30 min counting time.

Conclusion

A mathematical relation between $^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$ and ^{137}Cs is obtained and the developed methodology is rapid, simple which does not require radioanalytical separation. The present approach could be an alternative in determining ^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr in air filter samples compared to conventional methods.

References

Vajda N, Kim CK (2010). Applied Radiation and Isotopes 68(12):2306–2326.

ASSESSMENT OF RADIO XENON IN REACTOR SYSTEMS USING GAMMA SPECTROMETRY

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Introduction

Xenon is a chemically inert noble gas present in trace amounts (87 ppb) in Earth's atmosphere. Radioactive xenon isotopes ¹³³Xe and ¹³⁵Xe are generated through fission in nuclear facilities with a half-life of 5.2 days and 9.1 hours, respectively. They can migrate widely and their presence in the environment plays a crucial role in monitoring abnormal releases from nuclear facilities and any nuclear accidents. The detection of these isotopes involves sampling of the gas and measuring its activity by gamma spectrometry techniques. The spectrometry measurement requires accurate efficiency calibration using standard radioactive sources. However, as standard radioactive sources are not available, Monte Carlo simulation technique was adopted to generate efficiency function for measurement of radioactive xenon. In the present work, activity of the xenon isotopes was measured in the cover gas from the research reactor using High Purity Germanium (HPGe) gamma spectrometry system.

Materials and Methods

A cylindrical gas cell of aluminium, volume (~22 ml) was designed and fabricated for collecting and measuring of radioxenon. The gas cell was designed for easy mounting on a HPGe detector system with inlet and outlet valves for gas purging and filling. The gamma spectrometry system consist of 30%HPGe detector coupled with 8k multichannel analyser. The gas cell was positioned on the face of the detector during the experiment. Cover gas samples were collected from the research reactor and analysed for Xe isotopes.

Results

The gas sample containing the noble gases was analyzed and activity concentration of ⁴¹Ar, ^{85m}Kr, ⁸⁷Kr, ⁸⁸Kr, ¹³³Xe and ¹³⁵Xe isotopes were characterized and determined. The efficiency function for detector and gas cell geometry was generated using simulated gamma spectra and were fitted into a following semi empirical function (Eq.1). $\ln(\varepsilon_\gamma) = \sum_{i=0}^n A_i(\ln(E_\gamma))^i$ (1) Where ε_γ is the full energy peak efficiency at a given gamma energy of E_γ and A_i is regression coefficients obtained from the fitting of efficiency data with energy. It was possible to measure the activity concentrations of ⁴¹Ar, ^{85m}Kr, ⁸⁷Kr, ⁸⁸Kr, ¹³³Xe and ¹³⁵Xe isotopes at very low levels using this technique. Minimum detectable concentration (MDC) of ⁴¹Ar, ^{85m}Kr, ⁸⁷Kr, ⁸⁸Kr, ¹³³Xe and ¹³⁵Xe isotopes for the present system, with a counting time of 2000 seconds are 9.1, 7.7, 18.3, 25.3, 29.7 and 8.0 Bq/L respectively.

Conclusion

The method provides valuable data for assessing the reactor's safety status, as the release of these radioxenon is also important for detecting abnormal conditions. This method can also be applied in the monitoring of radioxenon in environment by prior pre-concentration of xenon from ambient air.

References

- Matthew A. Goodwin, Ashley V. Davies and Richard Britton (2021) *Journal of Environmental. Radioactivity* **234**, 106629.
Amit K. Verma, Amar D. Pant, Anilkumar S. Pillai and A. Vinod Kumar (2024) *MAPAN Journal of Metrology Society of India*, **39**, 8993.

DIGITALIZATION OF RADIOLOGICAL SURVEILLANCE DATA AT FF

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Introduction

Fuel Fabrication (FF) is manufacturing PuO₂ based Mixed Oxide (MOX) fuel for Prototype Fast Breeder Reactor (PFBR) [1]. During fabrication process, radiation workers has potential for external and internal exposure. To ensure the integrity of engineering systems & safety of radiation workers a radiation surveillance programme is implemented for workplace monitoring [2]. External exposure monitoring is carried out using alarm-based installed AGMs & periodic radiation survey of labs. While air borne contamination monitoring is carried out by alarm based installed CAMs & passive sampling through air sampling points of glove box. Approximately 200 nos. of filter paper are changed daily & counted for immediate counting and after four-day delay to estimate long lived air activity. All these HP records are maintained on paper-based log books. The management of extensive data in offline mode poses several challenges with data processing, potential human errors in calculations, data retrieval and carbon footprint from paper usage. These difficulties can be overcome by transitioning to digital platforms. This paper highlights the features of a newly developed software called "Digital HP" designed specifically for the digitalization of HP data at FF.

Material & Method

A local network based software is developed for HP data handling in which HTML is used at front-end and SQL & PHP used at back-end. Users are categorized into three types—Admin, Normal and Viewer with varying levels of access and control. This software is organized into distinct modules focusing on internal and external exposure control data management. For radiation survey data software offers form in which user can select the location within the plant to record radiation levels and options to upload PDF file of survey sheets. To record air activity data software contains two forms, one for

immediate another for delay counting. It automatically calculates the Forward/Reverse ratio and DAC-h values, alerting users if values exceed safe thresholds. Report generation feature allows users to create customized reports for air activity data. Digital HP dashboard offers overview of monitoring data including graphical displays of air activity trends, maximum gamma and neutron radiation levels and laboratory specific radiation readings. This data is stored at main server of FF with its periodic backup.

Results & Discussion

The transition to Digitalization, offers significant benefits in handling of huge HP data. Digital HP software eliminates manual calculations, improves the accuracy & reliability of Health Physics data. It streamlines in prompt decision by RSO & FF management by access to radiological surveillance data from any location within the plant. It facilitate easy generation of various HP reports for any time & air activity window. Moreover, it reduces carbon footprint by replacing paperwork with digital records. It also provides the foundation for advanced analytics, enabling predictive monitoring and proactive risk mitigation.

Conclusion

Implementation of Digital HP at FF facility marks a pivotal step towards digitalization. Future versions of the software are expected to expand its functionality to include additional HP data and extending its utility to other plants within the BARC network.

References

- [1]R B Bhatt, Experience and Developments in Fabrication of MOX Fuel at Advanced Fuel Fabrication Facility, *BARC Newsletter, Founder's Day special issue, 2018.*
- [2]Radiation Protection Manual for BARC Facilities, BSC/SM/2020/3.

THEORETICAL ESTIMATION OF EFFICIENCY FOR AR-41 MEASUREMENT IN NAI(TL) DETECTOR USING GEANT4 CODE

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Introduction

Dhruva is a 100 MWth research reactor utilizing natural Uranium fuel, heavy water as both moderator and primary coolant. It is having maximum thermal neutron flux of 2.0×10^{14} n/cm²/sec. Ar-41, which is produced by the activation of air used for cooling of reactor core assemblies such as Shut of Rods, Adjuster rods etc. During normal reactor operation, Ar-41 is produced and subsequently discharged through a 100-meter stack.

Accurate measurement of Ar-41 using NaI(Tl) system requires photo peak efficiency for photo peak energy, sample geometry and detector dimensions. Argon-41 reference sources are not available for calibrating the system therefore theoretical estimation of the efficiency is carried out using GEANT4 code, which is a Montecarlo based technique for simulation and modelling. This theoretical estimated efficiency was used in measurement and quantification of Ar-41 releases from Dhruva reactor. The measurements carried out using this system were compared with the existing HPGe based detector system.

Materials and Methods

A methodology was developed using NaI(Tl) Gamma Spectrometry system for measurement and quantification of the Ar-41 before discharge to the environment. GEANT4 code has been used to simulate the marinelli beaker geometry with NaI(Tl) detector Crystal of size 762mm x 7.62 mm along with Aluminium housing of 1.5 mm and top cover thickness of 1.0 mm. GEANT4 version 11.1.2 is used with ROOT 6.26.14 analysis Software for efficiency estimation. Mono energetic gamma photons of energy 1293keV were generated uniformly in the annular space of marinelli beaker with isotropic distribution in all directions. Total number of events simulated were $1E+07$. ROOT software was used for processing of energy deposited in the sensitive volume of

the detector and energy spectrum was plotted after including the Gaussian energy response for the photo peak energy 1293keV.

Results

Simulated photon interaction in NaI(Tl) detector system and its energy spectrum was used for estimation of the efficiency for the marinelli beaker geometry for photo peak energy of 1293keV. Area under the simulated photo peak was used for photo peak efficiency estimation. The efficiency of the system for Ar-41 gamma energy 1293keV was found to be 2.69%. The measurement of the daily release of Ar-41 was carried out at different reactor power levels. Variation in average daily releases measured using NaI(Tl) detector system and existing HPGe detector system was found to be <1 %.

Conclusion

Average daily release of Ar-41 calculated using theoretical estimated efficiency found in good agreement with compare to measurement carried out with HPGe detector. Therefore, Ar41 measurement methodology using NaI(Tl) detector system is able to cater the requirement of Ar-41 quantification in gaseous effluent before discharge from the Dhruva reactor. Monitoring of Ar-41 in gaseous effluents from Dhruva research reactor is being done for its quantification and compliance with regulatory limits of radioactive discharges.

References:

- Geant4 a Simulation toolkit Introduction to Geant4 Release 11.2
- Glenn F Knoll, Radiation Detection and Measurement, 3rd edition.
- Engineering drawing of Marinelli Cup geometry.

A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR AN IOT BASED OPERATIONAL RADIATION PROTECTION PROGRAMME

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Introduction

Managing radiation exposure is vital in nuclear facilities to ensure worker safety, environmental protection, and regulatory compliance. Traditional radiation protection methods rely on manual monitoring and fixed or handheld instruments. They often lead to delay in detection and response to transient radiation events. The Internet of Things (IoT) offers a transformative solution to this challenge by, enabling real-time data collection, continuous monitoring, and automated decision-making in the nuclear industry [1]. IoT's network of interconnected sensors and systems enhances operational radiation protection through actionable insights, predictive analytics, and automation. This paper presents a conceptual framework for such an IoT-based operational radiation protection program.

Conceptual Framework

A. Data Acquisition Layer

A.1. Radiation monitors: Fixed and portable IoT-enabled gamma, neutron, and beta radiation detectors placed strategically across the facility to monitor controlled areas;

A.2. Wearable devices: Personal dosimeters with data transfer capabilities, for workers to track individual radiation exposure;

A.3. Environmental monitors: Devices that monitor radioactive releases to environment, including factors influencing radiation dispersion, such as airflow, humidity, and temperature.

A.4. Robotics and drones: Automated systems equipped with radiation monitors for inspecting inaccessible or hazardous areas.

B. Data Processing and Analytics Layer

B.1. Edge computing: Immediate analysis of Data Acquisition Layer data at or near the source to enable instant feedback (e.g., alerts when radiation levels exceed thresholds).

B.2. Cloud integration: Storage and advanced processing of historical and real-time data in a secure internal cloud environment.

B.3. Predictive analytics: Machine learning models use historical data to predict potential radiation spikes or equipment failures, enabling proactive measures.

B.4. Visualization tools: Interactive dashboards display real-time heatmaps of radiation levels, worker exposure trends, and safety zone demarcation.

C. Decision and Action Layer

C.1. Automated alerts: Notifications sent to workers, operators, and emergency response teams in case of anomalies.

C.2. Access control: Integration with facility access systems to automatically restrict entry to high-radiation zones based on real-time data.

C.4. Compliance reporting: Automated generation of reports for regulatory authorities, ensuring transparency and adherence to safety standards.

Supportive mechanisms within the framework would include robust cybersecurity, periodic calibration and maintenance and finally regular training for workers to use and interpret the data appropriately.

Conclusion

A conceptual IoT-driven framework is presented as a transformative, data-driven approach to radiation protection in nuclear facilities.

References

[1]. C. Lu et al., "Nuclear Power Plants With Artificial Intelligence in Industry 4.0 Era: Top-Level Design and Current Applications—A Systemic Review," IEEE Access, vol. 8, pp. 194315-194332, 2020.

ESTIMATION OF RELATIVE EFFICIENCY OF A HPGe DETECTOR BY SIMULATION TECHNIQUE

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Introduction

A high-resolution gamma ray spectrometer using a High-Purity Germanium (HPGe) detector is an advanced radioanalytical tool for the qualitative and quantitative analysis of radioactivity in samples from diverse areas of nuclear fuel cycle operations and environmental studies.

The efficiency calibration of the system requires standard radioactive sources with the same geometrical dimensions, density and composition as the sample. However, it is not feasible to have physical standards for all nuclides encountered in the laboratory. An alternate approach involves applying Monte Carlo simulation techniques (Marcos et al., 2015; Narayani et al., 2018).

Relative efficiency is a key parameter used to specify the dimension and configuration of the detector system. It is defined as the ratio of the absolute efficiency of HPGe detector to that of a 3"x3" NaI(Tl) detector for 1.33 MeV at 25 cm. This study estimates the relative efficiency theoretically using simulation techniques, compares the results with experimental values, and validates the operational specifications provided by the manufacturer.

Materials and Methods

The detector used in this study is a P type coaxial HPGe detector (GCD 100-220 of Bruker Baltic) with a crystal length of 81.2 mm, a diameter of 81.3 mm, and a relative efficiency of 100% as per the manufacturer's specifications. The detector model is developed using the manufacturer-supplied dimensions. The absolute efficiency of the 3"x3" NaI(Tl) detector for 1.33 MeV at 25 cm is 0.12%. The spectral response of gamma photons from ⁶⁰Co source at 25 cm is estimated using Monte Carlo simulation techniques. From the peak area under the 1332.46 keV energy line in the simulated spectra, the relative efficiency of the detector is calculated.

Results

The relative efficiency of the detector is determined experimentally using a standard ⁶⁰Co reference source at 25 cm and theoretically using Monte Carlo simulations. The experimentally determined relative efficiency calculated is 94.2%, while the simulation yielded a value of 98.3%. Both the values are within 6% deviation from relative efficiency provided by the manufacturer (i.e., 100%).

Conclusion

The results validate the developed detector model, demonstrating its applicability for generating absolute efficiency calibration data for sources across various practical geometries. This source-less calibration procedure can also be applied to samples for which standard sources are unavailable or impractical.

References

- Marcos P. C. et al. (2015) International Nuclear Atlantic Conference - INAC 2015 São Paulo, SP, Brazil, October 4-9, 2015.
Narayani K., Amar Pant, Amit K. and Anilkumar S. (2018) Proc. 33rd IARP conference, Mumbai.

OFFLINE ANALYSIS OF DIGITAL WAVEFORM DATA FROM PHOSWICH DETECTOR FOR IMPROVEMENT IN ACTINIDE MONITORING

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Keywords: Phoswich, actinide monitoring, pulse shape, digital signal.

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Introduction

Phoswich detector is used for actinide monitoring of the radiation workers involved in fuel fabrication and reprocessing. Traditionally, Pulse Height Spectra (PHS) for actinide monitoring is obtained by pulse shape analysis based anti-coincidence technique with this detector. However, adopting a Digital Pulse Processing (DPP) system can enhance it by extracting both low energy (LEP) and high energy photon (HEP) emitter information simultaneously. Further, digital waveforms of pulses acquired in a single measurement can be offline analyzed with different set of parameters to get PHS with minimal losses.

Materials and Methods

A cylindrical Phoswich detector (diameter of 20 cm, 3 mm thick NaI(Tl) followed by a 5 cm thick CsI(Tl) crystals), was used in this study. The scintillation light decay time for the NaI(Tl) crystal is 230 ns and for CsI(Tl) crystal, two decay components of 680 ns (64%) and 3340 ns (36%) exist (Knoll, 2010). This difference is utilized to discriminate photons of different energies as LEPs (<100 keV) deposit their maximum energy in the NaI(Tl) crystal, while HEPs interact more in the CsI(Tl) crystal. Data was acquired using a CAEN DT5725 14-bit digitizer with sampling rate of 250 MegaSamples/second with record length of 4000 ns, and the data was stored in TTree data structure of ROOT (Brun, 1997). The acquired data consist of sampled waveforms of pulses generated in the detector for ²⁴¹Am and ¹³⁷Cs sources, placed at 10 cm distance from the detector face. A program was developed to analyse this data using charge integration method with different long and short gate values to extract the pulse height and shape parameters for separate NaI(Tl) and CsI(Tl) PHS.

Results

The PHS from phoswich detector shows a mixed response due to interactions in the phoswich detector. Using the shape parameter for each pulse, the pulses were stored in NaI(Tl) or CsI(Tl) PHS. The NaI(Tl) PHS exhibits peaks from ²⁴¹Am along with an additional signature due to X-rays (~32 keV) from ¹³⁷Cs. The CsI(Tl) PHS displays the characteristic response of 662 keV photons from ¹³⁷Cs, excluding the 32 keV peak which got recorded in NaI(Tl). Validation of these spectra was performed by comparing them with the standard spectra for ²⁴¹Am and ¹³⁷Cs sources.

Conclusion

The methodology enables the simultaneous quantification of actinides and fission/activation products. The offline data analysis of pulses empowers the user to extract the information by varying certain parameters on a single dataset which removes statistical variation arising by multiple measurements.

References

- G. F. Knoll, 2010.
- R. Brun and F. Rademakers, Nuclear instruments and methods in physics research section A: accelerators, spectrometers, detectors and associated equipment, 389(1-2):81–86, 1997.
- UM5960, CAEN Spa, 2023.

STANDARDIZATION OF MULTI-CUVETTE LED FLUORIMETER FOR AUTOMATED URANIUM ANALYSIS IN BIOASSAY SAMPLES

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Keywords: uranium, multicuvette LED fluorimeter, bioassay

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Introduction

Uranium poses health hazards due to its chemical toxicity and radiological properties once it enters the body. Hence, it is essential to assess internal contamination among radiation workers handling uranium. In-vitro analysis through urinalysis for uranium is highly sensitive and hence is preferred for routine bioassays. On average, about 600-700 bioassay samples are being analyzed for uranium annually. This number has increased in recent years and is expected to rise further. To manage the anticipated increase in workload, it is planned to implement automation at various stages of sample processing and analysis. This study describes the standardization of a newly developed multi-cuvette LED fluorimeter system (LF-3) and its comparative study with the existing single cuvette LED fluorimeter system (LF-2) [1]. The LF-3 system features 4 modes for measuring uranium concentration: Calibrated Fluorescence Mode (CFM), Standard Addition Mode (SAM), Uncalibrated Mode (UCM) and a fourth mode that combines CFM and SAM. The system is designed in such a way that once all 16 samples are loaded in their respective chambers, all samples can be counted in a single run.

Materials and Methods

The LF-3 system is designed to measure uranium concentration based on a fluorescence measurement technique. The excitation source for the LF-3 system consist of a bank of pulsed LEDs that emit light at 340 nm. This light is directed onto a quartz cuvette containing the sample. The uranyl ions in the sample become excited, and, upon de-excitation, emit fluorescence at 496, 516, and 540 nm which is detected by a photomultiplier tube (PMT). The fluorescence intensity is further enhanced by mixing a known aliquot of the sample with a 5% sodium pyrophosphate buffer solution at pH 7.2. The uranium concentration in the

sample is calculated using the following formula:

$$U \text{ (ppb)} = \frac{(x - b)}{(q - x)} \times c$$

Where, x, b and q are fluorescence counts due to sample, buffer and sample plus uranium standard respectively and c is the concentration of uranium standard solution.

The LF-3 system was calibrated using five U(nat.) standards with known concentrations of 5, 10, 50, 100 and 200 ppb. After calibration, 16 uranium samples with concentrations ranging from 5 to 100 ppb were prepared. These samples were measured using both the new multi-cuvette LF-3 and the existing single cuvette LF-2 system, using both CFM and SAM modes.

Results

The measurement results for uranium

concentrations obtained from the LF-2 and LF3 systems were in agreement within an error margin of <10% for lower uranium concentrations (< 10 ppb) and < 5% for uranium concentrations > 10 ppb. The new LF-3 system significantly reduced the sample counting time to 2-3 minutes for 16 samples. Additionally, the software modified format as per user requirement from the new LF-3 system can be stored on a laptop and making it convenient for further data analysis.

Conclusion

The new multicuvette LF-3 system is designed to effectively manage increased workloads. This capability not only reduces the manual intervention but also streamlines and automates the data processing.

References

1. Suja A. et al. (2012) *J Radioanal Nucl Chem* **294**, 439–442

A PORTABLE TECHNIQUE FOR RADIUM BODY BURDEN MEASUREMENT USING ALPHAGUARD

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Introduction

The assessment of radium body burden traditionally relies on measuring radon concentration using low-level radon detection system (LLRDS) techniques [1]. LLRDS methods requires a metal disc for radon daughter deposition, a negative voltage source (-800 V) and an alpha counter. The measured radon concentration is then converted into radium activity, providing an estimate of the radium content in the body. While effective, these methods are complex and lack portability. In the present study has explored AlphaGUARD as an alternative for radon detection.

Materials and Methods

In this study, a novel method is presented using the AlphaGUARD portable radon monitor, which simplifies the measurement process by directly detecting radon concentration and converting it into radium activity. The methodology eliminates the need for metal disc for deposition of radon daughters, a high-voltage deposition system, and an alpha counter, thus enhancing portability and ease of use. A mathematical relation for radium activity in terms of radon is governed by equation (1) [1].

$$Q = \frac{C_{Rn} I}{\lambda_{Rn} f} \quad (1)$$

In equation (1), C_{Rn} represents radon (^{222}Rn) activity in Bq m^{-3} , Q represents radium (^{226}Ra) in Bq , I is breathing rate in $\text{m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, λ_{Rn} is radioactive decay constant in s^{-1} for radon and f is release fraction for radon with typical values lies from 0.7-1.0 [1].

The measurement process for the present study consists of a 40-day (approximately 10 halflives of radon) old medical oxygen source, an oxygen mask with both inlet and outlet connections, a cooling system for moisture removal, an LLRDS chamber, and an AlphaGUARD device for radon detection. The 40-day period allows for the decay of any

residual radon originally present in the medical oxygen to negligible levels, ensuring it does not interfere with subsequent measurements. Radon-free oxygen is inhaled, and exhaled breaths containing radon are collected in the LLRDS chamber through a cooling system. The cooling system ensures the gas is filled from the bottom of the chamber by increasing its density through cooling and reduces humidity (<90%) for AlphaGUARD compatibility. It measures the radon concentration, which is then converted into radium activity using Equation (1).

Results

The equilibrium radon concentration measured by AlphaGUARD is $49 \pm 6 \text{ Bq m}^{-3}$ corresponding to a radium body burden of $3.61 \pm 0.44 \text{ kBq}$. The radium body burden estimated using the conventional technique, 3.21 kBq , shows good agreement with the value obtained using AlphaGUARD.

Conclusions

Replacing the radon measurement system with AlphaGUARD simplified the complex processes of daughter deposition and counting, significantly reducing the counting time and improving portability. Additionally, AlphaGUARD can detect residual radon in inhaled medical oxygen, minimizing the risk of overestimation. However, a notable drawback of using AlphaGUARD is the longer collection time required (20 minutes) compared to the conventional technique, which takes only 10 minutes.

References

Srivastava, G.K., Raghavayya, M., Kotrappa, P. and Somasundaram, S. (1986) *Health physics*, 50(2), pp.217-221.

DEVELOPMENT OF A COMMUNICATION INTERFACE MODULE FOR BACKPACK GAMMA SPECTROMETRY SYSTEM FOR REAL TIME DATA TRANSFER TO A SERVER-BASED WEB APPLICATION

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Introduction

In the event of a radiation emergency, prompt communication of environmental monitoring data to the decision makers is important for the swift implementation of the countermeasures to minimize the radiation exposure to the affected people. Achieving this requires the integration of environmental monitoring data acquired by the various radiation monitoring instruments into a unified platform. A server-based web application with radiation monitoring systems capable of communicating the measurement data to the server directly can provide a robust and efficient framework for handling emergency situations [1]. This paper presents the development of a communication interface for Backpack Gamma Spectrometry System (BGSS) for the real-time radiation data transfer to a server-based web application.

System Description

BGSS is a gamma spectrometry system in the backpack configuration. It includes a Radiation Detection Unit (RDU), housed in a backpack, and an Android smartphone. The RDU includes a detector assembly comprising a 2" x 2" NaI(Tl) detector for gamma spectrometry and measuring low-dose rate and a GM detector for measuring high-dose rates. An inhouse developed Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA)-based 512 channel multichannel analyzer (MCA) is used for gamma spectrometry. A 250 g sample of potassium chloride powder is used for the self-energy calibration of the system. RDU transmits spectrum and count data to the smartphone via Bluetooth. The BGSS Android application performs real-time analysis of the data to compute dose rates, generate alarms, and identify radionuclides. The application also transfers dose rate and spectrum data, tagged with latitude, longitude, and time, to the server in real time and offline over internet.

Application Software Architecture

The BGSS Android application is developed using 'Basic 4 Android', an android application development tool. HTTPS protocol is used for the secure communication between BGSS and server for device registration, and online and offline data transfer. OAuth2.0 Device flow protocol is used for the secure device registration with the server. The registration process begins with sending an HTTPS POST request to the server and receives two strings, "device-code" and "OTP". The user authenticates the device registration using this OTP shown in BGSS through the user interface provided in web application. After the authentication, request from the device results in the server sending a username, and password. Subsequently these credentials are used for getting access token, and refresh token from the server, which are then used for sending the radiological data to the server securely.

Results and Conclusion

The developed BGSS application has been tested successfully with the server-based Integrated Radiation Emergency Management System (IREMS) for the real-time and offline transfer of dose rate and gamma spectrum. IREMS presents gamma spectrum and dose rate profile of the survey area in an intuitive GUI in the form of map and chart. The live radiation data facilitates immediate access to spatial and temporal profiles enabling timely and well-informed decision making.

References

1. IAEA, International Radiation Monitoring Information System, User Manual. IAEA, 2019.

DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF NEUTRON FLUX MONITOR

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Introduction

Neutron monitoring is essential in nuclear facilities where commercially available REM counters are typically used by health physicist. These monitors employ small detectors with AndersonBraun or Leake designs which converts fluence to dose using conversion coefficient curves. However, these monitors are heavy (weight 15-20 Kg) and exhibit low sensitivity. For applications involving known neutron sources in the field highly sensitive neutron flux monitor is beneficial for mapping neutron flux variation efficiently. The paper describes the design and development of neutron flux monitor with 2.54 cm diameter 50 cm long He³ proportional thermal neutron detector ^[1] combined with a 3 cm High Density Polyethylene (HDPE). The high thermal neutron cross section of He³ along with its availability at higher gas pressure, makes it a favourable choice for neutron measurement applications requiring maximum detection efficiency. This paper describes development of a He³ proportional counter based thermal neutron flux monitor.

Material and Methods

Developed Neutron flux monitor utilizes a He3 detector housed in a 1 mm thick stainless steel cylinder. The detector enclosure is welded with 5 cm diameter circular SS plate which is attached to the electronic enclosure box. Detector sleeve is surrounded with HDPE moderator. While the optimal HDPE thickness for 2.2 MeV neutron is 8 cm^[2], considering the portability 3.87 cm thick HDPE is used. The electronics for detector pulse processing, control, display and memory storage was designed, developed and fabricated in house as shown in Figure 1. The monitor incorporates a Philips P89LPC917 microcontroller. The embedded software interprets detector response, displays counts per minute on Liquid Crystal Display (LCD) and stores data in memory, which can be retrieved and sent to PC for further analysis and record keeping.

Results and Discussion

The system has been calibrated using thermal neutron as well as ²⁵²Cf (2.2 MeV) and AmBe (4 MeV) sources positioned at 25 cm from the center. The measured efficiencies for these sources were 25%, 13% and 8% respectively. The system continuously monitors the Flux data with acquisition time of 1 minute and updates on the LCD. The system has been tested in laboratory for stability, reproducibility and continuous operation and has been successfully used for neutron flux measurements in the field.

The system demonstrated a response of 18 mg/CPM for research reactor grade plutonium measurements at a distance of 25 cm. The monitor is versatile and can be used for applications such as detecting illicit trafficking and contaminations of plutonium, inspecting nuclear waste, finding of neutron sources and Monitoring of neutron radiation field intensities.

References:

1. LND INC. 252130 Cylindrical He3 Neutron Detector datasheet, Web Site: www.lndinc.com
2. Vaishali M Thakur, Amit Jain, K Biju, C Sunil, S Anilkumar, D A R Babu & D N Sharma, Studies on optimization of moderator thickness for BF₃ detectors used for monitoring of fissile material. Indian J Pure & Appl. Phys. 50 811-813 2012

MACHINE LEARNING BASED APPROACH TO PRECONDITION IMBALANCED DATASET FOR NUCLEAR FORENSIC ANALYSIS.

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Keywords: Machine Learning, Nuclear Forensics, Imbalance Ratio.

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Introduction

This paper explores and studies a machine learning based approach to pre-condition samples for multi class prediction in nuclear forensic analysis. Missing values and imbalance within samples' distribution may bias prediction results. In such cases, overall prediction accuracy is not a good metric of performance as it mostly works in favor of class with majority samples. This paper focuses on effects of imbalance in a Machine Learning (ML) classification problem.

Methodology

The open source data [1] from various mines contains attribution of minerals to their origin on the basis of isotopic concentration. Labelled data from 22 sites with 565 samples has been used to train a ML model.

It is a practice to perform exploratory data analysis before applying any machine learning algorithm. A summary of data was generated to see mismatch in scales of various features and missing (Not a Number) values. Missing values which were found to be completely absent for a label (mine) were replaced by 0, instead of mean, as likely no measurement was made for that isotope on that site. All scales were also normalized. In addition to this, Imbalance Ratio (IR) of each label was calculated to access imbalance in number of samples for each label. The samples in various classes ranged from 84 as highest (majority class) and 1 as lowest with IR=84.

When predictions were made using this data deploying a Multi-Layer Perceptron (4 layers) ML model, a fairly good overall accuracy of 92.94% was achieved. A confusion matrix, that tabulates predicted labels against actual ones, was generated to identify how accurate was prediction in each class. Observing per class accuracy for each label, some labels were completely missing in prediction as they had very few samples. Majority classes were

predicted with 100% of accuracy and minority classes with 0% having only one sample. Some labels with IR higher than 3 were predicted poorly (~50%). It was evident that classifier was working in favour of majority classes and overall accuracy is governed by majority prediction.

To deal with imbalance, labels with imbalance ratio more than 4 were curtailed from the dataset [2]. This reduced 565 samples to 524 containing 16 labels instead of 22 for training and prediction. On tabulating the per-class accuracy against imbalance ratio for these new set of labels the least per class accuracy for an imbalanced label (IR=4) was found to be 57% .

As the dataset is already small, synthetic data points were generated using Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE), which generates synthetic samples from the minority class instead of simply duplicating existing ones. This assures a better generality in prediction avoiding over fitting even if no significant improvement in overall accuracy is observed.

Results

The data used in the study was preconditioned by curtailing samples based on IR and by SMOTE. In effect, the mean per-class accuracy which was 84.39% in original dataset improved to 91.77% and the overall accuracy was also seen to improve 93.67% from 92.94%.

References

[1]<https://www.mdpi.com/2075-3X/9/9/537/s1>

[2] *A review of ensemble learning and data augmentation models for class imbalanced problems: Combination, implementation and evaluation*, Expert Systems with Applications, Volume 244, 15 June 2024.

INDUSTRIAL HYGIENE AND SAFETY PRACTICES IN RADIATION FACILITIES

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Keywords: Safety practices, Recognition, evaluation and control of hazards, work environment,

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Introduction

Industrial Hygiene and Safety practices are the integral part of occupational safety along with radiation safety in radiation facilities. The radiation facilities also encompass industrial operations such as handling industrial gas cylinders and hazardous chemicals, RF sealers, high voltage and high temperature equipment, working in a confined space or maintenance of equipment, and hot works, transport of exposure devices/shielding equipment, hazards related to non-ionizing radiation equipment etc. This paper discusses on the importance of various Industrial Hygiene and safety practices in ensuring safety in Radiation Facilities.

Materials and Methods

The work environment in radiation facilities is mixed blend of industrial and radiation hazards. Combination of Industrial and radiation hygiene practices together help radiation facilities in control of exposures to workers. The principles of industrial hygiene and safety are recognition, evaluation and control of occupational hazards applied in all the radiation facilities are described below: Monitoring of work place for physical and chemical agents. Checking of effectiveness of Control measures in work environment through measurements for Noise, Illumination, Ventilation, heat stress, RF & MW as per standards. Industrial Hygiene and Safety elements in Regulatory Inspections Recommending Control Measures Individual control and Management Control. Employee training and awareness building Working in research and development laboratories of Radiation Facilities involves inherent hazards. The various laboratory equipment such as, autoclaves, furnace, ovens, Gas cylinders, handling hazardous chemicals Lasers and high voltage equipment's and cryogenic dewars, laboratory centrifuges including handling of radioactive materials attract stringent safety procedures. Also, the guidelines given in Indian

Standards IS 4209, IS 4906 and IS 12035 for safe practices in Chemical, Radio Chemical and Microbiological Laboratories respectively, are followed. A detailed Checklist and SOP/EOP, Log book documents are essential for working in any radiation facility. Process equipment normally handle hazardous substances under various operating conditions. Jobs/equipment need to be made safe from potential hazards before work can be started. These practices are most important and are ensured by the line managers. Specific Audits such as Fire & Electrical Safety audits are mandatory in all Facilities once a year to ensure healthiness of electrical connections/equipment as regulatory safety measures.

Results

Established procedures through Safe work Permits for the entry to Radiation areas with a consent of Health Physicist after verifying that the designated area is safe to commence work and all observable hazards with respect to mechanical, electrical, civil, and structural components are under control.

Conclusion

Recognition, evaluation and control of hazards applied to ensure occupational safety in Radiation Facilities has yielded good safety track record. Periodic monitoring of workplace as well personal monitoring are key aspects to occupational safety in all radiation facilities.

References

- Recognition of Health Hazards in Industry*, (William A BURGESS)
- Patty's Industrial Hygiene and Toxicology Voll* (1978)
- IS 4209 (2013) and IS 4906: (2017)

APPLICATION OF HAZARD OPERABILITY STUDY (HAZOP) IN RADIOLOGICAL OPERATION

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Keywords: Radiological operation, Hazard, HAZOP, Study node, Parameters, Guidewords

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Introduction

BARC has R&D activities in nuclear technologies and their applications to health, agriculture and environment. A Radiological operations involves the chemical process along with radioactive materials. It needs a special attention because it involves additional radiation hazards and spread of radioactivity apart from chemical hazards. For compliance of legal requirement, BARC adopted a comprehensive Safety Management Systems with the aim of protection of workers, public and the environment. An integral element of such systems i.e Hazard and Operability Analysis (HAZOP) used to identify potential hazards and operational problems in terms of plant design and human error. This paper focuses on the application of HAZOP technique in hazard identification on each step of the radiological process by using guidewords, parameters and suggested a suitable counter measures to prevent the hazards. This study reveals that the effectiveness of existing safeguard mechanism and necessary improvement in operating procedures for reduction of subsequent operability problems.

Materials and Methods

However HAZOP technique is more beneficial at the design stage but it can also be done during the major changes in the process or after major modifications in the system. For this study, a multi-disciplinary team with experts from various fields (production, maintenance, R&D etc.) works together to identify hazards by identifying the deviations from design intents. It helps to prevent possible minor or major occurrences from being overlooked. The main elements of HAZOP study are: intention, deviation, possible causes, consequences, existing safeguards, corrective action etc. The team studied the piping and instrumentation diagrams, operating procedures, process flow diagrams, process description, interlock description, past safety audit reports, safety manual of the plant,

material safety data sheets. A line-by-line examination of a design of the process or operation has been carried out. By applying guidewords like No, Less, More, Reverse, Part of, As Well As, Other than etc at specific nodes in the plant design they identified the potential deviations of the plant process parameters like Level, Flow, Temperature, Pressure etc at those nodes. Realistic and significant possible causes of those deviations and their consequences have been identified and recorded for corrective action.

Results

HAZOP study observed that there was possibility of reverse sequence of addition of reactants which can lead to sudden surge in reaction rate leading to hazardous scenario, absence of flow level indication with alarm, absence of pressure indication, possibility of spread of contamination, release of air activity, revision of standard operating procedures and emergency operating procedure etc.

Conclusion

HAZOP study produces a number of theoretical deviations, possible causes and consequences. All recommended corrective actions were incorporated by plant management to improve its safety before getting approval from regulatory body.

Acknowledgement

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References

Frank Crawley, Brian Tyler (2015) HAZOP: Guide to best practices for chemical and process industries, third edition, Elsevier, Netherlands

PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS ON COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY IMAGING FOR ENHANCED DISEASE DETECTION AND DIAGNOSIS.

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Key words: Computer Tomography (CT), Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Random Forests, Support Vector Machine (SVM)

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Introduction

Computed Tomography imaging is an important tool for diagnosing diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular conditions, and neurological disorders. Due to its highdimensional nature, however, it's hard to interpret manually, and difficult to integrate into machine learning, which really limits the efficiency and accuracy of diagnosis. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a statistical technique that reduces the dimensionality of data while retaining its most relevant features. PCA can simplify CT data and hence improve the diagnosis of disease and enhance the performance of ML models.

Materials and Methods

The data from the CT images are pre-processing including normalization, Gaussian smoothing, and optional segmentation to enhance image quality and isolate regions of interest. PCA reduced the dimensionality of the data. Features that were optimized through PCA reduction were used to train machine learning classifiers, such as SVM, Random Forests, and K-Nearest Neighbors.

Results and Discussion

Applying PCA actually reduced the dimensionality of the CT imaging data, but retained all the essential features for diagnosis while discarding the irrelevant information. Such simplification enabled machine learning models to process the data with greater efficiency and improved disease classification outcomes, such as lung cancer and liver tumors. This generalizable framework showed the versatility across a broad array of CT modalities, bringing out the potential of PCA to highlight subtle patterns that could help diagnose diseases.

Conclusion

PCA was thus employed to reduce the dimension of CT imaging data while maintaining a diagnostic feature and eliminating uncorrelated information. This simplified format made it easier for machine learning models to process and enhance the classification of diseases including lung cancer and liver tumor. The framework thus depicted its versatility, having efficiency in various CT modalities with PCA's ability to allow subtle patterns to emphasize patterns critical for disease detection. The study streamlined diagnosis by reducing the complexity and time required for diagnosis through automation of these analyses through an integrated software tool.

Reference:

Li, R.,et al "Automated Classification of Lung Cancer Subtypes Using Deep Learning and CT-ScanBasedRadiomicAnalysis." *Bioengineering*, vol. 10, no. ,2023,doi:10.3390/bioengineering1006 0690.

Liu, Z., Zhang, Y., & Liu, X. "A Novel Principal Component Analysis Approach for Dimensionality Reduction and Classification in CT Imaging." *Journal of Imaging*, vol. 7, no. 8,2021,doi:10.3390/jimaging708010.

OPTIMIZATION OF DETECTORS FOR GROSS BETA ACTIVITY ESTIMATION

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Introduction

Gross beta activity measurements are quantitative analysis for determining the gross beta activity radionuclides in a given sample. It is one of the preliminary screening method before gamma analysis. To analyse the samples efficiently and estimate the activity it is required to know the background of the system, efficiency and minimum detectable activity. This study focus on the parameters like Background, efficiency and MDA of three Gross beta counting system in the Nuclear counting facility at IGCAR.

Materials and Methods

Three different types of detectors were used for this study and it is described below.

Detector-1 Model LND 72314 End Window GM counter which was kept inside 4 inch thickness of lead shielding. The counter was provided with mica window thickness of $2\text{mg}/\text{cm}^2$

Detector-2 Model LB615 Beta counting system. This system uses thin plastic scintillation detector based main counter and another wide area plastic scintillator based guard counter. The entire assembly is provided with 80mm lead shield.

System-3 Model WPC 1050 is gas flow based detector using P10 has counting gas. It is pancake style gas flow proportional detector of 2.25 in. (5.7 cm) diameter. It is provided with Aluminized window of thickness $80\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$. It is provided with 4 inch thickness of lead shielding. Effective background reduction is achieved in plastic scintillator and Gas flow counter through anticoincidence technique.

Five sources namely C-14, Tc-99, Sr-90 Cl-36 from Eckert and Ziegler and K-40 standard source prepared in laboratory were used for determination of efficiencies of all the detectors.

The aluminium planchets were used for preparation of the sample. The standard sources were counted for 10 minutes in all the detectors and efficiency was determined.

Results

In GM Counter the efficiency varied between 3% to 14%. In plastic scintillator counting system the efficiency varied between 0.6% to 36%

and in gas flow detector the efficiency varied between 19% to 40%. All the detectors showed the lowest efficiency for C-14. Similarly the MDA was calculated for all the detectors for different energy which is listed. All the detectors had highest MDA for C-14. In order to have confidence in the analyses of the samples validate the efficiency, a sample-1 from IAEA 2024 inter comparison was plancheted and the gross beta activity was estimated by using all the detectors.

Conclusion

Even though variations were observed in the efficiency for different radionuclides in different systems. The activity estimation of IAEA sample-1 in all the three detectors was within 20% variation with the target values given IAEA 2024 proficiency test. Hence the depending upon the nature of the sample such as potentially active, intermediate active, high active samples we can choose the detectors and do the radioactivity analysis. The lowest background, MDA and good efficiency was achieved using anticoincidence background reduction method. Gas flow counter and plastic scintillator based detectors gave good efficiency and MDA.

References

Marija M. Janković*, Nataša B. Sarap, Gordana K. Pantelić, Dragana J. Todorović, *Open Chem.*, 2015; 13: 668–674 Comparison of two different methods for gross alpha and beta activity determination in water samples.

Phan Long Ho^{1,2,4}, Le Dinh Hung⁴, VuTuan Minh⁴, DangVanChinh⁴, TranThienThanh ^{1,2,3*} & ChauVanTao^{1,2,3} Simultaneous Determination of Gross Alpha/Beta Activities in Groundwater for Ingestion Effective Dose and its Associated Public Health Risk Prevention.

Hindawi Journal of Chemistry Volume 2020, Article ID 1741430, 4 pages Screening Level of Gross Alpha and Beta Activities in Building Materials

DISTRIBUTION OF NATURAL RADIOACTIVE ELEMENTS IN SOIL AND BUILDING MATERIAL SAMPLES OF CHAMARAJANAGAR DISTRICT, INDIA AND ASSOCIATED RADIATION DOSE TO THE POPULATION

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Introduction

Every living being is exposed to radiation originating from naturally occurring radionuclide, atmospheric radiation, and also from medical treatments. 87% of the radiation dose received by the population is from natural sources (UNSCEAR, 1993). The terrestrial component of the natural background is dependent on the composition of the soils and rocks in which the natural radionuclides are contained. Ground water is in direct contact with the soil and rocks that dissolves many compounds, minerals including uranium and its daughter products and pose inhalation and ingestion dose when used in household activities. Radionuclides in soil and building material contribute significant background radiation exposure to population. If a building is constructed with a material having higher concentration of natural radionuclide, then its indoor radiation dose rate will also be higher, which is the main reason for human lung and stomach cancer (Lubin and Boice Jr, 1997).

Materials and Methods

The activity concentration of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K in soil samples were analyzed using p-type coaxial Hyper Pure Germanium (HPGe) detector, ²²²Rn exhalation rate was measured using Smart Radon Monitor (SRM).

Results

²²⁶Ra concentration varied from 22.0 Bq kg⁻¹ to 61.1 Bq kg⁻¹. ²³²Th concentration ranges from 15.6 to 47.5 Bq kg⁻¹ and ⁴⁰K concentration ranges from 18.1 Bq kg⁻¹ to 456.0 Bq kg⁻¹. The radon exhalation rate from the soil sample of the study area varied from 2.52 to 13.91 mBq kg⁻¹ h. The ²²²Rn exhalation rate from the construction material varied from 4.65 to 18.34 mBq kg⁻¹ h⁻¹.

Activity concentration of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K in soil samples were used to estimate ²²⁶Ra equivalent activity, internal hazard index, external hazard index and gamma activity concentration index, which lie well below the recommended limit by UNSCEAR 2000 (UNSCEAR, 2000).

References

- UNSCEAR. (1993). Sources and effects of ionizing radiation: United Nations Publications, Scientific Annexes 49
- Lubin, J. H., Boice Jr, J. D., (1997) Lung cancer risk from residential radon: meta-analysis of eight epidemiologic studies. Jour. National Cancer Institute 89(1), 49-57.
- UNSCEAR. (2000). Sources and effects of ionizing radiation: sources. United Nations Publications, 1.

REGULATORY REQUIREMENT OF BOREHOLES FOR GROUND WATER SURVEILLANCE AROUND A RADIOLOGICAL FACILITY AND THEIR DESIGN BASIS

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Regulatory Requirement

The objective of radiation protection is not only to protect occupational worker but also to public and environment from immediate and long term effects. A radiological facility should implement approved radiological monitoring and surveillance program for the environment during pre-operational, operational and post operational period of it.

As per guidelines of Atomic Energy Regulatory Board (AERB), ground water contamination monitoring has to be carried out around any radiological/ waste disposal facility for ensuring environmental surveillance. Hence, Borehole water analysis is carried out from construction to decommissioning stage to evaluate the trend of ground water contamination and to ensure the integrity of the radiological facility during the operational phase. [1, 2]

Design Basis

The selection of Borehole locations are done by considering several factors such as ground water table, ground water flow rate and direction in that particular area. The hydrogeological investigations are carried out to determine above factors during pre-construction stage of the facility. Ground Water levels in the aquifer fluctuate in response to recharge due to precipitation and discharge towards the surface water bodies. The ground water level increases during monsoon and get depleted during summer. A minimum of three ground water sampling points (Bore-holes) are required to describe the plane of the theoretical “water table” and infer a direction of groundwater flow.^[3] The location of Bore-holes shall be in the flow path of contaminants released from the source in the area of interest.

Design Specifications

The depth of boreholes shall be sufficiently more to be operational during all seasons. There shall be at least 2 (two) grids of Bore-holes around the facility to identify the direction of the flow of contaminants, thereby identifying the source of contamination at the earliest. The Bore-holes are to be provided in the vicinity of the underground tanks and trenches (most probable sources) to monitor any breach of activity to the ground water. The bore-holes shall be drilled in the summer season, the borehole pipe shall have at least 500 mm above ground with lid to avoid entrainment of surface water. There shall be concrete walking passage from main road to Bore-hole locations for easy access for sampling.

Conclusion

All radiological facilities should implement the ground water monitoring and surveillance program during per-operational, operational and post operational stages by providing well designed bore-hole network around the facility.

Reference

1. Liquid and Solid Rad waste Management in Pressurised Heavy Water Reactor Based Nuclear Power Plants, 2002, AERB SAFETY GUIDE NO. AERB/SG/D-13 Near Surface Disposal of Radioactive Solid Waste, AERB SAFETY GUIDE NO. AERB/NRF/SG/RW-4 Groundwater Protection Guidelines for Nuclear Power Plants: Public Edition. EPRI, Palo Alto, CA: 2008. 1016099.

SURFACE CONTAMINATION CLEARANCE LEVELS FOR METAL WASTES WITH URANIUM CONTAMINATION

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Keywords: Uranium, Clearance, Surface Contamination, Metal Wastes.

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Introduction

For clearance of alpha contaminated metal scrap, clearance levels in terms of surface contamination is necessary. As per IAEA GSR part-3 (2014), for general clearance of material, effective dose due to the cleared material to an individual should be of the order of 10 $\mu\text{Sv/a}$ or less in reasonably foreseeable circumstances and less than 1 mSv/a in any low probability scenarios. The document does not mention clearance levels for surface contamination.

IAEA GSG-18 (2023) document specifies that surface contamination value of 0.4 Bq/cm^2 for low toxicity alpha emitters and 0.04 Bq/cm^2 for all other alpha emitters averaged over an area of 300 cm^2 is “frequently misused as clearance levels” and “are not applicable for clearance”. These values were derived in 1960s for limiting contamination on transport packages using Fairburn model for Pu-239. Limits were derived based on the dose coefficients available at that time using annual dose limit of 50 mSv/a . Clearance level of 1 Bq/cm^2 is recommended for ^{234}U , ^{235}U and ^{238}U by European Commission and UK.

Materials and Methods

Dose due to transport, processing and reuse of 1 tonne (1000 kg) of metal scrap contaminated with 1 Bq/cm^2 surface contamination is calculated for ^{234}U , ^{235}U and ^{238}U using method described in RP 101 by European Commission (1999) as suggested by IAEA GSG-18 (2023). Automated as well as manual scrap processing is considered. In manual processing segmenting using thermal segmenting, saw and manual grinder is considered. Dose due to inhalation, external gamma dose, beta skin dose and inadvertent ingestion is calculated as applicable for each step. Lower room size and lower air exchange rate is used compared to RP 101. Thickness of the metal scrap is assumed as

0.5 cm. Clearance level is set using the most restrictive scenario.

Results

Negligible beta skin dose and negligible external gamma dose is received by individuals during scrap processing or during reuse. Manual scrap processing results in higher dose rate compared to automatic scrap processing. Release rate per cut length is higher for manual grinders compared to saws or thermal segmenting, Inhalation dose received during manual processing of the scrap wastes using manual grinders is the most restrictive out of all the scenarios considered. Assuming 0.04 Bq/cm^2 surface contamination, dose received during manual processing of 1 tonne of metal scrap metal using manual grinders is $\sim 10 \mu\text{Sv}$ for ^{234}U , ^{235}U and ^{238}U . Using this method, averaging area of several hundred cm^2 to 1 m^2 averaging area is acceptable depending on contamination levels and homogeneity.

Conclusion

1 Bq/cm^2 surface contamination limit set in RP 101 is based on dose received during manual processing thermal segmenting as it is assumed that only small portion of the scrap is processed using manual grinders. If it is assumed that entire 1-ton scrap is segmented using manual grinders, then using 0.04 Bq/cm^2 is acceptable. Averaging area may be increased from 300 cm^2 to 1 m^2 based on the homogeneity of the contamination in the waste.

References

- IAEA, *GSG-18 - Application of Concept of Clearance*, 2023
- European Commission, *Radiation Protection 101 (RP 101)*, 1999.
- IAEA, *GSR Part 3*, 2014.

CONCEPTUAL DIVERGENCE AMONGST TLV & EFFECTIVE DOSE BASED PHILOSOPHIES FOR URANIUM

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Introduction

While dealing with protection of humans from adverse effects (deterministic) of inhalation exposure to hazardous chemicals, Threshold limit value (TLV) or Permissible exposure level (PEL) are recommended for non-radioactive as well as radioactive compounds and are based upon the threshold dose response models. Further, for radioactive substances, dose limits based upon linear non-threshold (LNT) as well as threshold dose response models are also recommended by International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP). However, for chemicals which are both radioactive & chemically toxic, the question whether adherence to one of the limit would result compliance of the other, always prevails [1].

In this paper, conceptual difference & adequacy of TLV resulting towards effective dose limit, E for Uranium (U) is explored as various agencies have recommended different limits/values. The study was necessary as chemical toxicity of U as a heavy metal has been generally of greater concern for human health than its radiological toxicity and anomaly between radiological and chemical limits for U via inhalation route have been a topic of discussion in literature [1-2].

Materials and Methods

TLV is generally 8 hour time weighted average air concentration to which a worker can be exposed safely day by day to the entire working lifetime without any adverse health effects whereas ICRPs yearly i) The limit on effective dose, E i.e. 20 or 50 mSv is intended to minimize the probability of occurrence of stochastic effects & ii) Equivalent dose limits (20 or 50 mSv for eye lens & 500 mSv each for extremities, skin) are to rule out the occurrence of any deterministic effects i.e. tissue reactions.

OSHA has adopted 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ & 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ as PEL (inhalation) for soluble & non-soluble U compounds whereas ACGIH has recommended TLV of 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for all U compounds. Another agency NIOSH has also suggested REL of 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ & 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for soluble & non-soluble U compounds with 10 mg/m³ as IDLH irrespective of solubility. Further, NRC, USA has recommended that in addition to the annual dose limits, E; the soluble U intake should be limited to 10 mg/week to avoid renal damage [3].

Results

Considering air borne specific activity, dose conversion factor (DCFs) for soluble (fast phase) & insoluble compounds (slow phase) of U, 2000 hours as working time/year & breathing rate: i) PEL of 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ & 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ corresponds to effective doses of E of 0.95 mSv & 230 mSv ii) TLV of 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ leads to E of 3.81mSv (soluble-U) & 184 mSv (non-soluble, U).

Conclusion

For soluble natural U compounds, the TLV may be adequate but for non-soluble compounds, ICRP's limits based on radiotoxicity may be preferred indicating that situations may prevail where compliance to TLV or E alone is not sufficient.

References

Stradlin N. et al. (2003) Radiat. Prot. Dosim. 105 (1–4), 175–178. IAEA Safety Series No. 100(2020) 1-217. <https://www.nrc.gov/docs/ML1122/ML11227A239.pdf>

AN APPROACH TOWARDS ABSOLUTE MEASURE OF PRUDENCE IN RADIATION SAFETY PHILOSOPHY USING SURPRISE THEORY FRAMEWORK

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Introduction

Prudence is a cornerstone philosophy in radiation protection. It means making informed and cautious decisions, even when there is uncertainty about the potential risks of radiation exposure. In the realm of information theory, the "surprise function" is a concept related to the amount of information conveyed by an event. Essentially, it measures how unexpected or surprising an event is. It is important here to note that the concept of prudence and surprise are intimately related and display complementary values. As the prudence, in the broad sense of the term refers to the prior computational and non-computational features towards an endeavour, which is radiation safety in our case; the surprise mostly refers to their posterior counterparts in reference to these priori features or dissimilarity between these two.

Current paradigms in vogue provide the degree of prudence a finite value as factor of conservatism typically in the range of 1 to 30, (Roger, 2016) which in our opinion are unable to strike the optimality or trade-off between the extremes of ultra-conservatism paradigm and its opposite in radiation safety i.e. most in-conservative ones. Considering the importance of prudence concept in the radiation safety endeavours, along with the stress given to conservative paradigms viz. Linear No Threshold (LNT) hypothesis, it is necessary to develop a formulation for prudence which is open-ended i.e. post-quantification the degree of prudence may be assigned any value between 0(zero) and ∞ (infinite).

Methodology

In proposed approach the surprise theory in the probabilistic framework has to be employed in order to serve this purpose. As the surprise (S) may be quantified by the formulation in the term of the probabilities, typically in the form of logarithm of inverse of probability (p) to the base two as in equation 1. This quantification yields the value of 0

and ∞ corresponding to probabilities of 1 and 0 respectively.

$$S = \log_2 \left(\frac{1}{p} \right) \dots (1)$$

A comprehensive mathematical treatment mapping the computed degree of prudence (from theoretical models as well as empirical observations) to quantified magnitude of surprise and open-ended measure of prudence has been undertaken in this approach. The above developed framework of 'Surprise' may be extended for other cases also for example the safety analysis of radiological plants. The comparison of prior (expected) and posterior (observed) values/features of relevant critical parameters may be used as input for quantification of surprise and treating it as an independent random variable, the control boundaries may be set accordingly.

Results & Conclusion

To demonstrate the proposed framework, two scenarios were analysed: a radioactive release event and an elevated air activity event. Both scenarios exhibited a factor of safety deviation of 2. However, a significant difference in the calculated surprise values was observed, with the air activity event yielding a surprise value approximately 5 times lesser than the radioactive release event. This discrepancy highlights the potential for the proposed framework to differentiate between events with similar safety margins but varying levels of unexpectedness or surprise.

References

- ICRP, 2018. Ethical foundations of the system of radiological protection. ICRP Publication 138. Ann. ICRP 47(1).
- Roger Coates, Radiation Protection Dosimetry (2017), Vol. 173, No. 1-3, pp. 100–103
- Baldi, Pierre. (2002). A Computational Theory of Surprise. 10.1007/978-1-4757-3585-7
- Maguire, Phil & Maguire, Rebecca. (2009). Investigating the Difference between Surprise and Probability Judgments. (Conference Paper)

RADIOLOGICAL EMERGENCY PREPAREDNESS FOR PREVENTION OF MALICIOUS ACTS DURING MAJOR PUBLIC EVENTS

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Introduction

The International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA,2012) emphasizes the critical importance of preventive measures to be taken up and comprehensive emergency response plans to effectively manage radiological hazards during any large-scale events. For a Major Public event such as international summits, there is a need for specialized radiological emergency preparedness for response measures. These efforts rely on highly sensitive radiation monitoring systems designed to detect orphan radiation sources, abnormal radiation levels or other malicious radiological activities. This report outlines the preparedness and response measures adopted for any Major Public Event, with a focus on detection and prevention of radiological threats.

During Pre-Event Preparedness

For a proposed Major Public Event (MPE), extensive preparatory work is required to ensure a robust preparedness and response for potential radiological emergencies, if any. These measures include the following: 1. Training to Event security, Security and Emergency Staff; 2. Developing Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs); 3. Conducting mock exercises and simulations

During the Event

During the MPE, extensive radiation monitoring systems need to be deployed for detection and mitigate potential radiological threats with proper protocols for operation and SOP at all entry points (personnel, cargo etc.) with trained security staff.

Radiation Monitoring Instruments

The important radiation monitoring instruments deployed to ensure continuous surveillance and prompt response to radiological threats. The systems include: Mobile Monitoring Lab, Area Gamma Monitors (AGMs) at entry exit locations, Portable Survey Meters, Portable Radiation Scanners, Personal Radiation Detectors, Compact Radiation Monitoring System, Emergency Response Kits and Global Positioning System (GPS). The functional

requirements for emergency preparedness and response includes communication and coordination with District authority, RERCs and other stack holders.

Methodology

The preparedness strategy for handling the radiological emergency for the MPE should be designed to provide continuous and comprehensive surveillance of key locations throughout the event. The following methodology needs to be employed to ensure a graded effective approach for preparedness and response to potential radiological emergency. Continuous Radiation Surveillance, Regular Radiation Checks, Systematic implementation of SOPs, Incident Response Protocols.

Conclusion

The radiological emergency preparedness and response measures for the Major Public Event (MPE) should be comprehensive and well-structured, ensuring the safety of attendees and staff against any potential radiological threats. By using sensitive monitoring systems, conducting pre-event training, and establishing clear protocols for emergency response, the event organizers should be demonstrated detection and preparedness for response against radiological threats. The deployment of radiation detection instruments and the prompt coordination is key for response to potential threats. These preparedness for detection and mitigation of the impact of radiological emergencies during Major public events will ensure that the event is carried out smoothly.

References

Nuclear security systems and measures for major public event, iaea nuclear security series no. 18 (2012)

HAZARD CATEGORIZATION FOR A BERYLLIUM HANDLING FACILITY

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Introduction

Hazard classification (HC) is crucial for safeguarding public health and the environment, ensuring regulatory compliance, and effectively managing risks. By identifying and assessing potential hazards, implementing appropriate safety measures, and developing robust emergency response plans, these facilities can prevent accidents, minimize consequences, and protect workers and the public from radiation and chemical exposure.

Materials and Methods

HC involves systematic identification of potential hazards or accident (fire, explosions, and material releases due to mechanical impacts, etc.) followed by quantification of the exposure or risk. Exposure is then compared with Emergency Response Planning guidelines (ERPGs)/Temporary Emergency Exposure Levels (TEELs) for necessary regulatory clearances and emergency preparedness. ERPG/TEEL levels categorize airborne concentrations based on potential health effects, ranging from mild, transient effects to life-threatening consequences and are function of form of beryllium (Be) being handled. The exposure is estimated based on the source term (ST); strongly dependent on the accident and is given by,

$$ST = MAR * DR * ARF * RF * LPF$$

where, MAR is material at risk, DR is damage ratio, ARF is air-borne release fraction, RF is respirable fraction and LPF is leak path factor. The source term then disperses as per the prevailing meteorological conditions. The corresponding beryllium concentration is;

$$C \text{ (mg/m}^3\text{)} = (\chi/Q) ST (1/T)$$

where, C is the beryllium concentration at a given downwind distance in mg/m³, χ/Q is the dilution factor in s/m³ and T is the release duration in seconds.

Results

In order to demonstrate the application of methodology, 100g (MAR) beryllium is exposed under different accidental conditions. DR=LPF=RF=1 are used as a conservative estimate. ARF=1.0E-06 in case of crushimpact, ARF=3.1E-03 for explosive release and ARF=0.4 (Laul and Rich, 2008; Jofu *et al*, 2008) in case of

fire involving ignition of Be. Assuming ground level releases, stability category 'F' with a wind speed of 1.0m/s is used as a conservative input and T=900s is considered. χ/Q at a downwind distance of 100m is estimated to be 3.06E-02 s/m³. Using the above inputs, the source term due to crushimpact, explosive release and fire involving ignition of Be is estimated to be 1.0E-04g, 3.1E-01g and 4.0E+01 g respectively and the corresponding Be concentration at 100m is 3.4E-06 mg/m³, 1.05E-02 mg/m³ and 1.36 mg/m³ respectively. The results can be scaled wrt the ST and χ/Q as per the facility design. During explosive release and ignition, Be will be oxidized to form BeO, which has a higher threshold value as compared to Be metal. Thus ERPGs/TEELs values for Be are used accordingly.

Conclusion

The beryllium concentration exceeds ERPGs/TEEL-2 (Ref value=1.25 for BeO) in the case of ignition of Be due to fire. It should be noted that the design must ensure that ERPGs/TEEL-3 (Ref value=10 in BeO form and 0.1 in Be metal form) is not exceeded to ensure safety of workers and public.

References

- Laul J C, Norman Rich (2008) *Journal of Chemical Health and Safety* 15(4), 13-25
- Mishima Jofu, Foppe L. T., Laul J.C. (2008) *Journal of Chemical Health and Safety* 15(4), 26-45

A CRITIQUE ON CRITERIA FOR NOTIFYING NUCLEAR INCIDENT UNDER CIVIL LIABILITY FOR NUCLEAR DAMAGE ACT, 2010

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Introduction

Government of India enacted the Civil Liability for Nuclear Damage (CLND) Act in 2010. Under the Act, for a claimant to submit claims for nuclear damage, the nuclear incident is to be first notified by AERB after satisfying the gravity of threat and risk involved. For this, the CLND Rules, 2011 required the criteria for reporting of events to be specified by AERB.

Accordingly, the requirement of reporting of 'extraordinary nuclear events' was notified by AERB in September 2013 in official gazette. The extraordinary nuclear event reported to AERB will then be reviewed to ascertain if it qualifies for being notified as 'nuclear incident'. For this purpose, AERB issued a safety directive in December 2013 on "Criteria and Assessment Procedures for Notification of Nuclear Incident under the CLND Act, 2010"

Materials and Methods

To understand the rationale behind the criteria specified by AERB, a study was undertaken of the underlying principles of liability conventions, CLND Act and Rules, the legislative debates, USNRC's criteria for Extraordinary Nuclear Occurrence, AERB's internal deliberations and records and submissions made to judicial authorities.

Results

An event which leads to release of radiologically equivalent I-131 corresponding to a quantity of radioactivity 500 times or more of the annual release limit prescribed in technical specifications for operation of the plant is to be reported to AERB as extraordinary nuclear event. This is based on the rationale that release more than 500 times technical specification limit of I-131 may lead to a dose of 1mSv at plant boundary. 1 mSv is

the AERB prescribed dose limit for public. However, based on review within AERB, if it is found that any single event would result in stack release of radiologically equivalent I-131 of 1000 TBq or more, than that event will be notified by AERB as 'nuclear incident'. This is based on the consideration that a stack release of 1000 TBq of I-131 can lead to a whole body dose of 100 mSv, a level at which detectable increase in chromosomal aberrations is expected. Similarly, other criteria for notifying a nuclear incident are also based on 100mSv dose criteria, in addition to those circumstances where actual radiation related injury or death has occurred or when evacuation is necessitated or when alpha contamination offsite is comparable to derived surface contamination levels at workplace.

Conclusion

The criteria specified by AERB in 2013 were based on the prevalent radiation protection concepts and emergency response actions. In view of evolved emergency preparedness and response framework, emergent technologies, these criteria may need to be revisited and revalidated,

References

AERB deliberations on development of reporting and notifying criteria (2011 -2013)

SEASONAL VARIATIONS OF URANIUM CONCENTRATION IN WATER PRODUCED AROUND CHIKKABALLAPURA DISTRICT, KARNATAKA, INDIA

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Introduction

Uranium is a radioactive element which is having importance regarding health concern owing to its radio and chemo toxic nature in the human body, because of their daughter products can be concentrated and accumulated in tubing and surface equipment in the form of scale and sludge as a consequence of physical and chemical processes associated with the oil and gas industry (Virk, 2016). Enhanced levels of uranium, thorium and their daughter products might be present in producing water. The major radionuclides found were ^{226}Ra , ^{228}Ra , ^{224}Ra and ^{210}Pb , in concentration of up to a few hundred Becquerels per litre (Misdaq and Elharti, 1997). Uranium occurs naturally in groundwater and surface water and also the changes in its concentration in seasons is also significant. In the present investigation, the concentration of uranium in water samples of Chikkaballapura district were measured.

Materials and Methods

Water samples were collected from different sources such as Borewells, Pond, open well and hand pump in different location of Chikkaballapura district. About 32 samples were collected and filled in 200 ml airtight plastic bottles. All the Samples were then brought to the laboratory and filtered using whatman filter paper (CAT No 1001 -110). Filtered water samples were collected in conical flask and each sample is poured in 10% of buffer solution (sodium pyrophosphate and orthophosphoric acid) to have a uniformity in yield for all complexes of Uranium. About 6 ml of mixture was then rigorously filled in quartz cuvette and kept in LED fluorimeter for further analysis.

Results

The measured Uranium concentrations were found to be in the range 0.03 ± 0.002 ppb to 1606 ± 4 ppb in monsoon with an average value of 115.4 ppb and 0.18 ± 0.01 ppb to 614 ± 3 ppb with a mean value of 132.54 ppb

in winter. Borewells of Machahalli, Dibburhalli, Inaminchenahalli, Pathpalya, Thimmampalli were attributed with significant values of concentrations with the values 1606 ± 4 ppb, 251 ± 1 ppb, 588 ± 2 ppb, 235 ± 1 ppb, 604 ± 1 ppb in monsoon and 1614 ± 3 ppb, 631 ± 3 ppb, 505 ± 3 ppb, 305 ± 2 ppb and 129 ± 1 ppb in winter season respectively. The variation may be due to the geological variation and type of rocks present in the location. The calculated annual effective dose below the threshold values.

Conclusion

Uranium concentrations in different regions of Chikkaballapura were determined and the average values of samples were found to exceeded the world limit 60 ppb by AERB and 30 ppb by EPA, USA. The changes in the Uranium concentrations were observed in two different seasons.

References

- H. S. Virk.(2016), *Environmental Science and Disaster Management*, ISSN:0975-587X
- Misdaq M A, Elharti A (1997), *J Radioanal Nucl Chem* 218(2):219–222
- S. A. Panditetal (2021).*Current science*, Vol 121, 11

MEASUREMENT OF INDOOR RADON CONCENTRATION IN THE ENVIRONMENT OF CHIKKABALLAPURA DISTRICT, KARNATAKA, INDIA

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Introduction

Radon (^{222}Rn) is a naturally occurring radioactive isotope of ^{238}U series, which is colorless and odorless gas with half-life of 3.82 days. Among many natural radiation sources, radon is one of the significant sources because of its potential exposure to the human beings. Radon gas and its daughter products can easily enter the human lungs through the inhalation. The daughter products of the radon (^{218}Po , ^{214}Pb , ^{214}Bi and ^{214}Po) which deposit in the lungs can result in biological damage to the lungs through the emission of alpha and beta particles, with carcinogenic potential. The main source of environmental radon is primordial radionuclides present in building materials, soils and rocks. The radon exhalation rate hence mainly depends on the presence of radium content in the material (Tufai et al., 2000). In the present study, the indoor Radon concentration in the environment of Chikkaballapura was measured.

Materials and Methods

Indoor radon concentration has been measured in different regions of Chikkaballapura district. About 38 locations were selected and in each location pinhole dosimeter with cellulose nitrate film are deployed in the indoor environment of schools. Dosimeters were installed above 2 meters from the floor and with a gap of 1.5 feet away from the wall. Films were kept for the period of 90 days and etched using 2.5 NaOH solution as keeping in constant temperature bath maintaining temperature of $60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. After etching films were washed with distilled water and kept for drying. Then the track densities of the films were noted by placing films inside the spark counter with the help of mylar film. By knowing the values of track density radon concentration is calculated

(DeepShikha et al 2023).

Results

Indoor radon concentration in the region were varied from 6.19 ± 1.90 to 600.42 ± 18.73 Bqm-3 and indoor thoron concentration were in the domain 0.56 ± 0.14 to 714.46 ± 18.33 Bqm-3 with the mean value of 139.08 Bqm-3. Maximum values of radon concentrations were observed in Thondebavi, Allipura, Hosur, Gudibande town, Chikkaballapura town Chikkakurugodu regions with the values 600.175 ± 18.73 Bqm-3, 330.3 ± 13.83 Bqm-3, 278.73 ± 12.76 Bqm-3, 257.75 ± 12.27 Bqm-3, 210.19 ± 1.08 Bqm-3, 170.41 ± 9.98 Bqm-3 respectively. The maximum activity may be due to the low ventilation and construction materials used in the buildings.

Conclusion

Radon and Thoron concentrations in the indoor environment of Chikkaballapura district were identified. Average radon and thoron concentrations crossed WHO limit 100 Bqm-3. Some samples were crossed the ICRP limit $200-300$ Bqm-3 which poses serious health concerns in the particular area of study.

References

- DeepShikha et al., (2023), *Indian Journal of Pure and Applied Physics*, 509-514
LungiDeMaria et al (2023), *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, 20, 4685
M. Tufai, et al., (2000), *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity* 50, 267-275.

STUDY OF GAMMA BACKGROUND FLUCTUATIONS AND ITS ASSOCIATED UNCERTAINTY IN NORM ACTIVITY ESTIMATION USING A SHIELDED HPGE DETECTOR

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Introduction

Environmental radioactivity measurements deal with very low activity levels making it challenging specially under high background conditions. This problem is more prominent for gamma spectrometric measurements of naturally occurring radioactive material (NORM). Extensive studies have been done previously to achieve reasonable minimum detectable activity values (MDA) and precision in the reported activity values. (Rameback et al, 2018), (Naskar et al, 2017). In the present study, the gamma background fluctuations of a shielded 30% HPGe detector is studied and its role in uncertainty of NORM estimations.

Materials and Methods

Measurements were done with HPGe detector (30%, ORTEC make) interfaced with the DSPEC LF (Ortec make) spectroscopy module with 16K MCA. The detector is provided with 10cm lead shielding. The background spectrum was acquired for three different counting time periods-5000, 10000 and 20000 s. For each of the time periods, 10 measurements were done to observe the fluctuations. Three regions of interest (ROI's), corresponding to 40K, 214 Bi and 208Tl peaks at 1460 keV, 1764 keV and 2614 keV respectively, were taken into consideration. The uncertainty in observed background counts were compared to the Poisson statistics. Soil samples were analyzed for 40K, 238U and 232Th using the above mentioned gamma peaks. The activities and the associated overall uncertainty inclusive of uncertainties in net count rate and efficiency were estimated for different counting periods and compared.

Results

The background count rate of the system was found to be 0.034, 0.003 and 0.014 cps at

1460 keV, 1764 keV and 2614 keV ROI's respectively. The background fluctuations of 1460 keV ROI was found to deviate from the poisson predicted value by +30%. The uncertainty in background count rate for the 1460 keV ROI reduced by 34% and 55% when counting period was increased to 10000 s and 20000 s respectively. Considering a soil sample with 40K activity-130 Bq, 238U activity-12 Bq and 232Th activity-75 Bq, the overall relative uncertainty (1σ) in activity estimation for 5000 sec counting time, was 8.3%, 28.9% and 7.7% for 40K, 238U and 232Th respectively. For the same soil sample, the overall relative uncertainty for 20000 sec counting time was 3.9%, 11.9% and 6.4% for 40K, 238U and 232Th respectively

Conclusion

The uncertainty in background measurements of the HPGe based gamma spectrometer was studied for different counting periods and the uncertainties in activity estimation were also compared.

References

- Ramebäck, H., & Lindgren, P. (2018). Uncertainty evaluation in gamma spectrometric measurements: Uncertainty propagation versus Monte Carlo simulation. *Applied Radiation and Isotopes*, 142, 71-76.
- Naskar, N., Lahiri, S., Chaudhuri, P., & Srivastava, A. (2017). Measurement of naturally occurring radioactive material, 238 U and 232 Th: part 2—optimization of counting time. *Journal of Radioanalytical and Nuclear Chemistry*, 312, 161-171.

UTILIZING SCATTERED RADIATION: ACTIVATED CARBON-BASED SOLAR CELLS FOR ALTERNATIVE ENERGY

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Keywords: Coconut Shell, Activated Carbon, Scatter Radiation, Telecobalt Machine, and Renewable Energy.

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Introduction

Alternative energy sources that do not rely on fossil fuels or contribute to greenhouse gas emissions are crucial to combating climate change and mitigating the depletion of traditional energy resources. Scattered radiation, a byproduct of radiotherapy and diagnostic radiology, presents an innovative opportunity to create sustainable energy solutions. Traditionally viewed as a source of interference, scattered radiation can be repurposed as an energy source. This study introduces a novel solar cell design incorporating activated carbon derived from coconut shells, replacing the conventional cadmium telluride material. This approach leverages scattered radiation to produce renewable energy while addressing radiation management issues in medical practices.

Methods

The study focused on the development and characterization of coconut shell-based activated carbon as a core material in solar cells. The preparation process involved carbonizing coconut shells and activating the material to achieve a high surface area and enhanced conductivity. The material was evaluated for its absorption capacity, electrical conductivity, and stability under radiation exposure. A prototype solar cell was constructed, and its performance was tested in simulated radiology and radiotherapy environments to assess its ability to harvest scattered radiation. Integration feasibility with existing medical equipment was also analyzed to ensure seamless application in clinical settings.

Results

Characterization studies demonstrated that the activated carbon material derived from coconut shells possessed favorable properties for energy harvesting. The high surface area facilitated efficient absorption of scattered radiation, while its electrical conductivity enabled effective conversion into electrical energy. The prototype solar cell exhibited promising energy output levels in environments replicating scattered radiation conditions found in teletherapy and

diagnostic radiology. Moreover, the design of the solar cell allowed for easy integration into existing medical infrastructures, requiring minimal modifications. The findings suggest that scattered radiation, a previously untapped byproduct, can be effectively converted into renewable energy using this novel approach.

Conclusion

The activated carbon-based solar cell represents a significant advancement in the intersection of renewable energy and medical technology. By utilizing scattered radiation, this innovative approach addresses two critical challenges: managing medical radiation byproducts and producing sustainable energy. The solution is environmentally friendly, cost-effective, and scalable, with the potential to reduce healthcare facilities' carbon footprint and operational costs. Future work will focus on optimizing the solar cell design, exploring additional radiation environments, and scaling up production for widespread clinical adoption. This interdisciplinary innovation underscores the potential of alternative energy technologies to contribute to sustainable development while enhancing healthcare practices.

References

1. C. John Kirubakaran, K. Krishnaiah, and S. K. Seshadri "Experimental study of the production of activated carbon from coconut shells in a fluidized bed reactor" *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 1991, 30, 2411-2416.
2. M.K.B. Gratuito Panyathanmaporn R. Chumnanklang N. Sirinuntawittaya A. Dutta, Production of activated carbon from coconut shell: Optimization using response surface methodology, *Bioresource Technology* 99 (2008) 4887–4895
3. Technical reports series no. 188 "Radiological Safety Aspects of the operation of electron Linear Accelerators" International atomic energy agency, Vienna, 1979.

MEASUREMENT OF NATURAL RADIOACTIVITY AND EXTERNAL HAZARD INDEX IN SOIL AROUND GHAVP SITE, HARYANA

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(Eq. –1)

Introduction

Natural radioactivity in soils is due to presence of U, Th and their progeny and natural K. The study of the distribution of natural radionuclides allows to understand the radiological implication of these elements for the gamma-ray exposure and irradiation of lung tissue from inhalation of radon and its daughters. The objective of this paper is to evaluate the radiological hazards due to natural radioactivity associated with soil samples collected from construction GHAVP site in Haryana by calculating the absorbed dose rate, annual effective dose rate and external hazard index.

Materials and Methods

152 soil samples up to 30 km radial distance from GHAVP site were collected during 2021-2024 from an undisturbed open area of one square meter and processed as per standard procedure (Hegde et.al.1998). The container was sealed hermetically and externally using cellophane tape and kept aside for about a month to ensure equilibrium between Ra and its daughter products before being taken for gamma ray spectrometric analysis. The equilibrated samples were subjected to gamma spectrometry using HPGe spectrometric system (50% Relative Efficiency). These samples were counted for 18 hours and ⁴⁰K, ²²⁶Ra and ²³²Th were evaluated by using ⁴⁰K(1460 keV), ²¹⁴Bi(609 keV) and ²⁰⁸Tl (583 keV) gamma peaks respectively. The existence of ²³⁸U and ²³²Th in these samples can be verified by presence of ²¹⁴Bi (1764 keV) and ²⁰⁸Tl (2615 keV) peaks. The system was calibrated using uranium ore from UCIL Jadugoda, analar Grade KCl and other reference standards .

Dose rate calculation

The absorbed dose rate was calculated from the measured activities of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K in the soil samples using the formula given below .

$$D (\text{nGy}/\text{h}) = 0.462 C_U + 0.604 C_{Th} + 0.042 C_K$$

Where D is the absorbed dose rate (nGy/h). C_U, C_{Th} and C_K are the activity concentrations (Bq/kg) of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K respectively. To estimate the annual effective dose rates, the conversion coefficient from absorbed dose to effective dose, 0.7 Sv/Gy. The outdoor and indoor occupancy factor has taken as 0.2 and 0.8 respectively . The effective dose rate in units of mSv/y was calculated by the following formula

$$\text{Effective dose rate (mSv/y)} = D (\text{nGy/h}) \times 8760 \text{ h} \times 0.2 \times 0.7 \text{ Sv/Gy} \times 10^{-6} \quad (\text{Eq. -2})$$

Calculation of hazard indexes:

The external hazard index, Hex, is defined as

$$\text{Hex} = (C_U / 370 + C_{Th} / 259 + C_K / 4810) < 1 \quad (\text{Eq. -3})$$

Results

The measured mean activity concentrations ranged from 28.1 ± 0.98 to 37.8 ± 1.12 Bq.kg⁻¹ for ²³⁸U, 48.5 ± 1.6 to 62.5 ± 2.1 Bq.kg⁻¹ for ²³²Th and 428.2 ± 10.3 to 534.4 ± 14.8 Bq.kg⁻¹ ⁴⁰K. The absorbed dose rate is found to be varied from 61.6 to 75.4 nGy.h⁻¹. Natural concentration of U, Th and ⁴⁰K in soils is known to vary from place to place even in the same region. The calculated values of total annual effective out door dose rate ranging from 0.30 to 0.38 mSv with a mean of 0.34 mSv. The calculated value of external hazard index ranges from 0.26 to 0.58 with a mean of 0.40 which is much less than of one prescribed by UNSCEAR-2000.

Conclusion

Present study is based on pre-operational study of newly under construction site at GHAVP, Haryana. The base line data on radioactivity will be useful during the operational phase of site.

References

Hegde ,A.G et.al(1998),Environmental Radiological Laboratory Procedure Manual ,BARC, Mumbai, India, pp 1 - 86.

UNCEAR 2000. Sources, effects and risks of ionizing radiation, (New York, NY: United Nations)

ESTIMATION OF NATURAL RADIOACTIVITY IN BUILDING CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS AROUND KUDANKULAM, TAMIL NADU

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Introduction

Human beings are continuously exposed to ionizing radiation from naturally occurring radioactive materials (NORM). The origin of these materials is the earth's crust but they find their way into building materials, air, water, food and the human body itself. The building raw materials and products used for construction mostly originate from rock and soil containing natural radioactive isotopes mainly from ^{238}U , ^{232}Th series and ^{40}K (Senthilkumar et al, 2014). The aim of this work was to estimate the specific activity concentration of ^{238}U , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K in commonly used building materials sourced from Kudankulam, Tamil Nadu, India, using gamma-ray spectrometry.

Materials and Methods

30 samples comprising of six types of building materials (bricks, river sand, M sand, cement, tiles and granites) were collected. All the samples except sand were ground and powdered finely. Then the samples were dried in an air oven at 100°-110°C, and sieved through a 70 mesh-size sieve. Around 500 g of the homogenized sample was placed in an airtight container. The inner lid was placed in and closed tightly with outer cap. The container was sealed airtight, and kept aside for about a month to ensure equilibrium between ^{226}Ra and its daughter products. A high resolution low background HPGe detector was employed for the determination of primordial radio nuclides using pre calibrated geometry.

Results

The activity concentrations of ^{238}U , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K in bricks ranged from 13-20 with a mean value of 16 Bq.kg⁻¹, 63-128 with a mean value of 95 Bq.kg⁻¹ and 625-1100 with a mean value of 796 Bq.kg⁻¹ respectively, whereas in cement it ranged from 14-46 with a mean value of 28 Bq.kg⁻¹, 26-160 with a mean value of 56 Bq.kg⁻¹, 140-355 with a mean value of 227 Bq.kg⁻¹ respectively. The activity concentrations of ^{238}U , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K in the river sand and M sand ranged from 11-84, 26-984, 236-684 and 3-17, 17-207, 399-1078 Bq.kg⁻¹ with an overall average values of 25, 104, 445 and 6.5, 56, 655 respectively, whereas the activity concentrations of ^{238}U , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K in the tiles ranged from 31-44, 60-150, 442-815 Bq.kg⁻¹ with an overall

average values of 37, 93 and 579 respectively. The radioactivity content of ^{238}U , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K in Granite samples was 77.4, 224 and 1147 Bq.kg⁻¹ respectively. The overall average activity concentrations in Bq kg⁻¹ of ^{238}U , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K in building materials is 24, 123 and 650. The average worldwide activity concentrations of ^{238}U , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K in building materials are 40, 40 and 400 Bq.kg⁻¹ respectively (UNSCEAR 2000). The marginally higher values observed in some building materials are due to the presence of the monazite mineral along the coast. However, these values are comparable with the high background radiation areas in India as well as world.

Conclusion

The study estimated the natural radioactivity present in various building materials around Kudankulam site. Estimation of naturally occurring radionuclides in building materials is useful for determination of external dose to the members of public from exposure to natural radioactivity.

References

- Senthilkumar G, Raghu T et al. (2014) Natural radioactivity measurement and evaluation of radiological hazards in some commercial flooring materials used in Thiruvannamalai, Tamil Nadu, India. J Rad Res App Sci. ;7:116–122.
UNSCEAR; (2000) Sources and Risks of Ionizing Radiation, Report to the General Assembly with annexes, New York, United Nations.

RADIOLOGICAL SURVEILLANCE OF ENAYAM AND MIDALAM VILLAGES OF KANYAKUMARI, INDIA

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Introduction

Indian peninsular coast is known for rich deposit of heavy minerals including Ilmenite, Rutile, Garnet, Zircon, Sillimanite and Monazite. Monazite is a radioactive mineral containing Thorium (8-9%, 300 Bq g⁻¹) and Uranium (0.3%, 32 Bq g⁻¹). Decay of thorium and uranium results in emission of alpha, beta particles and a number of gamma photons. The regions rich in monazite deposits are often classified as Natural High Background Radiation Areas (NHBRA). Residents of these areas receive radiation doses significantly higher than other places. Enayamputhenthurai, Keezh Midalam and Midalam are three tiny adjoining villages along western coast of Tamil Nadu. The total area of this cluster of villages is approximately 5.5 sq. km within boundary coordinates of N08°11'19.78" to N08°13'33.12" and E77°11'53.12" to E77°14'08.82". This area is characterized by high monazite content in the soil and subsequent high gamma radiation levels. Grid based radiological monitoring of these three villages were carried out and results are discussed in this paper.

Materials and Methods

The study area was divided into 12 grids of 1 km x 1 km area. Major radiological parameters like ambient dose rate, concentration of ²³²Th and ²³⁸U in soil and external exposure to the residents are measured. For ambient radiation dose rate [Hp(10)], area of approximate area 10m x 10 m was selected and 8-10 readings were taken. A set of three measurements done for better accuracy and average is calculated.

The ambient dose rate at each grid location was measured using BARC make INERTS Surveymeter and RDS-31. Soil samples up to depth of 30 cm were collected using auger tool. It was subjected to preliminary cleaning and processing to remove organic matter, pebbles and stones. Gamma spectrometry was done to estimate ²³²Th and ²³⁸U content in it. For estimation of external dose [Hp(10)], Indoor and outdoor dose rate [Hp(10)] was measured at selected houses in

each grid. This data was used to estimate annual external dose received by the residents. Occupancy factor of 0.8 and 0.2 are considered for indoor and outdoor respectively.

Results

Radiological monitoring of Midalam, Enayamputhenthurai and Keezhmidalam villages were done. Ambient dose rate at these villages varied from 2.1 to 13.1 μSv h⁻¹. Higher dose rate was observed at Enayam and Kurupantai regions. ²³²Th and ²³⁸U content in the soil varied from 5.14 to 23.9 Bq g⁻¹ and 0.43 to 2.65 Bq g⁻¹ respectively. Good correlation between monazite content in the soil and ambient dose rate was observed. The external dose received [Hp(10)] by the residents of study area varied from 7.44 to 87.16 mSv y⁻¹. Most of the population receive external dose over 20 mSv y⁻¹

Conclusion

The Study locations are within Natural High Background Area of Manavalakurichi. The study confirms presence of high monazite content in the soil and associated high external dose rate. Further studies are in progress.

References

- (1) BARC/HSEG/PROTOCOL/TECHDC Standard protocol for conducting preoperational environmental surveillance around nuclear facilities (February 2010).

DIURNAL VARIATION OF ^{222}Rn AND ITS PROGENY LEVELS AROUND A URANIUM MINING AND MILLING SITE AT TURAMDIH, JHARKHAND

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Introduction

^{222}Rn gas is present in the air in outdoor and all dwellings, including workplaces due to its continuous emanation from the earth's crusts and building materials. The radon exhalation rate depends on soil and rock mineralogy, the distribution ^{226}Ra , temperature, porosity, etc. Additionally, in the vicinity of the uranium mining and milling area, radioactive radon gas continuously emanates into the surrounding environment from mine exhausts, ore, and waste piles, the crushing and grinding processes at the mill, and the mill tailings stored in the tailing pond. ^{222}Rn and its short-lived progeny account for over 50% of the total radiation exposure to humans from natural sources (UNSCEAR, 2000). Around the Turamdih site in Jharkhand, India, there are two underground uranium mines, one open-pit uranium mine, and one uranium processing plant. A brief study has been carried out to understand the background radon levels in the mining and milling sites.

Materials and Methods

Radon, equilibrium equivalent radon (EER), and equilibrium factor measurements were conducted day and night in seven villages (L1 to L7) around the Turamdih site. Alpha GUARD (Make: Bertin, Model: DF2000) and AlphaPM (Make: Bertin) were used for the measurement of ^{222}Rn and EER levels.

Results

The average ^{222}Rn concentrations ranged from 22 to 53 Bqm^{-3} during the day and 33 to 187 Bqm^{-3} at night with an overall mean of 31 ± 10 and 73 ± 51 Bqm^{-3} , respectively. The average EER varied from 8 to 30 Bqm^{-3} during the day and 16 to 140 Bqm^{-3} at night with an overall mean of 14 ± 8 and 47 ± 42 Bqm^{-3} , respectively. The highest ^{222}Rn concentrations, EER, and equilibrium factors were observed in Dhodanga village (L4). The location-specific variations in ^{222}Rn , EER, and equilibrium

factors may be attributed to local geological characteristics of soil, building materials, and ventilation conditions. For example, the higher radon levels in Dhodanga may be due to the presence of uranium-rich rocks in the area. The observed indoor radon levels are much lower than the reference levels recommended by different national and international organizations such as WHO (300 Bqm^{-3}), IAEA (300 Bqm^{-3}), and Swedish Board of Housing (200 Bqm^{-3}). The atmospheric radon levels are comparable to other uranium mining regions in Jharkhand (Jha et al., 2000).

The Equilibrium factor ranged from 0.35 to 0.56 during the day and 0.41 to 0.75 at night with an overall mean of 0.44 ± 0.09 and 0.60 ± 0.14 , respectively. The day-night average equilibrium factor was observed to be 0.52 which is slightly higher than the ICRP recommended equilibrium factor (0.4) which may be attributed to the differences in geology, climate, and radioactivity content in construction material and techniques.

The data indicated that radon, EER, and equilibrium factors are generally higher at night compared to the day, which is consistent with typical diurnal patterns of radon concentration. During the day, the radon is diluted by ventilation, but at night, the ventilation is reduced, allowing the radon to accumulate.

Conclusion

The indoor radon levels around the uranium mining and milling site are low and within the maximum reference levels recommended by international agencies.

References

- UNSCEAR (2000), Vol.1, United Nations, New York.
Jha et al., (2000), J. Environ. Radioact. 48:223-234.

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF COMPOSITE ALPHA-BETA CONTAMINATION MONITORING DEVICES

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Introduction

Radiological facilities handling alpha and beta-emitting radionuclides require reliable contamination monitoring systems to assess the contamination levels. The study presents a comparative analysis of two different contamination monitors each comprises of composite of thin plastic scintillator and ZnS (Ag) detectors. The focus is on evaluating their performance, accuracy, and reliability in detecting contamination levels. The comparison was also carried out by assessing their efficiencies with alpha and beta sources. The sources were placed at various positions on the detector surfaces and the deviations of the respective efficiency from central value was evaluated.

Materials and Methods

For simultaneous measurement of alpha and beta activity two commercially available systems i.e. NUVIA Instruments make CoMo-170 D (CM-1) and PLA Electro Appliances make PCRM 170 (CM-2) were considered. These systems have effective detector surface area of 170 cm² for monitoring of alpha as well as beta contamination. The detector surfaces were divided into a different matrices for measurement, and efficiency was evaluated at each matrix point. These efficiencies were compared for both detectors at each location, and the percentage deviation in efficiency at each matrix point from the central matrix was evaluated using Equation.

$$d(\%) = \frac{E - E'}{E} * 100 \dots (1)$$

Where, d stands for deviation, E and E' represent efficiencies at the central and peripheral locations of the detector surface, respectively (Mohanty et. al.). The Sources used for this experiment was ²³⁸Pu and ⁹⁰Sr-⁹⁰Y.

Results

The average detection efficiency of CM-1 & CM-2 was found to be 24.13 ± 0.28%, and 16.64 ± 0.46% respectively for alpha source.

Similarly, for beta particles, the efficiencies were found to be of 21.5±4.58% and 20.58 ± 4.36 % respectively. Furthermore, the study examined the variation in detection efficiency across the detector surface. The percentage deviation ($d\%$) was evaluated for both the monitors using equation (1). The maximum $d\%$ for alpha source was found to be 3.78% and 7.26% for CM-1 and CM-2. However, for the beta source, the CM-2 exhibited a more pronounced variation, with a maximum percentage deviation of 52.55%, while CM-1 showed a more consistent response, with a maximum deviation of 35.91% due to scattering of beta radiation. However, using a collimator, the scattering components were minimized and the percentage deviation in efficiencies was found to be in the range of 12-20 %. While estimating the detector efficiencies, the transmission factors provided by the metallic grill were also taken into account.

Conclusion

These findings suggest that CM-1 offers superior overall performance for both alpha and beta radiation detection, particularly for applications requiring accurate and reliable measurements. The difference in efficiencies is mainly due to the distance between source and detector which is found to be more in CM-2. The observed variation in efficiency across the detector surface, especially for beta particles, highlights the importance of careful source placement and calibration procedures to ensure accurate measurements. This comparison provides valuable insights for selecting the appropriate contamination monitoring system based on specific operational requirements and contamination types.

References

Mohanty B.P. et. al., *Nucl. Inst. and Meth. in Phy. Research Section A*: Volume 584, Issue 1, January 2008, Pages 186-190

MEASUREMENT OF RADON AND THORON CONCENTRATIONS AT REPROCESSED U₃O₈ STORAGE FACILITY

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Keywords: Indoor Radon & Thoron, Reprocessed U₃O₈, Inhalation dose, Occupational exposure.

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Introduction

Half of the average global annual effective dose comes from ²²²Rn, ²²⁰Rn and their progeny, making them radiologically significant. Their contribution to the radiation dose increases further due to their presence throughout various stages of the nuclear fuel cycle facilities. Radon and thoron are noble gases produced by the decay of ²²⁶Ra and ²³⁴Th in the natural decay series of ²³⁸U and ²³²Th respectively. Indoors, radon primarily originates from emissions of building materials, soil beneath structures, and stored nuclear materials containing radium etc., In the nuclear fuel cycle, thorium and uranium fuel reprocessing are significant sources of occupational exposure to thoron. In a spent fuel reprocessing facility buildup of thoron and its short-lived progeny primarily arises from ²³²U, which forms in the fuel during reactor irradiation, as well as from ²³²Th impurity present in the original uranium fuel, leads to exposure of radiation workers involved in uranium handling operation. ²³²U is always present in uranium product U₃O₈ and thus poses the risk of radiation exposure to occupational workers in U₃O₈ storage facilities. This study measured indoor radon and thoron concentrations under ventilated and non-ventilated conditions at a reprocessed U₃O₈ storage facility (SF1&SF2), evaluating their contribution to the annual inhalation dose for radiation workers.

Materials and Methods

Measurement of ²²²Rn & ²²⁰Rn at U₃O₈ storage facility was carried out by using RAD7 monitor. The sampling was carried out for 24h×3days on monthly basis for both ventilated and non-ventilated conditions. Study was continued for one year. Further, Equilibrium equivalent concentration of radon (EECRn) and thoron (EECTn) progeny estimated using equilibrium factor (F) of 0.4^[1] and 0.02(UNSCEAR2000) respectively. Subsequently Annual Inhalation Dose (AID) from radon, thoron & its progeny to the radiation workers has been estimated using expression below for different indoor occupancy at SF1 and SF2 in both the ventilation condition as

$$AID_{Rn,Tn}(mSv/y)=[(C_{Rn,Tn} \times DCF_{Rn,Tn}) + (EEC_{Rn,Tn} \times DCF_{Rn,Tn})] \times 8760 \times OF \times 10^{-1} \quad (1)$$

Where, C_{Rn,Tn} is the measured radon and thoron concentration. DCF for radon & their progeny are 0.17 & 9 nSv/Bq/m³/h and for thoron & their progeny it is 0.11 & 40 nSv/Bq/m³/h respectively. The occupancy factor (OF) for 1 to 3h indoor occupancy is obtained as 0.03 to 0.09.

Results

The Geometric mean (GM) of indoor radon & thoron concentrations at SF1 in ventilated condition is 35.6 & 6.49 Bq/m³ with GSD of 1.26, 1.17, while in non-ventilated condition it is 94.3, 10.11 Bq/m³ with GSD 1.55, 1.29. The GM of radon and thoron concentration at SF2 in ventilated condition is 53.26, 7.98 Bq/m³ with GSD 1.25, 1.11 while in non-ventilated condition it is 584.65, 30.34 Bq/m³ with GSD 1.61, 1.11. The radon concentration in both the facility with different ventilation condition is less than 59% of IAEA-BSS (2014) and national regulatory reference level. The indoor radon concentration at SF1 and SF2 in non-ventilated case is 2.36 and 14.67 times of global average value. The thoron concentration at SF1 in non-ventilated condition is comparable to global average value of 10 Bq/m³ while at SF2 it is three times higher. The higher value of Indoor radon and thoron levels at SF2 observed due to complete air tight condition of facility during non-ventilated condition. The GM for outdoor radon and thoron concentration in outside area of storage facilities is 12.25, 3.71 Bq/m³ with GSD 1.56, 1.17, which is in the range of global average of 10 Bq/m³. The higher concentration of radon and thoron in Indoor environment than outdoor is influenced by building materials, stored item and airflow patterns etc., Lower concentration of thoron is to be observed since its half-life is much shorter (55.6s) than radon (3.8d), so their environmental behaviors differ significantly. The annual inhalation dose for 1 to 3h occupancy due to radon in ventilated and non-ventilated condition at SF1 is lying between 0.04-0.11, 0.09-0.28 mSv/y & for thoron it is 0 and 0-0.01 mSv/y but for SF2 it is lying from 0.05-0.16, 0.58-1.74 mSv/y & for thoron it is 0-0.01, 0.01-0.02 mSv/y, which is below reference level & in-line with the exposure scenario in the other nuclear fuel cycle facilities.

Conclusion

The average annual inhalation dose from radon, thoron, and their progeny was found to be well below the recommended limits set by regulatory bodies.

References

1. International Commission on Radiological Protection. Protection against radon-222 at home and at work. ICRP Publication 65. Ann ICRP. 1993; 23(2):1–4. Pergamon Press.

ANALYSIS OF NEUTRON SHIELDING ADEQUACY OF PHWR SPENT FUEL SHIPPING CASK

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Keywords: PHWR, Spent Fuel, Shipping Cask, Neutron dose rate.

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Introduction:

A specially designed PHWR spent fuel cask called shipping cask is used for transportation of spent fuel. During loading and unloading of spent fuel bundles, the bolts on the cask lid are unbolted manually. The workers involved in this job get exposed to neutron field emitted from the spent fuel in the cask. The neutron dose contribution from spent fuel is due to the spontaneous fission neutrons from Plutonium and Curium isotopes, and the (α , n) reaction of these isotopes with Oxygen isotopes (^{17}O & ^{18}O). Before carrying out personnel monitoring for neutron dose, a preliminary study was carried out to estimate the neutron dose on and around the shipping cask to verify the adequacy of neutron shielding.

Materials and Methods:

Neutron radiation survey was carried out by neutron dose rate meter such as REM Counter (model no: 12-4, count rate meter, LUDLUM Measurement INC., Sweet water Texas.) on the shipping cask. In addition to this, neutron dose was also measured by exposing SSNTD based CR-39 dosimeters (M/s Pershore Moldings, UK. of dimension 3 cm \times 3 cm \times 0.625 mm (thickness) packed in triple laminated aluminized pouch from M/s TASL, UK) and Electronic Personnel Dosimeters (Model no: DMC 2000GN, Mirion Technologies) on the side of the shipping cask. The CR-39 and digital dosimeters were exposed for 3 to 24 hours depending upon the dose rate measured. The accumulated dose measured was divided by the exposure time duration to find the dose rate. At least three to five measurements were carried out for the cask having spent fuel of similar cooling period to have better average value of the dose rates.

Results & Discussion:

It is observed that neutron dose rates measured by Rem counter, varied widely from 30 - 120 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$. The variation of the dose rates is due to two factors, burn up and cooling

period of the spent fuel. The dose rates measured by digital dosimeter (MGP) and CR-39 varied from 11 - 45 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ and from 21- 87 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ respectively. This indicates that neutron dose rate decreases rapidly as cooling period of the spent fuel increases. This is due to the decrease of activity of ^{242}Cm which has high neutron emission rate (2.48E+07 n/g/s) but short half-life (163 days).

Conclusion:

The neutron dose rate on the Shipping cask decreases rapidly as cooling period of the spent fuel increases. It indicates that shielding provided in the shipping cask has to be upgraded for neutron radiation.

References

1. Long term storage of spent nuclear fuel — Survey and recommendations; IAEA-TECDOC-1293, 2002
2. Safe handling and storage of plutonium, IAEA safety series-9.1998.

HEALTH PHYSICS EXPERIENCE DURING IN-SERVICE INSPECTION OF WASTE VAULT AT CORAL

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Introduction

Reprocessing of spent fuel from Fast Breeder Test Reactor (FBTR) is being carried out in CORAL (COmpact Reprocessing of Advanced fuels in Lead cells) facility, situated at Indira Gandhi Centre for Atomic Research (IGCAR). Irradiated FBTR fuel pins of burn-ups ranging from 25 to 155 GWd/t have been successfully reprocessed at CORAL. The liquid waste such as raffinate solution, organic wastes, scrubber solutions etc. generated since the commissioning of the plant is kept in the Waste vault tanks as interim storage. All the tanks in the waste vault are located underground and only the auxiliary facility exists above the ground level. The In Service Inspection (ISI) of the waste vault tanks were carried once in five years, as a regulatory mandate. During ISI, visual inspection is carried out to determine the integrity of tanks, degradation of piping and presence of foreign materials. A remote control operated vehicle is used for the inspection due to the presence of very high radiation levels. This paper describes the experience gained during radiological surveillance of the ISI process.

Material and Methods

A temporary safety barrier was erected along the sides of the located man hole at waste vault ground level. The man hole is closed with six MS blocks which act as shielding from high radiation levels. The inspection of the high active storage tanks, equipments and other components inside the WTF was carried out using robotic Pan-tilt-zoom (PTZ) camera attached with a remote controlled vehicle and operated at waste vault ground level. The ISI vehicle was inserted through the plug of seventh MS shield and the inspection was completed using a controller remotely. Total of 18 persons were involved in this inspection. PPEs used by the workers were Lead coat, Half face mask, Lab coat, Hand gloves and shoe

covers. Personal dosimeter is given to all the workers and an EPD is fixed with the vehicle.

Results

The radiation levels over the shielding blocks was 3 μ Gy/h and no change was observed upto removal of first four layers of MS blocks. After removal of fifth and sixth layer, the radiation level increased to 20 μ Gy/h and 60 mGy/h respectively. The dose rate near safety barrier varied between 200 – 300 μ Gy/h. An EPD was kept at underground at a depth of 6 meters for 2 minutes, the dose on the EPD was found to be 43.43 mGy and the maximum dose rate recorded was 1.58 Gy/h. Dose measured on the EPD attached with the vehicle was 619.4 mGy. No long lived activity was detected in the air samples taken during removal of the shielding and during the job.

Conclusion

ISI of waste vault was successfully completed with all high active tanks integrity and degradation of pipings were found to be satisfactory. Total collective dose received for the work was 6.29 PmSv. Maximum individual dose was 1.74 mSv received by operational personnel. The collective dose for the entire operation was 70 % of the estimated dose budget which was possible because of proper planning, ALARA discussions, effective coordination among the agencies involved, continuous supervision and strictly adhering to RPP and HP practices.

DEVELOPMENT OF INDIGENOUS ALPHA SPECTROMETRY SOFTWARE (IGASPEC) FOR REVAMPED ALPHA DETECTION SYSTEM

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Keywords: Alpha spectrometer, detector, MCA, amplifier, software, vacuum chamber

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Introduction

Alpha spectrometer plays a vital role in identifying and quantifying alpha emitting radionuclides in different samples. In HPU, CORAL facility ORTEC[®] based alpha spectrometer is revamped with electronics modules from EEIPL[®] and interfaced with USB based 1K MCA. The detector is made up of Silicon Charged-Particle Detector and housed in a vacuum chamber. The MCA gathers all the pulses from the spectroscopy amplifier and makes a frequency distribution table depending on pulse height of the signals. To operate the spectrometer and acquire the spectrum, indigenous software, IGASPEC is developed in vb.net platform. The details of spectrometer and IGASPEC are discussed below.

Details of spectrometer and IGASPEC

An alpha spectrometer system is made by coupling detector and pre-amplifier (ORTEC) with spectroscopic amplifier and MCA (EEIPL). It was ensured that the signals from pre-amplifier are amenable for processing by the amplifier. The signals from MCA is accessed and processed by IGASPEC using the dynamic link library (DLL) files viz., Gspec.dll and SiUSBXp.dll. The vacuum of the chamber is measured by a sensor and the signal is available for processing by IGASPEC. The data from DLL files is then processed and displayed as spectrum in the graph tool of IGASPEC. It has provisions to set all the MCA parameters like LLD, HV, gain, counting time etc under MCA properties tab and the same is set in the MCA. The sample details tab stores information like nature of sample, sample location, work description, filter paper type, vacuum of the chamber and sample date and Auto sample Id gets generated. Once all the parameters are entered, the spectrum will run for the pre-determined time. The counts under various channels are updated every second and displayed. On completion of counting, the

spectral information is stored in the customer defined folder in Microsoft Excel[®] format and retrieval option is provided for analysis. The visual examination of the spectrum could be performed to identify the peaks in the spectrum. IGASPEC has a special provision for carrying out the leak test of the vacuum chamber. By clicking the “perform leak test option” the source will be counted in the pre determined time and cycle. Further, development of the IGASPEC for peak identification and calibration algorithm is in progress Preliminary experiments indicate that the spectrum acquired using standard sources of alpha energy of 5.15 Mev of Pu²³⁹ and 5.5 Mev of Am²⁴¹ appears in channel no 466 and 513 respectively with vacuum of the detector kept at 10 milli torr.

Conclusion

IGASPEC for the analysis of Alpha spectrum is functional. It acquires data from MCA and displays the same using a graph tool. All the parameters applicable for counting a sample including the vacuum of the detector chamber can be set and stored in a retrievable format.

References

Spectrum acquisition and analysis software version 2.1 and demo code vb.net from EEIPL

QUANTIFYING ALARA – A DOSE DYNAMICAL APPROACH TO RADIATION PROTECTION

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Keywords: ALARA, dose dynamics, radiological protection, dose optimization, occupational exposure, dose constraints

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Introduction

Optimization of radiation protection is implemented through the ALARA (*As Low as Reasonably Achievable*) principle, that seeks to optimize (not minimize) radiation exposure while maintaining operational efficiencies. Prior analyses of occupational dose distributions have demonstrated the role of dose limits in shaping optimization strategies (Kumazawa and Numakunai, 1981). In this paper, we propose a dose dynamical approach to radiation protection and model optimization as forces acting on individual dose trajectories, thus providing insights into dose constraint effects and providing a metric for cross-facility comparisons of radiological protection practices.

Materials and Methods

We modelled radiation protection as a dynamic force influencing individual worker doses $Di(t)$, represented by:

$$F(D_i) = -\frac{\partial V_A(D_i)}{\partial D_i} - \frac{\partial V_C(D_i)}{\partial D_i} + \eta_i(t)$$

where $V_A(D_i)$ is the ALARA potential, $V_C(D_i)$ is the constraint potential, and $\eta_i(t)$ is the operational noise which is normally distributed. We tested this model with 9-year historical exposure data from a spent fuel reprocessing facility, and identified the exponential form for $V_A(D)$ and a linear inverse function for $V_C(D)$ as the best fits. Specifically, the ALARA potential $V_A(D) = k(e^{(\alpha_{\text{potential}} \cdot D)} - 1)$ and the constraint potential $V_C(D) = (1 + \alpha_{\text{constraint}}|D - D_C|)^{-1}$, where D_C is the dose constraint in the monitoring period. Alternative forms, such as harmonic and logarithmic potentials, and other constraint potentials were considered, but the combination mentioned above yielded the best fit based on RMSE, AIC, and log-likelihood criteria. By adjusting constraint (changing D_C) by a scaling factor a from 0.8 to 1.5, we studied how dose constraints influence other parameters. The ratios b_k

$$b_k = \frac{k_{\text{new dose constraint}}}{k_{\text{baseline}}}$$

and similarly defined $b_{\alpha\text{ALARA}}$ and $b_{\alpha\text{constraint}}$ were plotted against a , thus showing the behavior of the respective parameters with new dose constraints against the baseline values (existing values of D_C).

Results

It was observed that b_k (the relative strength of ALARA dose reduction) decreased as a increased, thus showing the diminishing effectiveness of ALARA measures when constraints were relaxed. Conversely, $b_{\alpha\text{potential}}$ (the dose sensitivity within the ALARA potential), increased with higher doses under more lenient ($a > 1$) constraints, thus showing increased responsiveness to dose changes in these conditions. The constraint adherence factor, $b_{\alpha\text{constraint}}$, showed a variable response, thus suggesting a threshold-based behavior depending on dose constraints. The coefficients thus defined, provide a radiological practice agnostic metric for cross-facility comparison of radiological protection practices.

Conclusion

The proposed dose dynamical model provides a quantitative framework for assessing ALARA measures. This approach allows for cross-facility comparisons and may support cost-benefit analyses of dose mitigation practices, enhancing radiological protection strategies. Our findings provide insights into behavior of radiation protection practices with varying regulatory constraints.

References

Kumazawa, S., and Numakunai, T. *Health Physics* **41**(3) (1981): 465-475.

IMPLEMENTATION OF ALARA DURING REPLACEMENT OF HAWE HEAT EXCHANGERS AT REPROCESSING PLANT

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Introduction

At a PHWR spent fuel reprocessing facility, various process cells are designed to house the equipment handling different cycles of the PUREX process (Dey and Bansal, 2006). In a specific example, Process Cell-1 consist of HA cycles (Co-decontamination cum partitioning cycle), HAW evaporators and Rework cycle equipment. Thermosyphon Evaporators are used to concentrate HA cycle raffinate (HAW) having activity concentration in the range of 4000-7000 TBq/m³ ($\beta\gamma$). During the course of operations, the heat exchangers (HX) of these evaporators showed minor breaches in their containment efficiency and hence it was planned to replace with new ones inside Process Cell-1. The replacement of failed HX involves cutting of old HX, edge preparation by grinding and welding of new HX in the circuit. The general radiation fields inside the cells before commencement of the works were in the range of 3-5 Sv/h, and transferrable contaminations were greater than 100 Bq/cm² (α) and 1000 Bq/cm² (β). In this paper, we present the radiological protective measures taken to keep the exposures as low as reasonably achievable (ALARA).

Materials and Methods

The process of managing radiation exposure in a facility involved several steps to identify and mitigate hotspots, control airborne contamination, and manage external and internal worker exposure. Radiation mapping was first conducted inside the process cells to identify equipment and transfer lines with high radiation levels, with highest levels (3-5 Sv/h) observed near evaporators. Decontamination procedures were performed using caustic and carbonate solutions, followed by washing with demineralized water (DMW). This was repeated several times to reduce radiation levels in the cell, which then allowed physical entry to identify specific hotspots, particularly

in choked sampling uptake lines, where radiation levels exceeded 10 Sv/h. These lines were de-choked remotely using chemical and mechanical methods. After decontamination, the background radiation in the cell reduced less than 0.20 mSv/h. Airborne contamination was monitored using continuous air monitors and personal air samplers. A local exhaust system minimized airborne radioactivity. For external exposure control, Electronic Personal Dosimeters were used to monitor external exposure, while automation systems and protective equipment (PPE) ensured protection from internal exposure, with a dedicated team handling PPE removal post-work.

Results

Vertical radiation mapping, investigative radiation surveys by physical entry inside process cells, and through improvised but precise survey techniques for hotspot identification assisted the facility-efforts of internal decontamination & mechanical dechoking, ultimately lowering the radiation fields much below the stipulated limits. Total 590 personal entries consuming 1650 man-hours were utilized for replacement five number of exchangers inside process cell-1.

Conclusion

ALARA principle was implemented to control both external and internal exposures. HAWE HX replacement works were concluded within 37% of revised collective dose budget. There were *zero* cases of intake. No worker involved in works incurred doses above investigation levels.

References

P K Dey & N K Bansal (2006) *Nuclear Engineering & Design*; **236**,723-729.

PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION ANALYSIS DURING SS LINING CUTTING OF VITRIFICATION CELL FLOOR

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Introduction

The vitrification process, essential in high-level radioactive waste management, converts liquid waste into a stable, glass-like solid form, ensuring long-term containment and isolation of hazardous materials. However, this process generates particulate matter, including respirable particles that can pose health risks if inhaled (MacMillan et al., 2013). Vitrification cell decommissioning involves cutting of stainless steel (SS) floor lines, which can produce particles of different sizes depending on the materials and cutting parameters. While studies have explored particle generation in other aspects, such as contaminated vitrification cell equipment dismantling (Ashish et al., 2023), there is limited knowledge about particle size distribution during SS floor line cutting. The intent of present study was to determine the activity median aerodynamic diameter (AMAD) and geometrical standard deviation (GSD) of aerosols sampled during SS lining cutting operations in vitrification cell. Understanding particle characteristics enables a clearer assessment of associated health risks and informs the development of targeted mitigation strategies for workplace safety.

Materials and Methods

To determine AMAD, cumulative activity fraction less than the stated size versus log-probability of particle diameter was plotted, and the 50th percentile was interpolated. Assuming log-normal particle distribution, the following equation is used to calculate particle size GSD (σ_g):

$$\sigma_g = \frac{84th\ percentile\ value}{50th\ percentile\ value}$$

Particle Aerodynamic Size Separator (PASS) impactor, operating at 45 lpm and designed by EAD, BARC, to separate particles from 0.53 to 8.95 μm . Glass fiber filters, offering >99% filtration efficiency, were used for sampling. Three sample sets were collected over 1-2 hours during SS line cutting for particle size and

isotopic analysis using High Purity Germanium (HPGe).

Results

The activity data sets were developed collectively by combining the three sets. The results were used to develop aerodynamic diameter and AMAD and GSD (σ_g) were then determined by plotting data on a log-probability plot. The AMAD was determined to be 5.8 μm with its GSD (σ_g) equal to 1.8. The ^{137}Cs distribution obtained in HPGe confirms predominant radionuclide in the facility. Obtained AMAD is consistent with the default AMAD value for occupational workers i.e. 5 μm as referenced in ICRP 130. The inhalation dose coefficient for Type M ^{137}Cs , corresponding to the measured AMAD, was determined to be 5.14×10^{-9} Sv/Bq.

Conclusion

Particle generation during floor SS line cutting in a vitrification cell poses health and safety risks due to the radioactive content of the waste. The size and composition of these particles determine their potential for inhalation and related health impacts. This study's particle size distribution analysis highlights respirable particle fractions, aiding inhalation risk assessment. The calculated dose coefficient enables adjustment of the Annual Limit on Intake (ALI) for real scenarios and supports risk assessments by providing data on potential particle concentrations, guiding safety measures for workers exposed to radioactive materials during the cutting process.

References

- MacMillan et al., Particle size characterization of aerosols generated during surface contaminated concrete demolition. Health Physics 104 (2013), no. 5S: S83-S86.
- Ashish Kumar Singh, et al., Particle size characterization of aerosols generated during dismantling of contaminated cell equipment, Book of Abstract, AOCRP6, Mumbai, 7-11 February, 2023, Pages 65-66.

A REVIEW ON INTERNAL DOSE MONITORING PROGRAM AT KUDANKULAM NUCLEAR SITE

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Introduction

The potential for occurrence of internal contamination of radioactivity exists at all nuclear facilities. So, it is one of the important regulatory mandates to be complied by the operating stations. For evaluation of internal exposure due to gamma emitting fission and activation products like ¹³⁷Cs, ¹³¹I, ⁶⁰Co, etc., shadow shield bed whole body monitors are conventionally used. The subject is scanned from head to toes in this Shadow Shield Bed Whole Body Monitors (SSBWBM). It is used for profile scanning of the subject and for locating contamination in the body. The system having variable scanning time has been adopted. This system is provided with bed drive control unit, reduced background and well improved aesthetic look. Depending on the requirement, the subject counting time can be changed with the help of this bed drive mechanism.

Materials and Methods

The essential requirement for a WBM is good shielding, a detector which has fairly good energy resolution and a pulse height analyzer. In Kudankulam, the shadow shield radioactivity monitor developed in late 1960s and further standardised in 1971 (Hukku, 1971) was used with improvements on aesthetics and shielding. These detectors employ large size (4'X4'X16') NaI (Tl) detectors to achieve the required sensitivity. The detector is well shielded all around with 15 mm thick mild steel plates. The bed drive and other control equipment for uniform bed movement are fixed with the bottom shield. A linear motion (LM) guide based bed drive mechanism is used to operate the bed. None of the internal parts, motor and its accessories are visible to the subjects and the subjects feel at ease during the counting time.

Results

The internal dose monitoring in Kudankulam is carried out as per methods outlined in ICRP 54 and 78. The counting is conducted in any one of the three categories, viz. routine monitoring, special monitoring and confirmatory monitoring. The derived recording

levels (DRLs) and investigation levels (DILs), worked out by Pramilla et al (1999) are followed for routine and special monitoring. Using bio kinetic models of respective radio nuclides, the recording levels are modified to obtain derived recording levels and derived investigation levels by applying the appropriate retention factors for the nuclides concerned. About 24000 subjects have been monitored so far from the date of commissioning of the system and the internal dose contribution to workers due to KKNPP plant operation is zero.

Conclusion

The system used in Kudankulam for internal dose monitoring was successfully upgraded with LM guide based drive controllers. It has given trouble free operation over the last 10 years. There is a considerable reduction in background due to improvement in the lead shielding which results in lower detectable activity of about 300-600 Bq for ⁶⁰Co and ¹³⁷Cs respectively. It gives the provision to the user to change the speed and direction of the bed during the monitoring time and for ease of operation.

References

- Hukku R.K. and Katoch D.S. (1971), Whole body counting of radiation workers, BARC-548, 1971.
- ICRP-54 (1988), Individual Monitoring for intakes of radionuclides by workers: Design and Interpretation.
- ICRP-78 (1998), Individual Monitoring for internal exposure of workers; Replacement of ICRP Publication 54.
- Pramilla D.S., Jyoti V.S., Gurg R.P., Kamala Rudran and Gupta V.K. (1999), Manual on internal dose computation and reporting, BARC/1999/E/010

STANDARDIZATION OF TDCR BASED LIQUID SCINTILLATION AND CERENKOV COUNTING TECHNIQUES FOR ESTIMATION OF ^{106}Ru IN VARIOUS PLANT SAMPLES

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Introduction

The closed loop nuclear fuel cycle facilitates the recovery of valuable nuclides from the radioactive waste [1]. ^{106}Ru is beneficial for societal applications, making its separation and quantification from radioactive waste essential. ^{106}Ru ($t_{1/2}$ -373days, E_{max} -0.039 MeV) is a fission product that decays to stable palladium via ^{106}Rh ($t_{1/2}$ -30.1s, E_{max} -3.54 MeV). This isotope is widely used for the treatment of various types of cancers [2]. The objective of the present study was to standardize a Triple-to-Double Coincidence Ratio (TDCR) based Liquid Scintillation Counting (LSC) and Cerenkov Counting (CC) techniques for the determination of ^{106}Ru in various plant samples.

Materials and Methods

HIDEX 300SL LSC was used for both LSC and CC measurements. To calibrate the LSC, a ^{106}Ru standard source (standardized at RSS, RSSD) with an activity of 1kBq was used. In LSC, the Counting Efficiency (CE) can vary due to sample impurities (quenching), thus, conducting quench calibration studies is essential for the accurate quantification of ^{106}Ru . In HIDEX LSC, the degree of sample quenching is indicated by the TDCR parameter, which directly reflects the CE for pure β emitters. Two different sets of quenched $^{106}\text{Ru}/^{106}\text{Rh}$ standards were used for calibration. In the 1st set, standards were prepared by mixing 1mL of spiked aqueous sample with 10mL of Optiphase Hisafe-3 cocktail in glass vials. Incremental amounts of Nitromethane (0-100mg) were added to simulate various quench levels. LSC spectrum of ^{106}Ru in equilibrium with ^{106}Rh exhibited two different peaks viz. lower peak due to ^{106}Ru (5-400 channels) and higher one due to ^{106}Rh (400-1023 channels). Count rates and TDCR parameters were noted in 3 different Regions of Interest (ROIs): the entire ROI (5-1023 channels), as well as the lower and the higher ROIs. The 2nd set of standards used for CC consisted of 10mL of spiked aqueous samples (activity: 1kBq) with varying amount of

quencher (brown dye). CC Efficiencies (CCE) were determined (5-450channels) and TDCR values were recorded for these standards.

Results

When count rate and TDCR parameter in full ROI were used for the determination of $^{106}\text{Ru}/^{106}\text{Ru}$ activity, significant deviation (up to 30%) from the reference activity was observed with increasing quench. Nonuniformity of the TDCR with actual efficiencies at higher degrees of quench was prominent in entire ROI, contributing significantly to the observed deviation. In contrast, it was observed that TDCR for the higher energy peak approached 1, resulting in precise measurements with a % deviation within $\pm 3\%$, regardless of the degree of quenching. Uniformity in the TDCR (~ 1) parameter for the higher ROI may be attributed to the ^{106}Rh energy (3.54 MeV). Further, for the quenched standards in the 2nd set, the experimentally derived CCE did not align with TDCR. To rectify this, a Correction Factor (CF), which is the ratio of TDCR and CCE, was applied. A unique CF of 0.9 was derived which remained consistent irrespective of degree of quenching with CCE as high as 80%. MDA achieved using LSC and CC techniques were 0.2 BqmL^{-1} and 0.02 BqmL^{-1} respectively.

Conclusion

LSC and CC techniques were standardized and effectively applied for determination of ^{106}Ru activities in spiked aqueous samples. Further, the standardized techniques can be implemented to estimation of ^{106}Ru in effluent samples.

References

1. Kaushik C.P. (2021) *BARC e-book*, Chap.1,1-10.
2. Zuba I. *et al* (2020) *Appl Radi Isot* **162**, 109176.

STUDY ON DISTRIBUTION OF ACTIVITY PROFILE IN EXHAUST FILTER

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Introduction

During the process of radioactive waste treatment, a significant amount of off-gases is generated, consisting of a diverse mixture of radioactive particulates. These off-gases undergo exhaust filtration, during which they are deposited and distributed within the filter media. Effective filtration of these off-gases is essential to mitigate the potential environmental impact. Understanding the distribution of radioactivity within exhaust filters is vital for assessing the filtration system's performance and optimizing its design.

This study focuses on analyzing how radionuclides, are distributed within the filter media. By examining samples at various depths and rows from the filter using gamma-ray spectroscopy, the aim is to understand the radioactive concentration profiles of radionuclides within the depth of the filter medium.

Materials and Methods

To comprehensively investigate the distribution of radioactive concentration within the exhaust filter, which is made up of a glass (borosilicate) fiber medium with dimensions of 61 cm (L) x 29.2 cm (W) x 61 cm (H). A total of twenty samples were systematically collected from different depths of the filter media, specifically at 2.7 cm, 7.2 cm, 11.7 cm, 16.2 cm, and 20.7 cm, spanning from the inlet to the outlet. Additionally, samples were taken across four vertical rows within the filter, maintaining consistent separation across the rows. Each of these samples was subjected to gamma spectrometry analysis using a highly sensitive p-type High Purity Germanium (HPGe) detector, with 45% relative efficiency and renowned for its accuracy in detecting and measuring gamma radiation. The resulting gamma spectra were meticulously analyzed to identify and quantify the radionuclides present, providing detailed insights into their distribution within the filter media.

Results

The spectral analysis revealed the presence of two radionuclides, ^{137}Cs and ^{241}Am , within the filter media. The activity concentrations (Bq/gm) of ^{137}Cs and ^{241}Am along the depth of a single vertical row were observed as follows: ^{137}Cs (in MBq/g): 0.30 ± 0.02 , 1.06 ± 0.06 , 1.99 ± 0.11 , 4.22 ± 0.24 , 7.02 ± 0.40 ; ^{241}Am (in Bq/g): 73.9 ± 4.1 , 111.1 ± 6.7 , 308.3 ± 20.1 , 497.7 ± 33.9 , 901.7 ± 63.1 . Both radionuclides displayed a clear increasing trend in concentration with depth, starting from relatively lower concentrations at the inlet and progressively increasing, reaching their maximum levels near the outlet. A similar distribution trend was observed in samples collected from other vertical rows. This pattern of radionuclide distribution reflects a distinct exponential growth trend along the depth of the filter, highlighting the accumulation dynamics within the media.

Conclusion

This study investigated the depth-dependent distribution of radionuclides, specifically ^{137}Cs and ^{241}Am , within the exhaust filter media. The radioactive concentration of both radionuclides increased with depth of filter media. The exponential growth pattern observed emphasizes the need for accurate monitoring and understanding of activity distribution to ensure efficient radioactive waste treatment.

References

Ji, Y.-Y., Hong, D.-S., Kang, I.-S., Seo, B.-K., and Shon, J.-S. (2014) Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology, 45, 439–442.

QUALITY CONTROL ACTIVITIES DURING FABRICATION OF GRADED SHIELD ROOM FOR ACTINIDE MONITOR

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Keywords: Quality control, Welding, Materials standards, mild steel, streaming, background radiation

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Introduction

At IRMF a shield room is being constructed for the monitoring of actinides. The shield room is being constructed using 200 mm mild steel, 3 mm Pb, 2mm Sn and 1mm Cu. This would reduce the natural background radiation 200 times in the energy range 12-200 keV, which is the energy region of interest for actinides. Stacking of MS plates of 50 mm have been used for getting the required thickness. Field deployable quality practices have been put-in place during fabrication of the facility to meet the intended service requirements right from raw material qualification to final integrity testing by means of radiometry testing. It is to be ensured that the steel plates used is free from radioactive contamination particularly ⁶⁰Co. Also the natural radio activity level should be less than the acceptable level. The welding should be in such a way that there is no streaming of dose through the weld joints. This paper discusses the quality assurance program carried out to ensure the above conditions.

Materials and Methods

The IS 2062BR (IS 2062, 2011) steel material was chosen due to its malleability, high density and nominal cost. It was decided to use stack 5 cm thickness sheet to achieve the 200 mm thickness, so that a balance is there between handling and work load. The plates are sandwiched through plug weld. The weld types (plug and edge) and their positions (staggered) were opted to avoid streaming. The welders were qualified for 3G (Vertical uphill) position welding by doing a test weld with 20 cm mild steel. The welded materials were subjected to tensile and bend test. The welding procedure was qualified by carried out a radiometry test on a mockup structure fabricated with four 5 cm plates, along with hole plugs, using 2 mCi ⁶⁰Co. Test certificates were obtained from the OEM for all the

material used like MS, electrodes, material for dye penetrate test, red oxide paint etc. Submerged Arc welding and shielded metal arc welding are used to weld all plates to achieve higher productivity without offsetting quality requirements. After fabrication of each layer all the joints were inspected with liquid penetration test.

Results

With the results of the tensile and bend test of the welding coupons the welders were qualified for 3G. The radiometry tests showed that the observed dose rates were less than the expected ones in all the locations qualifying the welding procedure. The material test certificates and the ladle analysis showed that the steel plates were of IS 2062BR grade. The penetrant materials satisfied the limits (25 ppm) for Sulphur and Halogen contents as per the latest ASME specifications. The Liquid Penetration Test showed that there was no streaming through the joints.

Conclusion

The robust Quality Assurance program undertaken will result in a sturdy and low background steel room for actinide monitoring at IRMF.

Reference

IS 2062, 2011. Hot Rolled Medium and High Tensile Structural Steel — Specification

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF VARIOUS SCINTILLATION SOLUTIONS FOR ESTIMATION OF RADIOCARBON (C-14) ACTIVITY IN DIFFERENT STRENGTHS OF SODIUM HYDROXIDE FROM GASEOUS EFFLUENTS OF KAIGA GENERATING STATION-3&4

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Introduction

¹⁴C (half-life~5730 years, pure beta emitter) is one of the cosmogenic radionuclides which own the interest of studying its existence in nature. The main significance of ¹⁴C originates from its entry into the carbon cycle and the resulting global dispersion, leading to long-term irradiation. The isotope ¹⁴C, a radioactive one, is produced in the upper atmosphere by the irradiation of ¹⁴N by neutrons of cosmic ray origin. The rate of formation of ¹⁴C in reactors depends on the reactor type, being the highest in PHWRs and lowest in PWRs. In PHWR, ¹⁴C is produced in the fuel, moderator, reactor coolant and Annulus Gas Monitoring System (AGMS) by activation reactions of ¹³C(n,γ)¹⁴C, ¹⁴N(n,p)¹⁴C and ¹⁷O(n,α)¹⁴C, with major contribution from moderator system for its large inventory. However, most of the ¹⁴C activity is formed in the moderator system is absorbed in the ion exchange resin of moderator purification system[1]. Therefore the amount of ¹⁴C in gaseous emissions is significantly reduced but still there is need to quantify the ¹⁴C activity from gaseous effluents through ventilation stack.

Kaiga Generating Station-3&4(KGS-3&4) consist of twin units of PHWR of 220 MWe each capacity located in Karnataka State, India. Gaseous effluent releases are continuously monitored for radioactive constituents before discharged through 100m height stack to comply with regulatory and technical specification requirements. At KGS 3&4, a sampling and analytical method was developed for ¹⁴C activity measurement [2]. In this method, the gaseous effluents are passed through a set of bubbler containing 1N NaOH solution to trap CO₂ by absorption in the alkaline medium. The sampled solution is then mixed with scintillation cocktail and analyzed in Liquid Scintillation Analyser (LSA) to assess the ¹⁴C activity. Meridian Biotechnologies make Goldstar (DIN) Di-isopropyl Naphthalene Isomer was used for LSA. Studies were continued to explore the practicability of different scintillation solutions with different strengths of NaOH. This paper brings out the performance parameters of different scintillation solutions used for ¹⁴C activity measurement.

Materials and methods:

The ¹⁴C samples were collected from stack exhaust air of KGS-3&4 in a set of bubbler containing in 0.5N, 1.0N, 2.0N and 4.0 N NaOH. Experiments were conducted to check sample compatibility, chemiluminescence and Figure of Merit (FOM) for five different commercially available scintillation solutions. The cocktails tested are 1,4 Dioxane, Ultima Gold, Optiphase, Hionic Fluor and Combustion Count. The samples were prepared in 20mL low potassium glass vial. To assess performance parameters for every liquid

scintillation solution, series of counting vials containing ¹⁴C sample with scintillation solution in a ratio of 1:3, 1:5, and 1:10 were prepared and the samples were counted after sample preparation and again counted after allowing dark adaption of 24h and spectral data were recorded.

Results and discussions: The results reveal that

1. *Sample compatibility:* Overall good results were obtained with Ultima Gold and Hionic flour compared to other three scintillation solution. 1,4 Dioxane based scintillation solution is observed to be immiscible and forming turbidity with sample. Hionic Fluor is miscible with 1.0N, 2.0N and 4N NaOH.
2. *Figure Of Merit (FOM):* DIN based scintillation solutions like Ultima Gold showed higher FOM. Observed value for Combustion count was significantly low. Results tabulated below:
3. *Stability:* Except 1,4 Dioxane and Combustion count, all other scintillation solutions were showing good stability over time.
4. *Chemiluminescence:* Effects of chemiluminescence increases with increase in strength of NaOH with all scintillation solutions. However, Ultima Gold and Hionic flour showed fast chemiluminescence decay rate.

Conclusion:

The choice of good scintillation solution for the measurement of ¹⁴C activity depends upon many factors of which sample compatibility, chemiluminescence and FOM are very important. All these factors were studied with various alkaline strengths of NaOH at KGS-3&4 and it indicated that overall good results were observed in DIN based scintillation solutions like Ultima Gold with 0.5N, 1.0N NaOH with sample to scintillation solution ratio of 1:5 and 2.0N NaOH with sample to solution ratio of 1:10. Hionic Fluor is also found to be good scintillation solution for higher alkaline strengths (>1N) of NaOH for the sample to scintillation solution ratio 1:5.

References:

1. R.K Diwedi, M L Joshi et.al, 1987, Estimation of Carbon-14 in moderator system in a standard PHWR.
2. G.S.Salunke et.al,2023 Development of methodology for measurement of Carbon-14 activity in stack exhaust air at Kaiga Generating Station-3&4.
3. Verrezen.F, Loots H and Hurtgen C A Performance Comparison of Nine Selected Liquid Scintillation Cocktails.

DETERMINING SELF-ABSORPTION COEFFICIENTS IN GLASS FIBER FILTERS FOR MOX FUEL FABRICATION

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Introduction

The facilities in which actinides are handled in bulk quantity such as MOX fuel fabrication (FF), accurate monitoring of alpha airborne activity is essential for controlling internal exposure and meeting regulatory dose limits. MOX fuel fabrication plants use both online and offline monitoring systems to assess alpha airborne activity. Online monitoring is typically achieved with continuous air monitors (CAMs), but these monitors cannot be placed close to equipment handling radioactive materials due to spatial constraints. Therefore, offline monitoring on every glove boxes is carried out through air sampling points having a filter holder carrying glass fiber filter paper which is connected to centralized vacuum system. The glass fiber air (GFA) filter paper samples from both CAM & sampling points are periodically replaced and counted to estimate the airborne activity due to long-lived alpha emitters. GFA filters are then analyzed using ZnS (Ag) based alpha scintillation counting systems to determine alpha activity due to long-lived alpha emitters. However, in laboratory environments with significant particulate dust, dust is accumulated on collection surface of the GFA filter. This dust load causes attenuation of alpha particles [1], leading to inaccurate results from direct counting. To address this, an experiment was conducted to determine the self-absorption coefficients for alpha particles in glass fiber air filters due to particulate dust load.

Materials and Methods

In this study, GFA filter paper samples were first directly counted under ZnS (Ag) based alpha counting system, and then same FPs were dissolved in a chemical process to estimate the self-absorption factor. The dissolution involved treating the filters with a combination of 5 ml 16M nitric acid (HNO₃) and hydrofluoric acid (HF) in a Teflon beaker, followed by stirring and heating on a hot plate until evaporation. A second dissolution step with HNO₃ and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) was followed by additional drying. After drying, the solution was treated with 1M HNO₃, add tracer Pu²⁴² and then

transferred to an electroplating cell for electrodeposition at 0.3A for 120 minutes. The activity on the samples were then analyzed using alpha spectroscopy. To calculate the self-absorption coefficients, multiple experiments were conducted with dissolved active glass fiber air filter samples.

Results and Discussion

The self-absorption coefficients (SAC) were defined as the ratio of the gross alpha count of the electrodeposited planchette sample to the gross alpha count of glass fiber filter paper. U&Pu both are electrodeposited and percentage recovery is 90%. The results indicated that the presence of dust significantly affected alpha particle absorption. The absorption coefficients varied between 1.22 and 1.37, with an average value of 1.28, highlighting the degree of particle attenuation due to dust load on the glass fiber air filters. These findings demonstrate the importance of considering dust load when measuring alpha airborne activity, as it leads to underestimation of actual activity levels if not accounted for. By applying the SAC, facilities can achieve more accurate measurements of alpha activity concentration, ensuring better control of internal exposure and compliance with regulatory dose limits.

Conclusion

This study provides a viable approach for assessing the impact of particulate dust and improving the accuracy of alpha air activity measurements at MOX fuel fabrication.

References

1. IAEA, Radiation Protection & Dosimetry -S61, Energy Degradation and flux attenuation of alpha particles due to absorbing media, Nov- 2019

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF BACKGROUND LUNG MONITORING DATA USING PHOSWICH DETECTOR

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Introduction

In-vivo monitoring of radiation workers for internal contamination by actinides is performed within a steel room to ensure precise assessment of low-level Pu and Am activity. Accurate estimation of the subject's background is critical when measuring low-energy photons with low yield, as it minimizes uncertainty in the results. Background counts are subtracted from the gross counts in the region of interest (ROI) of the acquired spectrum to determine the deposited activity in the lungs (Nadar et. al., 2024). The background counts in low-energy regions arise from internal radionuclides such as ⁴⁰K and ¹³⁷Cs, as well as from scattered cosmic rays and terrestrial radiation interacting with the individual's body. ⁴⁰K (body potassium) level is proportional to the body weight. The observed background counts are influenced by various parameters, including the individual's weight, height, chest circumference, and age. This study analyzes the variation in background counts with these parameters and explores the development of a machine learning model for subject-specific background prediction.

Materials and Methods

Supervised learning, a subset of machine learning, trains a model on a portion of the data and evaluates its performance on the remaining data. In this study, background counts from approx. 3,000 radiation workers, monitored with a phoswich detector (target/output), were analyzed alongside various physical parameters. Outliers were removed using the interquartile range method. Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated to identify the strongest correlations with the target variable, and the most relevant variables were selected for model development. Linear, polynomial regression, and Random Forest Regression models were used to predict background counts. The performance of these models was

assessed through metrics like root mean square error (RMSE) and accuracy score.

Results

Background counts in the 60 keV ROI show moderate dependence on parameters such as weight, chest circumference, chest wall thickness, and weight-to-height ratio, with Pearson correlation coefficients (PCC) around 0.45. Linear and polynomial regression models, using single or combined inputs, achieved accuracy scores of up to 25%. In contrast, the Random Forest Regression algorithm, which incorporated all significant inputs, attained an accuracy score of 40%, correctly predicting background counts 40% of the time. Low-energy gamma photons and low count rates cause statistical fluctuations, limiting the performance of linear and polynomial models. The Random Forest algorithm, based on random conditions in input data, achieves higher accuracy due to its non-deterministic nature.

Conclusion

This study investigates the prediction of background radiation counts in radiation workers using machine learning models. The variation in background count, was analyzed against physical parameters, with Random Forest Regression model outperforming linear and polynomial models by achieving 40% accuracy. Advanced techniques like Artificial Neural Networks show promise for improved accuracy with optimized data and iterations.

References

M.Y. Nadar, L. Mishra, and I. S. Singh (2024) Handbook on Radiation, Environment. Vol. II.

INTERNAL DOSE CONTROL MEASURES AT MADRAS ATOMIC POWER STATION, A 220MWE PRESSURIZED HEAVY WATER REACTOR USING MODIFIED PPES

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Introduction

In India's current indigenous Nuclear Power Program is based on Pressurized Heavy Water Reactors (PHWRs), Heavy water (D₂O) is used as the coolant and moderator. In PHWRs, Neutron irradiation of Deuterium is the major source of Tritium ($T_{1/2}=12.3y$) which is an ever-present hazard leading to Internal Dose to the Radiation workers [1]. Tritium is a pure Beta Emitter ($E_{\beta max}=18$ KeV and $E_{\beta avg}=5.7$ KeV), hence it does not contribute to the external dose but rises the internal dose of the Radiation workers significantly. The pathway for exposure of tritium is mostly through inhalation and skin absorption. Biological half-life in human body varies from 4-10 days and depends on various individual and environmental parameters. Even though the most effective method for controlling the internal dose to the Radiation Worker is Source Control, 100% effective methods are either not available or not cost effective. So, when the jobs have to be carried out in a Tritiated environment, the effective use of appropriate PPEs plays a vital role in Internal Dose control.

Hence, Efforts were taken at MAPS to modify the traditional PPEs which were cumbersome into user-friendly versions which will encourage the workers to use the PPEs continually in non-ideal work locations.

Methodology

- *VP Suit with SCBA*- Replaces use of traditional VP Suit hood for short duration in high DACs as it allows unrestricted movement in congested locations such as D₂O recovery and System Opening. It's versatile design allows the workers to comfortably communicate while using it and finish the job in minimum time.
- *Face Hood with flexible air supply hose* – Eliminates fogging inside the hood by circulating air and outside the hood by providing an air curtain. The light flexible hose enable unrestricted movement.
- *Blue Tooth Communication Head Set* – Addresses the challenges faced by personnel

for communicating while wearing a VP Suit Hood/ when the intercom is away from the work location/ when mobile signal is unavailable.

- *Multi-Cartridge Tritium Bottle Respirator* – Ease of change from one bottle to another, allows prolongs duration of usage in low DAC area like dryer jobs in 110'E1 at MAPS. As it is mounted in a backpack like contraption the hindrance caused by hooking the elephant truck to the hip of the worker is removed.
- *Mechanized Decontamination and Flushing of Tritium Bottle Respirators* –Eliminates chances of hold-up tritium in the respirators which can happen during Manual Cleaning
- *Mechanized tritium bottle respirator cartridge spinner*-Helps eliminate excess water from the respirator cartridge before use.
- *Respirator drying facility* -Improved cleanliness of the respirator cartridges and to ensure complete removal of Tritium from respirator sponge
- *Set-up for Cotton squeezing and Complete D₂O recovery* - Reduction in Internal dose consumed due to manual handling of D₂O soaked cotton.

Conclusion

Since these PPEs are used in challenging environments there is always scope to make it more user-friendly. Exposure control is achieved at MAPS as use of these modified PPEs has reduced the time taken for the job and improved the working conditions for the radiation workers.

References

AERB/NF/SM/O-2 (Rev-4) Safety Manual on Radiation Protection for Nuclear Facilities (2005)

INHERENT ^{137}Cs CONTAMINATION IN THE CsI(Tl) CRYSTAL OF PHOSWICH DETECTOR

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Introduction

In vivo monitoring of the radiation workers is carried out inside totally shielded steel room using Phoswich detector with pulse shape discrimination (PSD) to detect internal contamination due to actinides (Nadar et al., 2024). PSD helps in reducing the background in LEP region by rejecting the contribution of high energy photons (HEPs) in NaI(Tl) and improves minimum detectable activity (MDA) of the system for detecting Pu isotopes, ^{241}Am and both natural and enriched uranium in person's body. By analyzing the rejected pulses of digital pulse processing based PSD system (Akar et al., 2023), HEP emitting contaminants can be identified.

During routine monitoring, the spectrum of rejected pulses of a radiation worker showed contamination due to ^{137}Cs despite the worker having no history of exposure to ^{137}Cs . In this study, this anomaly was investigated.

Material and Methods

Phoswich detector: Phoswich is a sandwich of two scintillators, thin NaI(Tl) (3 mm thick) and thick CsI(Tl) (5 cm thick). LEPs of energy < 100 keV are almost absorbed in NaI(Tl). HEPs deposits their maximum energy in CsI(Tl). As the decay times of two detectors are different (Knoll, 2010), pulses of low and HEPs are separated electronically using analog or digital PSD.

HPGE array: An array of three HPGe detectors (70 mm dia. and 2.5 cm thick) was used for measurement of Phoswich detector inside steel room.

Results and Discussion

In this paper, the inherent contamination of ^{137}Cs in the Phoswich detector was quantified using Monte Carlo and experimental methods. Initially steel room walls, bed sheet, detector window were decontaminated to ensure there is no contamination in the steel room due to ^{137}Cs . But spectrum with worker and without worker still showed ^{137}Cs contamination of the

same level. This concluded that ^{137}Cs contaminant must be present inherently in detector. ^{137}Cs has been found in CsI(Tl) crystal in literature (Kim et al., 2005). Therefore, Phoswich detector was measured with HPGe array for 60 hours inside steel room. It showed ^{137}Cs contamination in the detector. The calibration factor (CF) for this geometry is evaluated using Monte Carlo simulation in FLUKA. HPGe array and Phoswich detector were modelled inside steel room by sampling uniformly distributed ^{137}Cs source in CsI(Tl) crystal of Phoswich detector. Using the CF, the ^{137}Cs activity is estimated to be ~ 2 Bq. The MDA of the HPGe array is ~ 0.1 Bq using its 60 hours background in steel room whole body counter.

Conclusion

The investigation revealed that the rejected pulses originated from the ^{137}Cs contamination present in the CsI(Tl) crystal of Phoswich detector itself. The activity of ^{137}Cs present in the 3 mm Phoswich detector was quantified.

References

- M.Y. Nadar, L. Mishra, and I. S. Singh (2024) Handbook on Radiation, Environment. Vol. II.
- D. K. Akar, I. S. Singh, M. Y. Nadar, L. Mishra and P. D. Sawant. (2023) Abstracts of ICMP 2023.
- G. F. Knoll. (2010)
- Kim Y.D. et. al. (2005) Nuclear instruments and methods in physics research A 552.

SIGNIFICANCE OF DOSE ESTIMATION AND RADIOLOGICAL DATA ANALYSIS IN SAFE MANAGEMENT OF HIGH ACTIVE SPENT RESINS

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Introduction

High active resin hoppers from research reactor Spent Fuel Storage Facility are fluidized and immobilized with specific cement matrix in Resin Fixation Facility (RFF) before disposal in suitable engineered modules in the Near Surface Disposal Facility (NSDF). Continuous radiological safety surveillance is important during fluidization, fixation in cement and disposal of product to NSDF. Potential exposure rates at various locations in the plant were estimated before active runs of the facility and the same was re-verified during hot commissioning and actual operations. Radiation safety protocol was chalked down before the hot commissioning of the facility. This paper discusses the radiological safety measures adopted for meeting ALARA objectives during the design, commissioning and operation of RFF.

Material and Methods

Dose estimation on the hopper was carried out assuming two concentrations of 14 Ci and 40 Ci of ¹³⁷Cs per 110 liters of resin hopper and at 500 lpm fluidization liquid flow rate activity in pipe line was assumed as 150 mCi/l and 450 mCi/l respectively. Equipment and transfer lines were modelled as per design and dose rate estimations were carried out using the QAD-CG point kernel code. For validation of the estimated dose and monitoring flow path of resin and radiological protection during active operations, 10 process AGMs were installed at different locations. Two no. of area AGM and two CAMs, one for general area and one at exhaust of resin fixation enclosure after HEPA filter, were provided as radiological safety measures. β - γ contamination monitors were installed before the change room facility. Double shoe barrier was provided before the resin fixation enclosure. Till date about 14 hoppers loaded with activity ranging from 14.4 Ci to 40 Ci ¹³⁷Cs were fluidized and immobilized in the facility.

Results and Discussion

Measured dose rates on contact of fluidization line were ranging from 80-250

mGy/h, which is within 80% accuracy of estimated dose using standard codes. The peak radiation level in the working area was 0.01-0.02 mGy/h which is also in accordance with the estimation. Measured dose rate on resin receiving column, and contact dose on enclosure were also well within the estimated values. Contact dose rate on the cemented waste product prior to disposal was observed to be ranging from 180-500 mGy/h, well within the estimated values. The background near trench after disposal was within acceptable limits for operational NSDF. No measurable air contamination observed in the operating area adjoining the RFF enclosure as well as in the facility exhaust. The average collective dose and maximum individual dose per hopper processing operations were found to be 4.9 person-mSv and 0.25 mSv respectively. This confirmed the adequacy of the shielding of the facility. There was no case of internal or external contamination during the operation of the facility.

Conclusion

Estimation of the dose rate, detailing of radiation protection measures prior to the hot commissioning of RFF facility and detailed radiological data analysis helped in safe operations, meeting ALARA principle.

Acknowledgement

Authors acknowledge contribution of all team members for safe commissioning and operations of the RFF.

References

1. HS&EG, BARC(2018) Internal report on dose estimation of RFF facility, Mumbai.
2. Pancholi K C et al (2018) Challenges and Innovations in Management & Disposal of Radioactive Solid Wastes, Proc. ICRWMD conference, ICRWMD-2018, Mumbai.

PUBLIC OUTREACH PROGRAMS AT KUDANKULAM NUCLEAR POWER PROJECT

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Introduction

The overall public perspective of nuclear power is predicated upon miscellany of perceptions, both positive and negative. When it is beginning to dawn on people that nuclear power is required in the future in the energy mix due to its environmental advantage vis-avis other electricity generating options and alternatives, various misconceptions, which are strong and pervasive, are still prevalent in the public. Among the factors which create nuclear phobia, the fear of radiological hazards, nuclear accidents, long term health effects, environmental aspects, fear of working in nuclear power industries, inability to draw distinction between civilian use and military use, distrust in nuclear community are some major concerns of the public. The public fear over nuclear is deep rooted and historic and derives from a wide spectrum of motivations and persuasive influences. Nuclear power, despite the environmental advantages, is regarded as part of the environmental problem. Following the Fukushima Daiichi accident in Japan in 2011, environmental activism became mainstream, direct and vocal, and pressure groups are being widely recognised as legitimate voices in the environmental debate. It is in that evolving context that the nuclear public outreach and awareness programs have assumed significance to educate the public on the benign nature of nuclear power.

Standardization of Awareness Campaigns

Post Fukushima accident, the public concerns were heightened and the safety of nuclear power plants, long term health effects, cancers, congenital abnormalities, infertility, loss of traditional livelihoods like fishing and agriculture, environmental issues and concerns, biodiversity loss, etc. caught the imagination of the public and were fanned by the ideologically opposed misinformation groups and campaigns. The modest outreach and public communication programs which

were in place till 2011 at Kudankulam Nuclear Power Plant site were galvanized to address and allay the public concerns about nuclear power by restructuring and institutionalizing the outreach programs and intensifying them manifold. The programs were conducted in two distinct modes, onsite and offsite. The onsite mode involves a full day program, with visitors calling on state of the art Nuclear Information Centre (NIC) for a briefing followed by visit to the 3D theatres, light and sound shows and visit to interactive models and quizzing kiosks. Then, the site visit is conducted with visit to various key facilities and dyke area. This visit is open to all the public from all walks of life. The offsite programs are conducted in host's institutes with the officials visiting their premises for an interactive communication session with set up of an exhibition pavilion. During these programs, pamphlets and hand outs are distributed to them.

Conclusion

Till the year 2023, through these robust awareness campaigns, more than 1 million public in the state and neighbouring states were reached out to and about 4 million pamphlets were distributed to the public. Effective public outreach, consistent plant performance, impeccable safety records, minimum personnel exposures, negligible public dose, near zero environmental releases, engineered solutions for effective waste management, capacity building programs for students and professionals, neighbourhood welfare activities and activities under Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) have turned the tide in favour of nuclear power in the region reversing the trends seen in the aftermath of Fukushima.

RADIATION LEVEL IN REACTOR CONTAINMENT BUILDING OF FBTR AFTER A POSTULATED SINGLE PIN FAILURE INCIDENT

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Introduction

In FBTR, a mixture of argon and helium gases is used as Reactor Cover Gas (RCG) during operation. ⁴¹Ar and Fission Product Noble Gases (FPNGs) are present in RCG during operation due to neutron irradiation of argon, tramp fuel and uranium impurities in coolant sodium. There is a possibility of RCG leak to Reactor Containment Building (RCB) through the frozen Liquid Metal seals, which provide the primary barrier between reactor vessel and Rotating Plugs and through the elastomeric seals of various Canal plugs, CRD plug, sampling canal plug etc. The estimated maximum radiation level in RCB during normal operation and after a postulated single pin failure scenario is discussed.

Radiological measurements

The background gamma radiation level at 0 m elevation of RCB is about 10 µGy/h. RCB atmosphere air and particulates are collected every shift and analysed. The mean gas and particulate air activity (Short lived ⁸⁸Rb & ¹³⁸Cs, decay products of ⁸⁸Kr and ¹³⁸Xe) in RCB is 0.16 Bq/m³ and 145 Bq/m³. RCG is sampled at least once in each campaign and analyzed using HPGe detector. The equilibrium RCG activity during reactor power at 30 MWt is 1.52E+04 Bq/m³ with Ar-41 is about 98% and rest are FPNGs. It is deduced that the gas activity concentration of 0.06 Bq/cc gives a radiation field of 1 µGy/h.

Radiation level in RCB after a postulated single pin failure

The estimated RCG FPNG activity in case of a single pin failure based on the previous incident is 1.53E+06 Bq/cc. The concentration of RCG activity and gas activity in RCB at time 't' after the clad rupture incident and dose rate is estimated using the first order exponential decay expressions [Roger, 1998] by considering radioactive decay of FPNGs, RCG leak rate of 4.8 m³/h

and RCB exhaust flow rate of 1300 m³/h. The variation in the specific activity with time after the pin failure incident indicates that the maximum specific activity for ¹³⁸Xe, ⁸⁸Kr and ¹³⁵Xe is observed at 19 min, 115 min and 1186 min respectively after the pin failure incident. The estimated maximum dose rate in RCB at 18 MWt with a leak rate of 1.2 m³/h is 4.05 mSv/h and the contribution from ¹³⁸Xe (t_{1/2}: 14.3 m) is 91 %. The peak specific activity is 21.87 Bq/cc observed at 21 minutes after the pin failure incident. The estimated maximum dose rate in RCB due to FPNGs at 30 MWt with a leak rate of 4.8 m³/h is 23.0 mSv/h. However, with the cocoon blower that gives a reduction factor of 12, the maximum dose rate is about 2 mSv/h.

Conclusions

During normal operation and single pin failure condition, the maximum radiation field in RCB is estimated to be 20 µGy/h and 2 mSv/h respectively at 30 MWt. Personal entries to RCB will be restricted under work permit system and thereby exposures will be controlled.

Reference

Roger L. Wabeke, CRC press, (1998), *Air Contaminants and Industrial Hygiene Ventilation: A Handbook of Practical Calculations, Problems, and Solutions*

RADIOLOGICAL SAFETY UNVEILED: SURVEILLANCE AND EXPOSURE CONTROL IN SPNDS EMPLACEMENT

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Introduction

Self-Powered Neutron Detectors (SPNDs) are critical components in nuclear reactors for measuring neutron flux. These detectors are made from various materials, including cobalt, vanadium, and Inconel, each with distinct radiation emission profiles. Cobalt-based SPNDs, often incorporating ^{60}Co , are highly radioactive and require careful emplacement practices due to their significant gamma radiation emissions. Vanadium and Inconel-based SPNDs, while still radioactive, typically emit lower levels of radiation compared to cobalt. The emplacement of SPNDs involves radiological safety considerations to protect workers, the public, and the environment. Tile holes specially designed storage cavities within waste facilities are commonly used for the secure emplacement of these radioactive materials.

Materials and Methods

The study focused on cobalt, vanadium, and Inconel-based SPNDs that were removed from service in a nuclear reactor. Each type of SPND was first subjected to radiological surveys to assess residual radioactivity. For cobalt-based SPNDs, gamma spectroscopy and portable radiation survey meters were used to measure the gamma radiation emitted by ^{60}Co . Vanadium and Inconel SPNDs were evaluated for neutron capture and residual gamma activity, which were notably lower than those from cobalt-based detectors. Before emplacement, the SPNDs working areas were decontaminated to minimize contamination spread. The detectors were placed in shielded casks to mitigate gamma radiation exposure during transport and emplacement. These containers were then placed in tile hole, a specially designed cavity that provides both physical containment and radiation shielding. Emplacement is carried out remotely using EOT cranes. Post-emplacement, radiation monitoring was performed to confirm that the tile hole was securely sealed and radiation levels remained within safe limits. The tile holes, which are designed to minimize external radiation exposure, were regularly monitored for no streaming or significant increase due to containment integrity failure.

Results

Radiological surveillance during SPND emplacement revealed higher gamma radiation levels from cobalt-based detectors compared to vanadium and Inconel types. To control contamination, decontamination of the work area was performed. Cobalt SPNDs, emitting significant gamma radiation due to ^{60}Co , were disposed of in specially designed tile holes with increased depth and vault thickness. In contrast, vanadium and Inconel SPNDs exhibited minimal residual radiation and were safely disposed of in standard tile holes. A total of 290 cobalt, 217 vanadium, and 153 Inconel SPNDs were emplaced following regulatory guidelines. Personnel dosimetry confirmed worker exposures remained well below permissible limits, with no significant radiation incidents. Radiation levels at the site remained within safe limits, and continuous monitoring verified no streaming or radiation leakage from the sealed tile holes, ensuring compliance with operational safety standards.

Conclusion

The emplacement of cobalt, vanadium, and Inconel-based SPNDs in tile holes is a safe and effective method for managing radioactive waste from neutron detectors. Proper decontamination, remote operation, and use of radiation shielding were crucial in minimizing radiological risks during the emplacement process. The results from this study confirm that, with appropriate safety measures, the emplacement of SPNDs can be performed with minimal radiological hazards to workers and the environment. Continued monitoring and adherence to safety protocols remain essential to ensuring safe emplacement of these detectors.

References

International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), Management of Low and Intermediate Level Radioactive Waste, IAEA Safety Standards, Vienna, Austria, 2003.

STUDY ON THE LEACHING OF RADIOACTIVITY FROM SOIL SAMPLES INTO AQUEOUS SOLUBLE MATRIX

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Introduction

Environmental monitoring is a vital component of the radiation protection programme in any radiological facility. Soil being a part of the environment, needs to be analyzed for its radioactivity content. The radionuclides in the soil are expected to be embedded deep into the matrix, hence accounting for the total activity will require its leaching out into a water soluble matrix. Mechanistically, nitric acid is known to dissolve actinides by forming soluble nitrates. This study is aimed at understanding the leaching phenomenon for analysis of activity content in a contaminated soil sample with induced alpha and beta-gamma activities.

Materials and Methods

The soil sample with induced activity spiked with maximum of 1 kBq of Nat. U was dried to eliminate moisture and crushed into a uniform powder. Known weights of the dried sample were taken in centrifuge tubes and treated with different concentrations of nitric acid upto 6 M. The samples were subjected to ultrasonic agitation for one hour, followed by centrifugation for 15 minutes. The supernatants were separated, and 1 ml aliquots were plancheted and subjected to gross alpha and beta-gamma counting using calibrated ZnS(Ag) and Geiger Müller counters respectively. Their average efficiencies being 25 % and 10 % respectively. Few plancheted samples were further analyzed using alpha and gamma spectrometry for ascertaining the radionuclide incorporated as the induced activity.

Results and Discussion

The study demonstrated that the radioactive soil sample was partially soluble in the varying nitric acid

concentrations. At lower concentrations, the leaching efficiency was limited, likely due to insufficient acid strength to break down the complex matrix. The extraction with water was negligible. As the acid concentration was increased, leaching improved significantly, till 3 M. Beyond this, till 6 M, the leaching of activity into the aqueous medium remained almost constant with a maximum value of 85 % of the spiked activity.

Arguably, the presence of iron oxides, may have consumed some of the acid, thereby, competing with actinides for dissolution. This competition could limit further extraction at higher acid concentrations, as supported by findings in related studies. [Prakash, 2023]

Spectrometric analysis successfully helped in identification of the radionuclide in the leachate.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that the optimal leaching out of radioactivity from soil samples into aqueous medium could be achieved by 3 M nitric acid. This finding is expected to serve as the preliminary step for the assessment of radioactivity in soil samples.

Reference

1. A.D. Prakash *et al.*, (2023) *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, 194(1-3):110102

VARIATION IN SHORT-LIVED AIR ACTIVITY IN A RADIOCHEMICAL LABORATORY: DEPENDENCE ON RELATIVE HUMIDITY AND TEMPERATURE

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Introduction

Air quality monitoring is an integral part of the radiological surveillance programme in any plant or laboratory. A dedicated radiochemical laboratory with once through ventilation system and adequate air changes as per regulatory requirements was considered in this study, which houses several sub-laboratories and deals with the quality control and developmental research with transuranics. The monitoring of airborne activity is done by sampling the ambient air on a Glass Fibre (GF) filter paper and estimating the activity deposited on it, thereafter. The radioactive radon daughters, which are solid particles under ordinary conditions, attach themselves to the atmospheric dust, and being alpha active, they interfere with the detection of alpha particles emitted by the transuranic isotopes. Moreover, the radon progeny concentration is studied to understand seasonal variation (Kumar, 2016). Hence, a facility specific study on the dependence of short lived alpha and associated beta activity concentrations with varying relative humidity (RH) and temperature, for an air conditioned radiochemical laboratory with once through ventilation, was performed for generating a comprehensive database for background correction in air activity measurements.

Materials and Methods

Static air samples were collected daily for a period of one year on GF filter papers. The samples were counted for gross lived α and β activity using ZnS(Ag) and GM counter respectively with average efficiencies of 25% and 10%. The average delay in counting after sampling was 20 minutes. The air samples were counted for duration of 1 min to obtain the gross activities on the filter paper. A delay counting after 3 days confirmed the absence of long lived radioactivity. The RH and

temperature measurements were carried out in representative labs using a sling psychrometer. The monthly averages of the short-lived α and β activities, temperatures and RH, derived from the yearlong exhaustive data collected from different laboratories, were plotted for trend analysis.

Results & Discussions

Both the short lived α and β activity concentrations on the air samples were observed to vary inversely with both RH and temperature. In the winter months i.e. in December and January, when both temperature and RH are at the lowest, the activities are found to be the highest. In addition, in the rainy months i.e. June to September, although the temperature is slightly higher than the average, but the RH is significantly high. In these months, the short-lived activities are observed to be minimum, i.e. about 25% of the maximum. Lower activity in the rainy season may be attributed to the charge neutralisation of radon progenies by the ambient moisture, which renders the solid particulates inefficient in getting airborne.

Conclusion

The analysis of the yearlong data base for season-wise variation of lived α and β activities of short-lived components in daily air samples is expected to serve as an input for background correction during the continuous estimation of transuranic alpha activity in lab air samples for the facility.

Reference

[1] Kumar K.C. *et al*, (2016), *Int. J. Radiat. Res.*; 14(2): 105-111

EVALUATION OF DILUTION FACTORS FOR AIRBORNE RADIOACTIVITY DURING IN-CELL WORKS IN PUREX PROCESS CELLS

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Introduction

This study evaluates the dilution factors of airborne radioactivity during maintenance activities in process cells of the spent nuclear fuel reprocessing facility. These process cells included equipment that were involved in codecontamination and partitioning (Cell-1), various waste evaporation processes (Cell-2), and the partitioning stages of PUREX (Cell-3). During an extended repair shutdown of the facility, the heat exchangers of multiple thermosyphon evaporators were replaced. This involved abrasive operations (cutting, grinding, welding etc.) of highly radioactive process fluid lines. These process fluid lines handled activities of the order of PBq/m³ ($\beta\gamma$) (Srivastava *et. al.* 2024). The objective of this work was to assess the efficiency of ventilation systems and the implications of dilution factors on worker safety during in-cell repair works.

Materials and Methods

Continuous Air Monitors (CAMs) were deployed at two locations within these process cells, specifically near the working area (NWA) and near the cell ventilation duct (NCV), to monitor real-time air activity. The CAMs were connected to the Central Radiation Protection Console (CRPC), allowing for continuous data logging. Since this was not part of the routine monitoring, the sampling time (which was usually only for the period of repair work) was noted when changing the filter papers of these CAMs. The gross α and β activities collected on the filter papers were measured, and along with the sampling time, flow rate and the ALI value of the most limiting radionuclides of interest, the DAC-h (α) and DAC-h (β) were estimated. The minimum detectable activity of this monitoring system was 3×10^{-2} DAC-h (α) and 2×10^{-4} DAC-h (β). In the course of repair, 706 observations were recorded. We estimated the dilution factor (DF_i) for Cell i

as the ratio of DAC-h (α and/or β) near working area to that near cell ventilation as:

$$DF_i = \frac{DAC-h (\alpha \text{ and/or } \beta) NWA}{DAC-h (\alpha \text{ and/or } \beta) NCV}$$

The choice of whether to use DAC-h (α) or DAC-h (β) was based on correlation of between NWA and NCV activities, since while calculating a ratio, we were assuming a linear relationship. For Cell-3 it was the alpha activity, for Cell-1 it was the beta activity and for Cell-2 it was calculated as an average of both alpha and beta activity.

Results

The dilution factors varied across the different cells, because of the differences in process types and ventilation efficiency. Cell-1, associated with co-decontamination and partitioning, had the highest dilution factor of 1.74 ± 0.14 , suggesting that its ventilation system effectively reduced airborne contaminants near the NCV. In contrast, Cell-2, which handled waste evaporation, showed a lower dilution factor of 1.25 ± 0.22 , indicating lesser efficiency in air contaminant dilution.

Conclusion

The study demonstrates that the dilution factors vary significantly across the PUREX process cells, with implications for worker safety. The highest dilution factor observed in the co-decontamination and partitioning cell highlights the need for design ventilation and protection strategies depending on the specific activities and cell functions.

References

Srivastava *et. al.* (2024). *Decontamination of high active process cells in a PHWR spent nuclear fuel reprocessing facility*, in Science and Technology in Nuclear Fuel Cycle, IANCAS Bulletin, March 2024.

EXPERIENCE WITH LORA™ BASED TELEDOSIMETERS FOR DOSE MONITORING AND CONTROL

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Introduction

External individual whole-body dose [Hp(10)] monitoring is an important aspect of occupational radiation safety. For day-to-day dose monitoring and control, secondary devices such as Direct Reading Dosimeters (DRD) and Electronic dosimeters are used. For assessing the external dose received by a radiation worker in performing any specific task, electronic dosimeters are issued prior to entering to radiation area and collected back soon after the worker returns from there. The reading obtained on the dosimeter is taken as the dose received by the worker for the specific job.

One of the main disadvantages of this practice is that often worker spends more time in the radiation area and receive more radiation dose than planned. Often the jobs require more attention and alertness so that the worker becomes less attentive to radiological conditions and dose received during the job. This necessitates additional requirement of supervisory dose monitoring in which another person (often Health Physicist) is assigned to monitor the dose received by the radiation workers. This method also has some drawbacks as (a) additional dose to monitoring person (b) hindrance to the workers as somebody frequently stops the worker to read dosimeter readings. Both the issues contribute significantly to collective dose of the organization.

This paper discusses briefly about design aspects and performance of a system of 5 teledosimeters developed by Health Physics Unit, IREL (India) Limited, Manavalakurichi, under Health Physics Division, BARC. This system uses LoRa™ based Internet of Things (IoT) platform for long distance real-time data communication between dosimeter and HPU server.

Materials and Methods

The system consists of 05 Number of personal electronic dosimeters issued to

radiation workers. It uses Si PIN diode based TEVISO 51 BG radiation detector and internally attached with LoRa™ transmitter to share data with server computer through 865-867,868 MHz ISM band. The pocket dosimeter is incorporated with a 3 dBi internally mounted antenna. It uses a 400 mAh Li-ion battery, charged through type C port. Each dosimeter is fitted with a 1" OLED display for local readout.

The receiver consists of a 13 dBi LoRa™ antenna mounted on top of Health Physics Laboratory. This antenna is common for teledosimeters as well as for 15 No of LoRa™ based Area Gamma Monitors installed at various plant and premise locations.

Cumulative dose [Hp(10)] and current dose rate information is transmitted to HPU server in every 20 second interval. Wireless transmission range of pocket teledosimeters is approximately 1 km and covers entire work locations of IREL Mineral Separation Plant (MSP).

Results

The LoRa™ based Teledosimeters developed by Health Physics Unit are unique and very important tool for external dose monitoring and control. Real-time dose and dose rate information of radiation workers associated with major radioactive jobs are received at HPU server computer. It is evaluated as suitable innovation for entire spectrum of nuclear fuel cycle operations.

References

- (1) Sreekumar K., Jayaram U.K., Mohan, V., & Rajan, S. (2003). Feasibility study of tele dosimetry in personnel monitoring at Madras Atomic Power Station. Radiation Protection and Environment, 26(1-2,pt2), 385-386

STUDY OF CORROSION PRODUCTS, CONTROL MEASURES AND RADIATION SAFETY AT KAIGA GENERATING STATION-3&4

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Key words: Primary Heat Transport System, Biennial Shutdown, radiation field, isotopic composition, Specific Gamma Ray Emission Constant

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Introduction

Activated corrosion products are generated in the Primary Heat Transport (PHT) System of Pressurized Heavy Water Reactors (PHWRs) due to continuous interaction of coolant water with metallic elements present in the alloys of piping and feeders. The main structural materials in the PHT system are, low carbon steel (SA 106 Gr.B) as the piping material, Incoloy 800 as the Steam Generator (SG) material and Zr-2.5% Nb / Zircoloy as the coolant channel/fuel cladding material. These structural materials become corroded and cause CRUD (activated corrosion products). The CRUD is having radioactive composition of activated corrosion products namely ⁵¹Cr, ⁵⁹Fe, ⁶⁰Co, ⁹⁵Zr and ⁹⁵Nb which are beta and gamma emitters. CRUD deposition leads to elevated radiation field on PHT system equipment mainly in SGs. During reactor Biennial Shutdown (BSD) campaign, SGs manhole covers are opened for In Service Inspection (ISI) jobs. Then the accumulated CRUD is having potential for external and internal exposure. The nuclear industry has the mandate to keep the radiation exposures “As low As Reasonably Achievable (ALARA)”. And also corrosion of the reactor coolant system is of concern as it is a detrimental to the system. So all efforts are made to keep the corrosion minimum by maintaining good chemistry and optimized PHT purification system.

Materials and methods

At KGS-3&4, SGs are subjected to ISI as per the station Quality Assurance (QA) policy by Eddy Current Testing (ECT). For ISI, SG hot leg and cold leg manhole covers are opened. Before start of ECT, chemical decontamination and thorough radiation field monitoring is carried out. Radiation field is measured with Teletectors (Automess make, 6112M). Radiation field measured is used for job planning to keep the exposures ALARA. All radiation workers are made aware of the existing radiological conditions and are trained to follow the radiation protection procedures in the mockup facility. During ECT of SG, probe is inserted in each tube and the CRUD accumulated inside the tubes gets detached and is collected with proper arrangements to avoid spread of radioactive contamination. To check the isotopic composition, the collected CRUD is

subjected to qualitative analysis by HPGe based gamma spectrometer. To assess the contamination levels, the smear samples collected from the SG inside surfaces are counted in Geiger Muller Counting System. Based on the radiation field and contamination levels, adequate Personal Protective Equipment (PPEs) are used while executing the job. The records of dose, radiation field, contamination levels and isotopic composition are maintained and trending is carried out.

Results and discussions

Trending of radiation field of KGS-3 and KGS-4 is carried out. During 2011 BSD campaign of KGS-3, radiation field in SGs hot legs and cold legs was in the range of 8-10 mSv/h and 10-15 mSv/h respectively. In the consequent BSDs, it was in the range of 2.0-3.0 mSv/h and 2.5-4.5 mSv/h. Higher radiation field during 2011 BSD campaign of KGS-3 is attributed to longer duration (4 years) of operation after synchronization. During 2013 BSD campaign of KGS-4, radiation field in SGs hot legs and cold legs was in the range of 1.5-2.0 mSv/h and 2.0-4.0 mSv/h and the same trend is maintained in the consequent BSDs. Qualitative analysis of CRUD samples from KGS-3 and KGS-4 indicated presence of ⁵⁹Fe, ⁶⁰Co, ⁹⁵Zr and ⁹⁵Nb. Higher radiation field in KGS-3 SGs as compared to KGS-4 SGs is due to higher composition of ⁶⁰Co whose Specific Gamma Ray emission Constant is higher.

Conclusion

Over the years, radiation field in SGs of KGS-3 and KGS-4 is maintained steady due to good chemistry control and optimized PHT purification. Effective radiation protection program of KGS-3&4 is helping to keep the radiation exposures ALARA during ISI of SGs.

References

1. Lucia Bonavigo and Mario De Salve (2011) “Issues for Nuclear Power Plants Steam Generators”
2. Moez Benfarah, Meddy Zouiter, Thomas Jobert, Frederic Dacquait, Marie Bultot and Jean-Baptiste Genin (2016) “PWR circuit contamination assessment tool. Use of OSCAR code for engineering studies at EDF”

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON AEROSOL TRANSPORT AND TEMPORAL EVOLUTION IN A MECHANICALLY VENTILATED CHAMBER

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Introduction

In the nuclear facilities, radioactive aerosols are generated during various operation and maintenance activities. Ventilation plays a critical role as an engineering safety feature to control airborne radioactive contamination. From a design optimization perspective, understanding aerosol transport behavior is essential. The effectiveness of ventilation is governed by complex aerosol transport mechanisms such as diffusion, settling, re-suspension, and coagulation. Although numerous numerical models addressing aerosol transport are reported in the literature, experimental data for their validation remain limited. To address this gap, an Aerosol and Ventilation Test Facility (AVTF) is developed at WIP Trombay. This facility aims to study aerosol transport characteristics in ventilated environments and provide data for validating numerical models used in ventilation design.

Material and Methods

The AVTF is a 2 m × 1.5 m × 1.5 m a stainless steel chamber, equipped with an exhaust blower, thermal mass flow rate meter, and a variable frequency drive to controls the ventilation rate. HEPA filters are installed at both the inlet and outlet of the chamber. Solid NaCl aerosols are generated using a TOPAS aerosol generator, while liquid aerosols are produced using an ATI aerosol generator. Size distribution measurements are conducted using a GRIMM aerosol spectrometer.

Results and discussion

In the present study, DOP aerosols are generated and introduced into the chamber continuously for 3 hours at a flow rate of 5.5 LPM through a 150-mm-long, 50-mm-diameter stainless steel pipe. Aerosol size distribution and total number concentration are measured at the injection port and at three sampling ports located 0.5 m, 1 m, and 1.5 m downstream of

the injection port simultaneously. Measurements are conducted under varying ventilation rates ranging from 20 m³/h to 80 m³/h. This provides, Number of Air Change from 4 to 18, normally used in nuclear laboratory and plants. At the injection port, aerosol number concentration initially increases with time, reaches a peak within 3 minutes, and then decreases at a slow rate. The peak occurrence is unaffected by the ventilation rate. Similar peaking behavior is observed inside the chamber; however, the time to peak occurrence decreases with increasing ventilation rates. These observations align with the studies by Seipenbusch et al. (2008) and Anand et al. (2012), which attribute this behavior to heterogeneous coagulation. Additionally, peak aerosol concentrations at the first sampling port are higher than those at the second and third ports for all ventilation rates.

Conclusions

The temporal evolution of aerosol number concentration exhibit a peaking effect both at the injection port and inside the chamber. A negative correlation is observed between the time to peak occurrence and ventilation rate within the chamber. Further experiments are planned to investigate the influence of aerosol concentration on evolution and mixing behavior within the chamber.

Reference

- Seipenbusch et al. (2008) *Ann. Occup. Hyg.* 52, 707–716.
Anand S., et al. (2012) *J. Aerosol Sci.* 52:18–32.

A STUDY OF ^{14}C GENERATION IN HEMATITE CONCRETE FOR NPP DECOMMISSIONING

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Introduction

In decommissioning of nuclear power plants (NPPs), radionuclide characterization is the first step where, activity of various radionuclides produced by neutron activation in core structural components and shield materials needs to be estimated. ^{14}C , a pure beta-emitter with a half-life of 5730 y, is produced in various in-core and out of core reactor components and is an important long-lived radionuclide to be considered in NPP decommissioning. It is mainly produced by neutron activation of stable isotopes of ^{13}C , ^{14}N and ^{17}O . Hematite concrete is a shielding material used in nuclear reactors for providing shielding against neutrons and gamma radiations. In Pressurised Heavy Water Reactors (PHWRs) the calandria vault walls, roof, floor, and hatches are made from hematite concrete. Although the neutron flux reaching hematite concrete would be much lower than the flux seen by in-core components, neutron activation of inner part of the biological shield concrete can take place leading to the formation of long-lived radionuclides like ^{14}C . This paper presents a study of ^{14}C generation in hematite concrete used in reactor shielding.

Materials and Methods

The study involves determination of composition of elements in hematite concrete followed by theoretical estimation of ^{14}C activity generated due to neutron activation. Hematite concrete is obtained by adding hematite (iron ore) to the concrete mix. Iron ore is added in the form of coarse and fine aggregates along with water and cement. Hematite concrete comprises of major elements and trace elements. This study focusses on quantification of C, N and O which contribute to ^{14}C formation. Combining the data of densities and composition of coarse and fine aggregates and Portland cement, composition of oxygen was theoretically estimated. Carbon content was determined by analysis of hematite concrete samples obtained from two NPP sites using a carbon analyser. A value of 300 ppm

(Hou, 2005) has been used for nitrogen content. To study the buildup and decay of ^{14}C , computations were performed with ORIGEN2 code (Croff, A. G., 1983) using a typical thermal neutron flux of 1×10^{10} neutrons/cm²/s for two irradiation periods of 40y and 60y (considering bulk uniform irradiation). Activity of ^{14}C was estimated at the end of decay period of 50 years (deferred dismantling period).

Results

The weight percentage of O, C, and N in hematite concrete is 33.3, 0.72 and 0.03, respectively. With regards to ^{14}C radioactivity formed in hematite concrete, contribution of $^{14}\text{N}(n,p)^{14}\text{C}$ reaction is highest (97.5%) as compared to the $^{17}\text{O}(n,\gamma)^{14}\text{C}$ (2.45%) and $^{13}\text{C}(n,\gamma)^{14}\text{C}$ (0.008%) reactions. This can be attributed to higher cross section and abundance of ^{14}N among the N isotopes. Activity of ^{14}C in 1 kg of hematite concrete is estimated as 6.81×10^5 Bq and 1.02×10^6 Bq at the end of 40y and 60y irradiation, respectively. After a decay period of 50 years the activity of ^{14}C marginally reduces to 6.77×10^5 Bq (40y) and 1.01×10^6 Bq (60y). It is estimated that hematite concrete seeing a flux less than 1.43×10^7 neutrons/cm²/s will have activity levels of ^{14}C less than the AERB clearance level for ^{14}C (1 Bq/g).

Conclusion

Activity of ^{14}C in hematite concrete due to neutron activation has been theoretically estimated. Results of the study provide important inputs for waste characterization and decommissioning planning for NPPs.

References

- Hou, X. (2005). *Applied Radiation and Isotopes*, 62(6), 871-882.
- Croff, A. G. (1983). *Nuclear Technology*, 62(3), 335-352.

DEMONSTRATION OF SAFETY AGAINST SPATIAL PERTUBATIONS IN PFBR THROUGH EIGEN VALUE SEPERATION

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Introduction

Beyond design basis events in fast breeder reactors such as hypothetical core disruptive accidents can lead to inadvertent radioactivity release to the public. Even though such events are of very low probability, safety of the reactor should be adequately demonstrated. One of the parameters determining the stability of the reactor against spatial oscillations caused by any external perturbation is the eigen value separation. This quantity is a measure of the gap between the fundamental mode and the next higher harmonic mode of neutron flux in a reactor. The larger the separation, more stable will be the reactor to spatial perturbations. The eigen value separation of Prototype Fast Breeder Reactor (PFBR) is estimated in this study. Various higher harmonic modes such as azimuthal, radial and axial modes are also estimated and visualised.

Methodology

For estimating the higher harmonics and eigen value separation, an indigenous diffusion code named MDS-3D [Arun Stanley (2024)] is used. MDS-3D is a 3 dimensional multi-group neutron diffusion equation solver which uses finite difference formalism in triangular/hexagonal geometry. The code was benchmarked with three studies: SNR-300-A1, SNR-300-A6 & AER-FCM-002. The power iteration method used in MDS-3D gives the dominant eigen mode (known as fundamental mode). Steady state neutron flux shape will follow the fundamental mode. However, under perturbations, the flux shape can become a linear combination of fundamental and higher harmonic modes. The eigen values of the higher harmonic modes will decide the rate of decay of these modes and the time taken to stabilise the reactor to its original state.

For obtaining the higher harmonics, the deflation method is used in MDS-3D. This method involves the sequential subtraction of

lower harmonics from the original matrix to obtain higher harmonics. For the current study on PFBR, ABBN-93 nuclear data library is used to obtain the cross section data in 26 energy groups.

Results

The eigen value separation of PFBR core was estimated to be 10065 pcm. This can be considered as a large separation since the corresponding value for a typical PHWR-500 core [Obaidurrahman (2010)] is about 1500 pcm and for Chernobyl reactor it is about 196 pcm only [Hashimoto (1994)]. This along with the fact that the prompt neutron lifetime in fast reactors are of the order of 10^{-6} s implies that the higher harmonics will decay very fast. Additionally, five subsequent higher harmonics of PFBR were also identified.

Conclusion

The eigen value separation and higher harmonics of PFBR were estimated. The initial four harmonic modes were found to be azimuthal modes. Two subsequent modes were found to be radial and axial modes respectively. The estimated large value of eigen value separation in PFBR indicates the strong neutronic coupling of the core and its stability against spatial oscillations and other perturbations.

References

- Arun Stanley et al (2024), IGCAR internal report -PFBR/01113/DN/1113.
- K. Obaidurrahman and Om Pal Singh (2010), Nucl. Eng. Design 240 p 2755-2760.
- K. Hashimoto et al (1994), Ann. Nucl. Energy 21(4) p 211-217.

USAGE OF DIFFERENT TYPES OF SHIELD PLUGS FOR SHIELDING OF RETAINED PORTIONS OF REACTOR RECIRCULATION LOOP OPENING

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Introduction

Tarapur Atomic Power Station-1&2 (TAPS-1&2), India's first nuclear power reactor, has played a significant role over the past five decades in advancing the country's nuclear energy program. TAPS-1&2 comprises two Boiling Water Reactors (BWRs), each equipped with reactor recirculation system that forces the primary coolant to circulate. This system enhances heat transfer and mitigates power density limitations. There are two recirculation loops in each reactor. To minimize the build up of fission and activation products on recirculation loop piping and maintains good chemistry control, reactor clean up system takes water from primary system, purifies it and delivers back to the primary system. Despite these measures, a small amount of radionuclides may still deposit on the internal surfaces, leading to radioactivity build up Biological shield around RPV and concrete shield around drywell provide sufficient shielding during unit operating condition.

Material and methods

Indications of Intergranular Stress Corrosion Cracking (IGSCC) were observed on a weld joint in the TAPS-1 reactor recirculation loop-A during ISI. As a result, the station has initiated the replacement of both reactor recirculation loops, originally made of SS-316, with IGSCC-resistant SS-316LN material^[6]. After cutting of reactor recirculation pipes the retained components and its openings was a source of high beaming radiation levels resulting into increase in ambient radiation levels of the area. Given that this was a first-of-its-kind, high-dose activity, significant efforts were undertaken to minimize the Collective Radiation Exposure including shielding of various components.

ALARA efforts

This paper describes the ALARA measures such as shielding and ALARA tools implemented after the cutting of reactor recirculation loop especially the use of various special shield plugs arrangements, their material composition and specific locations, to reduce the beaming radiation from retained components. Retained components are Reactor Pressure Vessel(RPV) inlet outlet nozzles, Secondary Steam Generator(SSG)

nozzles, reactor recirculation pump and MOV openings. Being highly dose intensive and first of its kind activity considerable efforts were put to minimize the radiological impact during recirculation loop cutting, handling of removed spools and its disposal. The information in this paper deals with how different types of shield plugs such as combination of different materials (Lead, Aluminium and Iron) were used for shielding of retained portions of reactor recirculation pipe⁴. The location in which they were used and engineering modifications for facilitating remote visual inspection. The primary goal of health physics in such tasks is to minimize both beaming radiation levels and ambient radiation levels in surrounding areas. The improvement in type of shield as per requirement results in reduction of ambient radiation levels and radiation levels in vicinity for edge preparation. This resulted in reducing beaming radiation level at opening of retained portion. This reduction in radiation level eliminates the chances of inadvertent exposure of working person in the area. ALARA measures^[5] such as shield plugs, remote/long handled tools, walkie-talkie, closed circuit TV, enhanced visual testing of reactor internals, proper contamination control were implemented during work near retained components, There were no cases exposure exceeding investigation levels and personal contamination due to implementation of these measures.

Conclusion

Design, development and usage of special shield plugs has provided confidence in the safe execution of tasks, with no radiologically significant incidents reported.

References

- 1) Radiation protection procedures Manual for Tarapur Atomis Power Station 1&2 Rev.1.0^[5]
- 2) Tender document for replacement of recirculation line of TAPS 1&2 TMS/CTC/TSS-1&2/2022/2468^[6]

ALARA PRACTICES EMPLOYED AT TAPS 1&2 DURING REACTOR RECIRCULATION LOOP REPLACEMENT ACTIVITIES

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Introduction

Tarapur Atomic Power Station-1&2 (TAPS-1&2), India's first nuclear power reactor, has played a significant role in the development and success of the country's nuclear energy program over five decades. Each reactor has two recirculation loops. During In-Service Inspection, indications of Intergranular Stress Corrosion Cracking (IGSCC) were observed at one of the weld joints in the recirculation loop-A of the TAPS-1 reactor. Accordingly Station has planned to replace both reactor recirculation loops, originally made of SS-316, with SS-316LN, a material resistant to IGSCC.

Materials and Methods

This replacement work is first of its kind and involves high-dose environments, requiring the development and implementation of various ALARA tools and techniques. To minimize the radiological impact, various ALARA practices were designed and employed during the execution of the job.

ALARA Efforts: Several ALARA practices were adopted during the reactor recirculation piping replacement which contributed in significant reduction in station collective radiation exposure.

Radiation Shielding^[5]: Specially designed shield plugs with multiple shielding material were used at nozzle openings of retained components to reduce beam radiation fields. Use of Long-Handled Tools: Innovative, need based and customised long-handled tools were deployed for the job. Mockup facility: Mockup facilities for major activities i.e. cutting, disposal, installation etc. were deployed.

Remote Monitoring^[6]: Remote monitoring including CCTV system for continuous monitoring were installed. Work Conditions: Works were performed with optimized conditions which includes, water shielding, control over parallel works, ventilation etc. Waste disposal: Immediate waste collection, segregation and disposal after appropriate packing including removed piping. Modular Scaffolding: Modular scaffolds were utilised in high-radiation areas⁴. Continuous Dose Monitoring: Regular Health Physics coverage during the job which includes rotation of workforce, dose balance checking⁴ etc. were adopted. Decontamination: Mechanical

decontamination was attempted for the recirculation piping.

Internal Contamination Control:

Ventilation Systems^[6]: Local ventilation systems with pre and HEPA filters were installed in both units to minimize airborne contamination³. Cutting and Grinding Activities: Enclosures with dedicated exhaust systems were set up during cutting and grinding operations to contain and remove airborne contaminants. Steaming: Steaming of internal piping surfaces helped to reduce the generation of airborne contaminants. Personal Protective Equipment: Fresh airline respirators were provided to workers involved in cutting and grinding activities. Continuous Monitoring: Continuous air monitoring for alpha and beta-gamma Air borne activity was conducted in the work area. Contamination Checks: Personal contamination checks were performed at the end of each work session, with additional lung counting and nasal swabs to assess internal doses to workers. Quick scan type, Whole Body Counting System: Pre-whole body counting and on sample base checking during the work helped in controlling the internal exposure and time. Step off pad stations: Local step off pads were installed to control spread of contamination. Housekeeping: Intermittent housekeeping of work area with vacuum cleaner helped in maintain good radiological conditions.

Conclusion

The implementation of job specific ALARA practices during the replacement of the reactor recirculation loops had successfully minimized both internal and external radiation exposures. The effective management of radiological protection, including the use of shielding, remote monitoring and contamination control measures, has ensured the safety of personnel and the smooth progress of the project.

References

- 1..Radiation Protection Procedures Manual RPP/TAPS 1&2/Revision-10^[4]
- 2.Tender for replacement of Reactor Recirculation line replacement^[5].
- 3.Commissioning report of TAPS 1&2 for ventilation system^[6].

HEALTH PHYSICS OPERATING EXPERIENCE IN WASTE HANDLING DURING RECIRCULATION LOOP REPLACEMENT WORKS AT TAPS 1 & 2

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Introduction

Tarapur Atomic Power Station-1&2 (TAPS-1&2), India's first nuclear power station houses twin units of BWR. Each unit consists of two reactor recirculation loops. After observing indications of Inter Granular Stress Corrosion Cracking (IGSCC) on the loop weld joint at TAPS-1, inspections of other weld joints were carried out based on which station decided to replace both the reactor recirculation loops with IGSCC resistant material. It is observed that during reactor operation, the contaminants (activation and fission products from coolant) get deposited at the inner surface of the recirculation loop. Presence of this contamination resulted in an elevated radiation levels on these loops. Cut pieces of recirculation loops were disposed to Near Surface Disposal Facility (NSDF) complying the regulatory requirements⁴. Being a first of its kind activity and high dose intensive job, many efforts were implemented to minimize the radiological impact during disposal works. This paper outlines the health physics operating experiences during waste handling of cut recirculation line spools during Class-I piping replacement at TAPS-1&2.

Materials and Methods

Prior to taking up waste disposal activity, to enhance the accessibility and ease of material handling dedicated platform was erected at RB 125' el. Mock up of the material handling was demonstrated at actual work location. As per the recommendations suggested by the station, rigging plans and procedures were finalized and recirculation loop segments were cut into small pieces. Radiological status mapping of cut spool was carried out. Smear samples from internal surface of pipe piece were taken for β γ and α activity estimation. Spectroscopic analysis of collected smear samples was carried out using HPGe gamma spectrometer. Activity estimations were carried out using ACTDOR code developed

by HPD, BARC. It was decided to put end cap on recirculation loop pipe pieces of 24.75" dia. before putting inside shielded MS box/flask, such that radiation levels on external surface of box did not exceed 2.00 mSv/h. Trailer used for shipment was covered with PVC sheet. After usage the PVC sheets were disposed off as active waste.

Results

It is seen that all the waste consignment fall under B₂A₁ category⁴, which is at par with the category estimation during the calculations performed for authorization purpose. Volume of the box was utilized by filling it with assorted waste generated during the job. Usage of specially designed MS flasks for disposing straight cylindrical pipe pieces instead of MS boxes resulted in significant reduction of waste volume. Actual volume disposed was only 78% of the total authorized volume. There were no cases of exposure exceeding investigation levels, internal contamination and personal contamination during the waste handling work.

Conclusion

Reactor recirculation line cutting job was first of this kind, having high radiation levels and the safe disposal of removed pipe pieces at NSDF was a challenging task. Quantitative assessment of waste generated and regulatory compliance to transportation was successfully accomplished through procedures. The activity and volume discharges were within the limits authorized by the regulatory body.

References

1. AERB safety guide on Regulatory control of radioactive discharges to the environment and disposal of the solid waste AERB/NRF/SG/RW-1.page 9^[4].

QUANTIFICATION OF RADIOACTIVITY AND ITS CORRELATION WITH SURFACE DOSE RATE OF WASTE DRUMS CONTAINING EXHAUSTED MIXED BED RESIN FROM THE PCW PURIFICATION SYSTEM OF A RESEARCH REACTOR

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Introduction

In swimming pool type of research reactor, the Primary Heat Transport (PHT) system consists of delay tank, PCW (Primary Coolant Water) purification system and heat exchangers. Light water is used as a moderator and coolant.

Mixed Bed Ion exchange resin is used for purification of Primary Coolant System. After service period of resin, it is disposed as solid radioactive waste based on surface dose rate and radioactivity contained in it. During this study, resin samples were analysed in HPGe spectrometry system for identification of radio nuclide and Monte Carlo method was used to estimate the surface dose rate on radioactive waste packages. These simulations will be used in estimating dose rate and determining correlation factor with radioactivity inside waste drum, based on which categorization for the waste can be done (BSC Safety Manual; 2020).

Materials and Methods

The resin sample was collected from the mixed bed ion exchange after approximately three months of isolation from the reactor's purification system. The resin contains multiple radionuclides with different gamma energies thus for the estimation of radioactivity and identification of radioisotopes, gamma spectrometry of the sample was carried out using High Purity Germanium (HPGe) based detector system.

After identification of radioisotopes and quantification of radioactivity, Monte Carlo based simulation was used for the modelling of radioactive waste drum containing ion exchange resin removed from primary coolant water system. The result of simulation was compared with the actual measurement using radiation survey meter.

The assumptions/inputs for the simulation were; (i) Radioactive waste drum height 90cm, diameter 28cm and thickness 0.3cm.(ii)Resin weight: 100kg with density of 1.2g/cc.(iii)Carbon steel drum with density 7.860g/cc.(iv)The space

between the resin particles is negligible compared to the total volume of resin.

Results

The gamma spectrometry of the sample showed the presence of Cs-137, Ce144, Pr-144, Nb-95 etc. as the major gamma emitting radionuclides contributing approximately 83 % of the total radioactivity. Some short lived isotopes (e.g. Na-24) were not observed due to delay of three months in sample collection. The total radioactivity measured using HPGe detector was found to be 2.58 kBq/g.

Based on the measured radioactivity and radionuclides involved, the dose rates were calculated at four points around the radioactive waste drum containing 100Kg of resin. The calculated radiation dose rate at locations; Top of drum, side of the drum, bottom of the drum and 1m away from the drum, was 3.5 μ Sv/h, 200 μ Sv/h, 223 μ Sv/h and 7.4 μ Sv/h respectively. The maximum measured surface dose on the contact of actual drum containing exhausted resin was found to be 300 μ Sv/h.

Conclusion

The gamma spectrometry of the samples showed that Cs-137, Ce-144 and Pr-144 contributes approx. 75% of the total activity in the resin. The variation in calculated and measured dose rate is observed because of the assumptions made for the calculation; that the resin material inside drum is homogeneously distributed. Based on the results, the correlation factor for radioactive waste drum radioactivity to the surface dose rate is 11.5 kBq/g/mSv/h. Based upon results the resin used for the study has been disposed as category 1 solid radioactive waste.

References

Radiation Protection Manual for BARC Facilities; BSC/SM/2020/3 Rev.-0

HEALTH PHYSICS EXPERIENCE DURING IN-SERVICE INSPECTION OF WASTE VAULT AT CORAL

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Introduction

Reprocessing of spent fuel from Fast Breeder Test Reactor (FBTR) is being carried out in CORAL (COmpact Reprocessing of Advanced fuels in Lead cells) facility, situated at Indira Gandhi Centre for Atomic Research (IGCAR). Irradiated FBTR fuel pins of burn-ups ranging from 25 to 155 GWd/t have been successfully reprocessed at CORAL. The liquid waste such as raffinate solution, organic wastes, scrubber solutions etc. generated since the commissioning of the plant is kept in the Waste vault tanks as interim storage. All the tanks in the waste vault are located underground and only the auxiliary facility exists above the ground level. The In Service Inspection (ISI) of the waste vault tanks were carried once in five years, as a regulatory mandate. During ISI, visual inspection is carried out to determine the integrity of tanks, degradation of piping and presence of foreign materials. A remote control operated vehicle is used for the inspection due to the presence of very high radiation levels. This paper describes the experience gained during radiological surveillance of the ISI process.

Material and Methods

A temporary safety barrier was erected along the sides of the located man hole at waste vault ground level. The man hole is closed with six MS blocks which act as shielding from high radiation levels. The inspection of the high active storage tanks, equipment and other components inside the WTF was carried out using robotic Pan-tilt-zoom (PTZ) camera attached with a remote controlled vehicle and operated at waste vault ground level. The ISI vehicle was inserted through the plug of seventh MS shield and the inspection was completed using a controller remotely. Total of 18 persons were involved in this inspection. PPEs used by the workers were Lead coat, Half face mask, Lab coat, Hand gloves and shoe covers. TLD and Electronic Pocket Dosimeter (EPD) were

given to all workers for personal monitoring. An EPD was also fixed with the vehicle to get the cumulative dose received by the vehicle.

Results

The radiation levels over the shielding blocks was 3 μ Gy/h and no change was observed upto removal of first four layers of MS blocks. After removal of fifth and sixth layer, the radiation level increased to 20 μ Gy/h and 60 mGy/h respectively. The dose rate near safety barrier varied between 200 – 300 μ Gy/h. An EPD was kept at underground at a depth of 6 meters for 2 minutes, the dose on the EPD was found to be 43.43 mGy and the maximum dose rate recorded was 1.58 Gy/h. Dose measured on the EPD attached with the vehicle was 619.4 mGy. No long lived activity was detected in the air samples taken during removal of the shielding and during the job.

Conclusion

ISI of waste vault was successfully completed with all high active tanks integrity and degradation of pipings were found to be satisfactory. Total collective dose received for the work was 6.29 PmSv. Maximum individual dose was 1.74 mSv received by operational personnel. The collective dose for the entire operation was 70 % of the estimated dose budget which was possible because of proper planning, ALARA discussions, effective coordination among the agencies involved, continuous supervision and strictly adhering to RPP and HP practices.

PRELIMINARY INVESTIGATION OF THE TRANSDERMAL PENETRATION OF RUTHENIUM-106 CHLORIDE

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Keywords: transdermal penetration, Ru-106, pig ear skin.

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Introduction:

Radioactive contamination of skin is an accidental occurrence that has high probability in radiological facilities. In such cases, information about their transdermal penetration is essential to devise strategies to minimise the resulting exposures. Such data is available for a limited number of radionuclides^[1,2]. In the present work, an attempt has been made to study the transdermal potential of ¹⁰⁶RuCl₃ which is used for the fabrication of ¹⁰⁶Ru plaque.

Materials and Methods:

Pig ears were collected immediately after sacrifice in PBS medium and transported to the laboratory where the skin was excised and stored in PBS at -4°C. Prior to experimentation, the samples were allowed to thaw and then placed on a Franz Diffusion cell with PBS as the receptor compartment (RC) fluid whose temperature was maintained at 37°C using a circulating water bath. 25 µL of the contaminant containing the ~3.5kBq of ¹⁰⁶RuCl₃ was loaded on the epidermal side of the skin surface. A Teflon ring and glass disc was clamped over the skin to prevent drying of the skin surface. 1 mL aliquots of the RC fluid were withdrawn at intervals of 1 h starting from the moment the contaminant was loaded. These were dried on a planchette and counted using a low background GM based beta counter. After 8 h, the skin samples were removed, rinsed with distilled water and digested in 8 M HNO₃. This solution was filtered and its activity was estimated using the same method employed for the RC aliquots.

Results:

The fraction of applied activity in the RC fluid was found to be 1.39±0.41%, and that in the skin was 53.84±2.48%. The initial breakthrough of activity is observed after a lag time of 1-1.5 h and is followed by a steady increase in the amount of activity

transferred to the RC. The increase in activity concentration in the RC continues up to 5 to 6 h subsequent to which it reaches a saturation value. The lag time observed may be due to the build-up of activity in the skin layers. Alternatively, it may be the time taken for the radionuclide to diffuse across the skin layers. After this the second phase involves a rapid increase in RC activity, during which a continuous transfer of the radionuclide takes place across the skin to the RC fluid. The third phase, in which a saturation of the activity concentration is observed, has been confirmed by additional experiments in which the activity concentration has been measured 24 h post-contamination. The mechanism of this tendency of pig ear skin to prevent further transportation of the radionuclide beyond certain time needs further investigation.

Conclusion:

Preliminary experiments carried out on ¹⁰⁶RuCl₃ using the pig ear skin model indicate penetration of the radionuclide across intact skin is possible and some data regarding the kinetics and extent of penetration have been obtained during the present study. These can prove useful when planning decontamination strategies as well as assessing doses due to accidental contamination.

References

1. Bolzinger M.A., Bolot C., Galy G., Chabanel A., Pelletier J., Briancon S. (2010) *Int. J. Pharm.* **402**: 44-49.
2. Kassai Z., Koprda V., Harangozo M (1999) *J. Radioanal. Nucl. Chem.* **242**(2): 561-563.

URANIUM MOBILITY FROM MILL TAILINGS UNDER ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS

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Keywords: Uranium, mill tailings, rainfall, batch leaching, contact time
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Introduction:

Processing low-grade uranium ore generates substantial solid waste, termed uranium mill tailings (UMT). At Jaduguda, the acid leach method is used for uranium extraction, leaving residual uranium in the tailings. Coarse fractions are used as mine backfill, while finer fractions are stored in engineered tailings ponds (TP). Environmental factors like rainfall can dissolve residual uranium, posing migration risks. A study conducted on UMT in china revealed that pH, contact time, liquid-solid ratio, and particle size were found to significantly influence the mechanism and extent of uranium release from minerals to water (Liu et al 2017). This study focuses on uranium release and migration from UMT under environmental conditions, emphasizing seasonal rainfall's role.

Materials and Methods:

The study was conducted in a 30-hectare segment (3rd stage, non operational) of Jaduguda's (TP). Samples were collected at a depth of 20 cm, spaced 300 m apart. Samples were ground, sieved, and acid digested MW digestion system. Rainwater samples were collected during the pre-monsoon (PMS) and monsoon (MS) seasons, with parameters such as pH, electrical conductivity (EC), redox potential (Eh) recorded. Uranium content was analyzed using a UV-fluorometer (ECIL make for tailings samples) and an LED-fluorimeter (Quantalase make for water/leachate samples). Quality control was ensured using reference material Till-1 (soil-based), achieving up to 86% recovery at a 95% confidence level. A leaching test was performed to simulate uranium migration, considering factors such as pH, ionic strength, and contact time.

Results:

Rainwater's pH differed significantly, being acidic during PMS (pH=5.0) and neutral-to-basic during MS (pH=8.1). PMS Rainwater's higher ionic strength influenced uranium leaching. Contact time's effect on uranium release revealed three phases: **Initial Phase (0 hours)**: Rapid uranium release due to dissolution of soluble minerals. **Intermediate Phase (0.5-6 hours)**: Slower as uranium adsorbs onto mineral surfaces release. **Final Phase (9-18 hours)**: Steady release due to diffusion from internal tailing matrices. Maximum uranium release under batch leaching conditions reached 3.5% of total uranium content in the bulk sample (70 mg Kg⁻¹). PMS Rainwater's low pH and high ionic strength enhance uranium leaching compared to MS. Contact time also plays a significant role, with prolonged exposure enabling diffusion processes.

Conclusion:

Uranium migration from UMT is influenced by seasonal rainwater chemistry and contact time. The maximum leach fraction is impossible to achieve under normal environmental conditions due to the absence of prolonged contact and agitation. Additionally, the liner beneath the tailings serves as a barrier, as confirmed by routine monitoring of nearby subsurface aquatic environment.

Reference:

Liu B., Peng T., Sun H, Yue H. (2017) Journal of environmental radioactivity 171, 160-168.

EVALUATION OF DETECTOR POSITION AND ALARM SET POINT FOR OFF-GAS HEPA FILTER REPLACEMENT

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Keywords: Gamma monitor, HEPA filter, alarm set point, Monte-Carlo simulation.

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Introduction

In the operations of a spent fuel reprocessing facility, the release of off-gases accompanied by radioactive particulates is a common occurrence. To manage the gaseous effluent emissions and adhere to regulatory standards, High Efficiency Particulate Air (HEPA) filters are extensively used within the off-gas treatment systems. Gamma Monitors (GM) are installed adjacent to each HEPA filter to facilitate timely replacement once the surface dose rate criteria are met. This paper discusses the theoretical simulations and experimental work conducted to determine the optimal positioning of the GM detector, establishing an appropriate alarm set point when the surface dose rate on the filter reaches 2 mGy/h.

Materials and Methods

An arrangement of four HEPA filters within an off-gas treatment system, positioned approximately 50 cm apart, has been examined in this study. Dose rates at various distances from the HEPA filters were calculated using Open Monte-Carlo simulations, with ^{137}Cs identified as the primary nuclide through gamma spectrometry analysis (Ramesh et al., 2018). To validate the computational findings, dose rates were recorded with calibrated instruments, such as the Automess Teletector (Model: 6150 AD5), at different distances from each of the four HEPA filters during operational activities. A comparison of the experimentally obtained and computed dose rates was conducted to determine suitable alarm thresholds for filter replacement.

Results & Discussion

The surface dose rate of 2 mGy/h was considered to compute dose rates at distances of 5, 15, 25, 35, 50, and 100 cm from the four off-

gas HEPA filters being examined. Additionally, the influence of dose rates from each HEPA filter on the others was assessed. To verify the calculated values, four GM detectors were strategically placed at specified distances from the HEPA filters. GM readings were taken for various radiation levels across the different filters during a long period of facility operations. The experimentally obtained values matched with the theoretically derived dose rates, thereby validating the study's methodology. An optimal alarm threshold was established at 0.6 mGy/h, with the GM detector located 5 cm from each HEPA filter, where contributions from other filters remained under 20%. However, as the detector's distance increased to 15 cm or more, the dose contributions from neighboring HEPA filters became more pronounced.

Conclusion

Theoretical analyses and experimental assessments have been performed to determine the dose rate at various distances from an array of four HEPA filters in an off-gas treatment system. An alarm threshold of 0.6 mGy/h has been set for a distance of 5 cm from the filters, corresponding to a surface dose criterion of 2 mGy/h. The results indicate that the varying dose conditions across the HEPA filters influence the readings of each individual GM detector to different extents. These outcomes are crucial for enhancing the placement of detectors and setting suitable alarm thresholds.

Reference

B. Ramesh, V. Ramprasath *et al.* (2018) NSRP Conference, NSRP-21, 49, 43.

EFFECTIVENESS OF BORATED HDPE SHIELDING IN NEUTRON DOSE REDUCTION

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Introduction

Neutron exposure in the nuclear industry plays a significant role due to its penetrating nature and ability to cause biological damage at the cellular levels. Facility such as nuclear reactor, fissile material handling in fuel fabrication & reprocessing plant and particle accelerators, there is a potential external exposure to radiation worker due to neutron. Effective shielding is therefore necessary in reducing neutron exposure to radiation worker. Materials such as concrete and water are commonly used to reduce neutron dose rate in reactor, however these shielding materials are not feasible while handling fissile material (oxide/carbide of uranium and plutonium) inside glove box in fuel fabrication facility due to operational constraints. Fissile material, a source of neutrons, is handled in large quantities in various forms such as powder, granules, pellets and pellets encapsulated in pins during various fuel fabrication operations. Neutrons are mainly emitted from the even mass numbered isotope of plutonium due to spontaneous fission and (α, n) reaction with lighter element present in the fuel (Kousiki et al.). Neutron dose monitoring is regularly carried out by issuing SSNTD (CR-39) badge to radiation workers. In order to evaluate the effectiveness of neutron shielding for Borated High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE) a study was carried out for two different boron content (5% and 20% borated HDPE) as shielding material which is presented in this paper. Borated HDPE has high hydrogen content making it slowdown of fast neutron and boron content which have high capture cross section for thermal neutron makes it a suitable candidate for neutron shielding.

Materials and Methods

To study the shielding effectiveness, two composition of boron i.e 5% and 20 % borated HDPE sheet of thickness 25 mm were used for neutron shielding. Mixed oxide (mixture of plutonium and Uranium oxide) powder and pellet containers were used as

neutron source in this study. The neutron dose rate on containers were measured using a He-3 detector with & without borated HDPE sheet.

Results

The percentage of neutron dose reduction is determined by dividing the neutron dose rate with HDPE sheet to dose rate without HDPE sheet. The reduction percentage of neutron dose rate is found to be in the range of 50-55 % for 5% borated HDPE and 56-58 % for 20% borated HDPE as shielding material. Only a marginal increase in neutron dose reduction percentage was observed with the increase in boron content in HDPE shielding material i.e. from 5% borated HDPE to 20% borated HDPE. Hence, 5% borated HDPE is found to be preferred cost-effective shielding material for neutron shielding.

Conclusion

The shielding effectiveness of 5% and 20% borated HDPE is evaluated and 5% borated HDPE is found to be preferred cost-effective shielding material for neutron. This study offers a valuable insight in controlling the neutron doses with the use of borated HDPE sheet as shielding material while handling fissile material during fuel fabrication. It is also necessary to carry out criticality evolution of the process before putting any additional shielding on GBs or fissile material storage area.

References

1. Neutron spectral and dose distribution studies during fast reactor fuel fabrication: Kousiki Ghosh et al., RPE(2014), Volume 37, Issue 2.

CRITICALITY SAFETY EVALUATION OF A MOX MATERIAL HANDLING FACILITY

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Keywords: keff, sampling, interaction, eigenfunction, convergence. Presenting

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Introduction

Fissile material in a processing facility can undergo changes in geometry, composition or physical state as it passes through various stages of processing. It can also change from a non-interacting state to an interacting state with other fissile units. An estimation of neutron multiplication factor i.e., keff can indicate possibility of an unwanted chain reaction or criticality. In this work, keff has been evaluated for interacting fissile units of MOX.

Materials and Methods

A monte-carlo based method was used to estimate the keff of interacting MOX containers in a MOX processing facility. The monte-carlo method is based on the method of statistical sampling. In monte-carlo based criticality safety, keff is estimated by simulating the trajectory of a group of neutrons in fissile material containing regions and estimating the number of neutrons produced via fission events. The ratio of neutrons before and after fission provides an estimate of keff of a generation or cycle of neutrons. An average keff and error estimate is obtained after repeating over many generations or cycles. The correct keff value in monte-carlo method is obtained only after the spatial distribution of fission points become stationary and indicates convergence to the fundamental eigenfunction of the k-eigenvalue equation. The corresponding eigenvalue represents the keff. The results converge after sufficient number of neutron fission cycles.

Results

keff of three interacting MOX containers in a MOX processing facility is estimated for both air- and water-reflecting conditions. The possibility of changes in geometry during stages of processing was taken care of by considering fissile units of MOX as spheres

without changing mass and density. The estimated keff in air provided the criticality status considering no material other than air occupied the space between fissile elements and surrounding them. Another estimate with air replaced by water was also made to represent the situation of neutron moderating and reflecting media in the intervening and surrounding space. This in effect included the influence of the material of the containers, other materials with significant neutron interaction around fissile material, presence of workers and the reflecting walls of the room on keff. The distance between fissile units and the size of the surrounding media was chosen to optimize the keff and obtain the most critical configuration.

Conclusion

The keff value of the most critical fissile material, moderator and reflector configuration was found to be subcritical with a separation distance of 0.3m and hence safe from criticality point of view. It is also noted that under certain configuration of moderator and fissile material a weakly interacting fissile system (Blomquist, 2003) is formed and fission source spatial distribution is not converging to the fundamental eigenfunction even after running sufficient number of cycles (Whitesides, 1971).

References

- Whitesides, G. E., (1975) *Comments On The Use Of The Monte Carlo Method For Criticality Calculations* No. CONF-751101-23, Union Carbide Corporation.
- Blomquist, R. N., Gelbard E.M. (2003) *Monte Carlo Criticality Source Convergence In A Loosely Coupled Fuel Storage System*, Proceedings Of ICMC 2003, Tokyo, Japan, Vol. 5, 500-507.

EXPOSURE CONTROL AND ALARA IMPLEMENTATION DURING LLW PROCESS TANK PAINTING

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Introduction

Low level waste treatment plant is designed to process low-level radioactive liquid waste (LLW) generated from Nuclear Power Plant. LLW streams, such as chemical regenerants from polishing columns, floor drains, and decontaminated liquids, are segregated at the source and treated at low level waste treatment plant using chemical co-precipitation technique for removal of Cs^{137} , Co^{60} , and Sr^{90} . The treated waste is stored in hold-up tanks, for delay and decay of short-lived radionuclide like I^{131} . Treated decant is monitored and transferred back for sea discharge, while chemical sludge, containing over 99% of the activity, is sent to NSDF (Near Surface Disposal Facility) for in-situ cement fixation in RCC trenches. The plant plays a critical role in managing low level liquid waste and its discharges, ensuring environmental safety. Painting of the process tanks is performed to maintain the integrity of the material quality and to reduce radiation field by removing highly active components and accumulated sludge from the bottom of the process tank.

Materials and Methods

ALARA (As Low As Reasonably Achievable) methodology was adopted during the painting of process tanks and associated piping at the low level waste treatment plant with comprehensive safety approach to ensure both, worker's protection and regulatory compliance. Pre-painting radiological surveillance was done by portable radiation monitoring instruments and contamination monitors to assess baseline radiation levels on surfaces. Tanks were decontaminated using chemical washing, air jet washing and remotely scooping of metal scraps resulted in reduction of contact radiation level from 0.2 mGy/h to 0.1 mGy/h. Workers were equipped with personal protective equipment (PPE), including full-body PVC suits, gloves, and respiratory protective equipment. Local exhaust was provided in process tank through HEPA filter blower assembly to ensure negative pressure in the working area. Based on radiation levels, working time was restricted to minimize the exposure by conducting inactive mock-up

trials and proper training to workers. During painting, air sampling with Staplex air sampler and continuous radiation monitoring using area gamma monitors had ensured safe radiological status of the area. Worker's doses were monitored via electronics personal dosimeters (EPDs) and TLD (Thermo luminescent dosimeter). Paints with low volatile organic compounds (VOCs) were selected to minimize the airborne radioactivity. Post-painting surveys ensured compliance with safety standards, and waste was managed following radioactive waste management protocols.

Results

Radiological surveillance and ALARA principle minimizes exposure and ensure safe execution of painting activities with no cases of overexposure and internal contamination of occupational workers. Collective dose consumption for the job was restricted to 21 p-mSv whereas authorized dose limit was 26 p-mSv. Airborne radionuclide concentrations remained within permissible limits. Effective waste management had ensured safe disposal of contaminated materials, demonstrating the success of the implemented safety protocols.

Conclusion

Radiological surveillance during painting work had ensured worker's safety and environmental protection. The entire painting work was carried out within 80% of the authorized dose limit, adhering to regulatory guidelines. Workers' doses were kept low through effective radiological monitoring and efficient time management. Managing the generated waste further mitigated radiological risks and environmental hazards.

References

AERB Safety Guide, "Radiological Safety in Handling and Disposal of Radioactive Waste," Atomic Energy Regulatory Board, India, 2020.

A VALIDATION STUDY TO CONFIRM HOMOGENEITY OF RADIOACTIVITY AND ESTABLISH DOSE RATE- TO-ACTIVITY CONVERSION FACTOR FOR CEMENTED WASTE PRODUCT CONTAINING TREATED ORGANIC LIQUID WASTE

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Introduction

Reprocessing of spent fuel by PUREX process involves use of tri-n-butyl phosphate (TBP) as solvent. Repeated use of the solvent leads to its degradation thus affecting the extraction process and is discarded as 'Organic Liquid Waste' (OLW). Treatment of OLW results in generation of solidified cemented waste product (CWP) wherein the waste containing radioactivity is solidified in cement matrix. The homogeneity of radioactivity in the cemented waste product was assessed. The average specific gamma activity in the product, thus estimated, was used to compute the surface dose rate on the product by theoretical means and the same was compared with the measured values.

Materials and Methods

To assess the radioactivity content in different regions of the waste matrix, samples of waste-cement mixture were drawn from different depths inside the CWP drum soon after pouring the content into the drum (before the matrix solidifies completely). The samples are then spread out evenly in a planchette and their weights were measured. The content is allowed to dry and then counted in a HPGe-based gamma spectrometry system, which is pre-calibrated for gamma energy and counting efficiency using standard gamma reference sources. The exercise was carried out by drawing three samples each at different depth from ten CWPs and repeating the above procedure. ^{137}Cs was found to be the predominant radionuclide with ^{241}Am being another constituent. A few samples showed presence of ^{106}Ru in trace amount. Considering the radioactive inventory thus arrived, the composition of the waste matrix, quantity of waste cemented and dimensions of the CWP, a theoretical estimation of dose

rate on the CWP drum was done using the point kernel shielding code, *IGSHIELD*.

Results

^{241}Am and ^{137}Cs activity per unit mass of CWP determined at different depths in each of the CWPs confirmed the homogeneity of radioactivity in the CWPs. The average variation in activity was found to be about 13-15% for both the radionuclides. The dose rates computed theoretically using the above activity values for each of the CWP drum were found to be in agreement with the corresponding measured dose rates on the surface of CWP drums. The ratio between the computed and measured dose rates ranged from 0.6 to 1.2 averaging 0.9 ± 0.2 .

Conclusion

Following immobilization of radioactive liquid in cement matrix, the solid waste thus produced as cemented waste product is found to contain uniformly dispersed radioactivity within the matrix. The computed surface dose rate on CWP corresponding to the determined activity was comparable to the measured dose rate thus validating the estimated radioactivity content in the CWPs.

References

1. Treatment and Conditioning of Radioactive Organic Liquids, IAEA – TECDOC-656, July-1992
2. K.V. Subbaiah and R. Sarangapani, (2008), 'IGSHIELD: A New Interactive Point Kernel Gamma Ray Shielding Code', Annals of Nuclear Energy, Vol.35, pp 2234-2242.

OPTIMISATION OF DETECTOR-TO-SAMPLE DISTANCE FOR QUANTIFICATION OF GAMMA ACTIVITY IN A HIGH ACTIVE SAMPLE OF VITRIFIED WASTE PRODUCT

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Introduction

High level liquid waste (HLW), generated during reprocessing of spent fuel is conditioned in glass matrix by the process of vitrification and stored in vitrified waste product (VWP) canister containing as high as 22200 TBq of beta, gamma activity. Isotopic characterisation of VWP is difficult to achieve owing to high activity concentration and high dose rate on the VWP canister. This paper presents the study on determination of gamma emitting isotopes present in a sample of VWP and their activity concentration. The values thus derived are confirmed theoretically by comparing the computed and measured dose rates corresponding to the sample activity.

Materials and Methods

A tiny speck (sample) of VWP measuring contact gamma dose rate of 3-6 mGy/h of known mass was subjected to gamma spectrometry using Canberra-make Falcon 5000 HPGe-based Radionuclide Identifier. Owing to high activity, the dead time encountered by the detector system was more than 50% when measured at standard detector-sample distance. The distance between the detector and sample was varied, optimised (at 180cm) such that the detector dead time is <5% and gamma spectrum of the sample obtained. ¹³⁷Cs was found to be the predominant radionuclide among others (²⁴¹Am, ¹⁵⁴Eu and ¹³⁴Cs). Efficiency of the detector system at the reference distance for different energies is required to estimate the activity of individual isotopes. ¹³⁷Cs being the predominant radionuclide in VWP, it was decided to determine the detector efficiency corresponding to ¹³⁷Cs gamma (662 keV) at

the reference location. For this, the efficiency of the system using ¹³⁷Cs standard source at different detector-to-sample distances was determined. The values were used to arrive at an equation and efficiency of the detector at the desired distance was extrapolated using the equation.

Results

Taking into account the errors associated with source activity, determination of efficiency and the weight of the sample, ¹³⁷Cs activity in the VWP sample was estimated to be 7566 ± 2107 MBq/gm of VWP. To confirm the value deduced, dose rates at different distances corresponding to the estimated activity was computed using the Monte Carlo code, MCNP, compared with corresponding measured dose rates and found to be in agreement (13 to 18%).

Conclusion

The challenge faced in quantification of gamma activity in the VWP sample, despite containing higher activity and thereby posing higher dead time in carrying out gamma spectrometry, is overcome by optimising the detector-to-sample distance and arriving at the efficiency at the desired distance by extrapolation. The activity thus estimated was confirmed by comparing the computed and measured values of dose rates from the sample, which were in agreement.

References

- S Sangaroon et al (2017) J. Phys.: Conf. Ser. 901 012133 Efficiency calibrations of HPGe detector for PGNA system.
A Practical Guide to High Count Rate Germanium Gamma Spectroscopy, http://www.canberra.com/literature/technical_ref/gamma/nan0013.htm

GEOPOLYMER CONCRETE FROM URANIUM MILL TAILINGS: A STUDY ON PHYSICAL, MECHANICAL, AND RADIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES

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Introduction

A large volume of waste generated from the mining and milling process of mineral extraction industries is a global issue in terms of environmental safety. The waste generated from the mining and milling process is most commonly known as tailings. In India, the generated uranium mill tailings are segregated based on their particle size, and the coarse portions are sent back to the underground mines for backfilling and fine fractions are discharged to tailings pond. An effective alternative for managing the waste produced by the uranium processing industry is the recycling of mill tailings for raw materials in construction industries. The utilization of industrial waste materials through alkali activation has become a focus of research, as it offers a way to produce affordable and environmentally friendly cement-like building materials. Geopolymerization is a technology that relies on the chemical reaction of amorphous silica and alumina-rich solids with a high alkaline solution at ambient or slightly elevated temperatures to form amorphous to semi-crystalline aluminosilicate inorganic polymer or geopolymer. The present study aimed to assess the feasibility of geopolymer concrete formation from uranium mill tailings and characterization of physical and mechanical properties such as grain size and compressive strength. The complete radiological characterization for natural radionuclides in raw materials and final products were also carried out.

Materials and Methods

Grain size, compressive strength were evaluated using BIS methods. ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K activity levels were assessed by using a p-type HPGe gamma spectrometer (RE 50%). Raeq is calculated by using Eq. 1 (Medhat, 2009).

$$R_{\text{aeq}} = C_{\text{Ra}} + 1.43C_{\text{Th}} + 0.077C_{\text{K}} \quad (1)$$

Results

The compressive strength of the geopolymer blocks increased from 10.7 to 12.0 MPa and 15.6 MPa, when 19, 21, and 35% fly ash and 17, 17, and 27% tailings were used, respectively. Particles of size range <45, 45–75, 75–150, and >150 μm in uranium mill tailings were 67.4, 20.0, 10.2, and

2.4%, respectively. Mill tailings are very fine in size with 87.4% of the particles <74 μm, which causes high water absorption capacity and poor drainage system. Thus, bed materials were used with the mill tailings to increase effective coarse fractions.

²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K in geopolymer blocks were in the range of 419–644, 41–56, and 331–482 Bqkg⁻¹, respectively. The radionuclide activities have been diluted in the geopolymer blocks as compare to the uranium mill tailings. The radium equivalent (Raeq) activity was in the range of 512–761 Bqkg⁻¹ in the geopolymer blocks. Raeq activity levels indicated that the concretes are suitable for use in the construction of industrial buildings (Raeq: 370–740 Bqkg⁻¹), roads, bridges (Raeq: 740–2200 Bqkg⁻¹), and the foundation of non-residential buildings (Raeq: 2200–3700 Bqkg⁻¹) (Oresegun & Babalola, 1988).

Conclusion

A variety of naturally occurring or technologically processed wastes may be used along with uranium mill tailings for the development of geopolymer concrete.

References

1. Medhat ME (2009) Radiation protection dosimetry, 133(3), 177-185.
2. Oresegun MO and Babalola AI (1988) In: Rad. Prot. in Nuclear Energy, V. 2, 159-166, 18-22 April, IAEA, Vienna, Austria

ESTIMATION OF EFFECTIVE DOSE FROM RADON AND THORON AIR ACTIVITY DURING MAINTENANCE OF ROTARY TRAY DRIER AT URANIUM OXIDE FACILITY, KALPAKKAM

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Keywords: Radon, Thoron, Effective Dose,

Introduction

The Uranium Oxide Facility (UOF) at Kalpakkam is designed to receive uranyl nitrate solution and convert it into Ammonium di-uranate by sparging Ammonia gas at a rate of 17 kg/hr in precipitator to react with dilute uranyl nitrate solution. After attaining Ph 7.0 ammonia sparging is stopped and ammonium di urinate slurry containing ammonium di urinate particles and aqueous solution of ammonium nitrate is sent for filtration. After filtration ADU cake will be dried at Rotary Tray Drier (RTD) and converted into U3O8 by heating in calciner facility.

Since depleted uranium is being handled in this facility, the daughter product of the uranium and thorium series takes the major attention due to the short half-lives of the ²²²Rn and ²²⁰Rn that is 3.82 days and 55.6s respectively. The daughter product of ²²²Rn and ²²⁰Rn are alpha emitting particulates which get airborne and constitute inhalation hazard. Lung is the target organ for the radon exposure.

In this study ²²²Rn and ²²⁰Rn concentration in working area of UOF has been estimated using RAD7 instrument for 10 days during the maintenance of RTD. The RAD7 monitor's internal sample cell is a 0.7 liter hemisphere, coated on the inside with an electrical conductor. A solid-state, Ion-implanted, Planar, Silicon alpha detector is at the center of the hemisphere. The detector uses the alpha spectrometry technique to continuously sniff and grab out ²²²Rn and ²²⁰Rn gas, the result of which are

displayed in real time monitoring on the detector screen, printed out after the completion on one hour cycle and stored in the RAD7 memory for late references.

Table.1 gives the average ²²²Rn and ²²⁰Rn concentration in the area. Effective dose to the radiation worker has been calculated using the following equation.

$$H_{air} = C_{air} \times F \times O \times DCF$$

Where,

H_{air} (μ Sv) is the effective dose, C_{air} is the indoor ²²²Rn or ²²⁰Rn concentration, F the equilibrium factor between ²²²Rn and ²²⁰Rn with their daughter products, O is the occupancy time per person during the maintenance work.

The measured ²²²Rn, ²²⁰Rn and their progeny concentrations are presented in the table.1. The concentration of ²²²Rn and ²²⁰Rn varies from 10 ± 3 to 15 ± 4 Bq/m³ and 10 ± 2 to 19 ± 8 Bq/m³ with the average value of 13 ± 3.14 Bq/m³ and 13.1 ± 6.41 Bq/m³ respectively. Accumulated effective dose for the 10 working days is 5.0 μ Sv.

References

- Rohit Mehra, Pankaj bala, (2013) Radiation protection and environment, **158**, 111-114.
- Mustapha Kola Lawal, Paul Sola Ayanlola, Olukunle Olaonipokun Oladapo, Michael Olatunde Oni, Abraham Adewale Aremu, (2021) Radiatio Protection and environment, **44**, 161-166.

THE INFLUENCE OF VISUAL MEDIA ON RADIATION SAFETY PERCEPTION

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Keywords: visual communication, perception, illustration, display, poster design.

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Introduction

Nuclear facilities are engaged in diversified programmes in front and backend technologies. Visual Media in the domain of Radiation Safety can bring a shift in the risk perception and acceptance. The visual media plays a pivotal role in communication of risk perception by all strata of communities. There are a number of visual tools adopted in this endeavour. Radiation safety in nuclear facilities is utmost important aspect. In the high-risk work places, visual communication helps significantly towards implementation of protective measures.

Materials and Methods

Design of warning signs and behavioural response to them by the diverse audience have been studied for many years now [1]. This paper explores the importance of clear and engaging visual messages in radiation protection, appropriate visual communication that enhance comprehension, compliance, and safety awareness among workers. Nuclear facilities involve exposure to ionizing radiation, which poses significant health risks if, safety protocols are not followed. Visual tools, including signages, posters, and infographics, significantly improve comprehension and recall in high-stake environments. This study compiles various strategies employed for creating effective visual communication in nuclear environment. Effective radiation safety communication visuals reduce risks by alerting employees about safety concepts and through sharing past experiences and promote a culture of safety. This paper explores how visual communication can be optimized to promote safety in radiation-prone work areas and to create public awareness on importance of nuclear energy for clean environment [4]. In this paper, the emphasis is on the creative aspect of promoting safety awareness through safety posters, signages, pictorial information charts and related visual communication materials that are clear, engaging, and aligned with the cognitive

needs of nuclear facility personnel as well as of general public.

Results

This attempt proves that various interesting visuals, safety messages can be produced by creative imaginations, designing capabilities and through use of different colors, compositions for diversified workforce. Comparative analysis of communication tools e.g. static signages, digital displays, digital scrolling boards and interactive tools to determine which are most effective in reinforcing safety protocols. Studies shows that clear, engaging visuals can retain more information when paired with a relevant image.

Conclusion:

Effective visual communication in nuclear facilities requires thoughtful design that considers cognitive load, cultural symbolism, and real-time needs. The best practices outlined in this paper serve as a foundation to ensure that, every member of the workforce can be engaged for developing visual communication strategies that enhance safety compliance and create public awareness.

References

1. K.R. Laughery, M.S. Wogalter, A three-stage model summarize product warning and environmental sign research. *Safety Sci.* 61, 3–10 (2014)
2. Kailash Gharat, G.L.N. Padmavathi, Garima Singh, Visual representation: a powerful ally to convey safety Information. *Proc.31st SOHPM (2024, RRCAT, Indore).*
3. GLN Padmavathi and Kailash Gharat, Promotion of Safety Awareness: Role of Innovations, *Proc. 31st SOHPM (2014), Nuclear Energy and Clean Environment (NECE) Poster Book 2024, Kailash Gharat 152 – 168 (2024)*

NUMERICAL MODELLING OF AIRFLOW AND PARTICLE DEPOSITION IN CONTAINMENT PIPELINES

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Introduction

In nuclear facilities, like spent fuel reprocessing and waste management plants, radioactive liquids are often transferred through pipelines. For transfer of high level liquid waste, a pipe-in-pipe arrangement is employed as a safety feature. The inner pipe carries the liquid, while the outer pipe ensures containment of radioactivity in case of inner pipe failure. The annular space between pipes is purged with particle-free air, monitored for radioactivity to detect leaks. Understanding the effective leakage monitoring mechanisms, including flow rates, sampling distances, and minimum detectable leaks, requires analyzing aerosol transport and distribution. This study employs computational fluid-particle dynamics (CFPD) simulations to identify critical parameters influencing fluid flow and particle deposition in such geometries.

Materials and Methods

In this CFPD simulation, a laboratory scale experimental set-up of concentric stainless steel pipes (diameters: 40.94 mm and 48.3 mm; length: 4000 mm) is modelled with 5.8 million computational cells and refined boundary layers. The annular space includes an air inlet, an outlet, and seven equidistant sampling ports. Airflow patterns were simulated using open source CFD code OpenFOAM (v1906), solving the Navier-Stokes equations. To capture the effects of turbulent flow, the Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) shear stress transport (SST) $k-\omega$ turbulence model is applied, where k is turbulent kinetic energy and ω is specific turbulent dissipation rate. Aerosol transport was modelled with AeroSolved (v2.0) code using an Eulerian-Eulerian framework with sectional particle size discretization, incorporating drag, gravity, and Brownian diffusion via the compressible PISO algorithm.

Results

This study highlights the critical parameters that must be defined as boundary and initial conditions to accurately model the fluid flow within a pipe-in-pipe system. The findings demonstrate that airflow patterns are significantly influenced by boundary conditions at the inlet, outlet, and probe locations, especially when suction is applied at the outlet. A key observation is that the inlet velocity varies markedly depending on which probes are opened while a fixed suction pump operates at the outlet. Air tends to enter preferentially through the probe pipes closer to the outlet, leading to higher velocities at the probe locations compared to the main inlet. This behaviour underscores the necessity of carefully defining the pressure and velocity conditions at the probe locations as initial and boundary conditions, as well as the sequence and timing of probe openings during aerosol measurement. Moreover, the study reveals that particle deposition is non-uniform along the pipe's length and is heavily influenced by particle size.

Conclusion

This study not only identifies critical boundary and initial conditions for accurately modeling fluid flow and aerosol transport in pipe-in-pipe systems but also provides valuable insights into optimizing experimental measurements. The results highlight the importance of probe positioning, timing, and sequencing of probe openings to ensure reliable airflow and aerosol data. Thus it provides a robust framework for optimizing leakage detection mechanisms and designing safer and more efficient monitoring systems for high-level radioactive liquid transfers.

References

AeroSolved, (2019). <http://aerosolved.com>.

TAILOR-MADE ELECTROPLATED CALIBRATION SOURCES FOR ALPHA COUNTING OF AIR SAMPLES

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Introduction

Alpha radiation detection in air samples is essential for monitoring environments in which radioactive materials are handled. Alpha counting systems are used to detect alpha particles collected on 2" filter papers. For these systems to function accurately, precise calibration is required. The use of electroplated uranium of 1-inch planchets as calibration sources is a common practice in radiation detection systems. But 2-inch electroplated uranium sources are ideal for this calibration, as they match the size of the air sample collection area. This paper discusses the advantages and challenges of preparing 2-inch electroplated uranium sources for calibration of alpha counting systems.

Materials and Methods

An ingeniously designed electrodeposition setup was employed in this study. This setup was engineered for simplicity, operational ease, and leak-proof functionality. Precise adjustments in electrode distance were achieved using a screw-operated Vernier calliper. The experimental setup included a Teflon cylinder with threaded ends, a stainless steel (S.S.) cathode, a platinum (Pt) wire anode, and a DC power supply. The electrolyte consisted of ammonium sulphate solution to facilitate pH control during the deposition process. All chemicals (NH₃, NH₄OH and H₂SO₄) used were analytical grade reagents.

A series of experiments explored key parameters such as pH range, electrode distance, current density, and deposition time.

Results

Initial experiments identified optimal conditions for efficient deposition:

- Deposition time: 2 hour
- Current: 600 mA
- pH range: 2.0–2.2

The study found that reducing the electrode distance enhanced deposition efficiency. However, excessively small distances risked

electrolyte boiling, disrupting the process. However, keeping the distances very small (below 7 mm in the set up) resulted in electrolyte boiling, disrupting the process). Adjustments to the Pt electrode geometry, particularly into a spiral wire configuration, reduced the risk of non-uniform deposition and also lowered the deposition time.

Under the optimized conditions, the 2-inch planchets demonstrated uniform uranium films with minimal surface roughness. When utilized for alpha counting system calibration, these sources produced consistent and reliable results, significantly enhancing detection accuracy.

Conclusion

The 2-inch diameter electroplated uranium sources offer considerable advantages over smaller sources for alpha counting system calibration. Their size alignment with 2-inch filter papers ensures better efficiency and uniformity in calibration, ultimately improving the precision of alpha radiation detection. This advancement enhances radiation safety protocols in environments handling radioactive materials.

References

- Dumitru O.A et.al. (2013) Radioanal. Nucl. Chem., 298 (2), 1335–1339.
- Barnett J M and Kane J E. (1996). Radiation Protection Management 13(5),30–36.
- Lee M H & Lee CW. (2000) Nucl Instrum Meth A 447, 593–600.

QUALITATIVE ASSESSMENT OF URANIUM SAMPLES USING CZT DETECTORS

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Keywords: Uranium, Gamma Spectroscopy, CZT.

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Introduction

The present work focuses on the qualitative identification of uranium samples using CZT based detector systems. Uranium fuels always contain all the three isotopes, namely, ^{234}U , ^{235}U and ^{238}U , in different proportions. Its identification and estimation through gamma spectrometry becomes difficult because the signature photons of the isotopes and their daughters are always present and show different intensities based on the amount of ^{235}U present in the uranium fuel.

Materials and Methods

The Advanced GR1 Gamma Ray Spectrometer manufactured by Kromek, UK is a CZT based detector system. The detector is a 10 mm X 10 mm X 10 mm CZT coplanar grid detector with energy range from 30 keV to 3 MeV and quoted energy resolution of $\sim 2\%$ FWHM at 662 keV. In the present study the peak ratio measurement technique [1] was used for the identification of the samples. In this method, the ratios of gamma ray intensities from all the isotopes in the uranium sample are measured and the information obtained is used for deduction of the composition of samples. In the present case, samples of uranium were of different forms such as metal strip, chemical compound, metal alloy and electrodeposited discs. The energy calibration of the detector system was carried out using standard disk sources of ^{152}Eu and ^{133}Ba . Since all the samples were of similar size and shape, a common efficiency calibration curve was used for analysis of all the measurements carried out. Efficiency calibration of the detector system for the source detector orientation was obtained through Monte Carlo simulations. The efficiency curve is represented by the following polynomial expression with Adj R-square of 0.99854.

$$\ln(\epsilon) = -1.048 \ln(E) + 0.471 \ln(E)^2 + 0.523 \ln(E)^3 - 4.053$$

Where ϵ is the efficiency and E is the energy in MeV. The error estimation of the measurements was carried out using the

following general expression for the propagation of error of a physical quantity:

$$\frac{\Delta x}{x} = \left\{ \left(\frac{\Delta a}{a} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta b}{b} \right)^2 + \dots + \left(\frac{\Delta f}{f} \right)^2 \right\}^{1/3}$$

The sources of error included uncertainties in photon energy, emission probability, counts and detector efficiency. The gamma spectra of the samples were acquired and analysed through the Kromek Multispect software.

Results

The activity ratio of $^{238}\text{U}/^{235}\text{U}$ in case of natural uranium is 21.7. The activity ratio keeps on decreasing with increasing ^{235}U content since the specific activity of ^{235}U is greater than that of ^{238}U . The estimated activity ratios of all the three samples were 20.91 ± 0.54 , 21.96 ± 1.38 and 22.04 ± 0.56 which are in good agreement with the expected activity ratio (21.7) of natural uranium. Based on this methodology the isotopic composition of samples of uranium of unknown ^{235}U concentration were determined.

Conclusion

In the present study, CZT gamma spectrometry system was employed to measure the gamma emission from uranium samples for the purpose of estimation of ^{235}U content in the sample. The peak ratio measurement technique was used for the identification of the samples. The results of natural uranium samples indicated the possibility of determination of the isotopic composition of the samples. Based on this method the isotopic composition of uranium samples of undetermined ^{235}U concentrations were obtained.

References

1. Doug R., Nobert E., Hastings S and Sarah K (1991) NUREG/CR-5550, Chapter 8.

SHIELDING EVALUATION OF ION EXCHANGE RESIN BED DESIGNED FOR REMOVAL OF RADIOACTIVE CS-137 FROM ACTIVE PROCESS CONDENSATE WATER IN REPROCESSING

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Introduction

The process condensates returning from the process cell may pick up contamination due to breach of activity from evaporators. This may result in generation of a significant amount of Category-III liquid waste. This waste is undesirable from a disposal perspective. In order to minimize the amount of Category-III waste, plant has proposed to collect the condensate water in a Condensate Recovery Tank (CRU tank), for treatment using an Ion exchange Bed. The ion exchange Bed will remove both cationic and anionic impurities from the condensate water through an ion exchange process. As a result, Cs-137 and other fission product activities like Sr-90 will be trapped in ion exchange resin, leading to decontamination of the feed condensate water. The activity load analysis on ion exchange bed, surface dose estimation and its shielding requirements are discussed in this paper.

Materials and Methods

The activity load on resin was analysed based on processing volume of active process condensate and its 100% retention factor in ion exchange resin for different Cs-137 activity concentration of process condensate. The Monte Carlo code, FLUKA has been used for the surface dose and shielding evaluation. FLUKA is internationally recognized Monte Carlo code for analyzing the transport of neutrons and gamma rays. The ion exchange resin bed has a processing capacity of 50,000 liters of process condensate between each regeneration cycle. For treatment of process condensates with activity concentration of 1 Bq/ml, 10 Bq/ml, 50 Bq/ml, and 100 Bq/ml, the activity distribution on cation bed, cation and anion bed together and in total ion exchange bed were estimated. The corresponding surface dose rate and the shielding requirements have been evaluated for

three process scenario: Scenario-I: The cation resin (CR) of volume 205.3 litres completely traps the Cs-137 activity in 50,000 litres of process condensate. Scenario-II: During the regeneration process, trapped Cs-137 activity in the cation resin is redistributed within a total resin volume of 410.6 litres, consisting of 205.3 litres of cation resin and 205.3 litres of anion resin. Scenario III: The trapped Cs-137 activity is evenly redistributed throughout the entire 823-liter volume of the ion exchange Bed.

Results

The surface dose rate was found for Scenario I, Scenario II and Scenario III for treatment of process condensate of maximum activity concentration of 100 Bq/ml were 2.106 mSv/h, 0.615 mSv/h and 0.524 mSv/h and the corresponding estimated lead thickness values which will limit ambient dose equivalent $H^*(10)$ to AERB stipulated dose limit of $1\mu\text{Sv/h}$ on surface of the ion exchange resin were 4.77cm, 4.0cm and 3.90cm.

Conclusion

On the basis of above activity load analysis on ion exchange bed, the lead shielding of thicknesses for cation bed, anion bed and left out volume portion of the ion exchange resin were estimated to be 4.77cm, 4.0cm and 3.90cm respectively.

References

1. Ferrari A, Sala P, Fasso A, Ranft J. FLUKA: A Multi-Particle Transport Code. 2005

RADIOLOGICAL SAFETY EXPERIENCE DURING DECOMMISSIONING OF PRESSURISED WATER LOOP AT CIRUS REACTOR

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Introduction

The CIRUS reactor, a 40 MWth research facility, was primarily used for physics experiments and testing PHWR fuel assemblies. It operated until 2010, after which decommissioning began. CIRUS being first of its kind nuclear reactor to be decommissioned in India, adequate studies are important to gain adequate understanding of complexities associated with decommissioning specifically to radiological aspects.

This paper describes the implementation of radiological protection procedures and experience gained during the decommissioning of Pressurised Water Loop (PWL) of the reactor. PWL was provided in the reactor as engineered loop to simulate the high temperature and pressure conditions for testing PHWR fuel assemblies. The PWL consists of a vertical pressure tube (~30' long) made with Zr₂ alloy surrounded by double layered Al water jacket to prevent thermal damage to neighboring fuel assemblies of the reactor.

As a part of decommissioning activities/studies at Cirus, it was planned to extract samples from Zr pressure tube and Al jacket. The extraction and handling of samples was having potential of high radiation exposure and spread of contamination. The experience gained was helpful in planning, execution and waste handling during reactor component dismantling and disposal.

Materials and Methods

Radiological parameters were evaluated for planning the job to ensure the protection of workers. An in-situ measurement was done in the reactor vessel along the Zr pressure tube to estimate the radiation level, which is needed for shielding arrangement (TRS-389, 1998). In-situ measurements were carried out using a high range GM based detector with long cable for accessing the reactor core. With preliminary estimate of the radiation levels, the shielding requirement was evaluated and was arranged in the work space. Mock drills were conducted to

estimate time required for the job and also to train the personnel.

A detailed radiation survey was carried out on the test section once it was lifted from reactor vessel. 3 samples of ~9" size each were cut from the middle of 30' long test section. Shielding arrangements were made for the samples and the waste drum. Gamma spectrometry was done on the powder samples collected from the Zr pressure tube.

Results

Radiation field inside the reactor vessel around the Zr pressure tube was 0.1 Gy/h – 1.0 Gy/h. The higher field was from stainless steel tubes in the tube sheet of reactor core structure. The contact radiation field on the Zr pressure tube on cut sample pieces was 0.15 Gy/h and on the Al pieces was 0.02 Gy/h. A 3" Pb shield was arranged for handling the test section which resulted in reduced radiation field 0.30 mGy/h near working space. Maximum air activity during the sample extraction was found to be 2 DAC. Major radionuclide found in the air activity samples was ⁶⁰Co and ¹²⁵Sb. The collective dose consumed for the job was 4.4 p-mSv.

Conclusion

In-situ measurements were helpful in planning the job w.r.t the requirement of shielding, PPE's and manpower to minimize radiation exposure. The gamma spectrometry of samples will be helpful in radioactive waste management. The job provided valuable experience for future dismantling of reactor core structure components having high radiation levels.

References

TRS-389, "Radiological characterization of shut down nuclear reactors for decommissioning purposes", IAEA, 1998.

HEALTH PHYSICS SURVEILLANCE AND EXPERIENCE GAINED DURING THE REMOVAL OF ACTIVATED CORROSION DEPOSITS FROM LIQUID POISON INJECTION SYSTEM

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Keywords: liquid poison, corrosion deposits, ion exchange resin

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Introduction

In a nuclear reactor, the neutron activation of deposited or suspended circulating corrosion products, is one of the major source of radiation exposure to personnel during maintenance jobs. The structural materials used in the pipelines of the liquid poison injection system of the reactor are made of stainless steel (Facility Design manual,1984) . Over a period of time, there was an increase in radiation field of the order of ten times in the header pipelines and ⁶⁰Co (NEA,2014) was found to be the main radionuclide contributing to the radiation field. This paper describes the experience gained during the identification and removal of radiation hot spots using ion exchange resin beds implementing ALARA principles .

Materials and Methods

The gamma ray scanning of radiation hot spots in the liquid poison header pipelines was done using a portable gamma ray detector based on CZT with lead shield collimator and having an energy resolution of ≤ 18 keV for ¹³⁷Cs energy of 662 keV (RoSCAN,2011).For quantification of radio nuclides, a calibrated HPGe detector based gamma spectrometer having relative efficiency of 30% and resolution of 2 keV at 1332 keV for gamma energy of ⁶⁰Co was used.

After assessing the magnitude of occupational exposure to be incurred , radiation protection and safety procedures like physical barriers, contamination control, alarming personal dosimeters , mock up training to supervisory personnel etc. were implemented during the draining , removal and transfer operations radioactive water samples and its collection in carbuoy. A temporary mixed bed ion exchange resin cartridge was designed in closed loop with

adequate radiation shielding and was utilized to remove the radioactivity and acidity from the drained water.

Results

The chemical analysis concluded that the deposits was mainly crystallized ferric nitrate associated with a moist layer of concentrated nitric acid. The characterization and quantification of radioactivity in the poison header system was done and ⁶⁰Co (99%) was found to be the main radionuclide contributing to radiation field. The spent ion exchange resin bed was disposed off as category-III radioactive solid waste and the job was successfully completed with minimal radiation dose consumption employing ALARA principles.

Conclusions

Due to air, moisture and dust ingress in the system through leaky paths corrosion of system components had occurred in high radiation field environment, even though all pipelines and tanks are made of stainless steel. The radiation background of the pipe lines, was found to be reduced significantly, after the removal of the accumulated corrosion deposits and will help in reducing personnel exposure during maintenance.

References

- 1.Facility Design Manual (1984)
- 2.Radiation Protection Aspects of Primary Water Chemistry and Source-term Management ,NEA, July 2014.
- 3.RoSCAN Gamma imaging system manual (2011)

ESTIMATION OF ACTIVITY IN IRRADIATED NICKEL SUBASSEMBLY OF FBTR BY HPGE BASED GAMMA SPECTROMETRY

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Introduction

Nickel sub assembly (Ni-SA) is used as the neutron reflector in FBTR. One of the irradiated Ni-SAs was removed from core on reaching the desired fluence and stored in the decay pit. During the discharge, high gamma radiation field was recorded by the Gamma Ion Chamber of the discharge flask. For the first time an in-situ gamma spectrometry of Ni-SA was performed to identify the probable radionuclides contributing to the high dose rate and to estimate the total activity, which are the requirements during waste disposal. The experimental details and the results from spectral measurements are discussed in this abstract.

Experiment

For carrying out gamma spectrometry, the portable Gamma ray spectrometer was commissioned at Reactor Containment Building (RCB) of FBTR. The gamma ray spectrometer consists of HPGe (P-type) coaxial detector with 30% relative efficiency of DSG@ detector systems, ORION@ make high voltage unit and spectroscopic amplifier unit coupled with Inter-winner Software installed in a laptop computer. The portable HPGe was arranged in the line of sight with the ion chamber port. The ion chamber slot near the axis of the discharge flask is shielded with 10 cm thick lead to reduce the radiation intensity. In addition, the radiation level on the gamma spectrometer was reduced by providing lead shielding near the collimator. The distance between the Ni-SA and detector was kept at 200 cm and dead time was 5 %. The energy calibration and intrinsic efficiency of the detector were performed. The intrinsic efficiency, net count rate under 1332.5 keV peak and surface area of the detector were used to estimate the measured gamma flux at the detector location. The experimental arrangement was modeled in IGSHIELD

code to estimate the flux to activity conversion factor (CF) at the detector location.

Results and discussions

The gamma ray spectra were acquired at different length of Ni-SA. The spectrum indicates that the major contributor for the dose rate is ⁶⁰Co. The intrinsic efficiency (fraction) (ηI) of the detector for 1332.50 keV is 0.19. The uncollided flux at the detector location computed using IGSHIELD code for 1Ci of 1332.50 keV of ⁶⁰Co is $3.92 \times 10^{-2} \gamma \cdot \text{cm}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ and CF for ⁶⁰Co is $25.5 \text{ Ci} / (\gamma \cdot \text{cm}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1})$. The surface area (S_a) of the HPGe detector is 47.78 cm². The net count rate under the full peak of 1332.5 keV at 590 mm is 4.08 cps. Hence, the estimated activity is 425.13 GBq (11.49 Ci) for a Ni-SA segment of 6.25 cm at 590 mm. Similarly the activity was estimated based on gamma spectrometry measurements and thermal spectrum of FBTR core at other locations.

Conclusions

The gamma spectrometry of irradiated Ni-SA was performed at FBTR using HPGe based spectrometer. The gamma spectrum revealed the presence of ⁶⁰Co and the estimated activity of Ni-SA was 9.943 TBq (268.74 Ci).

ESTIMATION OF SHIELDING FACTORS FOR VARIOUS PHOTON ENERGIES USING LEAD IMPREGNATED APRONS

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Keywords: Radiation Shielding Apron, Shielding Factor

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Introduction

X-ray and gamma sources have widespread applications in nuclear, medical and industrial field. These sources pose external exposure to the working professionals during handling. There are many engineered safety measures to reduce the external exposure to the radiation workers viz. shielded glove boxes, Master Slave Manipulators (MSM) in hotcells etc. In situations where these safety features can not be deployed due to operational constraints, radiation shielding aprons are promising alternative to cater such exposure situations. Evaluation of shielding factors of these aprons is essential for optimizing occupational exposure. This study aimed to evaluate the shielding effectiveness of newly procured radiation shielding apron (0.3 mm lead equivalent) against various photon energy radiation sources prior to their deployment.

Materials and Methods

Radiation shielding apron made up of lead vinyl having 0.3 mm lead equivalent thickness was used for this study [1]. Am-241 ($E_{\gamma}=59.54$ keV), Cs-137 ($E_{\gamma}=661.66$ keV) and Co-60 ($E_{\gamma}=1173.23$ keV, 1332.49 keV) sources were used for the dose rate measurement. Gamma radiation survey meters were employed to measure dose rates at various distances from the sources. The measurements were carried out with and without the use of the lead impregnated apron at various distances viz. 10 cm, 30 cm, 50 cm and 100 cm [2]. The measured dose rates were used to estimate the shielding factors, SF (ratio of dose rate without shield to with shield).

$$SF = \frac{D}{D'} \dots (1)$$

Where, D and D' are dose rate without and with shield respectively.

Results

The average shielding factor for Am-241 source at various distances was found to be in the range of 2.50 ± 0.34 to 2.76 ± 0.38 . This indicates that the aprons significantly attenuated the radiation, thereby reducing the personnel exposure. The average shielding factor for Cs-137 source was determined to be between 1.15 ± 0.07 and 1.20 ± 0.10 . In case of Co-60 source, the shielding effectiveness was negligible. In contrast to Am-241 source, the shielding effectiveness of the lead impregnated aprons against Cs-137 source was relatively moderate.

Conclusion

The lead impregnated aprons offer good level of protection against lower photon energy (Am-241 source) but their impact on relatively higher energy radiation (Cs-137) was less pronounced and almost negligible for still higher photon energy (Co-60). The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the efficacy of radiation shielding aprons for different types of radiation sources. By understanding the limitations of shielding, especially for mixed or high-energy radiation sources, appropriate measures can be implemented to further minimize personnel exposure. This knowledge is essential for planning special operations in radioactive areas to ensure the safety of radiation workers.

References

1. R.N. Dubla, et. al. NUCAR-2023 page
2. Parvaresh R., et. al. J Biomed Phys Eng 2020; 10(5), 651-658

INVESTIGATION OF AMBIENT GAMMA RADIATION DOSE RATES AND RADON ACTIVITY CONCENTRATIONS IN THE MODEL HOUSE CONSTRUCTED USING URANIUM MILL TAILINGS

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Introduction

Uranium mill tailings (UMT), generated during ore processing, contain significant levels of elements such as Ca, Mg, Al, Fe, Si, and S, along with uranium-series radionuclides like ²²⁶Ra, ²³⁰Th, ²¹⁰Pb and ²¹⁰Po. The physicochemical properties of UMT can either support or require modifications for their use in manufacturing products or raw materials for infrastructural applications. However, the direct application of UMT in public-utility products is limited by its radioactivity, necessitating a comprehensive scientific evaluation. Mixing UMT with diluents in varying proportions could help produce suitable materials, but optimization is crucial. Therefore, it is essential to assess radiation exposure from finished products containing UMT. This study examines ambient gamma radiation and radon activity concentrations inside the model house constructed using uranium mill tailings bricks at the HPU, Jaduguda, Jharkhand.

Materials and Methods

Bricks were manufactured incorporating tailings as one of the key ingredients, to demonstrate the use of UMT as a component in construction materials. The proportion of mill tailings in the bricks ranged from 10 – 30%, combined with other materials such as sand, cement, gypsum, lime etc. Key parameters, including compressive strength, water absorption, and leaching properties were analyzed using standardized methods to evaluate the suitability of these bricks for construction purposes. With the major objective of utilization of UMT, a model house is built using these bricks containing tailings. In the model house, three rooms were constructed using bricks containing varying

proportions of tailings (10%, 20%, and 30%), alongside a control room built with standard bricks.

Results

Ambient gamma radiation dose and radon diurnal variation studies were conducted in the model dwelling units. Radon gas concentrations were measured under varying ventilation conditions, ranging from no ventilation to fully ventilated scenarios. Radiation survey meter (PM1405) was used to measure the gamma radiation dose rates, while a professional radon monitor (Bertin AlphaGuard) was employed to assess radon gas concentrations. The external gamma dose rates inside Room 1 (10% UMT), Room 2 (20% UMT), and Room 3 (30% UMT) were recorded in the ranges of 180–250 nSv/h, 200–300 nSv/h, and 220–320 nSv/h, respectively. Correspondingly, radon concentrations in these rooms were measured to range from 44–115 Bq/m³, 55–168 Bq/m³, and 146–251 Bq/m³, respectively.

Conclusion

The measured gamma dose rates and radon concentrations were found to be comparable to those observed in typical dwellings in the region.

References

IAEA (International Atomic Energy Agency),
The Long-Term Stabilization of Uranium
Mill Tailings – IAEA TECDOC-1403,
(2004) Vienna.

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON USE OF TRITIUM ACTIVITY AS A TOOL FOR IDENTIFICATION OF LEAKY COOLANT CHANNEL

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Keywords: NAPS, Dew Point, Tritium DAC, AGMS, PHT, Moderator, LSA, Pressure Tubes, Calandria Tube

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Narora Atomic Power Station (NAPS) is the first indigenous Pressurized Heavy Water Reactor (PHWR) located in district Bulandshahr, UP. At NAPS, Annulus Gas Monitoring System (AGMS) is used for healthiness check of Pressure Tubes (Coolant Channel) /Calandria Tubes during normal operating condition of the plant. This healthiness is assessed by monitoring of dew point and tritium activity of annulus gas at the outlet of AGMS.

In PHWR type of reactor, tritium is produced due to activation of deuterium present in the form of Heavy Water (D₂O) used in PHT and Moderator system. Tritium nucleus decays by emitting a single beta particle with half-life of 12.3 years and maximum beta energy of 18.56 keV (average beta energy ~ 5.6 keV). Liquid Scintillation Analyzer (LSA) is being used for analysis and estimation of tritium activities. Tritium measurement is widely used in investigative methods for identification of breach in system integrity.

Present article discusses about the comparative study and analysis of data pattern observed between online dew point measurement and that of measured tritium specific activity (expressed as DAC) of annulus gas, during the manual shutdown of NAPS-2 due to increase in AGMS outlet Dew Point. The study included the review of annulus gas tritium activity (DAC) data of coolant channels which helped in prompt identification of leaky coolant channel.

The behavior of Tritium DAC of AGMS was observed to follow the trend of Dew point closely at different conditions of PHT temperature and pressure i.e. from the onset of event of deterioration in dew point to the identification of leaky channel and further confirmation of the leaky channel during hot pressurized PHT conditions. The present study

provided an insight and strengthens the basis for applying tritium activity monitoring in annulus gas as a tool for identification of leaky coolant channel(s) for corrective actions.

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